

**THE RELIANCE ON FOSSIL FUEL ENERGY SOURCES IN THE SCOTTISH
PUBLIC SECTOR**

EBIYON OKPETORITSE IDUNDUN

**Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the
West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Philosophy**

University of the West of Scotland

November 2023

AUTHOR'S DECLARATION

I confirm that this thesis has not been submitted for a PhD or comparable academic award and the work contained within this thesis is my own. I certify that all material used in this thesis which is not my own is duly acknowledged.

ETHICS STATEMENT

This research study was approved by the ethics committee of the former School of Science and Sport at the University of the West of Scotland, approval number 3-5-16-001. Participants granted informed consent to voluntarily participate in a voice recorded semi-structured interview by signing a printed copy of the informed consent form prior to the commencement of the interview. The recorded interviews were transcribed by the researcher to ensure participant confidentiality, and the data subject to standard data use policies which protect the anonymity of individuals and institutions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The PhD journey as expected has been challenging, yet a rewarding experience for which I would like to give thanks first and foremost to God Almighty for the opportunity and grace to successfully complete this study.

My gratitude goes to my Director of Studies, Dr. Iain McLellan for his encouragement, guidance, patience, and support throughout the duration of this study, and to my second supervisor, Professor Andrew Hursthouse for his overview and insights right through the process. Despite their busy schedules, they promptly reviewed my draft submissions providing constructive feedback and comments, which have been invaluable in my academic writing and critical thinking development.

My gratitude extends to Dr. Jennifer Mc-Quaid Cook who was highly instrumental in the early stages of my PhD journey and served as my Director of Studies prior to her retirement.

I also offer my sincere blessings, regards and appreciation to my wife, daughter, parents, and siblings, for their utmost prayers, encouragement, and financial support. Special thanks go to my wife, Gemma Idundun for her sacrifices, understanding, and belief in my abilities, particularly through the most difficult of times during the PhD journey.

Finally, to all those who have assisted me in any respect during the duration of my PhD journey, thank you.

ABSTRACT

Ebiyon Idundun

The reliance on fossil fuel energy sources in the Scottish public sector

Despite increasing reports of predicted consequences of climate change from burning of fossil fuel (FF) energy sources for example wildfires, tropical storms, sea level rise, loss of ice, and long periods of draught, FFs remain the principal source of energy consumption. Scotland's significant progress in decarbonisation efforts within the United Kingdom (UK) context coupled with the acceptance and publicity of the public sectors key role in the delivery of net-zero societies brings the Scottish public sector into focus. The purpose of the research is to explore reliance and attitudes to FF energy sources by Scottish public sector bodies in a bid to co-create an optimised stakeholder driven framework for sector bodies to reduce FF use. The research was exploratory in nature and utilised an inductive approach to develop an understanding of the FF reliance phenomenon through a mixed method study. A systematic search of literature using The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) approach revealed a lack of publications focused on reducing public sector FF emissions. Consolidating findings from a case study to establish carbon footprint (CF) baseline, analysis of emissions reported by sector bodies to the Scottish Government, and semi-structured interviews with public sector actors, results in the concept of a framework to address the phenomenon based on a joined-up approach between public sector bodies and the Scottish Government to reduce FF reliance. The proposed framework resulting from the mixed method research represents the first known framework for addressing FF reliance, one that Scottish public sector bodies can adopt for planning and decision making in relation to FF use and reporting. The research discusses the implications of FF reliance for public sector bodies, highlighting the need for measuring and reporting FF sources and emissions, and facilitates the deepening of knowledge on the topic of FF reliance.

LIST OF CONTENTS

	Page
AUTHOR’S DECLARATION	1
ETHICS STATEMENT	2
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	3
ABSTRACT	4
LIST OF CONTENTS	5
LIST OF FIGURES	9
LIST OF TABLES	11
LIST OF EQUATIONS	15
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	16
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION	19
1.1. RESEARCH BACKGROUND	20
1.2. SCOPE OF THE RESEARCH TOPIC	21
1.3. RESEARCH JUSTIFICATION	22
1.4. RESEARCH QUESTION, AIMS AND OBJECTIVES	24
1.5. THESIS OUTLINE	25
CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW	27
2.1. INTRODUCTION	28
2.2. CARBON MANAGEMENT	28
2.2.1. Carbon Management in UK HEIs	31
2.2.2. Carbon Management in UK LGAs	34
2.3. METHODS OF CALCULATING CFs	37
2.4. GHG EMISSIONS REDUCTION	41
2.4.1. Overview of Scotland’s progress on carbon emissions reduction	45
2.5. LITERATURE SEARCH	47
CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY	51
3.1. INTRODUCTION AND RESEARCH DESIGN	52
3.2. LITERARY REVIEW (CHAPTER 2)	56
3.3. CF BASELINE ASSESSMENT CASE STUDY (CHAPTER 4)	56
3.4. DOCUMENT REVIEW (CHAPTER 5)	60
3.5. SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW (CHAPTER 6)	67
3.6. CONCLUSION	73

CHAPTER 4: CF FOOTPRINT and BASELINE ASSESSMENT of a HE	74
OPERATIONAL UNIT - SoSS (2014 – 2018), UWS	
4.1. INTRODUCTION	75
4.2. SoSS CARBON MANAGEMENT	78
4.3. DEVELOPING AN EMISSIONS BASELINE	79
4.3.1. Step 1 – Decide on the method to be followed	79
4.3.2. Step 2 – Define organisational and operational boundaries	79
4.3.3. Step 3 & Step 4 – Collate the data and apply emissions factors (see Table 4.17)	79
4.3.4. Step 5 - Verify results (optional)	80
4.3.5. Step 6 - Verify that you have taken action to reduce your emissions (optional)	80
4.4. ESTIMATING SCHOOL LEVEL EMISSIONS	80
4.4.1. Energy from buildings	81
4.4.2. Travel	82
4.4.3. Procurement	82
4.4.4. Water	82
4.4.5. Waste management	83
4.5. METHOD	83
4.5.1. Operational boundaries	83
4.5.2. Baseline footprint data sources	84
4.5.2.1. Energy from buildings and water data source	84
4.5.2.2. Travel data sources	85
4.5.2.3. Procurement data sources	87
4.5.2.4. Waste management data sources	88
4.5.3. Conversion factors	88
4.5.4. School infrastructure footprint	88
4.6. RESULTS	89
4.6.1. Energy from buildings	89
4.6.2. Travel	90
4.6.2.1. Staff commute	90
4.6.2.2. Business conference travel (Business Travel)	91
4.6.3. Procurement	92
4.6.3.1. IT equipment (PCs)	92
4.6.3.2. Publications and prints (Paper Use)	92
4.6.4. Water	93
4.6.5. Waste management	94
4.6.6. School baseline footprint	95
4.7. DISCUSSION	97

4.8. CONCLUSION	104
4.9. RECOMMENDATIONS	105
CHAPTER 5: REVIEW OF CORPORATE EMISSIONS REPORTED BY SCOTTISH PUBLIC SECTOR BODIES	107
5.1. INTRODUCTION	108
5.2. TOTAL SCOTTISH PUBLIC SECTOR EMISSIONS REPORTED TO SSN	110
5.3. SCOTTISH PUBLIC SECTOR FF CONSUMPTION REPORTED TO SSN	112
5.4. SCOTTISH PUBLIC SECTOR EMISSION REDUCTION PROJECTS REPORTED TO SSN	114
5.5. TOTAL REPORTED PARTICIPATING ORGANISATIONS EMISSIONS	117
5.6. PARTICIPATING ORGANISATIONS FF CONSUMPTION	119
5.7. PARTICIPATING ORGANISATIONS EMISSION REDUCTION PROJECTS	121
5.8. REPORTED TARGETS FOR SCOTTISH PUBLIC SECTOR BODIES AND PARTICIATING ORGANISATIONS	124
5.9. DISCUSSIONS – REPORTED EMISSIONS AND EMISSION REDUCTION PROJECTS FOR SCOTTISH PUBLIC SECTOR BODIES	125
5.10. CONCLUSION	127
CHAPTER 6: INTERVIEW DATA AND ANALYSIS	129
6.1. INTRODUCTION	130
6.2. SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW	130
6.3. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION	132
6.3.1. Theme 1: Evidence of ongoing reliance on FFs	132
6.3.1.1. Energy use in buildings	132
6.3.1.2. Fuel for transportation	134
6.3.2. Theme 2: Efforts to reduce FFs use	135
6.3.2.1. Government and organisational initiatives	136
6.3.2.2. Renewable energy and low carbon emission technology uptake	138
6.3.3. Theme 3: Barriers to moving away from FFs	140
6.3.3.1. Lack of funding and support	141
6.3.3.2. Practicalities and cost implications	144
6.3.3.3. Lack of an alternative energy source to replace FFs	147
6.3.4. Theme 4: Carbon reporting	151
6.3.4.1. Difficulties in estimating to Scope 3 emissions	151
6.3.5. Theme 5: Actions required to reduce reliance on FF	153
6.3.5.1. Radical zero-carbon revolution	154

6.3.5.2. Reduced energy consumption and carbon offsets	156
6.3.5.3. Financial instruments and governance	158
6.4. CONCLUSION	160
CHAPTER 7: FRAMEWORK DEVELOPMENT	163
7.1. INTRODUCTION	164
7.2. RESEARCH FINDINGS	164
7.3. DEVELOPING A FRAMEWORK TO REDUCE RELIANCE ON FF ENERGY SOURCES	166
7.3.1. Case study	166
7.3.2. Document review	167
7.3.3. Interviews	168
7.3.4. Significance of findings	169
CHAPTER 8: RESEARCH CONCLUSION	172
8.1. SUMMARY OF THESIS MAIN POINTS	173
8.2. CONCLUDING STATEMENTS	174
8.3. LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	175
8.4. RESEARCH OUTPUTS AND PREDICTIONS	176
8.5. SOLUTIONS	177
REFERENCES	178
LIST OF APPENDICES	216

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1: Boundaries of organisational, product and supply chain footprints (*Source: Based on Carbon Trust, 2018*).

Figure 2.2: Timeline of reports and conferences on Climate Change showing international action (post creation of IPCC in 1988) (IPCC, 2010; UNFCCC, 2016; UNFCCC, 2017; UNFCCC, 2018; UNFCCC, 2019; UNFCCC, 2021b; UNFCCC, 2021c; IPCC, 2021b). *Source: Author*.

Figure 2.3 PRISMA 2020 flow diagram showing results of literature search Relating to ‘Public Sector’ using Scopus database.

Figure 3.1 Schematic of the main aspects of the research design.

Figure 3.2: Steps taken to establish SoSS 2015/16 baseline CF.

Figure 3.3: Map of Paisley campus showing buildings occupied by SoSS in green.

Figure 3.4: Map of Hamilton campus showing buildings occupied by SoSS in green.

Figure 3.5: Outline steps undertaken in document review methodology.

Figure 3.6 Process flow chart methodology for analysis of semi-structured interview responses (Based on Braun and Clarke (2006)).

Figure 4.1: Chart of UWS CF 2012/13 to 2018/19 (Roxburgh, 2017; UWS, 2018, 2019, 2020).

Figure 4.2: Organisational boundaries within the SoSS.

Figure 4.3: Operational boundaries within the SoSS.

Figure 4.4: SoSS CF by Emission Source 2015/16.

Figure 5.1: Scottish Public Sector Total Reported Emissions 15/16 to 18/19 (See Table: 3.1).

Figure 5.2: Annual Combined Share of Total Reported Emissions for LGAs and Educational Institutions from 2015/16 – 2018/19 (See Table: 3.1).

Figure 5.3: Increase in reported FF emissions against the reduction in total reported Scottish public sector emissions 15/16 to 18/19 (See Table: 3.1).

Figure 5.4: Annual Composition of Scottish Public Sector reported emissions related to FFs between 15/16 and 18/19 (See Table: 3.1).

Figure 5.5: Scottish public sector annual emissions savings from reported emission reduction projects in tCO₂e 15/16 to 18/19 (See Table: 3.3).

Figure 5.6: Breakdown of emissions for Scottish Public Sector and Participating Organisations as a percentage of their total reported emissions 15/16 to 18/19 (See Table: 3.1 and Table: 3.2).

Figure 5.7: Increase in reported FF emissions against the reduction in total reported participating organisations emissions 15/16 to 18/19 (See Table: 3.2).

Figure 5.8: Average composition of Participating Organisations reported emissions related to FFs between 15/16 and 18/19 (See Table: 3.2).

Figure 5.9: Participating organisations annual emissions savings from reported emission reduction projects in tCO₂e 15/16 to 18/19 (See Table: 3.5).

Figure 6.1: Thematic map showing five key themes and corresponding sub-themes.

Figure 7.1: Highlights of some findings from each aspect of the mixed method study research.

Figure 7.2: Proposed framework for addressing FF reliance in the Scottish public sector.

LIST OF TABLES

Table 2.1: List of GHGs used in the UK and their corresponding GWP (*Source: UK Government, 2023*)

Table 2.2: Comparison of Bottom-up and Top-down approaches for CF estimation (*Source: the table is based on information from Wiedmann and Minx, 2008; Nicholls et al., 2015*).

Table 2.3: Breakdown of interim GHG Emission Reduction Targets up to 2050 for the UK, Wales, and Scotland.

Table 2.4: Scopus Structured Search Strings and Number of Results Relating to ‘Public Sector’.

Table 3.1: Reported Scottish Public Sector Corporate Emissions 2015/16 to 2018/19 in tCO₂e (*Source: data collated from SSN (2019; 2020)*).

Table 3.2: Reported Participating Organisations Corporate Emissions 2015/16 to 2018/19 in tCO₂e (*Source: data collated from SSN (no date)*).

Table 3.3: Reported Scottish Public Sector Emissions Savings from Emission Reduction projects 2015/16 to 2018/19 in tCO₂e (*Source: data collated from SSN (2019; 2020)*).

Table 3.4: Reported Scottish Public Sector and Participating Organisations Renewable Energy Generation 2015/16 to 2018/19 in tCO₂e (*Source: data collated from SSN (no date; 2019; 2020)*).

Table 3.5: Reported Participating Organisations Emissions Savings from Emission Reduction projects 2015/16 to 2018/19 in tCO₂e (*Source: data collated from SSN (no date)*).

Table 3.6: Reported Participating Organisations Emission Reduction Targets 2015/16 to 2018/19 in tCO₂e (*Source: data collated from SSN (no date)*).

Table 3.7: Examples of a code applied to a segment of data.

Table 3.8: Example of codes grouped into potential themes and sub-themes.

Table 4.1: Emission Sources Included and Excluded in the Baseline Footprint Calculation.

Table 4.2: 2015/16 Baseline Footprint Emission Factors and Data Sources.

Table 4.3: Building and Campus Room Size (m²).

Table 4.4: Electricity Baseline consumption and emissions associated with Energy from Buildings.

Table 4.5: Gas baseline consumption and emissions associated with Energy from Buildings.

Table 4.6 Total Energy from Buildings baseline consumption and emissions for the SoSS.

Table 4.7: Staff Commute consumption and emissions associated with Travel (see Appendix 5 for calculation breakdown).

Table 4.8: Total Business Travel baseline consumption and emissions for the SoSS.

Table 4.9: Total Travel baseline consumption and emissions for the SoSS.

Table 4.10: Total IT Equipment (PCs) consumption and emissions for the SoSS.

Table 4.11: Total Publications and Prints (Paper Use) consumption and emissions for the SoSS.

Table 4.12: Total Procurement consumption and emissions for the SoSS.

Table 4.13: Water Supply Baseline consumption and emissions associated with Water.

Table 4.14: Water Treatment Baseline consumption and emissions associated with Water.

Table 4.15: Total Water baseline consumption and emissions for the SoSS.

Table 4.16: Total Waste Management baseline consumption and emissions for the SoSS (Paisley campus).

Table 4.17: 2015/16 Carbon Emissions Baseline by Category and Emission Sources.

Table 4.18: Highlights of some University wide/University Departmental Footprints.

Table 5.1: Examples of emission reduction projects reported for emission sources, and average percentage contribution to the total Scottish public sector reported savings 2015/16 and 18/19 (SSN, 2019; 2020).

Table 5.2: Total percentage share of emissions for participating LGAs and HEIs 15/16 to 18/19.

Table 5.3: Examples of emission reduction projects reported for emission sources, and average percentage contribution to the total public sector and participating organisations reported savings 15/16 and 18/19.

Table 6.1: Interview Participants Job Remits and Titles (LGAs and HEIs).

Table 6.2: Theme 1 - developed key theme and sub-themes.

Table 6.3: Theme 2 - developed key theme and sub-themes.

Table 6.4: Theme 3 - developed key theme and sub-themes.

Table 6.5: Percentage of Scotland's Energy Consumption from Renewable Energy sources 2009 to 2019.

Table 6.6: Theme 4 - developed key theme and sub-themes.

Table 6.7: Theme 5 - developed key theme and sub-themes.

LIST OF EQUATIONS

Equation 4.1: Consumption (kWh). Building footprint taken from Table 4.3

Equation 4.2: Emissions (kg CO₂e) calculation. Conversion Factors taken from Table 4.2

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AMR – Automated Meter Readers

AR – Assessment Report

BEIS – Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy

BP – British Petroleum

BMS – Building Management System

CCC – Committee on Climate Change

CCS – Carbon Capture and Storage

CF – Carbon Footprint

CH₄ – methane

CHP – Combine Heat & Power

CMP – carbon management plan

CO₂ – carbon dioxide

CO₂e – carbon dioxide equivalent

COP – Conference of Parties

COVID-19 – Coronavirus Disease of 2019

CRC – Carbon Reduction Commitment

DECC – Department of Energy and Climate Change

EA – Environmental Auditing

EAc – Environmental Accounting

EAUC – Environmental Association for Universities and Colleges

EC – European Commission

EEIO – environmental extended input-output

EEMRIO – environmentally-extended multi-region-input-output

EIO – economic input-output

EMS – Environmental Management Systems

EMS – Estates Management Statistics

ESRC – Economic and Social Research Council

ETP – Energy Technology Partnership

ETS – Emissions Trading System

EU – European Union

EV – Electric Vehicles

FE – Further Education

FF – Fossil Fuels
GHG – greenhouse gas
GWP – global warming potential
HE – Higher Education
HEI – Higher Education Institutions
HESA – Higher Education Statistics Agency
HEFCE – Higher Education Funding Council for England
HFCs – hydrofluorocarbons
HP – Hewlett Packard
ICAO – International Civil Aviation Organization
IO – input-output
IPCC – Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change
LCA – Life Cycle Assessment
LCC – Life Cycle Costing
LED – Light Emitting Diode
LGA – Local Government Authority
LHEES – Local Heat & Energy Efficiency Strategy
LPG – Liquefied Petroleum Gas
MOP – Meeting of Parties to the Kyoto Protocol
N₂O – nitrous oxide
NAO – National Audit Office
NERC – Natural Environment Research Council
NF₃ – nitrogen trifluoride
ONS – Office for National Statistics
PA – process analysis
PAS – Publicly Available Specification
PFCs – perfluorocarbons
PICO – population, intervention, comparison, outcomes
PRISMA – Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses
PV – Photovoltaic
RHI – Renewable Heat Incentive
SDGs – Sustainable Development Goals
SECR – Streamlined Energy and Carbon Reporting
SF₆ – sulfur hexafluoride

SLG – School Leadership Group

SSN – Sustainable Scotland Network

SoSS – School of Science and Sport

UCCCfS – Universities and Colleges Climate Commitment for Scotland

UK – United Kingdom

UNFCCC – United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

UWS – University of the West of Scotland

WEEE – Waste Electrical & Electronic Equipment

WHO – World Health Organisation

CHAPTER 1:

INTRODUCTION

1.1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND

This thesis explores the reliance on FF energy sources within Scotland's public sector bodies. The focus on the Scottish public sector is on acknowledgement of the Scottish Government (and UK Government) acceptance and publicity of the public sectors key role in the delivery of net-zero societies, and Scotland's significant progress in decarbonisation efforts within the UK context.

It is recognised that climate change, and its associated issues, including the growing reliance on FFs and drastic need to reduce global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, continues to be a concern cutting across all spheres of our global society and environment. The IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change) is confident that the observed warming since the mid-20th Century is a consequence of anthropogenic influence (IPCC, 2013), responsible for retreating glaciers and estimated to be responsible for global warming of about 1.09°C above pre-industrial levels (IPCC, 2021a). The large-scale use of FFs determined the process of industrialisation, and its continued use has major environmental implications such as pollution and global warming (Wadanambi et al., 2020). FFs remain the principal source of global energy consumption with oil (33.1%), coal (27.0%), and gas (24.2%) having the largest shares in global primary energy consumption in 2019 and a combined share of 82% in 2022 (BP (British Petroleum), 2020; 2023; Singh et al., 2018; Ren, Deng & Chao, 2018), and the European Union (EU) relies on FFs, importing oil, gas, and hard coal estimated at approximately €266 billion in 2017 (European commission (EC), 2019). Hence, the increasing need to reduce the reliance on FFs and GHG emissions, for example the 'basket of seven' covered by Kyoto Protocol¹: carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), perfluorocarbons (PFCs), sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆), and nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃) (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), no date).

The role of the public sector as an influencer of resilient societies is pivotal in this (Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC), 2013; Owen et al., 2018), either

¹ The Kyoto Protocol was adopted in December 1997 and came into force in February 2005, aiming to reduce emissions from six major GHGs (UNFCCC, 2021a). In December 2012 the Doha Amendment to the Kyoto Protocol was adopted and included a seventh GHG (NF₃) known as the 'basket of seven' (UNFCCC, n.d.). This came into force on 31 December 2020 (UNFCCC, n.d.).

through carbon management practices or enabling sustainable private companies through grants to reach the estimated cost of >US\$125-149 billion per annum to reduce GHGs by 2035 (Kameyama et al., 2016). Although climate change is a global concern, its impacts are very much experienced locally and often managed through local governance systems (Measham et al., 2011; Birchall and Bonnett, 2021). Whilst the roles and responsibilities of Local Government Authorities (LGAs) are yet to be clarified (National Audit Office (NAO, 2021) they have a responsibility for creating and promoting good living conditions across the triple bottom line (i.e., social, economic, and environmental) within their communities, and their mandate is to measure and report GHG emissions (Granberg and Elander, 2007; Bulkeley and Kern, 2006; UK Government, 2015).

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) likewise have a mandate to report their GHG emissions (The Climate Change (Duties of Public Bodies: Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Order 2015 and Streamlined Energy and Carbon Reporting (SECR) scheme) and have considerable environmental impacts. They possess the capacity to influence social, economic and environmental aspects of society in recognition of the vast operational scope of the HEI sector; circa 2.5million enrolled students in the UK (Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA), 2021a); 223,525 academic staff working across 197 UK HEIs (HESA, 2021b); and over £37 billion annual operating expenditure (Universities UK, no date). HEIs have the educational and research capacities capable of informing decisions on sustainable carbon management and in combination with LGAs the potential exists for cross transferable knowledge and collaboration to reduce emissions across the public sector and wider society.

1.2 SCOPE OF THE RESEARCH TOPIC

This thesis explores the reliance on and attitudes to FF energy sources by Scottish public sector bodies in a bid to co-create an optimised stakeholder driven framework for sector bodies to reduce their FF use. It explores emissions associated with FF energy sources that is natural gas, other heating fuel, travel, transport fuel, and commuting, in tandem with the basket of seven GHGs specified under the Kyoto Protocol to develop a framework that public sector bodies could use to reduce reliance on FF energy sources. The thesis does not explicitly attempt to explore the range of individual GHGs, nor does it attempt to propose a CF definition however, it provides an overview of these subjects.

In this thesis the Scottish public sector refer to and encompassing those public bodies and organisations classed as major players as listed in Schedule 1 under The Climate Change (Duties of Public Bodies: Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Order 2015 (amended by the Amendment Order 2020). The public bodies listed in Schedule 1 include Local Authorities, Educational Institutions, Transport Partnerships, Integration Joint Boards, and other National and Regional public bodies such as the Scottish Prison Services, Police Authorities, Fire and Rescue Services, Scottish Environment Protection Agency, and Scottish Government amongst others are mandated to report on their climate change duties (Sustainable Scotland Network (SSN), 2020). The duties amongst others include to report annual quantitative data on their GHG emissions, providing a platform for data collation and assessment of emissions over time periods of this sector. Certain aspects of the thesis have a particular focus on LGAs and Universities in Scotland; in Chapters 5 and 6, reference is made to ‘Participating Organisation’. In the context of the thesis, participating organisations refer to those public sector bodies in Scotland (LGAs and HEIs) from which interviewed sector actors as part of the research are affiliated to.

1.3 RESEARCH JUSTIFICATION

The burning of FFs is the largest known contributor to climate change (Soeder, 2021) yet, responsible for 82% of global energy consumption with the remainder 18% from a combination of renewables, hydro and nuclear energy sources in 2022 (BP, 2023). Despite scientific evidence of the link between burning FFs in relation to anthropogenic climate change, and warnings of further warming and changes to the climate system resulting from continued emissions of GHGs (IPCC, 2021a), we are still heavily reliant on FFs. The impacts of the reliance on carbon intensive FF energy sources that is oil, coal and natural gas remains a course of concern for many governments across the globe and has led to actions, plans and road maps to decarbonise energy systems and rely more on low carbon and renewable energy sources. With coal being the dirtiest of FF energy sources (Soeder, 2021), not least for its global warming and air pollution contributions, it is no wonder it has been the focus of decarbonisation efforts with many governments including the UK setting out timelines to cease the use of coal power in its energy mix (Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (BEIS), Trevelyan, and Sharma, 2021). However, letters to the National Grid Electricity System Operator and coal plant operators on behalf of the UK government requesting the re-opening of

some coal fired plants to provide backup for winter energy supplies amidst the energy crisis (Department for Energy Security and Net Zero, BEIS, and Kwarteng, 2022) highlight the complexities of FF reliance. These complexities are further exacerbated by the evolving geopolitical earthquakes erupting in the nations of Ukraine, Russia, Israel and Gaza.

The role and significance of the public sector in reducing emissions, contributing to meeting national targets, and in fostering climate change resilient societies has been briefly discussed at the start of this chapter. Focusing on reducing FF emissions is a key part of reducing overall emissions, particularly in terms of heating emissions, and transport emissions which were projected by Hickman and Banister (2007) to rise beyond 2020. Therefore, there is a clear requirement to reduce reliance on FFs for example emissions from petrol, diesel and gas for meeting heating consumption demands. Scotland's progress in decarbonising electricity generation is well documented and makes for good readings; but with its refined ambition for net-zero emissions by 2045 urgent action is required by other sectors like the FF energy sector. Scotland's failure to meet its 2020 target of sourcing 11% of non-electrical heat demand from renewable sources (Committee on Climate Change (CCC, 2019b; 2020), implies the requirement to increase renewable heat capacity remains.

The search of literature (see Table 2.4) in the following chapter using the PRISMA approach revealed the lack of articles or conference papers focused on reducing public sector FF emissions. It is therefore on this premise that the aims and objectives of this research study are detailed in Section 1.4. Whilst studies relating to reducing FF emissions in Scotland have been undertaken, they do not specifically focus on HEIs and/or LGAs or more generally public sector bodies however, some may be relevant to the discussion about planning and decision-making on FF use in Scotland.

It may therefore be argued that studies specifically relating to reducing reliance on FFs in HEIs and LGAs is limited thereby justifying the importance of the research to address the gap and ultimately aid planning and decision making on FF reliance within the sector. Furthermore, although emissions associated with FF sources are often reported, they are reported individually. It may be possible to gather relevant data and ideas from various sources, nevertheless a lack of organisational reporting and

monitoring specifically on emissions associated with the collective use of FF sources required to monitor progress in reducing its reliance is apparent. As such this research develops a co-created stakeholder framework that Scottish public sector bodies can adopt for planning and decision making in relation to FF use and reporting. It represents the first decision making and planning framework drawn specifically from HEIs and LGAs and for use by the wider UK public sector.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTION, AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

Research Question:

Does a better understanding of an organisations emission profile enable the development of a decision-making and planning procedure to reduce FF reliance in public sector bodies?

Aim 1

To critically evaluate and understand reliance on FF as an energy source in Scotland's public sector, specifically LGAs and HEIs.

Objectives

- To conduct a systematic review of FF reliance by Scottish public sector from peer reviewed literature
- To establish a baseline assessment for the (former) School of Science and Sport (SoSS), University of the West of Scotland (UWS)
- To analyse and compare sources and quantities of corporate emissions reported by public sector bodies to the Scottish Government

Aim 2

To develop a framework for planning and decision-making on FF use for Scotland's public sector bodies

Objectives

- To conduct semi-structured interviews with sector actors and map potential pathways to minimise reliance on FF energy
- To consolidate the findings from the experimental aspects of the research into a framework

1.5 THESIS OUTLINE

The thesis is made up of an abstract and eight chapters, three of which (Chapters 4, 5 and 6) are experimental chapters from which a framework for public sector bodies on FF reliance is developed.

- Chapter 1 sets the scene for the research undertaken by introducing the thesis and justifying the need for the research. It details the research question, aims and objectives, and states the research contribution to knowledge.
- Chapter 2 presents a focused and up-to-date review of literature and subjects related to the research topic. Through a systematic review of the Scopus database the chapter highlights a gap in decision and planning procedures to reduce reliance on FFs in the public sector.
- Chapter 3 details the methods employed in collecting, generating, and analysing data in investigating the research question, aims and objectives. This includes a justification of the methods utilised and an explanation of the approaches taken using well-designed figures and tables.
- Chapter 4 presents the CF assessment of an operational unit at the UWS contributing to the evaluation of the public sectors reliance on FF energy sources. The chapter likewise highlights a requirement for specific reporting on emissions resulting directly from the combination of FF energy and provides recommendations for units within HEIs to improve their CF.
- Chapter 5 analyses mandatory climate change reports submitted by public bodies to the Scottish Government, identifying an increase in reliance of FF energy sources against a backdrop of overall reductions in reported emissions. This chapter provides an analysis and comparison of the sources and amounts of emissions reported to the Scottish Government in contribution to the evaluation of the sectors reliance on FFs.
- Chapter 6 provides an analysis of responses from the Scottish public sector actors who participated in the semi-structured interviews as part of the research. Using thematic analysis, five key themes are generated providing valuable insight into understanding the public sector reliance on the use of FFs.
- Chapter 7 consolidates the findings of Chapters 4, 5 and 6 creating a novel framework diagram as an output of the research, for Scottish public sector bodies to address reduction of reliance on FF.

- Finally, Chapter 8 concludes the thesis by summarising the main research findings, demonstrating the original contribution to knowledge and providing suggestions for further areas of inquiry.

CHAPTER 2:
LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents a review of literature and subjects relating to the research topic bringing the research into perspective. It covers carbon management including specifically within UK LGAs and HEIs, methods of calculating a CF, carbon emissions reduction, and includes an overview of Scotland's position on emission reductions. It further, highlights the gap and need for this research through an attempted systematic review of relevant literature.

There have been growing calls for a fossil free globe with the G7 leaders agreeing to phase out FF use by the year 2100 (Connolly, 2015) and an international movement calling on organisations and individuals to divest their financial support for the FF industry (Fossil Free, no date). Carbon management strategies within organisations is growing in popularity due to the perceived contribution organisations can make to reducing global emissions (Sullivan and Gouldson, 2013), in reducing their emissions (Mahmoudian et al., 2021), financial saving opportunities through energy efficiency measures (Alsaifi, Elnahass and Salama, 2020), and because of stakeholder pressure (Villena and Dhanorkar, 2020).

Focusing on the 'basket of seven' GHGs, it relies on careful carbon accounting (e.g., measuring organisational CF), reduction in energy use, raw material consumption and waste generation (Mahmoudian et al., 2021; Chan, 2009; Jowitt and Johnson, 2014; Tuesta, Soler and Feliu, 2021). Implementing such strategies would ultimately result in emissions reduction, yield cost savings for organisations, other benefits which cut across the triple bottom line (Chan, 2009; NetRegs, 2017a; NetRegs, 2017b; (World Health Organisation (WHO), 2014). For example, improving energy efficiency in buildings will decrease the building's energy consumption, operating costs, and its CF (Kneifel, 2010).

2.2 CARBON MANAGEMENT

As organisations bring to the fore of their agendas the need for reducing GHG emissions, it ultimately puts pressure on them to implement carbon management policies and practices. This often involves creating an inventory of emission sources, understanding the emissions profile, and taking steps to reduce emissions, including measuring and recording corresponding emissions, and establishing a baseline from

which subsequent emissions can be measured against. It also involves the efficient use of energy, investing in research and technology to develop and capitalise on alternative renewable and low carbon energy sources, including carbon capture and storage (CCS), and accountability through measurement and reporting (Chan, 2009; Jowitt and Johnson, 2014; Revelle and Shapero, 1978; Bui et al., 2018).

Purman (2008) and Pandey et al. (2011) suggest that emissions are measured, either directly or by using emission factors or models to calculate emissions. Whilst organisations are under increasing pressure to measure their CF, there is a lack of a clear definition of the term 'CF' and how it should be calculated, within public and academic domains (Wiedmann and Minx, 2008; Pandey et al., 2011). CFs are often used to describe emissions associated with CO₂ or other GHGs in CO₂ equivalents (CO₂e) (Pandey et al., 2011; Robertson and Grace, 2004; Shine et al., 2005), based on their Global Warming Potential (GWP). GWP is the heat absorbed by GHGs and relates all GHGs to CO₂ which has a GWP of 1. CH₄ has a 100-year GWP of 25, which in simple terms means it is 25 times more potent as a GHG than CO₂ (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2022). GWPs are occasionally updated in line with international guidelines for example when scientific research identify changes to lifespan of GHGs (UK Government, 2023). Table 2.1 shows a list of GHGs used in the UK and their corresponding GWP. The different types and variations in GHGs, and their corresponding 100-year GWPs pose potential difficulties an organisation can have when calculating their CF (UK Government, 2023).

Table 2.1: List of GHGs used in the UK and their corresponding GWP (Source: UK Government, 2023)

Greenhouse gas	Lifetime (years)*	100 years GWP (AR5)
Carbon dioxide	50-200	1
Carbon dioxide as Carbon	50-200	3.66667
Methane	12	28
Nitrous oxide	114	265
HFC-23	270	12,400
HFC-32	4.9	677
HFC-41	2.4	116
HFC-43-10mee	15.9	1,650
HFC-125	29	3,170
HFC-134	9.6	1,120
HFC-134a	14	1,300
HFC-143	3.5	328
HFC-143a	52	4,800
HFC-152	0.6	16
HFC-152a	1.4	138
HFC-161	0.3	4
HFC-227ea	34.2	3,350
HFC-236cb	13.6	1,210
HFC-236ea	10.7	1,330
HFC-236fa	240	8,060
HFC-245ca	6.2	716
HFC-245fa	7.6	858
HFC-365mfc	8.6	804
Perfluoromethane	50,000	6,630
Perfluoroethane	10,000	11,100
Perfluoropropane	2,600	8,900
Perfluorobutane	2,600	9,200
Perfluorocyclobutane	3,200	9,540
Perfluoropentane	4,100	8,550
Perfluorohexane	3,200	7,910
Perfluorodecalin	>1,000	7,190
Perfluoropropene	>1,000	9,200
Sulphur hexafluoride	3,200	23,500
Nitrogen trifluoride	740	16,100

* Atmospheric residence time, with some being adsorbed and others degraded

Adding to the complexity is Wiedmann and Minx (2008), who argue that CFs should measure CO₂ emissions only and other GHGs should not be included; where other GHGs are included, it should be termed ‘climate footprint’. They argue that some GHGs are not carbon based and are difficult to quantify due to lack of data; and conversions to CO₂ based on assumptions will likely increase uncertainties and errors in

footprint calculations. Wright, Kemp, and William (2014) do a thorough analysis of the factors crucial to defining the term CF, i.e., questions around the life cycle perspective, the metrics and methodology, for examples, ‘what does it measure?’ ‘is it a new indicator?’ ‘what GHGs to include?’ ‘how comparable and reliable are the boundary metrics?’ based upon which they propose their definition of a CF. They propose it as total CO₂ and CH₄ emissions only, considering all relevant sources, sinks and storage of a defined boundary (population, system, or activity) as CO₂e.

Whilst an agreed definition of ‘CF’ continues to be debated in literature, establishing, or proposing its definition falls outside the scope of this thesis. The arguments for CFs to measure CO₂ emissions only (Wiedmann and Minx, 2008; Durojaye, Laseinde and Oluwafemi, 2020), or CO₂ and CH₄ only (Wright, Kemp, and William, 2014) have sound basis, although current organisational CF reporting of CO₂ and other GHGs in CO₂e is well established (Valls-Val and Bovea, 2021). It forms the basis of baseline measurements for many organisations and as such the term ‘CF’ encompassing other GHGs from the ‘basket of seven’ in CO₂e is adopted for this research. Furthermore, it is the basis for which public bodies report on their corporate emissions to the Scottish Government and the CF metric covers emissions from the ‘basket of seven’, aligning consistently and reliably with the analysis undertaken in this research.

2.2.1 Carbon Management in UK HEIs

The UK HE sector, like other business sectors of the UK, is legally committed to reducing GHG emissions resulting from their operations in contribution to achieving net-zero emissions target by 2050 set by The Climate Change Act 2008 (as amended). The Climate Change (Duties of Public Bodies: Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Order (2015) as amended requires HEIs to annually report on compliance with climate change duties, whilst there are 27 registered education providers in England required to report their emissions under the Government’s SECR scheme (Office for Students, 2020). Sector specific requirements, such as Carbon Reduction Commitment (CRC), carbon reduction requirements for the Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE), and those set by the Universities and Colleges Climate Commitment for Scotland (UCCCfS), all indicate that the sector has a key part to play in contributing to achieving UK emission targets.

Through climate change legislation and sector specific requirements, UK HEIs (and indeed other public sector bodies) have developed and implemented Carbon Management Plans (CMPs) (Mazhar et al., 2019). However, Robinson, Kemp and Williams (2015) demonstrated through the application of a ‘reality check’ against carbon reduction targets, that CMPs were not a good indicator of future performance and underestimates the challenges faced by HEIs in reducing emissions. Some HEIs, however, have embedded the results of their CF into their CMPs and agreed emission reduction action plans, for example De Montford University, University of Leicester (Ozawa-Meida et al., 2013; Mazhar et al., 2019), and UWS (See Chapter 4). Despite the focus on carbon management at HEIs, a report reveals that 13% of HEIs do not have a carbon reduction plan (Environmental Association for Universities and Colleges (EAUC) et al., 2017), with few having a grasp of their GHG emission profile resulting directly and indirectly from their activities (Robinson et al., 2018).

Reports of previous surveys reveal overall sector emissions increased in Scotland (between 2007/08 and 2014/15) attributable to increased reporting of business travel emissions and increased provision of data for other emission sources, (EAUC, 2016) but decreased by 7% in English universities in 2015/16 based on a Britegreen (2017) report, with emission reductions attributed to overall improvements in energy management within the sector. The Britegreen report does not provide information on the emissions from different sources for example business travel, nor the improvements which yielded energy efficiency for example. However, these reports suggested most UK HEIs were not on track to meet their reduction targets (EAUC et al., 2015; EAUC, 2016; BriteGreen, 2017). Common to the reports referred to above is evidence of emission reductions however, only by some HEIs, and the conclusion that the UK HEI Sector was not on track to meet its voluntary carbon reduction target. A 30% voluntary emissions reduction target by 2020/21 compared to the 2009/10 baseline was introduced by the 2017 Clean Growth Strategy for the wider public and HE sectors in England (BEIS, 2018). The Climate Commission for UK Higher and Further Education, a partnership of Association of Colleges, EAUC, GuildHE and Universities UK created in 2019 (EAUC, 2022) have suggested that HEIs aim for net-zero GHG emissions for Scope 1 and 2 by 2030, and Scope 3 net-zero GHG emissions by 2050 (Office for Students, 2020).

Although these surveys suggest evidence of carbon reductions for some UK HE institutions, they corroborated the identified need for an organisational shift in shared responsibilities for carbon management and a uniform approach to carbon reduction across the sector (EAUC, 2016; BriteGreen, 2017). More recently, academic papers introducing a uniform standard to CF calculations for HEIs (and can be used by other organisations) (Robinson et al., 2018) and presenting a CF assessment tool (Valls-Val and Bovea, 2022) have been published. It would have been appropriate to report on progress of UK HEIs in achieving the 2020 carbon reduction target however, both Britegreen and the EAUC have not produced updated reports since these reports were published (Office for Students, 2020). This is possibly an impact of the replacement of the HEFCE with the Office for Students (EM Magazine, 2020) and its announcement in 2018 that English HEIs would not have to submit carbon emission data to the HESA (Office for Students, 2020).

It is worth highlighting the potential implication of the HEIs forced move to online delivery on emission, and although Filimonau, et al (2021) found the CF of a mid-sized UK University to have reduced during the Coronavirus Disease of 2019 (COVID-19) lockdown, these reductions were enforced due to a lack of campus activity as opposed to being policy driven. However, Filimonau, et al (2021) also found that emissions associated with online teaching and learning were substantial and as much as those associated with University commute pre lockdown. The decision to implement online teaching and learning will require consideration of a range of implications cutting across the triple bottom line for example environmental impacts like air quality, social impacts like internet accessibility and increased household energy consumption for staff and students, and the resulting economic impacts to staff, students and the institution, amongst others. It is therefore necessary for the implications of this move to be considered carefully (Filimonau, et al., 2021).

The growth and rapid expansion of HEIs (Altan, 2010; Erickson, Hanna and Walker, 2021), as well as being successful incubators of innovation (Robinson et al., 2018) with capacity for intellectual and practical leadership mounts the pressure on HEIs, to reduce their emissions. They should be motivated by the many benefits of carbon management strategies including the implementation of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Milner, Davies and Wilkinson, 2012; Okereke, 2007; Ramaswamy et al., 2021)

to do much more particularly with the increasing physical size of many HEIs resulting from student population growth (Klein-Banai and Theis, 2013). However, increase in physical size of HEIs may bring about an increase in its energy use and travel requirements, which are reliant on FF energy sources. The likelihood of increased consumption being impacted by the move to hybrid teaching with regards to the long-term physical footprints of HEIs, may be farfetched when considering a few factors. For example, the potential requirement to keep buildings running even when not in use (continued emissions), in addition to emissions associated with online delivery which can be substantial as found by Filimonau, et al., 2021, and the transfer of the cost of some of these implications to both facilitators and recipients of online education provisions. For carbon management in HEIs to be worthwhile it is vital to overcome the barriers of time, cost, and data reliability in assessing Scope 3 emissions (Robinson et al., 2018), financial and staff resources (EAUC et al., 2017) and focus on the use of low-carbon and renewable sources energy in tandem with divestment from the FF industry (Fossil Free, no date).

2.2.2 Carbon Management in UK LGAs

There are 353 principal councils in England, 32 in Scotland, 22 in Wales and 11 in Northern Ireland (NAO, 2017; Office for National Statistics (ONS), 2016a). This is the level of government at which community action is often taken, highlighting the significance of LGAs as drivers for addressing climate change. With responsibility for administering public finances in the provision of services to local communities like implementing the transport and housing measures identified by the Scottish Government (CCC, 2021), it is best placed to adapt to climate change impacts experienced at a local scale, opening them up to potential criticism and accountability from local populations on actions or inactions towards climate change in comparison to business and industry within their LGA areas (Measham et al., 2011; Birchall and Bonnett, 2021; Chou, 2021).

LGAs in the UK have an estimated annual energy consumption of at least 26 billion kWh, equating to more than 6.9 Million tonnes of CO₂ emissions and corresponds to energy expenditure of around £750 million per year (Carbon Trust, 2020). With the duty to promote their communities' social, economic, and environmental well-being, including significant areas of influence over energy planning and carbon reduction

(Bulkeley and Kern, 2006), LGAs have played an active role in tackling climate change for over 25 years (Gudde et al., 2021). They continue to have a key role in combating climate change and its impacts, not least in reducing their energy consumption amongst other drivers. This in addition to changes in the climate change regulatory environment, for example The Climate Change (Duties of Public Bodies: Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Order (2015) as amended and other organisational benefits associated with sustainable development (Rugg, 2004), has led LGAs to implement carbon management or emission reduction strategies.

In their efforts to achieve reductions, LGAs face the combined challenges of lack of adequate resources, financial planning, competing requirements to fund public services and climate emergency activities, particularly amidst fears of an economic recession following the COVID-19 lockdown (Jackson and Lynch, 2011; Gudde et al., 2021) and the Ukraine-Russia and Israel-Gaza wars. Despite the financial challenges, radical changes to renewable energy schemes or policies, and the challenge of transiting to a low carbon economy, some LGAs have committed to transition into a low carbon economy and set net-zero carbon targets from their operations by 2030 (Bramah, 2016; Tingey and Webb, 2020). In a further show of commitment by LGAs the majority have declared a Climate Emergency in direct relation to their operations or wider communities (Gudde et al., 2021; Tingey and Webb, 2020), however for these commitments to come to fruition several key issues need to be addressed. For examples, the issues associated with the scale of the investment and funding required by LGAs to deliver net zero emissions (Tingey and Webb, 2020; Gudde et al., 2021) exacerbated by issues associated with austerity and devolution (Kuzemko and Britton, 2020); concerns regarding effective community engagement and ability for LGAs to carry their communities with them in tackling climate change by increasing citizens' awareness of climate change (Gudde et al., 2021; Ruiz-Campillo, Castán Broto, and Westman, 2021); and limitations in the skills and resources within local authorities and communities, and fostering a joint up approach between central and local governments (Borrownan, Singh and Bulleid, 2020). Gudde et al. (2021) identify that LGAs are taking different approaches to tackling climate change which highlights the need for inter Authority and departmental collaborations. They likewise identify strong leadership from government, clear planning on climate action, and adequate resources as necessary to tackle the so-called Climate Emergency, whilst acknowledging the strain on LGA finances through

additional external factors like the coronavirus pandemic, the Ukraine war and financial market due to Government fiscal policies. Furthermore, they identify the lack of a coherent governance mechanism linking national and local government aspiration towards net-zero carbon commitments, proposing a new governance framework for local area ‘Climate Contract’.

Whilst the political desire to tackle climate change through LGA statements on or commitments to Climate Emergency is evident, alongside the progress being made by larger LGAs compared to smaller LGAs in terms of mobilising investment and delivery planning, the overall picture appears to be small scale, and one of variable progress in climate action by LGAs (Gudde et al., 2021; Tingey and Webb, 2020). Recent surveys into the performance of LGAs in relation to climate change emergency declarations and action across the UK have been undertaken and reveal similar findings. The Local Government Association (2020) conducted a survey to assess LGA climate change action and to establish policy change requirements to effectively tackle climate change across LGAs in England. The survey identified some of the main barriers to climate change action reported by respondents as (i) lack of funding, (ii) legislative barriers for example in building regulations and planning legislation, plus a lack of coherent national and local strategies, and (iii) limited workforce capacity and expertise. Correspondingly, the main areas of policy change support identified by respondents include lobby for change on funding policies and legislation and good practice guidance including for sector specific Scope 3 emissions (Local Government Association, 2020). APSE Energy (2020) similarly conducted an online survey of LGA sector actors throughout the UK in a bid to understand their views on LGA climate emergency declarations. The results of the survey reveal variable progress in climate change action across LGAs and identify (i) lack of significant funding from central government and financial constraints, (ii) uncertainty in government energy and planning policy (for example fracking licence approval by then UK Prime Minister Liz Truss and its revocation by the next Prime Minister Rishi Sunak within months), and (iii) and lack of resources and expertise for example in ‘green economic planning’, ‘low carbon procurement’ and ‘low carbon budgeting’, as significant barriers.

2.3 METHODS OF CALCULATING CFs

There are various environmental audit systems for example Environmental Accounting (EAc), Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC), Environmental Auditing (EA) and Environmental Management Systems (EMS) (Fet, 1998) used for assessing environmental management impacts at different levels i.e., micro, meso and macro (see Table 1.3). Carbon management impacts consider impacts ranging from individuals to organisation at a micro level (for example reducing personal and organisational travel requirements); impacts encompassing sectors, sub-regions, and nations at a meso level (for example implementation of actions by nations to limit carbon impacts), and international impacts at a macro level (for example international agreements like the Kyoto Protocol) (Molthan-Hill et al., 2020). Arena and de Rosa (2003) suggest LCA to be the only comprehensive legitimate method accepted by the scientific community for assessing environmental impacts of products and services through their life cycle. This is a couple of decades ago but remains true due to the development of LCA over the decades, from its conceptualisation and standardisation to the breadth and depth of its applications. It has seen the expansion of the range of environmental impact categories considered, and the broadening of social and economic impacts (Guinée et al., 2011), culminating in recent developments of conceptual guides of Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment which integrates LCA, LCC and Social Life Cycle analysis (Heijungs, Huppies and Guinee, 2010; Haque, 2020). LCA assists environmental assessments (Guinée et al., 2011) and plays an important role in tracking emissions of an entire supply chain, CF calculations and in the establishment of protocols and guides for GHG accounting (Pandey et al., 2011; Wiedmann and Minx, 2008; Matthews et al. 2008a). Carbon Trust (2018) identifies three main types of CF for organisations as follows: (i) organisational (based on GHG protocol, an international standardised framework for measuring and managing GHG direct and indirect emissions and must include Scopes 1 and 2 emissions; with flexibility for reporting Scope 3 emissions), (ii) product (based on Publicly Available Specification (PAS) 2050 and measures emissions associated with the entirety of a product's life from cradle to grave which could be a service or a product) and (iii) supply chain CFs. Based on Carbon Trust (2018), Figure 2.1 shows the different boundaries of organisational, product and supply chain footprints.

Figure 2.1: Boundaries of organisational, product and supply chain footprints (Source: Based on Carbon Trust, 2018).

It should be noted that GHG accounting assessments for specific regions like countries have also been established and based on two fundamental accounting principles, i.e., the traditional production-based principle which accounts for a region's GHG emissions and the complementary consumption-based principles which takes account of the region's international trade emissions (for example emissions associated with the

production and consumption of purchased goods and services) (Wiedmann et al., 2010; Fan et al., 2016). There are three main approaches to performing LCA for CFs that are currently being used: bottom up or process analysis (PA), top down or input-output (IO) (Pandey et al., 2011; Wiedmann and Minx, 2008; Matthews et al. 2008a), and a combination of both approaches also referred to as a Hybrid-EIO-LCA approach (for example: Pandey et al., 2011; Wiedmann and Minx, 2008; Gómez et al., 2016; Durojaye, Laseinde and Oluwafemi, 2020). IO analysis has various applications including in economic input-output (EIO) analysis (Matthews et al. 2008a and 2008b; Pandey et al., 2011), environmental extended input-output (EEIO) analysis (Gómez et al., 2016; Larsen et al., 2013; Ozawa-Meida et al., 2013) and environmentally extended multi-region-input-output (EEMRIO) analysis (Alvarez, Blanquer and Rubio, 2014). The key differences in IO analysis relate to the scope for which supply chain activities are tracked in monetary and environmental terms for example, for specific industry supply chains ((EIO and EEIO), and for national and international supply chains (EEMRIO). Much research into IO and PA approaches have been conducted, and there are advantages and disadvantages to both approaches, (Table 2.2). In practice, organisations are now using CF results to identify opportunities to reduce costs (for monetary benefits) associated with their operations (Zvezdov and Hack, 2016), and to meet their legal obligations for measuring and reporting their environmental impacts (Department for Energy Security and Net Zero, Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs, and BEIS (2019)). For example, reducing utility costs through energy efficient operations, consuming less energy and use of more energy efficient machinery and equipment.

Table 2.2: Comparison of Bottom-up and Top-down approaches for CF estimation

(Source: the table is based on information from Wiedmann and Minx, 2008; Nicholls et al., 2015).

PA – bottom-up approach	IO – top-down approach
Better suited for micro systems like an individual product or service, or relatively small groups of products and particular processes (cradle to grave estimation) due to local level and finer resolution data collection and processing	Better suited for meso (for example sector level and governments) and macro systems (aggregate of meso systems) like international and global industries (comprehensive and robust estimation) due to higher level data collection of costs, outputs and emissions
Suffers from a system boundary problem - only on-site, most first order (for example energy consumed by direct supplier), and some second-order impacts (for example energy consumed by the supplier of the direct suppliers)	Accounts for higher order impacts and sets the whole economic system as boundary (at the expense of site-specific detail)
Not suitable for calculating footprints for macro systems due to its assumption of homogeneity of price, outputs and emissions at sector level	Limited suitability for calculating footprints for micro systems
Potential for specific and dedicated strategies and incentives to reduce emissions in a micro system	Potential for overall efficiency gains across meso/macro systems
Site specific accuracy of data	Utilises aggregated data which may not accurately represent site specific conditions
Non-standardised measurements with potential to differ from site to site	Standardised measurements
Requires more staffing resources to for estimation	Requires fewer staffing resources for estimation
Limited data sources and potential to utilise a top-down database as proxy for missing data	Availability of a range of data sources

In their assessment of a university campus's CF using a LCA approach, Clabeaux, et al. (2020) concluded that there was a better understanding of the impact of operations particularly resulting from electricity generation and transportation with a potential to influence changes in the campus operations. Gómez, et al. (2016) suggest that the application of CFs could help identify and monitor key components of environmental sustainability performance and awareness among stakeholders. Lee (2011) also identifies the potential for cost savings in supply chain through energy efficient operations management, suggesting it may be more cost effective for organisations in comparison to reducing emissions from direct or purchased electricity. However, consideration will need to be given to the initial costs of implementing carbon reduction measures, and compared to the associated short, medium and/or long-term cost savings, to enable informed decisions to be made by an organisation.

2.4 GHG EMISSIONS REDUCTION

Reducing emissions is a key part of addressing climate change, at the same time presenting with challenges globally, nationally, and similarly for organisations. Take for instance IPCCs suggestion with high confidence of an almost linear correlation between cumulative human induced climate change and the corresponding global warming caused (IPCC, 2021a). Increasing amounts of GHGs in the atmosphere is another climate change challenge, detrimental to humans' mental health and well-being, earth's natural systems and impacting poorer nations (IPCC, 2014; Prowse and Snilstveit, 2010); resulting in calls for urgent concerted action in tackling climate change (Keeling, et al., 2005; IPCC, 2007; Uitto et al., 2017). In the media there are increasing reports of predicted consequences of human induced climate change for example wildfires, tropical storms, sea level rise, loss of ice, heat waves and long periods of draught (IPCC, 2013; IPCC, 2014). The recognition of human induced climate change has led to international action. Figure 2.2 shows a timeline of some international actions taken by way of reports and conferences since the establishment of the IPCC in 1988.

Figure 2.2: Timeline of reports and conferences on Climate Change showing international action (post creation of IPCC in 1988) (IPCC, 2010; UNFCCC, 2016; UNFCCC, 2017; UNFCCC, 2018; UNFCCC, 2019; UNFCCC, 2021b; UNFCCC, 2021c; IPCC, 2021b). *Source: Author.*

The EU requires its member states to participate in its initiatives to reduce GHG emissions, act to achieve reduction targets, and increase the efficiency and use of renewable energy. Some of these initiatives include: (i) EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), (ii) Renewable Energy Directive, (iii) Energy Efficiency Directive, (iv) New car and van CO₂ targets, (v) 2030 Climate & Energy Framework (EC, no date). As of January 2020, the UK ceased to be a member state of the EU. However, current legislation was transposed at national level and is still applicable post Brexit. For example, the statutory instrument ‘The Greenhouse Gas Emissions Trading Scheme Auctioning Regulations 2021’ which came into force in April 2021 to ensure that emissions from sectors covered by the EU ETS remain covered by a carbon pricing policy post Brexit (The Greenhouse Gas Emissions Trading Scheme Auctioning Regulations 2021, 2021).

The UK Climate Change Act 2008 (2050 Target Amendment) Order 2019, and the Scottish Climate Change (Emissions Reduction Target) (Scotland) Act 2019 regulate the reduction of net GHG emissions with targets to reduce emissions to Net-zero GHGs by 2050 in the UK, and by 2045 in Scotland, based on the 1990 baseline. The Act places the onus on the Secretary of State or Scottish Minister to achieve reduction targets however, there is no direct provision for measuring or targeting reduction of FF emissions within the Act(s). Whilst there are also no specific targets set for public sector bodies like HEIs, within the Act, the HEI sector aspires to exceed its sector-level targets (Saha et al., 2021). The Act covers all the UK however Wales, Northern Ireland and Scotland have dedicated reduction targets. The CCC recommended new targets following the assessment of the UK’s long-term emission targets of net-zero GHGs by 2050 for the whole of the UK (CCC, 2019a), recently passed by Parliament. Table 2.3 shows a breakdown of interim emission reduction targets up to 2050 for the whole of the UK, Wales, and Scotland.

Table 2.3: Breakdown of interim GHG Emission Reduction Targets up to 2050 for the UK, Wales, and Scotland.

Country	Baseline Year	Reduction Targets up to 2050
UK	1990	68% from baseline by 2030 78% from baseline by 2035 Net-zero by 2050 (UK Government, 2021)
Wales	1990	63% from baseline by 2030 89% from baseline by 2040 Net-zero by 2050 (Welsh Government, 2021)
Scotland	1990	75% from baseline by 2030 90% from baseline by 2040 Net-zero by 2045 (Climate Change (Emissions Reduction Targets) (Scotland) Act 2019)

The UK Government, and Devolved Administrations, have taken several actions in its bid to reduce GHG emissions and meet its reduction targets and EU targets. They include but are not limited to: (i) setting climate change targets to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050, (ii) incorporation of international aviation and shipping emissions into the Carbon Budget for consistent accounting, (iii) generation of 50 % of electricity from low carbon sources, (iv) ambitious strategies to support decarbonisation in polluting industries, (v) being the first G7 country to action support for a transition to clean, green energy in the oil and gas industry’s (50% reduction by 2030), (vi) launch of ‘Together For Our Planet’ campaign calling on all to take action on climate change, (vii) the public sector decarbonisation scheme, (viii) Scottish green public sector estate decarbonisation scheme, and (ix) the UK Prime Minister’s announcement of 18 deals worth £9.7 billion in support of green growth (UK Government, 2021; BEIS, 2022; Salix, 2022; HM Government 2021).

2.4.1 Overview of Scotland's progress on carbon emissions reduction

In September 2019 The Climate Change (Emissions Reduction Targets) (Scotland) Act 2019 gained Royal Assent, amending The Climate Change (Scotland) Act 2009 by setting new targets of net-zero GHG emissions by 2045. The Act requires Scottish ministers to ensure that the interim emission targets from the 1990 CO₂ emissions baseline year is met as follows: (a) 2020 is at least 56% lower than the baseline (a 58.7% reduction was achieved (Scottish Government, 2022)); (b) 2030 is at least 75% lower than the baseline; and (c) 2040 is at least 90% lower than the baseline. It revokes previous annual targets set by The Climate Change (Annual Targets) (Scotland) Order 2010, 2011 and 2016. Scottish ministers are also required to seek the CCC's advice on setting annual reduction targets, and to publish the government's plans and policies to achieve them for example the allocation of £1.8 billion towards low carbon infrastructure investment in the 2020-21 Scottish Budget (Scottish Government, 2020a). In line with the Act (as amended), the CCC publishes annual reports on Scotland's progress in meeting emission reduction targets with recent reports suggesting it is still performing well in comparison to other countries in the UK, and the UK (CCC, 2019b; CCC, 2020; CCC, 2021). Nevertheless, much more is required to improve the 75% fall in emissions over the last decade (between 2009 and 2019) attributed to the power sector decarbonisation (CCC, 2021).

It is important to note that there is a two-year time lag in the publishing of national and local annual GHG emission estimates by UK government(s) for example the 2022 reports relate to 2020 emissions (DECC, 2021). The Scottish Government (2022) Scottish Greenhouse Gas Emissions 2020 presents two measures of GHSs: source emissions and emissions for reporting against targets. The former estimates Scotland's emissions to be 40 MtCO_{2e} representing a 51% reduction between 1990 and 2020 (12% decrease from 2019), whilst the latter estimates emissions to have reduced by 58.7% between the same period, exceeding the 56% target set by The Climate Change (Emissions Reduction Targets) (Scotland) Act 2019 (Scottish Government, 2022). Although Scotland has seen the virtual elimination of emissions associated with coal-fired electricity generation in the power sector, there was a rise in emissions between 2017 and 2018 attributed almost entirely to increased emissions from power stations. This was a result of the increased demand in natural gas (a FF) generated electricity following the shutdown of reactors at a Scottish nuclear power station in 2018 (Scottish

Government, 2020b; Keane, 2020). Between 2019 and 2020 however, decrease in emissions were largely the result of reduced emissions from transport (combination of domestic, international aviation and shipping) due to forced restrictions brought about by Covid-19, and in energy supply emissions. The CCCs 10th report to the Scottish government recommends it to complete a comprehensive, detailed policy framework for its policy priorities to include transforming buildings to low-carbon heating systems (building decarbonisation) and decarbonising transport, amongst others to allow Scotland meets its 2030 reduction target (CCC, 2021).

In 2020, Scottish domestic transport emissions (excluding international aviation and shipping) decreased significantly by 20.9% (2.5 MtCO_{2e}), however accounts for 24% (9.5 MtCO_{2e}) of the total Scottish emissions in 2020. They are the largest contributor to the 2020 Scottish emissions and the sector is deemed as slowing overall emissions reduction, despite the forced reductions of the lockdown. This is because domestic transport emissions decreased by only 29.9% between 1990 and 2020, in comparison to a 51% reduction in overall emissions over the same period, considering that with lockdown lifted subsequent annual emissions are likely to rise significantly (Scottish Government, 2022). Emissions from the public category (mainly from natural gas use in public buildings) and the residential category (dominated by direct fuel combustion in households) on the other hand together accounted for 17.3% of total Scottish emissions in 2020. Whilst residential category emissions have decreased by 25.5% and by 51.4% for public category emissions between 1990 and 2020, residential category emissions have fluctuated over the past six years from 2015 to 2020 (Scottish Government, 2022). Residential category emissions decreased by 1.5% between 2018 and 2019 possibly driven by the warmer first quarter of 2019 but increased slightly by similar percentage (1.4%) between 2019 and 2020 possibly due to more people working from home during lockdown (Scottish Government, 2021a). The minimum temperature during Scottish winter (December to February) for 2016/17 was 0.8°C; – 1.2°C for 2017/18; – 0.2°C for 2018/19; and 0.4°C for 2019/20 (Jaganmohan, 2022) and likely partly responsible for the fluctuating residential category emissions.

Scotland's position on reducing carbon emissions is reflected in its legally binding target to reduce emissions to Net-zero levels by 2045. Scotland hosted COP26 held in Glasgow (31 October to 12 November 2021) raising the local population's (Glasgow

City Council, 2021a; 2021b) and international awareness on climate change, the drastic need to collectively reduce GHG emissions, and stimulating a global net-zero emissions campaign through global pledges and policies on climate action (ukcop26.org, 2021).

This review has so far been in relation to the subject area of carbon management and associated topics mainly with respect to the UK and specifically Scotland. In terms of its specific relation to the public sector or public sector bodies decision making on FF use, a systematic search is undertaken as shown in the following section.

2.5 LITERATURE SEARCH

The purpose of this literature search is to identify and summarise any existing evidence on decision and planning procedures to reduce FF reliance in the public sector using the PRISMA guide (Page et al., 2021). An explicit statement of the objective is structured according to the population, intervention, comparison, outcomes (PICO) framework suggested in the PRISMA guidance as follows: This review intended to evaluate the decision and planning procedures to reduce FF use in public sector bodies.

The inclusion and exclusion criteria to determine eligible literature was likewise structured using the PICO framework as follows:

Population: the public sector (including HEIs and LGAs)

Intervention: FF use reduction

Comparison: no comparison intervention was projected for this search

Outcomes: decision and planning procedure to reduce FF use in the public sector.

The Scopus abstract and citation electronic database which hosts and accesses significant peer-reviewed literature in several fields including science and technology from all over the world was used to conduct the search for literature (Scopus, 2022). The date range used for the search was between 2002 and 2022, to take account of the coming into force of the Climate Change Act 2008, with literature results restricted by document type to articles and conference proceedings reported in English language only.

The Scopus advanced search function allowed for a structured search aided by use of operators such as 'AND' and 'OR' to be carried out. Using keywords identified in

developing the explicit statement of search objective from the PICO framework, a total of 12 search strings were inputted into the syntax required by the Scopus database on 12 February 2023. Half of these yielded nil literature results whilst the other half yielded varying literature results. Table 2.4 shows the number of literature results yielded for each successful search strings however, the search string yielding the most literature results of 511 is used as the basis for the literature selection process that is (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("fossil fuel dependence*") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (public sector*)) AND DOCTYPE (ar OR cp) AND PUBYEAR > 2002 AND PUBYEAR < 2022 AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")).

Table 2.4: Scopus Structured Search Strings and Number of Results Relating to ‘Public Sector’

Search string	Document type	Publication year range	Language	Search results (n)
("fossil fuel dependence*") AND (public sector*)	ar OR cp	2002 to 2022	English	2
("fossil fuel reliance*") AND (public sector*)	ar OR cp	2002 to 2022	English	1
("fossil fuel*") AND (public sector*)	ar OR cp	2002 to 2022	English	511
("fossil fuel*") AND ("Higher Education Institution*" OR local government authority*)	ar OR cp	2002 to 2022	English	18
("fossil fuel*") AND ("Higher Education Institution*" OR local government authority* OR public sector*)	ar OR cp	2002 to 2022	English	26
("fossil fuel reduction*") AND (public sector*)	ar OR cp	2002 to 2022	English	3

The literature selection process of the was attempted in three stages, the first involving checking the title of each literature result for the inclusion of “fossil fuel” as a sequence words, with 20 literature results included at this stage. The second stage involved checking the inclusion in their abstracts the sequence of words “fossil fuel” AND, either higher education institution, or local government authority or public sector; of which only 4 met this criterion and 2 of which were by same author a year apart. None of the abstracts checked contained local government authority” or “higher education institution” or even “university” however, 3 of them contained the sequence of words “fossil fuel” AND “public sector”. The third stage involved the application of the outcome of interest criterion from the PICO framework to the 3 screened literature results however, none of them measured or reported on the outcome of interest of

decision and planning procedures to reduce FF use in the public sector thereby exhausting the literature results for analysis. Using the PRIMSA flow diagram Figure 2.3 shows the results of the search and selection process undertaken.

Figure 2.3 PRISMA 2020 flow diagram showing results of literature search Relating to ‘Public Sector’ using Scopus database

Some UK studies have been carried out for examples relating to the contribution of transport sector activities to environmental sustainability (Hickman and Banister, 2019), the influences on local authority choice of urban freight transport policy (Akgün et al, 2019), in positioning transport as a key actor to achieving low carbon futures in the so called ‘climate crisis’ (Banister, 2019), and even the impacts of covid-19 lockdown measures on transport emissions (Vickerman, 2021; Budd and Ison, 2020). Some have looked in general at building CFs, opportunities for reducing building emissions and making buildings more energy efficient, including the impact of national energy policies and building legislations (De Wolf, Pomponi and Moncaster, 2017; Lowe, 2007; Gibbs and O’Neill, 2015). Other studies relating specifically to Scotland have also looked at sustainable energy Scenarios (Child et al., 2019), potential for

implementation of Negative Emission Technologies (Alcalde et al., 2018), Making the shift to sustainable transport (Davis and Whyte, 2020), and Public views of Scotland's path to decarbonization: Evidence from citizens' juries and focus groups (Ostfeld and Reiner, 2020).

Burning of FFs to produce energy has significant environmental implications for climate change and reducing reliance on FF energy sources is one way of addressing this. The emphasis on the public sectors role in achieving fossil free societies is well publicised in the UK (DECC, 2013; Owen et al., 2018) however, the systematic review reveals a lack of research into procedures to reduce reliance on FFs reliance within public sector bodies. As such this thesis aims to address this gap in research by proposing a framework for public sector bodies to reduce FF reliance through the consolidation of findings from three experimental chapters (see Chapter 7) encompassing a CF assessment for a HEI unit, document review of mandatory climate change reports and interviews with Scottish public sector actors.

This chapter was developed through the review of available literature on subjects relating to the reliance on and reduction of the use of FFs in Scotland's public sector with the major sources of literature being publications, articles, reports, and website pages, from government organisations, established private and public organisations, and databases. The chapter also includes the systematic review of the Scopus database using PRISMA methodology. The following chapter details the methods employed in investigating the research question.

CHAPTER 3:
METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION AND RESEARCH DESIGN

The lack of focus on organisational monitoring and reporting on emissions associated FF use or reliance in Scotland's public sector needs to be addressed if the sector is to live up to its climate change responsibilities in contributing to achieving national carbon reduction targets (DECC, 2013; CCC, 2021), and decarbonisation efforts. The purpose of the research was to develop an understanding of the reliance and attitudes to FF energy sources from which procedures to overcome and minimise their reliance can be proposed for public sector bodies in Scotland. Research for this project took place at the UWS between 2015 and 2021 and involved interviewing research participants at their work premises. This chapter details the methods employed and actions taken to investigate the research question and achieve the aims and objectives including providing the rationale for the choice of methods used to identify, assess, gather, process, and analyse data.

The research purpose was exploratory in nature and conducted utilising an inductive approach to develop an understanding of the phenomenon that is FF reliance. Based on this the concept of a framework emerges to address the phenomenon (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018; Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019) using data collected from a combination of methods (see Section 3.3). The inductive approach was deemed the best option because the other main alternative approach, the deductive approach, is confirmatory in nature and entails deriving hypotheses from an existing theory and testing them to revise that theory (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). As deductive research builds on existing theory it was deemed not a suitable approach for this research which aimed to generate a theory (or concept) from the ground up using the collected data (Crossley, 2021) by uncovering the underlying factors on which FF reliance hinges based on which it proposed a means of addressing this reliance.

Whilst inductive approaches are often directly linked to qualitative research methods (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018; Jansen, 2021) this research employed a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods (Hunziker and Blankenagel, 2021) often referred to as a mixed method research (Warren, 2020; Jansen, 2021) to achieve the research aims and objectives as set out in Chapter 1, drawing from quantitative and qualitative data. The aims and objectives were in summary to: (i) critically evaluate reliance on FFs by conducting a review of literature,

establishing a baseline CF for the SoSS, and analysing corporate emissions reported by sector bodies; and (ii) develop a decision-making framework to minimise FF reliance by conducting semi-structured interviews with sector actors and consolidating findings with the CF assessment and corporate emissions analysis.

As alluded to in the preceding paragraph Figure 3.1 shows a schematic of the main aspects that comprised the research. The literature review was mainly qualitative with a quantitative element resulting from the undertaken systematic review, whilst the CF assessment based on a standard methodology that is the Carbon Trust Methodology for Organisational CFs calculations (Carbon Trust, 2018), and the review of corporate emissions to quantify the contribution FF related emissions to overall reported emissions were wholly quantitative. And finally, the semi-structured interview with sector actors through thematic analysis is wholly qualitative. The analysis of data gathered from each of the individual aspects of the research did not themselves in isolation provide sufficient insight and concepts on the reliance on FFs to present as a thesis. However, and complementing each other, the findings of each aspect of the research in combination not only validated them but offered ample and robust data to provide significant insights and concepts into the research topic. This mixed method approach provided a deeper understanding of the reliance on FF energy sources in public sector bodies (Molina Azorina and Cameron, 2010). Furthermore, this mixed method approach has contributed significantly to the research in this thesis and the subsequent framework developed as part of that work (see Figure 3.1).

The combination of the quantitative and qualitative methods in research have been applied in different fields and disciplines of study for example psychology, sociology and health sciences (Molina Azorina and Cameron, 2010). In addition, Quinlivan and Dunphy (2023) for example illustrated the potential use of a mixed method approach in identifying opportunities for reducing CFs and in developing a Climate Action Plan. In undertaking their research, the quantitative approach entailed developing a GHG inventory by the completion of a CF assessment whilst the qualitative approach entailed the employment of a structured dialogue – modified Delphi – method approach (Quinlivan and Dunphy, 2023).

Seyis (2020) similarly used a combination of comprehensive literary review, semi-structured interviews with three participants, and Delphi method with 10 subject matter experts applied in two structured rounds, to integrate building information modelling and life-cycle assessment. Zvezdov and Hack, (2016), utilised a combination of data gathered from company documents and semi-structured interviews to substantiate their findings, however, no detail of the number of interview participants was provided. A similar approach was used by Mura, Longo and Zanni (2020), by way of data gathering through interviews, surveys, and focus groups.

This chapter section provides detailed information on the procedures followed in the generation, collection and analysis of data for the key aspects of the research in order of the literary review, case study CF baseline assessment, document review of reported corporate emissions, and the semi-structured interviews with sector actors.

Figure 3.1 Schematic of the main aspects of the research design

3.2 LITERATURE REVIEW (CHAPTER 2)

The literary review was used as an opportunity to bring the research into perspective in line with the scope of the research topic as set out in Chapter 1 by briefly discussing pertinent subjects. These subjects which are critical to understanding the wider narrative of reducing FF reliance in the public sector and help the focus on engaging the research gap, covered in general carbon management, methodology for CF assessments and GHG emissions reductions, mainly from the perspective of Scotland and UK LGAs and HEIs. Peer-reviewed publications like journal articles and papers from databases, other publications or reports from government, established private and public organisations and website pages were the sources of literature referenced in the review.

Importantly and more specifically, a systematic review of the Scopus database using PRISMA methodology and PICO framework (Page et al., 2021) was undertaken to identify existing evidence on decision and planning procedures for reducing FF fuel use in public sector bodies. Scopus was chosen as the database to undertake the literature search due to its accessibility to a vast range of international peer-reviewed literature consequently, its use sufficed in at least giving an indication of published studies in the subject of interest. More specific detail on the application of the PRISMA methodology as used in the context of this research is available in section 2.5 of Chapter 2. However, the outcome of this review highlighted the gap in research into FF reliance reduction procedures for the public sector, worrying giving the peculiar responsibilities of the sector in relation to climate change. The electronic search on the Scopus database using 12 search strings one of which significantly yielded the most results (n=511) and used as the basis of the review. Of these results only 3 articles were retrieved and assessed at the screening stage of the PRISMA process however, none reported on decision and planning procedures to reduce FF use and were excluded from the review study. Therefore, no further analysis was carried out following the outcome of the systematic review undertaken using PRISMA.

3.3 CF BASELINE ASSESSMENT CASE STUDY (CHAPTER 4)

The case study undertaken to develop a CF baseline assessment for the SoSS was initiated by the SoSS management board as an idea to support UWS institutional targets and build into its operational planning process. This aspect of the research was in support of this idea with the SoSS then deciding and implementing recommendations where possible.

The results and findings from the case study were forwarded to the relevant SoSS management team within the required timeframe however, the SoSS ceases to exist following a university wide restructure.

The method used to establish the CF baseline assessment for the SoSS followed the Carbon Trusts standard CF methodology for organisational CFs (Carbon Trust, 2018). This was supported by consulting methodologies published by other organisations including HEFCE and GHG Protocol which set out how to calculate Scopes 1, 2 and 3 emissions. The carbon trust footprinting guide provides a six-step process to estimating organisational CFs as shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Steps taken to establish SoSS 2015/16 baseline CF

This method was used because it is based on the GHG Protocol an international and widely used accounting standard for GHG inventory and emissions reporting and provides a guide to estimating organisational CFs. However, it is important to note that whilst the estimation of CFs for organisations is primarily a technical task which many undertake as a standard exercise, it enabled the determination of the key emission sources particularly in relation to FF use and consequentially a better understanding of the emission profile to identify potential reduction opportunities (Quinlivan and Dunphy, 2023). The Carbon Trust methodology for organisational CF assessment can be summarised as the total of the estimated emissions for each emission source identified from defining the organisational and operational boundaries (Carbon Trust, 2018). Each emission source was estimated by multiplying the activity data by the associated emission conversion factor (see Step 4 for more detail).

Step 3 of the carbon trust methodology specifically covers data collection for the purpose of undertaking the CF assessment based on the identified emission categories and sources (see Table 4.1 for the emissions sources included and excluded) from the prior step (Step 2). The UWS Estates Management Statistics (EMS) returns were obtained through the Estates Solutions Department holding information on consumption and emissions associated with the use of gas, electricity, water supply and water treatment by campus. This was provided via email in an excel spreadsheet format and saved on a secure storage drive (no consent was sought at the time of its provision to include the data in the research however, EMS information submitted to HESA can be viewed on the HESA website). Information on the physical footprint (m^2) for spaces occupied by the SoSS within Paisley and Hamilton campuses in conjunction with the EMS data were used to estimate emissions from each of these emission sources in the ‘energy from buildings’ and ‘water’ categories. This approach raises its own questions in terms of (i) the accuracy of the physical footprint and therefore the emissions per m^2 , and (ii) what a room is used for, for example a teaching room with limited equipment (lighting, computer, projector) compared to a laboratory with extraction, analytical equipment, fume hoods, (in addition to lighting, computers) resulting in significantly different emissions, up to ten times more as highlighted by Klein-Banai, and Theis (2013).

A lack of data from the SoSS in relation to consumption data for electricity, gas and water consumption warranted the use of alternative means of obtaining this activity data. The EMS data provided information on energy consumption by building therefore accounting for all rooms within that building. Furthermore, the square meterage information provided by the Estates Solutions Department was regularly updated and up to date at the time of undertaking the case study. Where the physical footprint for a space occupied by the SoSS was not available, it was excluded from the total energy consumption used to calculate the baseline footprint. This affected the Robertson Sports Centre, which is not based within the Paisley campus and as such did not form part of this study. Figures 3.3 and 3.4 show the maps of Paisley and Hamilton campuses respectively, and identifies the buildings occupied by the SoSS in both campuses. Activity data for the other emission categories identified in Step 2 that is ‘travel’, ‘procurement’ and ‘waste’ categories were obtained differently. A mini travel survey was conducted to generate activity data associated with staff commute, and a combination of information from vehicle fleet usage and bookings from a travel management software used to generate activity data associated

with business travel. The total number of paper prints charged to the SoSS and total numbers of PCs used by the SoSS provided data used to estimate emissions associated with procurement, whilst tonnage information was obtained from Waste Consignment Notes for emissions associated with waste management. Step 4 applies conversion factors set by the UK government to the activity data collated (in appropriate unit or metric) to estimate the emissions associated with each emission source.

Figure 3.3: Map of Paisley campus showing buildings occupied by SoSS in green

Figure 3.4: Map of Hamilton campus showing buildings occupied by SoSS in green

3.4 DOCUMENT REVIEW (CHAPTER 5)

Chapter 5 formed the document review analysis aspect of the research and identified corporate emissions reported by public sector bodies to the Scottish Government through the SSN for analysis, including the analysis of reports of those organisations that participated in the semi-structured interviews as part of the research (participating organisations). The FF composition of reported corporate emissions was evaluated to understand the reliance on FFs in public sector bodies. At the same time the chapter looked at emission reduction performance and actions taken to reduce emissions as reported by public sector bodies. It covered the review and analysis of aspects of two main document types (all of which are readily downloadable from the SSN website <https://sustainablesotlandnetwork.org/>) which served as secondary data sources for this aspect of the research, in order of:

1. SSN summary analysis reports of Public Bodies Climate Change Reports for Scottish public sector bodies (SSN, 2019;2020). The 2017/18 and 2018/19 reports provided secondary data on total reported sector emissions by emission source and organisation type covering reporting periods 2015/16 to 2018/19.

2. The Climate Change (Duties of Public Bodies: Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Order 2015 reports for participating organisations (LGAs and HEIs). Each participating organisation's reports for 2015/16 to 2018/19 provided secondary data on total reported emissions for each participating organisation by emission source.

The SSN summary analysis report for public sector bodies were structured with dedicated headings which were directly relatable and of interest to this aspect of the research and include: corporate emissions breakdown, emission reduction projects, renewable energy initiatives, and targets. Similarly, the mandatory climate change duties reports for participating organisations is structured such that Part 3 of the reports were dedicated to 'Emissions, Targets and Projects'. The format and reporting structure of both sets of documents were presented in a way that the desired information for analysis and interpretation was easily pulled from the documents and collated for analysis using Microsoft Excel Software. Focusing initially on the sector wide reports and subsequently on the participating organisations' reports, data on the combined emissions associated with reported FF emission sources is sought and gathered for reporting periods between 2015 and 2019. These dates were chosen because it covered the period from which the research commenced in 2015/16 (coinciding with the first set of reports submitted by sector bodies in line with the public bodies duties) and the most up to date report (2018/19) at the time of commencing the analysis of these reports. The four-year period between 2015 and 2019 provided enough data on emissions and emission sources to allow patterns to be tracked and analysed.

Whilst it is acknowledged that document reviews may be undertaken using methodologies such as a standard content analysis or thematic content analysis, the approach employed in this section of the research was direct and purposeful in targeting desired reported information as highlighted above and is reproducible by following the list of steps outlined in Figure 3.5 in conjunction with the data collated and summarised in Tables 3.1 to 3.6. This approach was deemed the best approach to gaining a better understanding of FF reliance in the Scottish public sector however, it had to assume that the data reported in these documents were correct. This assumption is because data reported by Scottish public sector bodies including those LGAs and HEIs that participate in the semi-structured interviews (see Chapter 6) were compiled and

submitted to the Scottish Government as a regulatory requirement and is in the public domain. The presumption therefore remains that the data is accurate as any errors would have been published in the public domain as an errata where applicable lending this approach to be regarded as best practice by the researcher.

Figure 3.5: Outline steps undertaken in document review methodology

Table 3.1: Reported Scottish Public Sector Corporate Emissions 2015/16 to 2018/19 in tCO₂e (Source: data collated from SSN (2019; 2020))

	Reporting Period	2015/16 Emissions (tCO₂e)	2016/17 Emissions (tCO₂e)	2017/18 Emissions (tCO₂e)	2018/19 Emissions (tCO₂e)
Sector Groups	LGAs & Educational Institutions	2,033,967	1,895,377	1,846,765	1,537,239
	remainder of sector	1,234,625	1,127,508	1,036,023	968,390
Total Emissions		3,268,592	3,022,885	2,882,788	2,505,629
Emission Sources	heating	977,151	949,366	980,902	920,087
	transportation	362,284	350,154	349,379	349,836
	electricity	1,550,894	1,360,690	1,119,642	869,585
	others	378,263	362,675	432,865	366,121
Total Emissions		3,268,592	3,022,885	2,882,788	2,505,629
Fossil Fuels (FF) – Heat/Transport	FF share	1,339,435	1,299,520	1,330,281	1,269,923
	Percentage	41%	43%	46%	51%

Table 3.2: Reported Participating Organisations Corporate Emissions 2015/16 to 2018/19 in tCO₂e (Source: data collated from SSN (no date))

	Reporting Period	2015/16 Emissions (tCO₂e)	2016/17 Emissions (tCO₂e)	2017/18 Emissions (tCO₂e)	2018/19 Emissions (tCO₂e)
Emission Sources	FF emissions (heat/transport)	215,215	282,488	303,012	297,545
	electricity	241,317	234,207	181,000	141,393
	others	115,013	46,357	62,127	48,609
Total Emissions (tCO₂e)		571,545	563,052	546,139	487,547
Percentage share (%)	FF emissions (heat/transport)	38%	50%	55%	61%
	electricity	42%	42%	33%	29%
	others	20%	8%	11%	10%

Table 3.3: Reported Scottish Public Sector Emissions Savings from Emission Reduction projects 2015/16 to 2018/19 in tCO₂e (Source: data collated from SSN (2019; 2020))

	Reporting Period	2015/16 Emissions Savings (tCO₂e)	2016/17 Emissions Savings (tCO₂e)	2017/18 Emissions Savings (tCO₂e)	2018/19 Emissions Savings (tCO₂e)
Sector Groups	LGAs	48,066	45,918	43,714	47,885
	Educational Institutions	24,315	24,611	17,457	8,251
	remainder of sector	18,716	38,406	22,060	20,095
Total Emissions		91,097	108,935	83,231	76,231
Emission Sources	heating	22,095	14,250	13,555	15,313
	transportation	4,993	3,142	4,883	5,107
	electricity	42,054	66,337	40,970	34,215
	waste	19,136	23,188	15,533	17,366
	others	2,819	2,018	8,290	4,228
Total Emissions		91,097	108,935	83,231	76,231

Table 3.4: Reported Scottish Public Sector and Participating Organisations Renewable Energy Generation 2015/16 to 2018/19 in tCO₂e (Source: data collated from SSN (no date; 2019; 2020))

	Reporting Period	2015/16 Energy Generation (GWh)	2016/17 Energy Generation (GWh)	2017/18 Energy Generation (GWh)	2018/19 Energy Generation (GWh)
Scottish Public Sector	renewable heat generation	139	177	189	199
	renewable electricity generation	82	103	105	88
Participating Organisations	renewable heat generation	12	7	5	12
	renewable electricity generation	19	23	19	7

Table 3.5: Reported Participating Organisations Emissions Savings from Emission Reduction projects 2015/16 to 2018/19 in tCO₂e (Source: data collated from SSN (no date))

	Reporting Period	2015/16 Emissions Savings (tCO₂e)	2016/17 Emissions Savings (tCO₂e)	2017/18 Emissions Savings (tCO₂e)	2018/19 Emissions Savings (tCO₂e)
Sector Groups	LGAs	6,504	40,651	13,445	3,594
	Educational Institutions	20,047	13,477	5,558	6,220
Total Emissions		26,551	54,128	19,003	9,814
Emission Sources	heating	4,483	3,429	1,020	2,200
	transportation	589	237	901	927
	electricity	19,709	48,484	11,243	3,515
	waste	1,677	1,899	5,825	3,080
	others	93	79	14	92
Total Emissions		26,551	54,128	19,003	9,814

Table 3.6: Reported Participating Organisations Emission Reduction Targets 2015/16 to 2018/19 in tCO₂e (Source: data collated from SSN (no date))

	Reporting Period	2015/16 No. of Reported Targets	2016/17 No. of Reported Targets	2017/18 No. of Reported Targets	2018/19 No. of Reported Targets
Type of Target	overall emissions	10	15	15	12
	energy use in buildings	5	6	7	2
	waste	6	5	11	12
	water	1	1	0	0
	commuter and business travel	7	8	7	7
	fleet transport	3	2	1	1
	others	4	1	3	0

It is necessary to note the direct link between document review section of Chapter 5 and the semi-structured interviews with sector actors from participating organisations in Chapter 6. The climate change duties mandatory reports of the interviewed sector actor's organisational affiliation were reviewed and analysed post completion of the semi-structured interviews to compare the findings of the reported corporate emissions with those of the wider Scottish public sector (as defined in Chapter 1) as reported to the Scottish Government and based on the SSN summary analysis reports. The semi-

structured interviews conducted spanned eleven organisations and comparison of their reported corporate emissions assessed against the wider sector are shown in Section 5.9.

3.5 SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW (CHAPTER 6)

The preceding section provided a comparison of wider public sector (such as is defined in Chapter 1) corporate emissions with those of participating organisations (affiliated sector actor organisations totalling eleven). Chapter 6 assesses the views and opinions of sector actors in exploring the balance between FF use and renewable or low carbon technologies within their organisations; by establishing evidence of reliance on FFs, identifying barriers to moving away from reliance on FFs and how this reliance might be reduced. The focus on LGAs and HEIs sector actor engagement in this section is based on their organisational capacities and influence in climate change, likewise the potential to generate transferable knowledge or information on FF emission reduction opportunities beneficial to the wider sector.

In order to gather the best possible primary data that is valid, reliable and relevant to the research question and objectives in revealing and understanding the ‘what’, the ‘how’, and exploring the ‘why’, a semi-structured interview was undertaken (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). The use of semi-structured interview offered the flexibility during the interviews to probe responses, vary the order of the questioning, thereby adding significance and depth, and allowing for the collection of a rich detailed set of data. In comparison to the use of surveys, questionnaires, or other interview approaches, the semi-structured interview also offered the opportunity to target interviewees with specific roles, all of which are critical to exploring the complexity of the research topic and to address the research question. Whilst the Delphi method may have been a suitable alternative to semi-structured interviews in assessing the opinions of sector experts, it can be time-consuming for the researcher and participants (Fink-Hafner et al., 2022). A key decision against this method was its vulnerability to participant drop out which may be a result of the formulation of questions that challenge participant opinion (Harteis, 2022) or the extended duration of the process for example time factor in postal methods or chasing online participants to return questionnaires (Matsas et al., 2022) and the potential for participant attrition (Drumm, Bradley and Moriarty, 2022).

The reliability of findings following the analysis of data obtained through semi-structured interviews often raises concerns in terms of the ability for other researchers to replicate the research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). A potential drawback of completing semi-structured interviews is that it is not possible to determine if the responses are reproducible as doing so undermines the very purpose of the flexibility of this interview method in exploring the complexity of the research topic (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Nevertheless, the issue of interview participant response reproducibility has no meaningful direct impact on the interpretation of the research findings in this thesis, as such this approach was chosen because it enabled questions to be varied, responses to be probed in dealing with the complexity of the topic and the best method to collect rich data set from sector actors for analysis. The decision to undertake interviews was supported also by the increased potential of access to information and data required to undertake the research including sector actors, via the researchers existing network of contacts within the sector and those of the supervisory team.

The debate on adequate interview sample sizes in qualitative research is discussed in academic literature with suggestions varying from one to a hundred and more (Baker and Edwards, 2017). This aspect of the study originally aimed to interview thirty public sector professionals within environmental and sustainability remits from six organisations (i.e., five from each organisation), subsequently revised to twenty public sector professionals or actors from Scottish LGAs and HEIs. The decision to aim for twenty interviews came with the realisation of the difficulty in securing willing participants, for example, only six of the first fifteen prospective participants that were approached (i.e., five professionals from three organisation) agreed to participate, the remainder declined on the basis that they lacked detailed knowledge particularly because they felt the responsibility for carbon management did not sit ultimately with them. However, eighteen were completed and this transpired into eleven participating organisations that is six HEIs and five LGAs.

Based on the range of suggestions in academic literature for what constitutes an adequate interview sample size (Vasileiou et al., 2018), suffice it appropriate to suggest that aiming for twenty interviews was a good round number, particularly because the interviews supplement and strengthen the other aspects of the mixed method research

study. So much so when considering that the length of time (between July 2017 and June 2019) taken to complete the eighteen interviews undertaken in this research, difficulty of accessing sector actors and in transcribing the hours of interviews (Baker and Edwards, 2017). Nevertheless, the adequacy of interview sample sizes is subject to criticism by critical readers and research evaluators, and to the ability of a researcher to satisfy them.

Prior to conducting the interviews, several factors including developing the interview guide (see Appendix 1): identifying interview participants, scheduling interviews, collecting interview data, interview risk assessment, and ethical factors were taken into consideration. Some ethical factors considered during different stages of the research include the participant's right to be fully informed, to privacy, to quality research, to withdraw, to confidentiality and anonymity, to the processing and storing of their personal information, rights in relation to deception; the researcher's safety and maintaining the research objectivity; and the organisations right to confidentiality and anonymity. Ethics approval was granted by the ethics committee of the then SoSS at the UWS for this research study, ethics approval number 3-5-16- 001 (see Appendix 2). In preparing the interview guide, consideration was given to developing questions that reflect the research question and objectives, in a logical order, clear understandable language, allowing interviewees the opportunity to respond freely and at the same time affording the interviewer the opportunity to seek further meaning and explanation to interviewee responses. The interview guide lists the generic topics covered at the interview, initial questions that were, 'open' and 'probing' questions (Kallio et al., 2016).

The choice of sector actors from which organisations were identified is based on several factors including proximity, costs, accessibility, and availability of sector actors to undertake interviews. Whilst the factors of proximity and possibly costs may have been addressed using video conferencing interviews today, video conferencing was not commonplace for research at the time of seeking ethical approval for the research (ethics application submitted May 2016). Interview participants were identified based on the combination of existing network of contacts, contact details via some organisations' website, and through referrals and recommendations from colleagues and interview participants (see Packer, Scott and Geddes, 2019; Abbott et al., 2018; and

Roulston, 2018). Initial contact with interview participants was via email correspondence introducing the researcher, the research work and seeking consent to participate. Interview participants were given a duration of between one to two weeks to decide and respond on whether they wished to take part, furthermore, participants were informed that they can withdraw at any time without reason. To aid the identified participants' decision to participate in the research work, a participant information sheet (See Appendix 3) detailing the purpose of the research work, what it involved including the recording of the interview, and the interview guide were sent to the identified participants. Following receipt of this information some identified participants declined to participate on the basis that they lack detailed knowledge particularly because they feel the responsibility for carbon management does not ultimately sit with them. For example, all three of those approached with job titles in 'waste management' all declined to participate.

Data obtained from the semi-structured interviews with sector actors is analysed using thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Kiger and Varpio, 2020). Whilst the use of thematic analysis in science is not commonplace as is the case in other research areas like psychology, health, and wellbeing (Braun and Clarke, 2014), it has been used in this study to assess and analyse the opinions of sector actors in relation to climate change specific to this aspect of the research. Thematic analysis method identifies, analyses, and reports patterns or themes within data by organising and describing the data set in detail (Braun and Clarke, 2006; 2012).

Realist thematic analysis is used to analyse the interview responses which captures the opinions and experience of public sector actors on the research topic. This method was chosen as the best method to analyse data from the interview responses due to its accessible form of analysis, and flexibility in determining themes. It provides a detailed and nuanced account of groups of themes, within the data relating to the research topic. Themes are identified in a deductive or theoretical way and with a semantic approach allowing for themes to be identified within the explicit meanings of the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Kiger and Varpio, 2020). The six phases of Thematic Analysis guide suggested by Braun and Clarke (2006) include familiarizing yourself with your data; generating initial codes; searching for themes; reviewing themes; defining and naming themes; and producing the report (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Every effort was to limit

bias by analysing and interpreting the true meaning and perceptions of interview responses without interference with the results of analysis and being conscious of possible bias during thematic analysis. Figure 3.6 shows the process flow chart methodology employed in the analysis of data obtained from the semi-structured interviews based on Braun and Clarke's six-phase thematic analysis guide (the emergence of themes is discussed in Section 6.4).

Figure 3.6 Process flow chart methodology for analysis of semi-structured interview responses (Based on Braun and Clarke (2006))

Table 3.7: Examples of a code applied to a segment of data

Data extract	Coded for
“when I first started with the local authority back in 2002, utility prices were so cheap, there was no real incentive to try and reduce your consumption because we were not paying a lot for gas and the electricity”	Cheap utility prices encourage FF use
“Again, it is kind of comes down to cost benefit analysis, the ultra-low price of gas currently is not conducive to switch to alternatives”	Ultra-low gas prices hinder switch to alternative energy
“We have looked at in detail three projects, district heating projects for cost benefit analysis and each of them have failed. The primary problem/hurdle is the current cost of gas which is just ridiculously low”	District heating projects are not cost effective due to low gas prices

Table 3.8: Example of codes grouped into potential themes and sub-themes

Code	Sub-theme	Theme
Cheap utility prices encourage FF use	Cheaper to use FFs	Barriers to relying on renewable technology
Cost implications of switching from FFs to clean energy		
Uncertainties of the impact of investing in new technology which has not been trialled		
Ultra-low gas prices hinder switch to alternative energy		
Capital cost of installation is expensive	Renewable energy is not cost effective	
District heating projects are not cost effective due to low gas prices		
Although solar panel prices have reduced it is still not cost effective		
With any Scottish government funding even a loan you can't apply for Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI) or feed-in tariff		

3.6 CONCLUSION

This chapter started with a brief introduction providing the reasoning and purpose of the research, thereafter presented a discussion and schematic of the research design in response to fulfilling the research question and objectives, using a mixed method of quantitative and qualitative research. The chapter ended with the presentation of the rationale behind the data generation, collection and analysis procedures followed in the research. The following three chapters (4, 5, & 6) are experimental chapters from which a framework for use by public sector bodies to reduce reliance on FFs will be developed.

CHAPTER 4:

**CF and BASELINE ASSESSMENT of a HE OPERATIONAL UNIT - SoSS (2014
– 2018), UWS**

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter contributes to the research aim of evaluating and understanding reliance on FF energy sources. It specifically addresses the research objective of undertaking a CF case study and developing a baseline assessment for a HE operation cutting across many of the infrastructure units. Representing a real test for practical application, authentic data and barriers defined, it contributes to the development of the framework for decision making on FF use within public sector bodies.

The UWS CMP is controlled and managed centrally by the Estates and Buildings Department, through the Energy and Environmental Manager, and the Sustainability Team. According to the ‘UWS Delivering Sustainability 2018/19’ report (UWS, 2020) the UWS is committed to reducing carbon emissions resulting from its operations and ultimately its CF by embedding a sustainable carbon culture across its key functions. The following are the key drivers for UWS to become more carbon efficient:

- Legislative requirements including The Climate Change (Scotland) Act 2009 (as amended), The Climate Change (Duties of Public Bodies: Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Order 2015 and what was formerly The CRC Energy Efficiency Scheme Order 2013.
- A commitment to the Corporate Strategy of the university and improving its social and environmental profile (Corporate Social Responsibility), including staff and student satisfaction (UWS, 2014).
- Its pledged ambition to become amongst the global leaders in climate change research and enterprise activity (UWS, 2021), understand its GHG emissions profile and reduce its environmental impacts.
- Its pledged commitment to aligning its strategy to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UWS, 2021)
- UWS requirements to identify potential for financial savings through reduced consumption and efficiency measures (UWS, 2010; 2019).

UWS released its 2010 to 2014 Climate Action Plan, followed by the 2016 UWS Sustainability Plan in support of its commitment to reducing its CF and towards its sustainable carbon management ambition (UWS, 2010; UWS, 2016). Whilst this may represent a mere statement of ambition to embark on a journey towards sustainability,

progress in aligning its strategy to the SDGs is being reported by UWS and can be found in the UWS Delivering Sustainability Report 2019-20 (UWS, 2021). For example, the development and commissioning in September 2018 of the ‘UWS Lanarkshire’ campus which was awarded recognition for being a sustainable and inspiring UK HE building (UWS, 2020; The Guardian, 2019). In a bid to de-carbonise the UWS estate, one of the targets of the 2014 University Corporate Strategy is the reduction of CO₂ emissions by 20% by the 2019/20 academic year, known as Key Performance Indicator 23 (Reduction in carbon emissions) (School Leadership Group (SLG), SoSS & UWS, 2015; UWS, 2014). This reduction target is based on the 2012/13 CF baseline of 11075 tCO₂e according to Roxburgh (2017).

The 2018/19 UWS CF is estimated at approximately 6405 tCO₂e (UWS, 2020) encompassing Scope 1 (Natural Gas and Fuel Consumption from Vehicle Fleet), Scope 2 (Grid Electricity – generation) and Scope 3 (Water, Waste and Business Travel) emissions. The UWS breakdown of emission sources and their associated emissions which form the bases of the CF reported can be found in the UWS mandatory climate change duties report for 2018/19 submitted to the Scottish Government and available on the SSN website (SSN, no date). The 2018/19 CF represents a 22% reduction from the previous academic year and 42% reduction from the 2012/13 baseline. This indicates that UWS has already surpassed its 2019/20 carbon emission reduction target by more than double. Figure 4.1 shows the reduction in the university’s CF from the baseline with 2018/19 representing the largest annual decrease in emissions (22%). This is attributed to the opening of the new Lanarkshire campus which is designed for efficiency and carbon neutral for energy; electricity is claimed to be derived from a local windfarm supplemented by photovoltaic panels, and rainwater feeding toilets (UWS, 2020).

The data collection and estimation of the Carbon Emissions Baseline for the then SoSS (also referred to as the school) at the UWS was completed during the academic year 2016/17. It was intended for the results of the case study to support the school in its operational decision-making process and to better understand its emissions profile. It should be noted that in 2018 the school was merged with two other schools, becoming the Schools of Health and Life Sciences and Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences.

This case study aimed to identify steps to enable the school to estimate and improve its CF through establishing a carbon emissions baseline from which future emissions can be compared to whilst enabling carbon reduction targets to be set in the future if deemed appropriate by the school. Although the results of the study were intended to assist the school in deciding and implementing operational planning processes to reduce carbon emissions and contribute towards the wider UWS institutional targets, due to School reorganisation in 2018 this did not happen. However, the results provide valuable recommendations for schools within the institution, whilst also uncovering the challenges and complexities of the data gathering process to be faced by other schools within the institution.

The 2015/16 academic year was chosen as the baseline year for Scope 1 (direct emissions from activities within an organisation's control), Scope 2 (indirect emissions from activities outside an organisation's control) and Scope 3 (any other indirect emissions from activities outside organisational control but influenced by organisational choices) emissions resulting from the school's operations within the operational boundaries. Whilst the UWS 2019/20 emission reduction target is based on its 2012/13 CF baseline, the absence of data for certain emission categories at school level for example procurement, travel, and waste meant the case study baseline could not be based on the 2012/13 academic year. It was deemed best to gather school level data from the year in which the research study commenced and for which the first set of mandatory reports under the Climate Change (Duties of Public Bodies: Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Order (2015) were submitted; hence the decision to make 2015/16 the school baseline year.

Figure 4.1: Chart of UWS CF 2012/13 to 2018/19 (Roxburgh, 2017; UWS, 2018, 2019, 2020).

4.2 SoSS CARBON MANAGEMENT

The school was committed to the implementation of the University’ Corporate Strategy across the school through its Board (SLG, SoSS & UWS, 2015). The school made efforts to reduce its carbon emissions resulting from its operations, including recognising the need to identify projects to improve the quality of data supply reporting (SLG, SoSS & UWS, 2015) relevant to the measurement of its CF. The Chemistry laboratories in the 2014/15 session had twenty new fume hoods installed which reduced energy input by about 30%, contributing to a Gold Standard Award from the National Union of Students Green Impact awards (EAUC, 2015). It is important to note that in the context of the UWS that the school was the only academic school at the time to have been involved in Green Impact, achieved Gold Standard status, and started to work towards Platinum status. Platinum status was not achieved at the time of writing this thesis and was only properly introduced in 2019. This case study developed a carbon emissions baseline for the school and is a justification of the school’s efforts and commitment to reducing its carbon emissions (SoSS, 2016).

Establishing a baseline CF allows for subsequent footprints to be measured against targets. This proved a challenge as the school operated within three different campuses (Paisley, Hamilton, and Ayr) sharing buildings and rooms. This meant that the data was not readily available however details on how the data was collated can be seen in sections 4.6 and 4.7 as guided by the organisational boundaries as shown in Figure 4.2.

It should be noted that the Ayr campus was excluded from this study due to limited school activity at the campus as the five academic staff based at the campus delivered material for a different university at the time, and there was no administrative or technical support from the school. Likewise, worthy of note is that the UWS ceases to operate from the Hamilton campus post completion of case study and following the opening of the Lanarkshire campus.

4.3 DEVELOPING AN EMISSIONS BASELINE

The school CF baseline estimation was based on published methodologies which describe calculation processes for Scopes 1, 2 and 3 emission sources (Carbon Trust, 2018; HEFCE, 2010; HEFCE, 2012; World Resources Institute and World Business Council for Sustainable Development, 2011). Assumptions made in relation to data sources, calculation processes, emission factor choices and exclusions from the operational boundaries are highlighted where applicable in the relevant sections of this chapter. Using the Carbon Trust Carbon Footprinting Guide for calculating organisational footprints the following steps were followed (Carbon Trust, 2018):

4.3.1 Step 1 – Decide on the method to be followed

It is important to utilise a consistent method in the development of a CF to ensure that results are as accurate as they can be. The Carbon Trust Carbon Footprinting Guide which is based on the GHG Protocol standard (commonly used worldwide), and the HEFCE provide information on methods of calculating CFs and were referred to.

4.3.2 Step 2 – Define organisational and operational boundaries

This step can be complex for organisations with subsidiaries and joint venture organisations. However, an important step in setting clear and explicit boundaries on which part(s) of an organisation would be included in the footprint, and subsequently the emission sources to be quantified as determined by the operational boundary.

4.3.3 Step 3 & Step 4 – Collate the data and apply emissions factors (see Table 4.17)

The Carbon Trust (2018) suggests that CF accuracy depends on the availability of consumption data for the emission sources identified in the established operational boundary and emphasises the importance of clarifying gaps in the consumption data and

listing all assumptions made in calculating the footprint. Purman (2008) notes that emissions are measured directly or by using emission factors; following the identification of the emission sources within the draft operational boundaries, the next steps were to collate data for the identified emission sources and calculate the associated emissions by applying emission factors.

4.3.4 Step 5 - Verify results (optional)

This step requires verifying an organisations CF through a third party, adding credibility and confidence to an organisations mandatory carbon reporting requirement (Carbon Trust, 2018); however, as this step is optional it was not followed at the time of study.

4.3.5 Step 6 - Verify that you have taken action to reduce your emissions (optional)

This step is different from the above step in that whilst the above step seeks to verify organisational CF, this step involves verifying actions taken to reduce an organisations CF through a third party, adding credibility and confidence to emission reduction claims (Carbon Trust, 2018). In this case, it was an aim of this case study to identify actions to reduce the CF of the school.

4.4 ESTIMATING SCHOOL LEVEL EMISSIONS

CF is measured in tCO₂e and calculated by multiplying the activity data (consumption data) collated by a standard emissions factor i.e., Activity Data * Conversion Factor = Carbon emissions (Carbon Trust, 2018). All emission conversion factors used in the estimation of the CF were from the UK Government Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy Greenhouse gas reporting - Conversion factors 2016 (BEIS, 2016). Table 4.1 shows the emission sources considered in the baseline footprint calculation, itemising those that were included and excluded, including reason for exclusion.

Table 4.1: Emission Sources Included and Excluded in the Baseline Footprint Calculation

Emission Category	Sources included	Sources excluded	Reason for exclusion
Energy from Buildings	Electricity	Oil	No data - phased out
	Gas	Coal	
Travel	Business	Student Commute	Lack of data by way of a staff and student travel survey.
	Conference Travel	International	
		Student Travel	
	Staff Commute	Student Exchange Travel	
Inter Campus Travel			
Procurement	Publications	Laboratory Materials	Lack of readily available data to make calculations on the itemised emission sources
		Chemicals	
		Audio Visual Equipment	
	IT Equipment	Office Supplies	
		Consumables	
		Furniture and appliances	
Water	Water Supply	"Not Applicable"	"Not Applicable"
	Water Treatment	"Not Applicable"	
Waste Management	Hazardous Waste (Waste Electrical & Electronic Equipment (WEEE) & Batteries)	Composting	School has no operational control
		Recycling	
		Landfill	
		Heat Treatment	
		Waste to Energy	

4.4.1 Energy from buildings

The HEFCE explains how Scopes 1, 2 & 3 emissions can be calculated. It suggests establishing the annual energy consumption for each fuel source in the appropriate

metric (excluding Biomass) across a university estate from the EMS returns; in the absence of this obtaining information on consumption direct from the utility suppliers' estate (HEFCE, 2010).

4.4.2 Travel

The HEFCE explains how Scope 3 carbon emissions resulting from work-related travel can be calculated using core principles; which travel emissions should be considered in forming the Scope 3 travel emissions boundary; information sources that can be used to calculate Scope 3 travel emissions and potential stakeholders who can provide data for calculating emissions (HEFCE, 2012). In terms of work-related travel emissions, the school did not own or control any mode of transport and so had no Scope 1 travel emissions. All work-related travel emissions associated with the school were Scope 3 emissions.

In the absence of a travel plan or survey for the school the HEFCE suggest utilising a top-down approach (see Table 2.2) using national-level statistics to estimate the institutional share, however this method is less accurate (HEFCE, 2010). To develop an emissions baseline under this category a mini travel survey was sent out to school staff seeking information on their mode of travel to and from work (base campus) and other campuses. 70% of respondents travelled by car, 19% by train, 5% by foot, 4% by cycle and 2% by bus. Following the analysis of results from the mini survey, commute to the base campus and the main mode of transport for each response was the focus, results of which can be found in Appendix 4.

4.4.3 Procurement

The HEFCE acknowledges the difficulties in measuring emissions associated with procurement, however encourage close working between organisations, their procurement teams and relevant procurement consortia to understand the full scope of procurement. They suggest breaking down procurement emissions into broad categories such as building procurement for example design specification of buildings and material use, and procurement of goods and services for example information and communications technology equipment, stationery, and supplies (HEFCE, 2010).

4.4.4 Water

The HEFCE explains how Scope 3 emissions can be calculated; it suggests utilising water consumption figures reported in EMS returns (HEFCE, 2010). The UWS EMS returns holds information on consumption and emissions associated with the use of

water (i.e., water supply and water treatment by campus) however, the data available for the Paisley campus was limited number of buildings listed (4 buildings, none of which included school occupied buildings) and for Hamilton campus it was a total sum only. Therefore, an assumption has been made that the total consumption figures represent the whole of the Paisley and Hamilton campuses.

4.4.5 Waste management

The HEFCE recommends the use of waste-related information reported through the EMS in calculating emissions (HEFCE, 2010). Within UWS, the Estates and Buildings Department, and the Health and Safety Services Department share overall responsibility for managing waste generated from UWS' operations. Using available information, emissions associated with WEEE, and batteries were accounted for as hazardous waste.

4.5 METHOD

At the time of the study, emissions were reported at a university level, and not broken down to a school or Department level, making it difficult to estimate emissions associated with the school for some sources of emissions. Therefore, several assumptions had to be made based on the reporting format and using a combination of calculation methods.

4.5.1 Operational boundaries

The operational boundaries were determined by the extent to which the school has operational control and the potential for quality data to be readily available or easily generated, considering the absence of dedicated carbon management and reduction procedures at school levels across the university. Organisational boundary categories were identified (Figure 4.2) to identify and associate emissions within the school as direct and indirect emissions (Scopes 1, 2 and 3) in line with The GHG Protocol Standard (Carbon Trust, 2018).

Figure 4.2: Organisational boundaries within the SoSS.

Taking into consideration the Carbon Trust’s Guide, the school operational boundaries include emissions associated with the following categories:

- **Energy from buildings** – Gas and Electricity only and was based on UWS EMS returns.
- **Travel** – Staff Commute and Business Travel only. A mini survey which can be found in Appendix 4 was carried out for staff commute.
- **Procurement** – IT Equipment (PCs) and Publications & Prints (Paper Use) only.
- **Water** – Water Supply and Water Treatment.
- **Waste Management** – Hazardous (known as Special Waste in Scotland) Waste only encompassing WEEE and Batteries.

4.5.2 Baseline footprint data sources

In estimating the total CF baseline for the school, data for the 2015/16 academic year were used where available, and in conjunction with the use of proxy data. Table 4.2 shows data sources used to calculate the CF.

4.5.2.1 Energy from buildings and water data source

Data for electricity and gas consumption in kWh within the energy from building category, and for water supply and treatment in m³ within the water category were obtained from the 2015/16 UWS EMS returns spreadsheet. With these data readily available i.e., from the EMS returns and the physical footprint of UWS and the school

in m², calculating emissions associated with electricity, gas and water consumption was relatively straightforward.

4.5.2.2 Travel data sources

Travel data for staff commute were gathered from the results of the mini survey carried out (Appendix 4) broken down into travel by car, bus, and train, and used in conjunction with national-level statistics. There was a 52% response rate to the mini travel survey taken to be representative all staff on the assumption that non respondents shared similar travel characteristics (World Resources Institute and World Business Council for Sustainable Development, 2011). The Business Travel subcategory encompassed hire of the UWS vehicle fleet, and information from the Clarity travel management booking system which includes flights and rail travel for a four-month period (Clarity is a business travel expert that businesses and organisations use to plan and manage their business travel requirements (Clarity, 2022)). The corresponding emissions for this four-month period is multiplied by three to give an assumed emissions figure for the year period. Given data was only available and provided for the four-month period it is assumed that travel activity is the same across the year; for the purpose of getting an indication of the annual associated emissions, this approach is considered fair and reasonable. See Appendices 5, 8 and 9 for the Staff Commute, UWS Fleet Hire and Air calculation breakdown respectively.

Data for Business Travel were obtained through a couple of sources. Relevant information for Air and Rail business travel was downloaded from the Clarity Travel Management Software including departure and arrival information. Distances were calculated using International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) Carbon Emissions Calculator for flights and an online distance calculator for rail travel (ICAO, 2016; Distance Calculator, no date). Flights were broken down into domestic (within the UK), short-haul (within Europe), long-haul (outside of Europe), international (between non-UK destinations) and cabin class of flights (BEIS, 2016). Conversion factors for air travel are calculated based on the plane area occupied by each passenger; a plane comprising only business-class seats will have less passengers with a larger share of the emissions.

The UWS Vehicle Usage spreadsheet provided data on miles travelled by the school through the hire of the UWS vehicle fleet (information on vehicle engine size was used to determine the emission factors).

The JMP Consultants Ltd (2012) report to the HEFCE recommends the exclusion of emissions associated with travel made by students from their term time address to their home address, including international students travelling from their term time accommodation to their home countries. The report suggests that though there is recognition of the significance of emissions associated with student travel from term time address to home address, it is beyond an educational institution control and influence.

Table 4.2: 2015/16 Baseline Footprint Emission Factors and Data Sources

Categories	Emission Sources	Sub Emission Sources	Emission Factors Used	Data Source(s)
Energy from Buildings	Electricity	-	0.41205	UWS EMS Returns/Room sizes in square metres
	Gas	-	0.18400	
Travel	Staff Commute	Car	0.18695	Mini travel survey
		Bus	0.10172	
		Train	0.04885	
	Business Travel	Ford Focus 1.6 TDCI	0.23618	UWS Vehicle Usage/Vehicle details
		VW Transporter 1.8 TDCI	0.28551	
		Ford Mondeo 2.0 TDCI	0.28551	
		Ford Transit (minibus) 2.4TDCI	0.36166	SoSS Clarity Travel Management Software
		Air – Domestic	0.27867	
		Air - Short Haul	0.16508	
		Air - Long Haul	0.42565	
		Air - International	0.39764	
Rail	0.04885			
Procurement	Publications and Prints (Paper Use)	-	939	Request to Printing Services
	IT Equipment	PCs	1760.5	Request to IT & Digital Services
Water	Water Supply	-	0.344	UWS EMS Returns/Room sizes in square metres
	Water Treatment	-	0.708	
Waste	Hazardous Waste	WEEE	21	Waste Consignment Note
		Batteries	65	

4.5.2.3 Procurement data sources

Two of the draft sub-categories were changed (‘IT Equipment’ to “IT Equipment (PCs)” and ‘Publications’ to “Publications and Prints (Paper Use)”) to reflect data that were readily available for emission calculations under this category. The UWS Printing Services supplied the data used to calculate emissions associated with Publications & Prints (Paper Use) by way of total number of prints charged to the school. For IT Equipment (PCs), the UWS IT & Digital Services supplied the data used to calculate associated emissions by way of computer numbers owned/used by the school.

4.5.2.4 Waste management data sources

Waste Management data for WEEE and batteries disposal for the Paisley campus in tonnes was obtained from the Hazardous Waste Consignment Notes for both hazardous waste streams. At the time of the case study there was no data available for hazardous waste disposal relating to the Hamilton campus.

The draft school operational boundary for waste management included recycling, landfill, heat treatment, waste to energy and hazardous waste. Hazardous waste was the only emission source for which the school had a degree of control, particularly in relation to WEEE and battery disposal. Emissions associated with the emission sources relate to the Paisley campus only as information from Hamilton was not available at the time.

4.5.3 Conversion factors

The UK Government have determined several conversion factors (Table 4.2), and these have been applied throughout this chapter and based on the 2016 GHG reporting conversion factors (BEIS, 2016). These conversion factors are updated annually and suitable for use by organisations reporting on their operations in the UK. A methodology paper (BEIS, 2016) providing information on how these conversion factors are derived, the key data sources and assumptions used to define them is also published annually, accompanying the annual emission factors.

4.5.4 School infrastructure footprint

To allow the emissions from electricity, gas, and water consumption to be calculated solely for the school, room sizes (m²) was collated from Estates and Buildings (Table 4.3).

Table 4.3: Building and Campus Room Size (m²)

Campus	Total Size (m²)	SoSS Size (m²)
Paisley	52483.21	3996.91
Hamilton	26169.77	2599.37
Total	78652.98	6596.28

The school's electricity, gas and water consumption were calculated as per Equation 4.1. Emissions (CO₂e) for all emission sources were calculated as per Equation 4.2.

Equation 4.1: Consumption (kWh). Building footprint taken from Table 4.3

$$Consumption_{SoSS} = Consumption_{UWS} \times (SoSS \text{ m}^2 / UWS \text{ m}^2)$$

Equation 4.2: Emissions (kg CO₂e) calculation. Conversion Factors taken from Table 4.2

$$Emissions = Consumption \times Conversion \text{ Factor}$$

4.6 RESULTS

4.6.1 Energy from buildings

The EMS returns for the baseline shows that the total electricity consumption for the Paisley campus was 5,440,147 kWh (Table 4.4). This figure excludes consumption from the Robertson Sports Centre which is not part of the Paisley campus and for which square meterage information was not available and as such was excluded from the total Paisley electricity consumption. Total gas consumption for the Paisley campus was 8,265,273 kWh (Table 4.5). This figure includes consumption from the boiler house for which square meterage information was available however, the boiler house does not form part of the physical footprint of the school. Total baseline consumption and emissions for the school for Energy from Buildings is found in Table 4.6.

Table 4.4: Electricity Baseline consumption and emissions associated with Energy from Buildings.

Campus	Consumption (kWh)		Emissions (kg CO ₂ e)	
	UWS	SoSS	UWS	SoSS
Paisley	5,440,147	414,300	2,241,613	170,712
Hamilton	1,676,901	166,562	690,967	68,632
Total	7,117,048	580,862	2,932,580	239,344

Table 4.5: Gas baseline consumption and emissions associated with Energy from Buildings.

Campus	Consumption (kWh)		Emissions (kg CO ₂ e)	
	UWS	SoSS	UWS	SoSS
Paisley	8,265,673	629,480	1,520,884	115,824
Hamilton	5,438,050	540,146	1,000,601	99,387
Total	13,703,723	1,169,626	2,521,485	215,211

Table 4.6: Total Energy from Buildings baseline consumption and emissions for the SoSS

Campus	Total Consumption (kWh)	Total Emissions (kg CO ₂ e)
Paisley	1,043,780	286,536
Hamilton	706,708	168,019
Total	1,750,488	454,555

4.6.2 Travel

The travel emissions baseline shows that the total staff commute consumption for the school was 701,731 km split by travel means (Table 4.7). The business travel consumption was 316,227 km split by travel mode (Table 4.8). Total baseline consumption and emissions for the school for Travel is found in Table 4.9.

4.6.2.1 Staff commute

The mini travel survey in conjunction with Scottish national travel statistics (i.e., mileage per person, population & people in employment) were used to calculate carbon emission associated with each mode of travel following steps to calculate Scope 3 emissions associated with travel, as recommended by the HEFCE (HEFCE, 2010).

Table 4.7: Staff Commute consumption and emissions associated with Travel (see Appendix 5 for calculation breakdown).

Travel Means	Distance Travelled (km)	Emissions (kg CO ₂ e)
Car	539,793	100,914
Bus	15,423	1,569
Train	146,515	7,157
Total	701,731	109,640

4.6.2.2 Business conference travel (Business Travel)

This subcategory includes business travel paid for or reimbursed by the school, travel by hire of the UWS vehicle fleet, flight (air) and rail modes. It does not include business travel paid for by external sources. The university ‘welcome team’ provided data on travel by hire of the UWS vehicle fleet including mileage and vehicle type (see Appendices 10 - 13). Data on flight and rail travel were obtained through the school’s Clarity Booking System (see Appendix 6 & 7). Flight and rail data covered bookings made between periods August 2016 and November 2016, representing a third of the year and so the total emissions in this category was multiplied by three to determine the annual equivalent.

Table 4.8: Total Business Travel baseline consumption and emissions for the SoSS

Travel Mode		Distance Travelled (km)	Emissions (kg CO₂e)
UWS Vehicle Fleet Hire	Ford Focus 1.6 TDCI	4,138	607
	VW Transporter 1.8 TDCI	1,143	203
	Ford Mondeo 2.0 TDCI	3,553	630
	Ford Transit (minibus) 2.4TDCI	5,380	1209
Air	Domestic	8,982*	7509
	Short Haul	8,850*	4383
	Long Haul	61,501*	78534
	International	9,250*	11034
Rail		12,088**	1772
Total		316,227	105,881

*travel distance for 4-month period

**travel distance for 4-month period & total return rail journey

Table 4.9: Total Travel baseline consumption and emissions for the SoSS

Travel	Total Distance Travelled (km)	Total Emissions (kg CO₂e)
Staff Commute	701,731	109,640
Business Travel	316,227	105,881
Total	1,017,958	215,521

4.6.3 Procurement

The Procurement emissions baseline covers IT equipment (PCs) and publications and prints (paper use). The total consumption associated with PCs for Paisley and Hamilton campuses is found in Table 4.10, whilst the total consumption for publications and prints (paper use) is found in Table 4.11. Total baseline consumption and emissions for the school for Procurement is found in Table 4.12.

4.6.3.1 IT equipment (PCs)

The Consumption (Activity) data was derived by assuming an average weight for a PC and multiplying by the total number of PCs. A total of 172 PCs were associated with the school for both Paisley and Hamilton campuses. An average weight of 16.2 kg was used based on Hewlett-Packard (HP) Elite 8300 Desktop, 11.2kg (HP, 2022a) and HP Elite Display Monitor, 5 kg (HP, 2022b). The conversion factor used relate to the extraction, processing, manufacture and transportation of the PCs and not actual use of the PCs (BEIS, 2016).

4.6.3.2 Publications and prints (Paper Use):

The UWS uses several multi-function device printers across all campuses accessible for use by all staff and students. The total volume of prints for prints undertaken by the school in the 2015/16 academic year totalled **689,090 prints** and cost **£39,257.50**. The consumption data was derived by determining the total volume of printed sheets (689,000 sheets) and multiplying by the weight of one printing sheet (5 grams). The conversion factor used reflects the consumption of materials procured based on their primary or recycled materials only and not the materials in use (BEIS, 2016). The conversion factor for paper with recycled content is less than that without which implies the potential for reduced emissions and costs associated with the use of recycled paper.

Table 4.10: Total IT Equipment (PCs) consumption and emissions for the SoSS

IT Equipment (PCs)	Weight (tonnes)	Emissions (kg CO₂e)
Paisley	1.78	3,134
Hamilton	1.01	1,778
Total	2.79	4,912

Table 4.11: Total Publications and Prints (Paper Use) consumption and emissions for the SoSS

Publications and Prints (Paper Use)	Weight (tonnes)	Emissions (kg CO₂e)
Total	3.45	3,240

Table 4.12: Total Procurement consumption and emissions for the SoSS

Procurement	Total Weight (tonnes)	Total Emissions (kg CO₂e)
IT Equipment (PCs)	2.79	4,911
Publications and Prints (Paper use)	3.45	3,240
Total	6.24	8,151

4.6.4 Water

The EMS returns for the baseline shows that the total water supply consumption for the Paisley campus was 34067 m³ and for Hamilton campus 11810 m³ (Table 4.13). For water treatment the baseline shows the total wastewater consumption for the Paisley campus was 33321 m³ and for Hamilton campus 11921 m³ (Table 4.14).

Total baseline consumption and emissions for the school for Water is found in Table 4.15.

Table 4.13: Water Supply Baseline consumption and emissions associated with Water.

Campus	Consumption (m ³)		Emissions (kg CO ₂ e)	
	UWS	SoSS	UWS	SoSS
Paisley	34067	2594	11719	892
Hamilton	11810	1173	4063	404
Total	45877	3767	15782	1296

Table 4.14: Water Treatment Baseline consumption and emissions associated with Water.

Campus	Consumption (m ³)		Emissions (kg CO ₂ e)	
	UWS	SoSS	UWS	SoSS
Paisley	33321	2538	23591	1797
Hamilton	11921	1184	8440	838
Total	45242	3722	32031	2635

Table 4.15: Total Water baseline consumption and emissions for the SoSS

Campus	Total Consumption (m ³)	Total Emissions (kg CO ₂ e)
Paisley	5,132	2,689
Hamilton	2,357	1,242
Total	7,489	3,931

4.6.5 Waste management

The Waste Management emissions baseline covers Hazardous Waste only of which only WEEE and batteries are accounted for. The total baseline consumption and emissions for the school for Waste Management is found in Table 4.16. The Hazardous Waste Consignment Note provided consumption data information by weight for WEEE items and batteries for the Paisley campus only as no data was available for the Hamilton campus at the time of data collation.

Table 4.16: Total Waste Management baseline consumption and emissions for the SoSS (Paisley campus)

Waste Management	Total Weight (tonnes)	Total Emissions (kg CO₂e)
WEEE	5	105
Batteries	0.85	55
Total	5.85	160

4.6.6 School baseline footprint

The school CF baseline (2015/16 academic session) based on the model organisational boundaries is approximately **682,319 kgCO₂e** or **682 tCO₂e**. This result is as accurate as it can be based on the boundaries established and the availability of data. For a comparison with other HEIs per student/year please see Table 4.18. Table 4.17 shows the results of the carbon emissions calculations for each category and emission source in the model organisational boundaries, including Scope 1, Scope 2 and Scope 3 emissions associated with the school.

Table 4.17: 2015/16 Carbon Emissions Baseline by Category and Emission Sources

Categories	Emission Sources	Emission Scope	Sub Emission Sources	Emission (kgCO ₂ e)	% Contribution	% Contribution Total
Energy from Buildings	Gas	Scope 1	-	215211.00	31.54	66.62
	Electricity	Scope 2	-	239344.00	35.08	
Travel	Staff Commute	Scope 3	Car	100914.00	14.79	31.59
		Scope 3	Bus	1569.00	0.23	
		Scope 3	Train	7157.00	1.049	
	Business Travel	Scope 3	Ford Focus 1.6 TDCI	607.22	0.089	
		Scope 3	VW Transporter 1.8 TDCI	202.71	0.03	
		Scope 3	Ford Mondeo 2.0 TDCI	630.41	0.092	
		Scope 3	Ford Transit (minibus) 2.4TDCI	1209.03	0.177	
		Scope 3	Air – Domestic	7509.00	1.101	
		Scope 3	Air - Short Haul	4383.00	0.642	
		Scope 3	Air - Long Haul	78534.00	11.51	
		Scope 3	Air – International	11034.00	1.617	
		Scope 3	Rail	1772.00	0.26	
		Procurement	Publications and Prints (Paper Use)	Scope 3	-	
IT Equipment	Scope 3		PCs	4911.80	0.72	
Water	Water Supply	Scope 3	-	1295.80	0.19	0.58
	Water Treatment	Scope 3	-	2635.20	0.386	
Waste	Hazardous Waste	Scope 3	WEEE	105.00	0.015	0.02
		Scope 3	Batteries	55.25	0.008	
			Total	682318.97	100.00	100.00

4.7 DISCUSSION

Based on the available data from the school and university, the footprint for the school within identified operational boundaries was completed. Data collection for calculating emissions proved to be a significant challenge in terms of:

- identifying sources of information,
- getting the information in an appropriate format,
- the period(s) for which data is available,
- the completeness of the data, and
- reliability of the data.

Although the legal reporting requirement sits at university level, for the school to understand its emissions profile (and to determine areas within its control for potential improvement as required by its board) and work towards reducing its GHG emissions, it was essential to establish an emissions baseline. A CF was calculated for the academic year 2015/16 encompassing the emission sources as identified in the organisational boundaries shown in Figure 4.3 and is used as the emissions baseline. It is important to note that at the time the assessment was completed there was no reason to question the use of the baseline value which was established for a period prior to organisational restructure of the school in 2018.

Figure 4.3: Operational boundaries within the SoSS.

This case study identified how and where information was obtained to enable the baseline CF estimation of a well-defined, HE operational unit and highlights the need for improving the quality of data used for calculations. However, this can only be achieved through close working with the Estates department and steps taken to install Automated Meter Reader (AMR) across a university estate (See Recommendation 1).

Emissions from energy use in buildings and water were calculated from the EMS returns and room sizes (m²), however may be worth noting that the water emission results (approximately 0.6% of the estimated school emissions) fell slightly short of the HEFCE (2010) suggestion to assume that water accounts for 1% of all Scope1, Scope 2 and Scope 3 emissions in the absence of water data.

Emissions from travel were calculated based on several assumptions which are: (i) use of national level statistic for staff commute, (ii) use of booking dates as opposed to actual travel dates for air and rail business travel, (iii) projecting mini travel survey results for staff commute, and (iv) assuming non-respondents shared similar travel characteristics to respondents. However, a well-designed travel survey is required for both staff and students at university and school levels (See Recommendation 2) as well as configuring travel management or booking systems to produce high quality business travel data (See Recommendation 3).

Although several subcategories were identified in the draft operational boundaries, obtaining relevant information to calculate emissions associated with procurement and waste management was difficult. However, with inter departmental collaboration and aligning processes between campuses this can be improved (See Recommendations 4 and 5).

The greatest contributor to the school's CF was the Energy from Buildings category, accounting for two-thirds of the school's CF with electricity representing over a third of the total CF, whilst gas accounted for just under a third of the footprint at approximately 32%. The second most contributors to the footprint were from the Travel category, also accounting for just under a third of the footprint with staff commute representing 16% of the total footprint, and business travel similarly accounting for approximately 16% of the footprint. Of the total travel emissions, 49% were from road travel, 4% from rail and 47% from air travel. Emissions from Procurement, Water and Waste categories together accounted for approximately 2% of the footprint. Well over half (62%) of the school's footprint resulted from FF sources (these figures fully exclude emissions associated with electricity consumption and train/rail related travel) with road travel representing 25%, air travel 24% and gas use in buildings 51%.

Figure 4.4 shows the CF breakdown by emission sources for the school 2015/16 baseline year. The result highlights reducing emissions from the Energy from Buildings and Travel categories as the obvious target to reduce the school’s overall footprint. Reducing emissions associated with Procurement, Water and Waste will also contribute to the overall reduction of the school’s footprint; with the availability of more robust data to calculate emissions associated with Procurement, Water and Waste, and a better understanding of their emission profiles, reductions are achievable.

Figure 4.4: SoSS CF by Emission Sources 2015/16

Comparing the school’s CF and/or the UWS CF with the CF of other HEIs is challenging and must be done with caution however, achievable with the use of appropriate metrics. Generally, HEIs vary in size, population, activities undertaken, and have ranging emission sources. Furthermore, the approaches used for obtaining activity data to calculate emissions vary across HEIs, likewise the emission sources that are reported based on availability of reliable and complete data, especially Scope 3 emissions. However, similarities and differences can be drawn from the various methodologies for example, in calculating university wide or Departmental footprints;

with regards to data accessibility and collation; and in emission sources reported (Clabeaux *et al.*, 2020; Ridhosari and Rahman, 2020; Kandananond, 2017; Larsen *et al.*, 2013; Ozawa-Meida *et al.*, 2013; Alvarez, Blanquer and Rubio, 2014).

Clabeaux *et al.* (2020) calculated a university wide CF for a research-intensive university in 2014 using a streamlined LCA approach with most data recorded in terms of energy and mass units, and in monetary terms for university-related travel. Where data was lacking particularly for Scope 3 emission calculations and like the approach taken in this case study, estimates from other sources were used. Ozawa-Meida *et al.* (2013) calculated a university wide footprint for 2008/09 using a consumption-based approach to estimate Scopes 1, 2 and 3 emissions. They use a combination of spend data (bottom-up approach) and national average data (top-down approach) with data relatively easily derived. National average data was used to calculate emissions associated with staff commute in this case study. Ridhosari and Rahman (2020) calculated a university wide CF for 2017/18 using data from direct sampling, questionnaire survey, and secondary data. Kandananond (2017) also calculated a university wide footprint reporting only on Scopes 1 (direct emissions from car fleet) and 2 (indirect emissions from electricity consumption in buildings) emissions, in which case data is complete, reliable, and readily available.

However, whilst Larsen *et al.* (2013) calculated a university wide footprint for 2009 using financial accounts as the main source of data for EEIO modelling, their method allowed for easy footprint updates based on annual financial data and segmentation of the footprint into departmental, faculty or school CF. Their results show large variations in faculty footprints indicating different mitigation strategy requirements. In the case of Alvarez, Blanquer and Rubio (2014), they calculated a Faculty footprint for Scopes 1, 2 and 3 emissions for 2010 using Compound Method which is based on Financial Accounts allowing for easily obtained data.

The school footprint study and most of the footprints from the research papers considered above except one '(Ozawa-Meida *et al.*, 2013)' indicate that emissions associated with electricity were the largest contributors to overall footprints as shown below:

- School footprint (this study) – 35% contribution from electricity.

- Clabeaux *et al.* (2020) – 41% contribution from electricity generation.
- Ridhosari and Rahman (2020) – 92% contribution from electricity.
- Larsen *et al.* (2013) – 14% contribution from electricity.
- Kandananond (2017) – 98% contribution from electricity.
- Alvarez, Blanquer and Rubio (2014) – 42% contribution from electricity (accounting categories) and 31% contribution from materials (consumption categories), and
- Ozawa-Meida *et al.* (2013) – 38% contribution from procurement.

Table 4.18 shows further highlights from these studies in terms emission sources, footprints, and the per student and/or per person footprint equivalent which ranged from between 0.1 to 4.4 tCO₂e.

Table 4.18: Highlights of some University wide/University Departmental Footprints

Study	Emission Sources			Footprint (tCO ₂ e)			
	Scope 1	Scope 2	Scope 3	Scope 1	Scope 2	Scope 3	Total
This case study	Gas	Electricity	Travel, Procurement, Water, Hazardous Waste	215 (32%)	239 (35%)	228 (33%)	682 (0.5/student)
Clabeaux <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Steam generation, Refrigerants, Owned vehicles, Fertilizer Wastewater treatment	Electricity generation	Electricity life cycle, Distribution losses, University related travel, Paper, Natural gas leakage, Refrigerants, Waste transport, Treatment Chemicals, etc.	18,041 (19%)	38,718 (40.6%)	38,659 (40.5%)	95,418 (4.4/student)
Alvarez, Blanquer and Rubio (2014)	Natural Gas, Gasoil, Petrol,	Electricity	Materials, Works, Service Contracts, Agricultural resources, Water, Waste, Scopes 1 & 2 Life cycle emissions, etc.	169 (8%)	703 (33%)	1275 (59%)	2147 (1.9/student) (1.6/person)
Ozawa-Meida <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Gas use & Owned fleet	Grid electricity	Procurement, Travel	3545 (6%)	8934 (15%)	38602 (79%)	51,080 (2.4/student)
Kandananond (2017)	Fuel for car fleet	Electricity	'None reported'	13 (2%)	651 (98%)	None reported	664 (0.1/student)
Ridhosari and Rahman (2020)	'None identified'	Electricity	Transportation, Solid waste	None identified	1248 (92%)	104 (8%)	1,352 (0.5/person)
Larsen <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Energy – combustion of fuel & heating oil	Electricity & district heating	Purchases of goods & services	None identified	None identified	None identified	92,000 (4.4/student)

With regards to actions required to reduce organisational emissions from these, the following are highlighted:

- Switch from coal to natural gas for steam generation and increased energy efficiency of appliances and equipment (Clabeaux *et al.*, 2020).
- Renewable technology installation, improved lighting controls, and provision of shuttle buses and dormitories in living areas close to the university (Ridhosari and Rahman, 2020).
- Improved building energy efficiency measures and reduced opening hours, use of video conferencing, and sustainability strategies (Larsen *et al.*, 2013).
- Implementation of zero-cost measures through benefit from natural daylight (Alvarez, Blanquer and Rubio, 2014).

Since undertaking this case study, the UWS has taken several steps as highlighted in its 2018/19 annual sustainability report, to further reduce GHG emissions resulting from its operations, the most notable of which is its new Lanarkshire Campus which is claimed to be carbon neutral for energy (UWS, 2020). According to the report (UWS, 2020) other steps reported by UWS by way of actions and planned actions to reduce emissions and become more sustainable include:

- A 25-pence single-use coffee cup charge which significantly increased the number of customers using reusable cups.
- Planting of 308 trees to offset carbon emissions through a coffee partnership, nevertheless the offset value is not reported.
- Electrification of the university's vehicle fleet which will reduce onsite emissions and likely prevent some real emissions that would have otherwise been released because of FF driven vehicles.
- A range of planned sustainability research projects valued at £4.4million.
- Use of the Sustainable Flexible Procurement Framework to embed Sustainability in procurement activities.
- Upgrade of lighting to ultra-efficient light emitting diodes (LEDs) in some buildings at Paisley campus.
- Upgrade of the Paisley Campus Building Management System (BMS) allowing for better heating system control and saving 176 tCO_{2e} per year.

4.8 CONCLUSIONS

This CF baseline assessment was instigated by the then UWS SoSS board as part of its operational plan to define a baseline, enhance methodology to reduce carbon emissions, and improve data supply reporting relevant to its CF as such stipulated as part of the criteria for undertaking this PhD research. Whilst the undertaking of CF assessments is commonplace across global organisations, its relevance to this research as a case study presented the opportunity for a more focused study on a unit sizeable enough to reflect typical HEI structures but not too big to make data collection impossible. Furthermore, it contributes to the evaluation of FF energy reliance in public sector bodies and in the development of a framework for reducing reliance.

According to UWS reports, it has more than doubled its emission reduction target of 20% by 2020 having reduced its emissions from its baseline by 42% in 2018/19 however, no direct measurement of departmental footprints exists within UWS. In this chapter, through a case study to determine a departmental footprint, an emissions baseline is established for the school for the 2015/16 academic year, a record of where and how data is obtained, and steps identified to enable the reduction of its footprint. The school footprint is estimated by multiplying activity data for each emission source in the operational boundary by the corresponding conversion factors and adding them to get a total amount. The study covers the Paisley and Hamilton campuses only, highlights the need for improving the quality of data used to make the calculations and identifying a responsible person within the school to coordinate improving data quality, and emissions calculations.

The 2015/16 baseline footprint for the school is estimated at approximately 682 tCO₂e, 67% of which are associated with Energy use in buildings, 32% associated with Travel, and the remainder associated with procurement, Water and Waste. Scope 2 emissions represent 35% of reported emissions with electricity solely responsible for this, whilst Scope 3 emissions represent 33%, 32% of which relate to travel emissions. The remainder 32% represent Scope 1 emissions and solely attributed to gas consumption. Energy from buildings and Travel categories of emissions are undoubtedly the greatest contributors to the school's CF and should be targeted for emission reductions, particularly travel decisions for which the school has more of a control of comparison to use of energy in buildings. Whilst comparing these results with those of similar studies

is difficult due to several factors such as differences in physical footprints, population size, emissions sources reported etc., it highlights the need for comparative assessments. A common theme in similar studies referred to in the discussion section (4.7), is that electricity represents the single most contributor to overall emissions, ranging from 14% to 98% of overall emissions.

In terms of emissions from FF sources, approximately 62% of the footprint resulted from FFs, of which gas represents 51%, air travel represents 24% and 25% for road travel. Whilst individual FF sources like gas, diesel, petrol, and coal are commonly reported individually, specific reporting on the combination of emissions resulting from FF sources is not common within public sector bodies. This is explored in more detail in Chapter 5, part of which focuses on the assessment of the corporate emissions of Scottish public sector bodies in contribution to evaluating and understanding FF reliance.

4.9 RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are suggested:

1. Implement measures to ensure that individual schools can calculate their CF and take actions accordingly. For example, the physical footprint of school's should be regularly updated to ensure their accuracy likewise installing automatic meter readers across buildings to obtain actual electricity and gas consumption data.
2. Conduct staff and student travel surveys at a manageable frequency, which will provide a more detailed account of travel patterns, real time data and override the need to use average national level statistics for calculating associated emissions.
3. Ensure travel management system can calculate associated travel emissions or provide data to enable this for example information on actual travel dates, flight type (domestic, short haul etc.) and cabin class, and distances travelled for air and rail modes.
4. Work in collaboration with the wider UWS procurement team to better understand the school procurement profile and categorise it to enable the calculation of emissions associated with the procurement of goods and services. Whilst this should already be done at university level, collaboration will be key

and beneficial to both parties in developing more sustainable practices across the board.

5. Align the processes for the disposal of WEEE and batteries from all campuses of operation in line with legal requirements, ensuring they can be presented when sought.
6. Target reducing emissions associated with FF use for energy in buildings and for travel which are the greatest contributors to the school's CF, especially travel, as the school has more control over travel decisions.
7. Identify or appoint responsible persons to coordinate data collation and emission calculations across schools in event of the school actively seeks to take ownership of its CF assessment.
8. Reduce energy consumption where possible, and where appropriate explore opportunities to install renewable energy technologies like solar panels.
9. Create opportunities to aid academic learning and acquisition of new knowledge for its staff and students. This may be achieved through school research activities that aid standardisation of the CF data gathering process across Schools and the wider University, ensuring lessons learned are applied to the continuous improvement of organisational CF processes.

CHAPTER 5:

**REVIEW OF CORPORATE EMISSIONS REPORTED BY SCOTTISH PUBLIC
SECTOR BODIES**

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter contributes to the research aim of evaluating and understanding reliance on FF as an energy source in Scotland's public sector as defined in Chapter 1 of the thesis (Section 1.2); and to the specific objective of analysing and comparing sources and quantities of corporate emissions reported by public sector bodies to the Scottish Government. Given the scope of this thesis it will be ideal to highlight the percentage of Scotland's annual carbon emissions that come from public sector bodies' however, the answer appears elusive. This is because the main source of Scottish emission reports that is the Scottish GHG Statistics reports only accounts for emissions from fuel combustion (natural gas) in public sector buildings, and emissions associated with transport and fuel combustion for electricity are reported under separate categories i.e., Transport and Energy Supply respectively (Scottish Government, 2022). Whilst it may be argued that the emissions contribution of public sector bodies to Scotland's annual emissions is elusive, it presents as an area in need of further exploration given the significance of the public sector in the climate change narrative. This aspect of the research does not attempt to estimate the sector's contribution to annual emissions, nevertheless provides significant insights into the quantity and types of emissions reported by Scottish public sector bodies.

The public sector is vital in facilitating the drive to low carbon and carbon neutral technologies enabling the achievement of net-zero emissions and is at the heart of the transition in our energy systems through its role in democratic governance, in decarbonisation, its market power, and by virtue of being decentralised (Wade, 2021; Ottelin, Heinonen and Junnila, 2018). It should act as an exemplar and facilitator for positive societal transformation towards sustainable development (Filimonau *et al.*, 2021), an important part of which is reducing carbon emissions (Li *et al.*, 2021), through strategies that focus on sustainable energy consumption (Guerrieri *et al.*, 2019) and reducing energy consumption (Christis, Athanassiadis and Vercauteren, 2019). Not least because of its contribution to GHG emissions a result of its vast operations and spending power, for example public buildings like LGA and university buildings often have various use profiles from standard classrooms, offices, and function halls to the likes of laboratories which are very energy intensive (Guerrieri *et al.*, 2019; Filimonau *et al.*, 2021).

Scottish public sector bodies are mandated by the Scottish Government through the Climate Change (Duties of Public Bodies: Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Order 2015 (as amended), to report on GHG emissions associated with activities across their estate, owned asset, and service they provide. These emissions mostly include Scope 1 and 2 emissions (for example electricity, gas, and water) which are mandatory, and often Scope 3 emissions (for example waste, non-fleet business travel and procurement) which is reported voluntarily (Peters, 2010). The SSN Public Bodies Climate Change Reporting 2018/19 Analysis Report indicates a reduction in Scottish public bodies' emissions since 2015 when the Order came into effect (SSN, 2020). The SSN works with a range of public sector bodies in Scotland (comprising 32 LGAs, 19 HEIs and 26 Further Education (FE) institutions, amongst others), manages and coordinates the Public Bodies Climate Change reporting on behalf of the Scottish Government (SSN, no date). As of March 2023, the breakdown of Scottish public bodies who submitted climate change reports to the SSN is as follows:

- Transport Partnerships – 7
- Educational Institutions – 45
- Integration Joint Boards – 30
- LGAs – 32
- National health Services – 22
- Others – 58

Whilst it is acknowledged that there are other public bodies in Scotland as defined by the Scottish Government (2018a), the groups of public bodies itemised above are those listed in Schedule 1 of the Climate Change (Duties of Public Bodies; Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Order 2015. Two sets of reviewed documents, that is the SSNs summary analysis report encompassing returns for the relevant listed public bodies and those specifically relating to the participating organisations as defined in Chapter 1 cover reporting periods from 2015/16 to 2018/19. These represent the latest submissions at the time of undertaking the document analysis, are held on the SSN database and readily available to download. Whilst eighteen semi-structured interviews were undertaken, the sector actors' organisational affiliation cut across six LGAs and five HEIs, as such a total of eleven reports (see Section 5.5) from the participating organisations were reviewed and compared to the SSNs summary reports. In line with the study ethical approval, interview participants and their organisations remain

confidential. The analysis of the semi-structured interview responses for the participating organisations is available in Chapter 6 (see Section 6.4).

5.2 TOTAL SCOTTISH PUBLIC SECTOR EMISSIONS REPORTED TO SSN

The SSN 2018/19 Analysis Report indicates a 13.1% reduction in emissions from the 2017/18 period, and 23.3% from the 2015/16 period. The report attributes reductions largely to the reduction in the electricity generation emission factor because of the decarbonising electricity grid and a warmer 2018/19 resulting in less heating demand compared to the previous year, 2017/18 (SSN, 2020). Figure 5.1 shows the reduction in Scottish public sector reported corporate emissions between reporting periods 2015/16 and 2018/19.

Figure 5.1: Scottish Public Sector Total Reported Emissions 15/16 to 18/19 (See Table: 3.1)

In the 2015/16 reporting period Scottish public sector bodies reported a total of 3.27 MtCO₂e of emissions, reducing to 2.51 MtCO₂e in 2018/19. Over the last four reporting periods from 2015 to 2019, LGAs have reported the biggest share of emissions with an average of 49% of total reported emissions. Educational Institutions (HE and FE) have an average share of 14% of total emissions over the same reporting periods. It is relevant to remember that Educational Institutions don't include all organisational impacts and are probably under-reporting actual emissions. Student travel for example may have considerable contributions but is under-reported. Together, LGAs and Educational Institutions represent an average share of 63% of reported Scottish public sector emissions over the last four reporting periods. Figure 5.2 shows the annual

combined share of emissions for LGAs and Educational Institutions against the remainder of reported Scottish public sector emissions. There is an annual increase of 1% in the combined share of emissions for LGAs and Educational Institutions between 2015/16 – 2017/18, solely attributed to the increase in the share of LGAs over that period (SSN, 2019; SSN, 2020).

Figure 5.2: Annual Combined Share of Total Reported Emissions for LGAs and Educational Institutions from 2015/16 – 2018/19 (See Table: 3.1)

Emissions from Electricity and gas sources have consistently made up most of the total reported Scottish public sector emissions, representing an average share of just over 70% between reporting period 2015/16 to 2018/2019. Whilst emissions from electricity have reduced and largely attributed to a reduction in the emission factor, a fall in electricity consumption also played its part with a 2.2% reduction in electricity consumption between 2015/16 and 2016/17, a 2.9% reduction between 2015/16 and 2017/18, and a 4.4% reduction between 2015/16 and 2018/19. Although there is an increase in emissions from natural gas reported in 2017/18, there is equally a decrease in natural gas emissions reported in 2018/19. Emissions reported for renewables have consistently been low in comparison to other emission sources, making up an average 0.1% over the same reporting periods (SSN, 2019; 2020).

5.3 SCOTTISH PUBLIC SECTOR FF CONSUMPTION REPORTED TO SSN

Over the last four reporting periods between 2015 and 2019, reported Scottish public sector emissions reduced by over 23%; despite the annual reductions in emissions, the reliance on FF on the other hand appears to have increased over the same period (SSN, 2019; SSN, 2020). Whilst comparison over time is instructive, by virtue of the thesis definition of the Scottish public sector comparison overtime is from 2015 when the mandatory reporting duties came into force. The SSN 2018/19 Analysis Report splits the reported emissions into the following emission sources:

- Electricity
- Natural gas
- Other heating fuel
- Process
- Refrigerants
- Waste
- Water and sewerage
- Travel
- Transport fuel
- Commuting
- Procurement
- Other
- Renewables

From the above list the following sources of emissions represent FF emission sources:

- Natural gas
- Other heating fuel
- Travel
- Transport fuel
- Commuting

For the purpose of this thesis chapter section (5.3) FF emissions refer to the total emissions resulting from the above-named emission sources. These FF emissions can be broadly attributed to two main demands: heating (natural gas and other heating fuel) and transportation (travel, transport fuel, and commuting). Figure 5.3 shows an annual increase in the composition of FF emissions by percentage of total reported emissions

between 2015 and 2019, against the reduction in total reported Scottish public sector emissions over the same period.

Figure 5.3: Increase in reported FF emissions against the reduction in total reported Scottish public sector emissions 15/16 to 18/19 (See Table: 3.1).

In 2015/16, 1.34M tCO₂e of the reported 3.27M tCO₂e resulted from FF emissions, representing 41% of total reported emissions this increased to 51% of reported emissions in 2018/19. This indicates a 24% change in the percentage composition of emissions attributable to FF sources, and an average 45% FF composition of emissions, between the four-year reporting period from 2015 to 2019. Emissions associated with heating (natural gas and other heating fuel) represent an average 33% of total reported emissions and 73% of the FF emission composition, over the four-year period. Emissions associated with transportation (travel, transport fuel, and commuting) on the other hand represent an average 12% of total reported emissions and 27% of the FF emission composition, over the four-year period. Figure 5.4 shows the annual composition of reported emissions by source between 2015/16 and 2018/19.

Figure 5.4: Annual Composition of Scottish Public Sector reported emissions related to FFs between 15/16 and 18/19 (See Table: 3.1).

5.4 SCOTTISH PUBLIC SECTOR EMISSION REDUCTION PROJECTS REPORTED TO SSN

The SSN regard emission reduction projects as activities that reduce GHG emissions within a reporting year for example energy efficiency projects aiming to reduce the demand for energy and renewable energy projects which reduce emissions from energy supply (SSN, 2019; SSN, 2020; Scottish Government, 2018b; Gómez *et al.*, 2016).

Over the last four reporting periods from 2015 to 2019, the Scottish public sector reported average total annual savings in emissions from emission reduction projects of 89,873 tCO₂e which is 3% of the average total reported emissions. Over this period LGAs have the largest share of reported emissions and contributed the most to reported emission savings in the sector with an annual average of 46,396 tCO₂e, representing an annual average of 3% of LGA emissions. This is followed by Educational Institutions reporting an annual average emission savings of 18,659 tCO₂e, which represents an annual average of 4% of its reported emissions during the same period. Together, LGAs and Educational Institutions reported annual average emission savings of 65,055 tCO₂e (72% of average annual total reported public sector emission savings) through emission reduction projects. Whilst LGAs have realised more emission savings from projects in tCO₂e, Educational institutions have seen a decline in savings however, realised more emission savings as a percentage of its total reported emissions (SSN, 2020). Figure 5.5 shows an overall reduction in annual emissions savings from reported projects in tCO₂e

for reporting periods 2015/16 to 2018/19. These savings increased in 2016/17 but lost that momentum in the following years and may be due to standard emission reduction projects already implemented from the beginning of the reporting period (SSN, 2020).

Figure 5.5: Scottish public sector annual emissions savings from reported emission reduction projects in tCO₂e 15/16 to 18/19 (See Table: 3.3).

In terms of emission savings by source, the most reported emission reduction projects are those that involve management of electricity use with an average contribution of 45,894 tCO₂e (51% of total reported public sector emission savings). Savings from waste projects is the second with an average contribution of 18,806 tCO₂e representing 21% of total reported emission savings. Savings from the combination of projects associated with reported FF sources made up of natural gas, other heating fuels, business travel and fleet transport, contributed savings of 20,835 tCO₂e and represents 23% of total reported emission savings. Of the 23% FF emission savings, natural gas projects contributed 12%, other heating fuels 6%, business travel 2% and fleet transport 3%. Table 5.1 shows examples of emission reduction projects reported for each emission source, and the average percentage contribution to the total reported savings between 2015/16 and 2018/19.

Table 5.1: Examples of emission reduction projects reported for emission sources, and average percentage contribution to the total Scottish public sector reported savings 2015/16 and 18/19 (SSN, 2019; 2020).

Emission Source		Project Examples	Percentage of Reported Savings	
Electricity		LED lighting	51%	
		Lighting - internal, external and street		
		Photovoltaic (PV) panels		
		CHP (Combined Heat and Power) installations		
Waste		Diversion of waste-to-landfill projects through recycling and reuse projects	21%	
		Reduced printing projects		
		Installation of hand dryers		
FFs	Natural gas	Boiler upgrade or replacement	12%	23%
		BMS upgrade		
		Biomass boiler installations		
	Other heating fuels	Replacement fuel boilers (oil to gas or oil to biomass)	6%	
		BMS upgrades		
		Installation improvements		
	Business travel	Sustainable business travel policies and practices (i.e., 'Limited internal travel month')	2%	
		CO ₂ cap on leased fleet		
		Video conferencing projects		
	Fleet transport	Expansion of Electric Vehicles (EV) networks	3%	
Fleet replacement including hydrogen and EVs				
Water and sewerage		Water efficiency measures	1%	
		Waterless urinals		
		Water leakage reduction		
		Water efficiency audits		
Other			4%	

In terms of annual renewable energy generation, Scottish public sector bodies reported an average of 95GWh of renewable electricity generation and 176GWh of renewable heat generation between reporting periods 2015/16 and 2018/19. LGAs are responsible for an average 32% of reported renewable electricity generation and 57% of reported renewable heat generation, whilst the most reported renewable energy technology in use are solar panels and biomass boilers, with heat pumps, solar thermal and wind also commonly reported. Despite these efforts, the picture over this period (2015/16 to 2018/19) in terms of carbon savings with an average of 89,873tCO₂e from emission

reduction projects and 73,527 tCO₂e from renewable energy installations, relative to overall sector emissions 2,919,974 tCO₂e suggests that a lot more work is required.

5.5 TOTAL REPORTED PARTICIPATING ORGANISATIONS EMISSIONS

The purpose of this section is to allow for a comparison between overall reported corporate emissions to the SSN (by the listed bodies) and those of the participating organisations. There is a reduction in total annual reported emissions for these participating organisations, with a total of 571,545 tCO₂e reported in 2015/16 and 487,547 tCO₂e reported in 2018/19, representing a 15% decrease in emissions over this period. This is similar to the decrease in overall sector emissions of 23.3% over the same reporting period. Some of the participating organisations have performed better than others in terms of their percentage of emission reductions between 2015/16 and 2018/19. This is because four of the eleven participating organisations reduced their emissions by 24% or more within the period, the average reduction by a participating organisation being 17%. The biggest reduction over the period of 44% was from a LGA and attributed to a variety of projects like LED street lighting and solar panel installations. However, one University, increased its emissions over the same period by 19%. The increase was annual and due to expansion of the University estate that is the commissioning of new buildings and purchase of other buildings, with the biggest increment coming between 2017/18 and 2018/19 at 11.5%. From the review of submitted reports, emission reduction projects undertaken by those organisations reporting 24% and more reductions in emissions over the period, are in line with projects identified in Tables 5.1 and 5.3.

Emissions reported by participating organisations were 17% of the total sector emissions in 2015/16, rising to 19% in 2016/17 and remaining at 19% through to 2018/19. Figure 5.6 shows a breakdown of emission sources into electricity, FFs and others as a percentage of total reported emissions, for the Scottish public sector and Participating Organisations (data for individual organisational reports are available on the SSN website).

Figure 5.6: Breakdown of emissions for Scottish Public Sector and Participating Organisations as a percentage of their total reported emissions 15/16 to 18/19 (See Table: 3.1 and Table: 3.2).

Even though the participating organisations are made up of 6 HEIs and 5 LGAs, over the last four reporting periods from 2015 to 2019, participating LGAs have reported the biggest share of emissions representing an average of 57% of total reported emissions during this period, whilst participating HEIs account for the remainder 43%. Table 5.2 shows the total percentage share of emissions for participating LGAs and HEIs from 2015 to 2019.

Table 5.2: Total percentage share of emissions for participating LGAs and HEIs 15/16 to 18/19.

Participating Organisations	2015/16	2016/17	2017/18	2018/19	Avg 15 – 19
LGAs	59%	57%	57%	54%	57%
HEIs	41%	43%	43%	46%	43%

Emissions from Electricity and gas sources makes up most of the total reported participating organisations, representing an average share of 69% in the 2018/19 reporting period, and like the average share of over 70% of total reported Scottish public sector emissions over the same reporting period. Emissions from Biomass is the

only reported renewables emission source and only five of the participating organisations reported biomass emissions in 2018/19. In comparison to other emission sources biomass emissions are very low and represent only 0.1% of total reported emissions. This again is like the consistently low emissions from renewables (average 0.1%) reported by the Scottish public sector over the same reporting period.

5.6 PARTICIPATING ORGANISATIONS FF CONSUMPTION

In this thesis chapter section, FF emissions refer to the total emissions resulting from FF energy sources, reported by participating organisations. These FF emissions can be broadly attributed to two main demands; heating (natural gas, other fuels, and coal) and transportation (travel, transport fuels, vehicles and well to tank transport).

Despite the 15% reduction in emission reported by the participating organisations between 2015/16 (571,545 tCO₂e) and 2018/19 (487,547 tCO₂e), in 2018/19 the reliance on FFs by participating organisations is again evident as with the Scottish public sector. Figure 5.7 shows an increase in reported FF emissions by percentage of the total reported emissions between 2015 and 2019, against the reduction in total reported participating organisations emissions over the same period. A noticeable decrease in reported emissions can be seen in Figure 5.7. Reported emissions for all participating organisations bar one with an increase of nearly 20% reduced between 2015/16 and 2018/19, with one organisation (LGA) reducing its overall reported emissions by 44% over the stated period.

Figure 5.7: Increase in reported FF emissions against the reduction in total reported participating organisations emissions 15/16 to 18/19 (See Table: 3.2).

In 2015/16, participating organisations reported emissions of 571,545 tCO₂e of which 215,215 tCO₂e resulted from FF emissions, representing 38% of total reported emissions this increased to 61% of reported emissions in 2018/19. This indicates a 61% change in the percentage composition of emissions attributable to FF sources, and an average 51% FF composition of emissions, between the four-year reporting period from 2015/16 and 2018/19. These significant increases are mainly due to the increased capturing and reporting of travel relates emissions by Scottish public sector bodies. Emissions associated with heating (natural gas, coal, and other heating fuel except for Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) represent an average 33% of total reported emissions and 64% of the FF emission composition, over the four-year period. Emissions associated with transportation (travel, transport fuel, and commuting) on the other hand represent an average 18% of total reported emissions and 36% of the FF emission composition, over the four-year period. Figure 5.8 shows the average composition of participating organisations reported emissions by source between 2015/16 and 2018/19.

Figure 5.8: Average composition of Participating Organisations reported emissions related to FFs between 15/16 and 18/19 (See Table: 3.2).

5.7 PARTICIPATING ORGANISATIONS EMISSION REDUCTION PROJECTS

Over the last four reporting periods from 2015/16 to 2018/19, participating organisations reported average total annual savings in emissions from emission reduction projects of 27,374 tCO₂e which is 5% of the total reported emissions. Whilst unable to validate these emission savings, given the reports are returned as a legal requirement it is presumed to represent real reductions. Over this period LGAs have the largest share of reported emissions and contributed the most to reported emission savings in the sector with an annual average of 16,049 tCO₂e, representing an annual average of 5% of LGA emissions. HEIs report an annual average emission savings of 11,326 tCO₂e, which represents an average of 5% of its reported emissions during the same period. Participating LGAs and HEIs have realised the same savings (5%) as a percentage of their total reported emissions. Figure 5.9 shows the overall reduction in annual emissions savings from reported projects (see Table 5.3) in tCO₂e for reporting periods 2015/16 to 2018/19. This represents a 63% change in emissions savings from reported projects in tCO₂e between reporting periods 2015/16 to 2018/19. However, the sharp increase in emissions savings in 2016/17 as seen in Figure 5.9 is attributable mainly to the increase in reported savings from electricity related projects from the previous year (59%). Whilst there was a significant increase in overall emissions savings for these participating organisations between 2015/16 and 2016/17 of over 100%, a similar pattern in emissions savings for the overall sector is evident with emissions savings subsequently losing momentum in the following reporting periods, by 82% between 2016/17 and 2018/19. This may be interpreted as meaning that there has been no real change for participating organisations by way of emissions savings from emission reduction projects.

Figure 5.9: Participating organisations annual emissions savings from reported emission reduction projects in tCO₂e 15/16 to 18/19 (See Table: 3.5).

In terms of emission savings by source (See Table: 3.5), the most reported emission reduction projects that reduce emissions is electricity with an annual average contribution of 20,738 tCO₂e (76% of total reported participating organisations emission savings). Savings from waste projects is the second biggest with an average contribution of 3,120 tCO₂e representing 11% of total reported emission savings. Savings from the combination of projects associated with reported FF sources made up of natural gas, other heating fuels, business travel and fleet transport, contributed savings of 3,447 tCO₂e and represents 13% of total reported emission savings. Of the 13% FF emission savings, natural gas projects contributed 10%, business travel 2% and fleet transport 1%. Table 5.3 shows examples of emission reduction projects reported for each emission source, and the average percentage contribution to the total reported savings between 2015/16 and 2018/19. This covers and provides a comparison between emissions savings from projects for the public sector as a whole and for the participating organisations.

Table 5.3: Examples of emission reduction projects reported for emission sources, and average percentage contribution to the total public sector and participating organisations reported savings 15/16 and 18/19

Emission Sources		Project Examples	Percentage of Reported Savings for participating organisations		Percentage of Reported Savings for the sector			
Electricity		LED lighting	76%	51%				
		Lighting - internal, external and street						
		PV panels						
		CHP installations						
		Hot water controls (pumps)						
		VSDs and Voltage Optimisation						
Waste		Diversion of waste-to-landfill projects through recycling and reuse projects	11%	21%				
		Warp-it						
		Installation of hand dryers & drying cabinets						
		Reduced printing projects						
FFs	Natural gas	Boiler upgrade or replacement & vented cupboard conversion	10%	13%	12%	23%		
		BMS upgrade						
		Hot water controls						
		Biomass boiler installations						
	Other heating fuel	Replacement fuel boilers (oil to gas or oil to biomass)	0%	6%				
		BMS upgrades						
		Installation improvements						
	Business travel	Sustainable business travel policies and practices (Limited internal travel month)	2%	2%				
		CO ₂ cap on leased fleet						
		Video conferencing projects						
	Fleet transport	Initiatives to reduce business travel	1%	3%				
		Expansion of EV networks						
Fleet replacement including hydrogen and EVs								
Water and Sewerage		Water efficiency measures including AMRs	0%	1%				
		Waterless urinals						
		Water leakage reduction						
		Water efficiency audits						
Other			0%		4%			

In terms of annual renewable energy generation, participating organisations reported an annual average of 17 GWh of renewable electricity generation and 9 GWh of renewable heat generation between reporting periods 2015/16 and 2018/19 (See Table: 3.4). The most reported renewable energy technology in use are solar panels (78% of reported renewable electricity generation), biomass boilers (56% of reported renewable heat generation), and solar thermal (21% of reported renewable heat generation), with landfill gas CHP, wind, air source and ground source heat pumps, and biogas CHP also individually reported at 8% or lower.

5.8 REPORTED TARGETS FOR SCOTTISH PUBLIC SECTOR AND PARTICIPATING ORGANISATIONS

Scottish public sector bodies report on their targets to reduce emissions and contribute to public sector climate change action. These targets include overall emission reduction targets and specific targets which relate to various emission sources and organisational policy areas. From the review of the available annual public bodies climate change summary analysis reports (2015/16 to 2018/19), the most applied targets across Scottish public sector bodies are for overall emissions and energy use in buildings (See Table: 3.6). On average over 77% of Scottish public sector bodies annually reported at least one target between 2015/16 and 2018/19, with fleet transport being the least reported on. From the review of the available annual public bodies' climate change reporting returns for participating organisations (2015/16 to 2018/19), the most applied targets are in the following order: overall emissions (34%), waste (22%), energy use in buildings (13%) and commuter travel (13%). On average over 91% of participating organisations annually reported at least one target between 2015/16 and 2018/19, with fleet transport also being the least reported as with the overall Scottish public sector. The emission reductions target for Scotland has changed in recent years from a target of 80% emission reduction by 2050 to net-zero emissions by 2045. It is important to note that the Climate Change (Duties of Public Bodies; Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Order 2015 as amended now requires public sector bodies to report a target date for reducing direct emissions to net-zero levels (SSN, no date). Therefore, these organisations now must commit to achieving net-zero direct emissions by their stated target date of achievement.

5.9 DISCUSSIONS - REPORTED EMISSIONS AND EMISSION REDUCTION PROJECTS FOR SCOTTISH PUBLIC SECTOR BODIES

Some key points established from the analysis of aspects of the annual Climate Change mandatory reports for public sector bodies, encompassing the Scottish public sector and participating organisations, as defined in Chapter 1, for reporting periods 2015/16 and 2018/19 are presented in this section. LGAs are responsible for most total reported Scottish public sector emissions (by sector group), with an average of almost 50% of reported emissions between 2015/16 and 2018/19 (SSN, 2019; 2020). Together, LGAs and Educational Institutions are responsible for 63% of reported emissions. Energy use in buildings by way of electricity and gas consumption on average represents 70% of total reported Scottish public sector emissions between 2015/16 and 2018/19. Similarly, the combination of emissions resulting from electricity and gas use on average represents 69% of total reported participating organisations emissions between 2015/16 and 2018/19.

There is a clear indication of the reduction in total reported GHG emissions across Scottish public sector bodies with a 23% reduction in emissions between 2015/16 and 2018/19, corroborated also by a reduction in reported GHG emissions by participating organisations of 15% between 2015/16 and 2018/19. This mirrors the general GHG emission reduction trend for Scotland with source emissions reducing by 44.4% between 2016 and 2019 (Scottish Government, 2022). The reduction is due to the decarbonisation of the electricity grid and a reduction in electricity consumption. UK electricity consumption has reduced in recent years because of, energy efficiency regulations and products, decrease in industrial activities and increase in environmentally conscious consumers in the last decade (Evans, 2019). Great Britain's total electricity consumption in 2019 decreased by 1.5% compared to 2018, with Scotland having one of the highest decreases by region of 2.2% (BEIS, 2020). LGAs similarly showed reductions in electricity consumption over the same period, with changes often influenced by limited numbers of electricity meters in LGAs with large industrial sites (BEIS, 2020).

However, despite these reductions in reported emissions by public sector bodies to the Scottish Government through the SSN, there is an increase in the annual composition of emissions associated with FF energy sources reported suggesting an increased reliance

of FFs. Reported emissions associated with FF energy sources represent on average 45% of reported emissions by Scottish public sector bodies between 2015/16 and 2018/19, an increase in percentage composition of 24% over this period (41% FF composition in 15/16 and 51% FF composition in 18/19). The increasing trend in reported emissions associated with FF energy sources is evident in the analysis of the mandatory reports of participating organisations, with an average 51% of reported emissions resulting from FFs between 2015/16 and 2018/19, a significant increasing in composition of 61% over this period. This significant increase is attributed to the increase in reporting of Scope 3 travel and transport emissions. However, whilst the debate on the possibilities for reducing travel related emissions are likely to continue in the post COVID-19 world as organisations and businesses for example HEIs, consider different forms of online delivery of services and provisions, factors such as the CF of online delivery of services and provisions, and the implications of transfer of some associated emissions to service users. Emissions associated with heating, natural gas and other heating fuels like gas oil, kerosene, and fuel oil, represent the most of reported emissions associated with FFs with an average of 33% of total reported Scottish public sector emissions between 2015/16 and 2018/19 (73% of FF emissions) and an average 33% of total reported participating organisations emissions between 2015/16 and 2018/19 (64% of FF emissions). Whilst reported emissions associated with FFs have likewise decreased, they have only decreased by 5% between 2015/16 and 2018/19, compared to the 23% in overall reported emissions over the same period. This means that overall reported emission has decreased much faster than the emissions associated with FFs over the specified period and likely to be a contributing factor to the increased composition of FFs.

The implementation of emission reduction projects as reported across the Scottish public sector yielded average annual emissions savings of 89,873 tCO_{2e} for Scottish public sector bodies between reporting periods 2015/16 and 2018/19, and 27,374 tCO_{2e} for participating organisations over the same reporting period. However, these savings represent just 3% and 5% respectively of the average total reported emissions between the corresponding reporting periods. Most reported savings from emission reduction projects are associated with electricity (average 51% from Scottish public sector bodies 15/16 to 18/19, and 76% from participating organisations 15/16 to 18/19) followed by waste (average 21% from Scottish public sector bodies 15/16 to 18/19, and 11% from

participating organisations 15/16 to 18/19). Whilst it is difficult to ascertain the reason(s) for some of the differences in average percentages of reported emissions savings through projects between participating organisations (for which sector actors were interviewed) and the wider public sector (based on the SSN analysis reports), it may be reasonable to assume that these differences are the result of the number of participating organisations (11) versus the number of sector wide bodies for which average percentages were determined. For example, 51% vs 76% (a 25% difference); 21% vs 11% (a 10% difference); and 23% vs 13% (a 10% difference), see Table 5.3.

The combination of savings from projects associated with natural gas, other heating fuels, business travel and fleet transport (FF sources) average 23% from Scottish public sector bodies 15/16 to 18/19, and 13% from participating organisations 15/16 to 18/19. Renewable energy generation is also reported with an average of 95 GWh of electricity and 176 GWh of heat for Scottish public sector bodies 15/16 to 18/19, whilst an average 17 GWh of electricity and 9 GWh of heat for participating organisations 15/16 to 18/19. Solar panels and biomass are the most common renewable energy sources used across Scottish public sector bodies including participating organisations. Despite these efforts in reducing emissions through emission reduction projects and renewable energy installations for energy generation, relative to overall sector emissions a lot more work is required.

5.10 CONCLUSION

Public sector bodies in Scotland as listed in Schedule 1 of The Climate Change (Duties of Public Bodies: Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Order 2015 (as amended) are required to report on their emissions in relation to climate change, including setting targets for reducing emissions; most sector bodies set overall emission reduction targets, with targets for reducing energy use in buildings also being popular, whilst targets for reducing fleet transport emissions were the least set. In line with the general trend of Scottish emission reductions as reported for the whole of Scotland, the review of two main sets of documents reveals an overall reduction in corporate emissions, largely due to the decarbonising electricity grid and to a lesser extent reduced electricity consumption which fell by 4.4%.

The combination of LGAs and educational institutions are responsible for most of the emissions (63%) reported to the Scottish Government through the SSN, whilst combined emissions from electricity and gas represent a significant share of emissions (70% sector wide and 69% for participating organisations). Scottish public sector bodies reported savings of 3 to 5% of their emissions from emission reduction projects. As with their contribution to emissions, LGAs and educational institutions were responsible for 72% of overall savings resulting from emission reduction projects. Emissions savings from projects associated with electricity represent most savings, 51% of savings sector wide and 76% of savings for participating organisations; those associated with FFs (heating and transportation) represented 23% of savings sector wide and 13% for participating organisations. Solar panels for electricity generation and biomass boilers for heat generation were the most reported renewable energy technology.

Despite the actions and efforts to reduce emissions, and actual reductions in emissions by the sector between 2016 and 2019, reliance on FF energy sources for heating and transportation has increased over the same period. This is evident in the increase in annual composition of emissions attributed to FFs between reporting periods 2015/16 and 2018. This is the case for both sector wide emissions (45% average annual composition) and participating organisations (51% average annual consumption) and highlights the sectors reliance on FFs. Through a semi structured interview, the next chapter collates primary data from the interview responses to assess the views and opinions of sector professionals on the reliance of FFs within their organisations and how this reliance might be reduced.

CHAPTER 6:

INTERVIEW DATA AND ANALYSIS

6.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter contributes to the framework development for Scotland's public sector bodies on FF use and fulfils the objective of conducting semi-structured interviews with sector actors or professionals. Sector actors are well placed to provide insights to the issues associated with the consumption of FFs in the sector, drawn from their individual working experiences and knowledge within their organisations, and thus provides valuable insight into understanding the research topic. Whilst transportation activities rely heavily on FF energy sources recent progress in decarbonising national electricity if sustained and improved will ensure electricity supply remains much less dependent on FFs. The prospect of a fully decarbonised electricity grid in the immediate future is conceivable but we must not ignore natural gas, a FF heavily relied on to meet national heating demands. There is clearly a potential for the decarbonisation of the national grid however, at present FFs remain dominant fuel sources. Semi-structured interviews with Scottish public sector actors provided the opportunity to explore the implications of these issues of FF reliance in the context of their affiliated organisations.

6.2 SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW

All interviews conducted took place at each participant place of work as set out in the research ethics approval and deemed the best approach to engage and increase identified sector actors' participation. A total of eighteen interviews were carried out across eleven organisations which comprise six HEIs and five LGAs between July 2017 and June 2019. Two interviews were carried per organisation for seven organisations, and one interview each for another four organisations, each interview having an average duration of an hour. At the beginning of the interview, participants were given:

- An explanation of the project
- An update on the project progress
- A consent form to sign (see Appendix 14 for unsigned version)

The interviews were recorded using a digital recorder and stored securely which only the author of this study had access to. In addition to the audio recording, some handwritten notes were taken, the combination of which enabled the compilation of a full record for each interview. Subsequently, the recordings were transcribed. To ensure anonymity, participants and their organisations were given a unique code.

The job titles of all interview participants are detailed in Table 6.1 and cover environmental and sustainability remits (50% of interviewees), carbon management remits (28% of interviewees), and energy management remits (22% of interviewees) across LGAs and HEIs in the Scottish public sector.

Table 6.1: Interview Participants Job Remits and Titles (LGAs and HEIs)

Job Remits	LGA or HEI
Environmental and sustainability remits	
Environmental and Sustainability Manager	LGA
Sustainability Officer	HEI
Senior Sustainability Development Officer	HEI
Sustainability and Environment Officer	HEI
Environment Manager	HEI
Assistant Director Sustainability	HEI
Sustainability Project Coordinator	HEI
Environmental Advisor	HEI
Environmental Resource Manager	HEI
Energy management remits	
Energy Team Manager	LGA
Energy Officer	LGA
Energy Management Officer	LGA
Energy Manager	HEI
Carbon management remits	
Carbon Management Principal Officer	LGA
Carbon Reduction Officer	LGA
Housing Manager	LGA
Carbon Reduction Coordinator	HEI
Climate Policy Officer	HEI

6.3 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

6.3.1 THEME 1: EVIDENCE OF ONGOING RELIANCE ON FFs

The issues associated with FF use continue to be a global growing concern, with the burning of FFs as the largest known contributor of GHG emissions to the atmosphere (Soeder, 2021), and the apparent continued global reliance on FF energy sources as suggested by recent reports for example, BP (2020; 2023) and Tiseo (2022a; b).

Organisations consume FFs directly or indirectly in their day-to-day activities, however, often face the dichotomy between maintaining organisational standards and ethos and reducing organisational emissions.

This main theme has two sub-themes namely: ‘Energy use in buildings’ and ‘Fuel for transportation’; the use of FF energy sources in buildings for space heating, and electricity, and its persistent reliance for transportation, evidence the sectors reliance on FFs (Mehta and Wiesehan, 2013; Pietzcker *et al.*, 2014; Bompard, *et al.*, 2020). Table 6.2 shows the development of this key theme and sub-themes.

Table 6.2: Theme 1 - developed key theme and sub-themes

Initial sub-theme	Final sub-theme	Key theme
Government intervention through reduction targets	Energy use in buildings	Evidence of ongoing reliance on FFs
Continued reliance on FFs since industrial revolution		
Transport emission reduction is a key challenge	Fuel for transportation	
Renewable energy like biomass relies on FFs		

6.3.1.1 Energy use in buildings

Historically FFs have been used for heating and powering buildings and contributes its share to emissions from public sector bodies (see Figure 5.4). Interview responses suggest that the Scottish public sector is currently heavily reliant on FFs, largely by way of gas primarily for heating, electricity primarily for powering buildings and equipment, and fuel for travel and transportation, contributing significantly to overall carbon emissions and to the wider climate change. This is in line with recent statistical reports which highlight emissions from electricity, heating and transportation as significant contributors to global CO₂ emissions (Tiseo, 2022a). One LGA interviewee stated that,

“we are extensively reliant on FFs” and “majority of emissions come from FF sources”; whilst another stated that *“The reality is we are still overwhelmingly dependent on FFs”*. Reliance on FFs is echoed by all interviewees, confirming the increase in the percentage of Scottish public sector emissions associated with FFs (SSN, 2019; SSN, 2020). There is a corresponding cost to this reliance for these organisations; interview responses suggest huge annual utility bills for participating organisations ranging from £2.5 million to £33 million per annum, with LGAs being at the top end of the range. For example, one university interviewee stated *“...our budget is £7m for energy per annum”* whilst a LGA respondent stated *“...as a Local Authority we spend low 30 million (£), £32/33 million a year on gas, electricity, and water, that’s a chunk of money and that’s an ever-increasing chunk of money”*.

Energy use in buildings is one of the biggest impacts in relation to FF use in the Scottish public sector and most organisations depend on energy supplied from the National Grid for electricity and heating (gas). The make-up of grid energy fluctuates, particularly for electricity, and although Scotland’s electricity generation is made up mostly of renewable energy sources, FFs may still contribute to the fuel mix in Scotland whilst ultimately being supplied through the UK grid: the electricity generation fuel for Scotland in 2019 was made up of approximately 61% renewables, 25% nuclear, 13% FFs, and 1% other. Whereas by contrast it is made up 32% renewables, 17% nuclear and 49% FFs for the same period in England and Wales (Scottish Energy Statistics Hub 2021a).

The debate on Devolved powers enabling dedicated Scottish emission factors to reflect Scotland’s progress in renewable energy technologies came up in 50% of the interviews. Whilst the potential of having Scottish-only emission factors appears appealing in reducing its emissions, and it could potentially breach the two-year time lag in publishing national and local annual emission estimates (DECC, 2021) for example the ‘Scottish Greenhouse Gas Emissions, 1990-2019’ published in June 2021 (Scottish Government, 2021a); its fruition is debateable and not imminent. This will also require a separate energy grid infrastructure to the UK and will likely mean the inability to benchmark with peer cities nationally and internationally. One LGA interviewee stated that *“I mean we do use UK conversion factors and I think there is a good reason for that in that we also want to be able to benchmark ourselves [sic]*

against peer cities... the reality is we use a form of monitoring that is part of a UK wide network that also reports into Europe and can be compared with other cities throughout the EU at least for the time being”.

Accurately measuring the amount of FFs consumed by public sector bodies then becomes difficult. With grid electricity increasingly becoming decarbonised because of renewable and low-carbon energy sources reflected in lower electricity emission factors, and for the purpose of this thesis, electricity is excluded from contributing to FF emissions.

6.3.1.2 Fuel for transportation

Travel and transportation emissions is second to energy use in buildings in terms of reliance on FFs and is challenging in relation to reducing associated emissions. This is because emissions associated with components of travel and transport for example business travel, staff and student commute/air travel, and organisation business as usual travel, can be problematic to collate however, are significant when grouped together. The interview responses suggest measuring the full scope of travel emissions is problematic, for example two organisations exclude commuter travel from their footprint calculation, whilst one encountered increased emissions due to better reporting on travel emissions and the lack of strict policies on use of private travel and single travel.

Transportation relies heavily on FFs for example petrol, diesel, jet fuel and LPG, for road and air travel and is likely to be the case for some time yet particularly when considering air travel is a fundamental part of how many organisations operate; one LGA interviewee described transportation as a “*Black Art*”. However, the COVID-19 pandemic forced organisations to reconsider how they delivered their services, resulting in LGAs actively encouraging staff to work remotely were possible in line with national protocols on COVID-19. HEIs similarly transitioned to online delivery of education provisions (Filimonau *et al*, 2021), and whilst this presents the potential opportunity for HEIs to reduce emissions associated with business travel, there are the issues of education inequalities (Tasci, 2021) and the carbon implications of working and studying from home (Filimonau *et al*, 2021).

A particularly interesting point raised by one interviewee within the HE sector is the reduction in funding for domestic students. This interviewee states “...with funding reducing for domestic students there is more of a focus on encouraging international students to the university”. Nevertheless, this is well-established in literature alongside the dependency on international student tuition fees as a financial resource (Lomer, 2018; Yu and Moskal, 2019; Scott and Mhunpiew, 2021). This means HEIs actively seek international students resulting in higher emissions from international student travel, marketing, and other forms of engagement in meeting their globalisation agenda. It also highlights the difficult choices faced by organisations in upholding their standards and reputation versus environmental sustainability actions to reduce emissions, particularly for HEIs.

Reducing reliance on FFs is clearly challenging however, non-negotiable (Ebhotu and Jen, 2019). One university interviewee stated that “*There will always be reliance on FFs*” and another (LGA interviewee), “*It is unrealistic to eliminate FFs at the moment*”. Both suggestions tie in with responses from the remainder interviewees alluding to the fact that we are stuck with FFs, and it is very difficult to eliminate FFs. For example, six interviewees questioned the efficiency of biomass indicating that it still relies in some ways on FFs through transportation of wood stock and the use of gas boilers as back up (for high heating demand periods and during boiler repair or service) as examples and gives off CO₂.

Scottish public sector bodies are making efforts to reduce their reliance on FFs and ultimately their carbon emissions; the consensus is that although effort is evident within the bounds of what is realistically achievable, nothing at this stage is enough and a lot more is required.

6.3.2 THEME 2: EFFORTS TO REDUCE FF USE

The Climate Change (Scotland) Act 2009 (amended by the Climate Change (Emissions Reduction Targets) (Scotland) Act 2019) commits the Scottish government to reducing its GHG emissions to net-zero GHG emissions by 2045. Reducing the use of FFs poses a significant challenge within the Scottish public sector, not least, because of how much it is currently reliant on FFs. FFs are the major source of energy use in buildings and transportation in the Scottish public sector, and its composition of reported sector

emissions increased between 2015 and 2019 (see Figure 5.3). Table 6.3 shows the development of this key theme and sub-themes.

Table 6.3: Theme 2 - developed key theme and sub-themes

Initial sub-theme	Final sub-theme	Key theme
Organisational drive to reduce emissions	Government and organisational initiatives	Efforts to reduce FF use
Government initiatives		
EV uptake	Uptake of renewable and low carbon energy	
Renewables installations		

6.3.2.1 Government and organisational initiatives

There is consensus from interviewees that the CRC Energy Efficiency Scheme, a UK-wide policy that was mandatory, incentivised the public sector in Scotland to reduce carbon emissions however this scheme has now ended. New regulation, the SECR which came into force in April 2019 builds on the CRC however does not cover public sector bodies (Carbon Trust, 2019). The CCC 2018 Progress Report to the Scottish Parliament identified two areas which required urgent decarbonisation efforts: (i) transport, the highest-emitting sector and (ii) buildings which are a significantly challenging part of realising net-zero emissions, particularly with regards decarbonising heating systems (CCC, 2019b).

Interview responses highlight some initiatives led by the Scottish Government to reduce GHG emissions including setting reduction targets to net-zero emissions by 2045, efforts to decarbonise the grid with cleaner electricity and reduce reliance on gas, strategy on EVs, and ban on waste to landfill expected to yield significant carbon savings. The Scottish Government has a Climate Challenge Fund available to community-led organisations and funds the Scottish Energy Officers Network, a platform for LGA energy officers to discuss a range of issues relevant to reducing GHG emissions.

Other government funds highlighted by interviewees include Salix Fund, UK Green Investment Bank Loan, Central Energy Efficiency Fund, Geothermal Challenge Fund, Community Links Fund, Scottish Funding Council Loan and Transport Scotland Funding. The government is looking at decarbonising heat and energy efficiency

programmes at local level through Local Heat & Energy Efficiency Strategy (LHEES) and Regulation of District Heating, whilst also taking a range of other policy measures for example, a framework agreement for non-domestic energy efficiency in the Scottish public sector, plans to ensure new buildings do not use gas heating by 2025, plans to phase out the requirement for petrol and diesel cars and vans, and support for CCS. The promising potential of CCS technology in contributing to meeting climate change targets and a low-carbon future is well reported in literature however, this potential has yet to be achieved for example, the EUs target of 20 operating CCS by 2019 was not achieved (Romasheva and Ilinova, 2019).

Whilst the notion of lack of organisational support in relation to sustainability commitments divides opinion across interviewees, and is itself not an initiative, it may impact on an organisation's sustainability aspirations and actions, in developing, proposing, and signing up to initiatives which address climate change, therefore worthy of note. 72% of interviewees suggested that there was a lack of senior management leadership and commitment to sustainability goals, for example one HE interviewee stated, "*there is a lack of senior management understanding the effects of FFs on the environment and organisation, understanding their CF and how their CF is calculated*". This compared to 28% who suggested an organisational drive for sustainability led by senior management for example one interviewee stated "*So I will say that we are probably doing better than other authorities because we do have buy in from senior management at director level and from the chief executive as well. So, I think we are in a very favourable position compared to other authorities*". These responses identify organisational drive in the form of strategies (sustainability, energy, low carbon strategies), plans (climate change and transformational change plans), and targets to reduce emissions through energy efficiency measures (BMS systems, upgraded boilers and smart meters) and investment in renewable technology, albeit largely subject to cost benefit analysis and independent verification post implementation by third party organisations that provide such services.

Reducing the need for staff travel (and student travel in the case of HEIs, representing 56% of interviewees) also featured overwhelmingly in all interviews undertaken, as a means of reducing organisational emissions and subsequently its footprint. An expression of this view resides in this statement "*The other big culprit is the travel with*

business related travel and the staff and student commuting. So we are trying to get people out of aeroplanes, when it comes to business travel". Reducing travel emissions is compounded by the overwhelming reliance on FFs for transport in motorised forms (Brand, *et al.*, 2021) and to transition to zero or low emitting travel requires the appropriate infrastructure (Logan, *et al.*, 2020). Examples of suggestions by interviewees to achieve staff and student travel reductions through a range of means include encouraging active travel, use of video conferencing for lectures and meetings, car share policies, provision of EV pool vehicles, and reducing parking spaces.

Whilst 75% of LGA interviewees suggest a focus shift from financial implications to reducing emissions from individual sources, 60% of university interviewees suggest the need to investigate private sector funding and partnership. Staff and community education, and or engagement efforts, were common to all responses particularly around sustainable behavioural change. Examples of behavioural change approaches highlighted by interviewees include raising awareness on energy consumption and emission reduction through infographics; involving building users in emission reduction at work and at home; using sustainability initiatives like upskilling, reuse, repair, tool hire scheme, free shop to bring communities together; partnership working with local active travel organisations to encourage walking and cycling; provision of organisation sustainability funds to engage staff; and a call for embedding behavioural change within recruitment processes. Behavioural change outcomes can be achieved through training and education in issues such as relate to climate change (Reimers, 2021), with 70% of university interviewees suggesting that HEIs have a huge role to play as education providers in improving carbon literacy and engagement within the future workplace, by engaging in partnerships for sustainable development (Ryan and Hauser, 2020) as demonstrated by Findler *et al* (2019).

6.3.2.2 Renewable energy and low carbon emission technology uptake

Consideration for, and the uptake or installation of a range of renewable energy and low carbon emitting technologies is common to all responses. EV uptake and use of efficient vehicles such as dual fuel vehicles was the most prominent of responses in terms of reducing emissions, featuring in 80% of interviews, with suggestions of increase of organisational electric fleet vehicles and charging points in a few years. 11% of interviewees suggest that dual fuel vehicles are reasonable and practical and therefore

should be an option when upgrading organisational fleet vehicles, this LGA interviewee stated, *“There may be internal politics involved, there may be practicalities involved, although there is not a reason for the fleet not to be systematically switched over to dual fuel, at the very least”*. Also highlighted from the responses is the opinion that EV fleet may initially increase travel emissions because of their manufacture, purchase and charging requirements, but in the long term would reduce overall staff mileage. However, whilst an increase in electricity consumption is probable, if it is sourced from greener electricity, it is better than using FF sources of energy like petrol or diesel.

District heating options including in conjunction with CHP systems, as a means of decarbonising energy at local level is also prominent in 78% of responses and in line with the Scottish Government LHEES consultation for LGAs; however, two LGA interviewees suggest that LHEES does not lead to viable projects, with one confirming trials of district heating projects did not proceed due to cost benefit analysis. One LGA interviewee stated *“LHEES drives us to look at drawing circles around areas based on heat density. But that does not equate to projects or viable projects... we have to look at identified projects which are not necessarily within or without those designated areas. We have looked at in detail three projects, district heating projects for cost benefit analysis and each of them have failed”*. About 50% of interviewees suggested they have already invested in gas heating networks with one university respondent highlighting they invested over a twenty-year period and subsequently realised they laid pipes next to existing ones placed by the LGA. This highlights the need for and importance of collaborative work between organisations, in this case between a university and an LGA. Biomass installations are also popular but come with concerns regarding its efficiency in relation to relying on FFs in some shape or another (see section 6.3.1.2).

Other popular renewable energy and low carbon technology options highlighted in the interview responses include photovoltaics and wind turbine installations. Most interviewees suggested they are considering looking into the possibilities of having at least one of the following renewable energy and low carbon technologies, with only 22% already having at least one: air source heat pumps, water source heat pumps, ground source heat pumps, battery storage, solar to run hydrogen cells, and heating from sewerage.

What is clear from the interview responses is the level of awareness of a range of low-carbon and renewable energy technologies amongst participating sector actors. At the same time, it highlights the intricacies of reducing carbon emissions and indeed achieving net-zero emissions at all levels, inevitably presenting with barriers requiring significant collaborative steps and funding by governments, businesses, organisations, educational institutions, and other stakeholders.

Raybould, *et al.* (2020) investigated the UK Government's commitments to renewable energy and GHG reduction and concluded that its policies and legislation are significant in renewable energy technology investment and uptake through collaboration, whilst also having a positive effect on emissions and the costs of energy. However, despite these efforts and those of the Scottish Government, organisational drive and uptake of renewable energy technologies, the transition to cleaner and renewable energy comes with its challenges (Painuly, 2001; Foxon *et al.*, 2005; Yaqoot, Diwan and Kandpal, 2016) and there is still a requirement for increased efforts to reduce GHG emissions and reliance on FFs to be fast tracked for the ambitious Scottish Government target of net-zero emissions by 2045 to be achieved.

6.3.3 THEME 3: BARRIERS TO MOVING AWAY FROM FFs

Moving away from FF energy sources relies on several factors including the availability of alternative energy from renewable sources. The research and development of renewable energy technologies is continually advancing however, in 2018, renewable power accounted for 4.5% of global primary energy consumption increasing to 7.5% in 2022 (excluding hydroelectricity), whilst FF sources remained the global dominant fuel (BP, 2019; 2020; 2023). The dominance of FF sources in energy consumption across Scottish public sector bodies is also evidenced in other aspects of this research, for example, see Sections 4.7; 5.3 and 5.6.

Despite the advances in renewable energy technologies, the global share of renewable energy in the total energy consumption remains very low and this is worrying. In Scotland however, renewable sources accounted for 20.9% of total energy consumption in 2018 increasing to 24% in 2019 (Scottish Energy Statistics Hub, 2021b), and there is a target to achieve 50% by 2030 (Scottish Government, 2021b). Table 6.4 shows the development of this key theme and sub-themes.

Table 6.4: Theme 3 - developed key theme and sub-themes

Initial sub-theme	Final sub-theme	Key theme
Cheaper to use FFs	Practicalities and cost implications	Barriers to moving away from FFs
Renewable energy not cost efficient		
Available funding subject to cost benefit analysis of reduction measures	Lack of funding and support.	
Lack of government support and funding		
Decarbonising grid is challenging	Lack of an alternative renewable energy source to replace FFs	
EV has limitations		
Limited district heating systems which itself cannot achieve reduction targets		

6.3.3.1 Lack of funding and support

There is overwhelming consensus from interviewees alluding to the lack of grant funding, finances, budgets, government support and organisational leadership support as the main barriers to moving away from reliance on FF energy sources. These are by no means the only barriers, but finance and support in whatever forms they manifest from national down to organisational levels complement each other as such. Through adequate finance, funding, and government support other barriers for example as relate to the role of renewable and energy efficiency installations, trained personnel capacity for renewable installations, including in terms of infrastructure barriers which is highlighted under the sub-theme ‘practicalities and cost implications, stand a better chance of being overcome. In financial terms what needs to be done is different from what can be done; in summary public sector bodies are under pressure to deliver services and in some cases make profit, leading to a mismatch between aspiration and action, often referred to as ‘Hypocrisy’ (Christensen, Morsing and Thyssen, 2020). According to 61% of interviewees the Scottish public sector is facing financial challenges in line with the government’s austerity measures and is under increasing pressures to identify opportunities for financial savings, meaning that public spending in certain quarters suffer a great deal and lead to radical changes in government policies and schemes, for example in relation to renewable energy.

These financial challenges continue to be evident amidst increasing demand for services and come with real-life implications for people (Audit Scotland, 2022), adding more pressures to the sector and making it more risk averse. This also makes it increasingly difficult for partnership working within the public sector, hence the reason for calls by 78% of interviewees for more assistance, support, funding measures and a big step change from the Scottish Government, as well as the implementation of renewable urban carbon projects. One university interviewee stated that “*we need Scottish Government funding in the form of grants (rather than loans) could go a long way to shifting priorities so that ultimately sustainability is embedded in the organisation*”. These financial constraints filter through to Scottish public sector bodies where the lack of finances, funding, budgets, and capital funding to implement and invest in emission reduction technologies is a major barrier as alluded to by 78% of interviewees. One university interviewee stated that “*...the university is not without funds but as with all universities has seen funding cuts but is without key leaders at the top who would champion this embedding at the moment*”. Lack of leadership is often identified as a barrier to environmental sustainability within organisations (for examples, Waas, *et al.*, 2012; Blanco-Portela, *et al.*, 2018), likewise the importance of leadership (Woo and Kang, 2020; Al Khajeh, 2018).

Self-funding of emission reduction technologies by organisations is likely impossible without external funding and where funding is available (internal or external) it is subject to cost benefit analysis which must stack up financially. This brings about risk adversity amongst organisations, particularly in terms of lengthy loan payback periods and requirements for huge upfront investments. In instances where grants are available, for example, research grants, one of the university interviewees suggested that no sustainability criteria apply to the grants, rather there appears to be a stipulation of travel and face to face meetings. This university interviewee stated that “*...research grants sort of stipulate travel and collaboration and meetings etc, so how do you get round that? That is a huge ask, unless you change research grants to have a sustainability element, you are kind of stuck doing what you know you are doing... In terms of travel emissions, this appears a more difficult issue to address on our own (solely internally) due to stipulations in research grants that fund research. We would need to be able to influence grants in order to influence the ways in which researchers collaborate and disseminate their research*”. Whilst this may have been the perception

of this interviewee at the time of interview, it may differ today considering the impacts of COVID-19, and that several research grants bodies currently appear to encourage environmentally friendly travel options based on value for money. For example, train travel by standard class as opposed to first class, and economy class for flights rather than business class (Medical Research Council, 2021; Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC), 2021; Natural Environment Research Council (NERC), 2021).

Some of these bodies for example NERC and ESRC encourage low-carbon approaches to collaboration that is consistent with the Research Organisation policy acknowledging the potential long-term benefit of using videoconferencing for attendance at meetings rather than travel for face-to-face meetings (NERC, 2021; ESRC, 2021). With this potential shift from the perceived travel stipulations for research grants to an acknowledgement by research grant bodies for low-carbon collaborations, the impact of economic recovery from COVID-19 pandemic on funding for research grants is not known. However, additional funding may be required for research studies which have stopped participant enrolment and primary data collection (Marsden, 2020), a dichotomy with issues relating to loss of income for learned societies and job security (Beech and Anseel, 2020) for example, which may also be prominent issues post COVID-19 pandemic affecting, public spending.

75% of LGA interviewees suggested a degree of focus shift from overall budgets to focus on energy savings albeit at its early stages, whilst 11% of university interviewees suggest that the education sector is transforming into a business thereby shifting focus away from sustainability issues. Whilst not strictly true in that most universities are registered as charities (Synge, 2021), the suggestion that they are turning into a business is one that is understandable when considering institution income and expenditure (profits) reported by HESA (2022). Growth in competitive revenue of many universities, a result of the removal of student recruitment limits means universities seek principal sources of funding from tuition fees and other means of raising funds (Corver, 2019; Swain, 2016), creating a business-like outlook. This may also highlight the suggestion by some interviewees of the lack of strategic leadership by senior management and commitment to sustainability goals and carbon reduction. A study by Leal Filho (2020) revealed that sustainability leadership in HEIs is mainly hindered by the lack of funding and lack of support from their administrations. Furthermore,

turnover in management does not help the situation, for example change on national and local governments every four years, and continuous change in structure and staff within HEIs as highlighted by 33% of interviewees. One university interviewee's statement supports this opinion *"So you have a turnover of VPs or like our director of finance who was amazingly supportive, he's gone, he's retired. We have a new person who is more conservative. So, changes in upper-level management are an issue, if you don't have that continuity, you know you finally gain their trust and then they are gone and you have to start all over again trying to convince someone else, so that one issue"*.

One interviewee suggests that mismanagement of financial resources exist within the Scottish public sector and investment into renewable technologies is not yet a strategic priority for many organisations by stating *"In universities and local authorities in Scotland there is a lot of mismanagement of money because of old bureaucratic ways. Education is making peoples salaries go up after certain grades not proportional to the rest of the population. There is a widening gap...but with the widening gap you don't see the people on the top are taking interest in sustainability and social agendas. If you are giving a lot of money to few people who are not really interested in putting environment first so we will end up with nothing"*. This is despite evidence of the success of implemented carbon reduction technologies as reported by the interviewees affiliated institution, including initiatives in reducing GHG emissions, but relates back to leadership, or lack of, and the need for executive champions within organisations. 11% of interviewees also hinted at secured funds being absorbed into the organisations pot of money. This presents limitations to sub organisations within a wider organisational context for example departments, sections or services and raises the question around devolved responsibilities and the decision-making capacities to enact change.

6.3.3.2 Practicalities and cost implications

In addition to the financial constraints identified in the above sub-theme, practicalities and the costs involved with the move away from FF energy sources is a major barrier, as is investing in new technology, which has not been trialled and proven to be energy efficient, cost effective and subsequently widely accepted. There is also the perception by some interviewees (33%) that renewable energy initiatives are only fashionable and will be for a while only, adding to concerns about potential loss on investment; not to

mention the influence of political views at government and organisational levels, concerns about emissions associated with the manufacture and installation of renewable technologies. Some of these concerns have been addressed by developing renewable energy markets in recent times, and contrary to the perception that renewable energy initiatives are fashionable and as a matter of fact, renewable energy initiatives are well developed, see Ambrose (2019) for example.

There is a general perception by interviewees of possible government inconsistencies in that the UK Government heavily subsidises FFs due to vested interests by officials and politicians favouring existing FF contracts at the expense of support for renewables. Particularly frustrating to a few interviewees (22%) is the disappearance of certain energy efficient and renewable schemes with change in governments leading to business boom and burst in the renewables industry. This LGA interviewee stated that *“It’s also heavily subsidised, and that was my biggest criticism of the phase out of Feed-in Tariffs and RHI. It was the argument that the government shouldn’t be subsidising the industry. The FF industry is one of the most heavily subsidised, if not the most heavily subsidised industry in the world. So that’s fine, let’s not subsidise renewables but equally let’s not subsidise FFs. And if you really want a fair playing field, and this is where we get into my opinion against the councils, it’s because there is so much investment from organisations that politicians are heavily involved in one way or another”*.

FF energy technologies and markets are already established given their growing use since the 18th century, making it difficult for renewable energy technologies to compete financially, even with government incentives, and thereby presenting a major barrier to the move away from FFs. Existing energy infrastructure is not necessarily compatible with new emerging renewable technologies, for example, there is suggestion of a potential to connect gas mains to hydrogen but will require an upgrade to the grid, which is expensive. Other examples raised regarding existing energy infrastructure include the challenge in feeding directly from renewables; high cost of connecting wind turbines to grid; and difficulty in getting export grid connections for renewables. In the same vein, it is difficult to implement active travel initiatives in Scotland due to the lack of existing transport links (infrastructure) to support active travel, inclement weather conditions, and the ease of accessibility for staff to get to the organisations location(s) as alluded to by 72% of interviewees.

At organisational levels, retrofitting new technologies can be very costly, depending on a number of factors including: (i) building age which can affect its heating and cooling; (ii) building construction which can affect grid connection and outlay; (iii) building type, listed buildings posing more of a challenge, requiring planning permission; (iv) and building location which can lead to additional installation costs (drilling for ground source heat pump will be more expensive for buildings above mines). For example, all interviewees from city HEIs highlighted the challenge of installing wind, biomass, ground source heat pump and geothermal technologies within their estates one of which stated that *“this campus we are pretty reliant on FFs for that and unfortunately because of the type of Estate we have got it is very historic, we are very limited with planning. Other things such as PV, wind turbines, anything else that is renewable because they can’t put them outside our buildings, we are very limited”*. This is in line with other research that highlights the barriers to be overcome in making historic or heritage buildings more energy efficient, see for examples Fouseki and Cassar (2014) and Buda *et al.* (2021).

In the current austerity climate compounded by the necessity for a COVID-19 pandemic survival and recovery post pandemic, in which financial resilience will be key (Ahrens and Ferry, 2020), it is cheaper to use and rely on FFs for energy in comparison to cleaner or renewable energy. For example, historic low gas prices means that it is more convenient and economical for organisational assets to rely on FFs thereby hindering the potential switch to renewable energy. Although, the tide is quickly turning, and renewable energy is becoming cheaper than FFs in some respects (Ashworth, 2022). It has also historically been easier and cost effective to get around in a personal car particularly for those commuting long distances to their places of work, making it difficult for organisations to target reductions in travel emissions actively. 77% of interviewees suggest that the low cost of FFs means that organisations are likely to keep using FF energy sources from a financial point of view. Putting this into context, there was an overall decrease in UK average monthly gas prices over the duration of commencing and concluding all interviews; that is between July 2017 which was 36.21 British pence per therm, and June 2019 which was 27.96 British pence per therm (Sönnichsen, 2022). These sector actor views are likely to change now that energy prices have increased dramatically since the middle of 2021 with UK energy supply affected by the lack of gas storage capacity and the high reliance on gas for heating

amongst others (Sönnichsen, 2022). However, increasing the price of FFs and indeed the high cost of renewables has socio-economic impacts in relation to increased fuel poverty for people who cannot afford the higher taxes, and associated complications of fuel poverty. Lowes, *et al.* (2020) suggest that the cost of low carbon heating is expected to exceed that of FF energy sources.

The capital cost of renewable energy technology installations on the other hand is currently not cost effective for organisations in comparison to FFs according to 77% of interviewees. Low gas prices mean that district heating is currently not cost effective either. Similarly, a few interviewees (22%) suggest the reduction in RHI rates per kW of heat, reduce incentives for biomass installations. Since its inception, tariffs for RHI dropped steadily from 12.20p/kWh to 4.21p/kWh (domestic scheme) for biomass systems between 2015 and 2017 (Morgan *et al.*, 2020), and from 8.90p/kWh to 4.20p/kWh (non-domestic scheme) for biomass boilers between 2013 and 2015 (NAO, 2018). The payback period for photovoltaic installations, have increased and although solar panel prices have reduced, the government's reduction of feed-in tariffs for solar electricity means that it is still not cost effective.

6.3.3.3 Lack of an alternative renewable energy source to replace FFs

Unfortunately, there is not a single renewable energy source that is available and, in a position, to replace FF sources, in other words there is no one-size fits all renewable technology. However, whilst having a single source of reliable renewable energy to replace FF generated energy presents an ideal scenario, it should not be the aspiration but rather to find ways of reducing consumption and harnessing several renewable energy sources. The data presented in Table 6.5 represents the share of renewable energy sources in relation to the final total gross energy consumption in Scotland between 2015 and 2019 (Scottish Energy Statistics Hub, 2021b). It shows that the composition of energy consumption from renewable sources of energy increased by a change of 28% between the stated periods, however, indicates the necessity to speed up actions to achieve the target of 50% of energy generation from renewable energy sources in Scotland by 2030 (Scottish Government, 2021b).

Table 6.5: Percentage of Scotland’s Energy Consumption from Renewable Energy sources 2009 to 2019

Year	Total Renewable Energy (GW)	% of Total Energy Consumption from Renewables
2015	27,086	17.2%
2016	24,348	15.4%
2017	31,095	19.2%
2018	33,386	21.1%
2019	37,721	24.0%

Renewables are seen by 77% interviewees as intermittent and fluctuate seasonally depending on the renewable energy source. There is a range of renewable energy sources including solar, hydroelectricity, wind, geothermal, biomass etc, but the technologies for generating energy from these sources are still developing, however not without their individual issues. According to 33% of interviewees, the tide has turned on biomass installations with less RHI and declining installations bringing into question the potential loss of that funding and the lack of funding for potential replacements.

Biomass also raised concerns with respect to the moisture content of wood pellets, availability, and transportation of stock especially during winter season. Solar PV on the other hand although appears now to be at grid parity in terms of generation costs, the capital costs for installation and the payback are significant implications to be considered in the decision making of organisations as suggested by 44% of interviewees. Furthermore, the robustness of roofs to take on additional weight of PVs often is a concern from a structural design perspective. Even where the roof can accommodate the additional PV load, there is hardly enough roof space to install PVs which will meet the organisations utility consumption demand. One university respondent stated, *“If we wanted to install solar panel to provide us with the electricity that it takes to run the estate (pause), I think we had feasibilities done, someone looked at this for us about a year and a half ago and they reckon that we need to have about 86 football pitches worth of space covered in solar panels in order to provide us the electricity we need”*.

The negative public perception of wind turbines being huge, unattractive, and requiring great amount of space (alluded to in Yi and Kang (2020); Cranmer *et al.* (2020); Kealy

(2020)), and concerns of the effect of freezing events on water and ground source heat pumps (alluded to in Cardemil *et al.*, 2021; Zhang *et al.*, 2020); to mention a couple issues raised by interviewees regarding renewables.

All interviewees recognise the need for decarbonising the grid with renewable energy, however, agree that it is a challenging target to achieve and call for the government to do more in decarbonising the grid. One LGA interviewee suggests Scotland is decades behind the Scandinavia and needs to move away from relying on gas to reduce associated emissions, stating “...*at the moment Scotland is just not geared up to reduce our gas emissions by significant amounts, unless we have a severe step change. If you look at Scandinavia for example, they have significant resources put into district heating. I think in Denmark 96% of all heat is generated from district heating schemes, whereas over here we are decades behind*”. District heating systems feature prominently in Scandinavian countries representing 40 to 60% of the heat market share, providing 90% of heat to multi-family residential buildings in Sweden, meeting 46% of the heating demand of Denmark and has evolved to incorporate renewable heat sources (Arbeg, *et al.*, 2020; Manz, *et al.*, 2021; Mazhar, Liu and Shukla, 2018). Although district heating systems in Scotland are limited in comparison to the Scandinavia, with just 2% of the UK population connected to a district heating system as highlighted by Mazhar, Liu and Shukla (2020), and under 30,000 homes in 2018 connected to a district heating network in Scotland (Scottish Energy Statistics Hub, 2021c), installing district heating systems (networks) form part of Scotland’s strategy to achieve its climate change targets (Energy Saving Trust, 2019).

All interviewees alluded to the need for advancements in EV, EV infrastructure, and addressing the source of electricity for charging EVs if it is to be a substitute for diesel and petrol and contribute to the government’s plans for new vehicles to have zero emissions by 2040. This plan to phase out the manufacture of diesel and petrol run cars in the UK by 2040 was deemed “*completely unrealistic*” by one interviewee. Since these interviews, the UK government has confusingly shifted its position with respect to the target date and launched a consultation to bring forward the ban from 2040 to 2035 or earlier (Shale-Hester, 2022). This led to criticism of the government by The Society of Motor Manufacturers and Traders for having a date without a plan to fulfil such challenging ambitions (Hawes, 2020). The issue is exacerbated by current policy that

doesn't stack up and the cutting of EV subsidies nevertheless the ambition considered achievable (Bailey, 2022). Bailey (2022) highlights the need for approaches to be aligned to that of the EU to enable car makers sell EVs in the UK with EV sales in the likes of Norway averaging 50% of new car sales in recent months. Interviewees identified some limitation with EV largely around 'range anxiety' including the limitations in travel distance after a full charge; charging times particularly for long distances; need for a rapid charging system and for extensive installations of charging points. EVs have advanced in more recent times in their range capacity averaging 250 miles in comparison to older EV versions which average 60 miles per full charge, however most require a long time to achieve full charge and many owners do not have home charging infrastructure (Shahriar et al., 2020). The question of the source of electricity for charging EV came up at all interviews and the consensus is that potential exists for it to be sourced by 100% greener electricity and certainly better than the use of crude oil. At organisational levels there has been some EV uptake but not to levels deemed as success stories, as alluded to by all interviewees, who are looking to expand electrification of fleet vehicles.

With population growth in Scotland rising annually from 2001 to 2021 (an approximate 8% increment) according to statistics produced by Clark (2022), it is projected to continue to rise slightly to 2028 before falling by approximately 2% by 2045 (National Records of Scotland, 2022), the requirement to meet future energy demand with renewable energy as opposed to FFs is crucial in climate change terms. This puts some pressure on the renewable energy technology industry to invent technology that can meet the rising demand for energy, easily rolled out in mass and not limited in its functionality and adaptability to existing infrastructure. In general, interviewees suggest the industry must be set up in a way that enables the creation of new technology required to meet rising energy demands; for electricity, which is more advanced, and for heating which is less advanced. The availability of funding and investment in renewable energy technologies in the Scottish public sector needs to be secure and sustainable. According to a university interviewee, the Scottish public sector needs to embrace innovation in renewable energy technology and overcome its reluctance to take risks. More importantly, it must be flexible enough to find ways to adapt with the advancements in renewable energy technologies and harness the opportunities this

presents in order not to compromise its position of enabling and facilitating climate resilient societies for the coming generations.

6.3.4 THEME 4: CARBON REPORTING

The Scottish Government introduced a ‘climate change duties’ mandatory order in 2015 requiring reporting on carbon emissions (see Section 5.1) managed by SSN on behalf of the government². In the context of this study, whilst LGAs tend to have more robust and systematic CMPs by detailing carbon reduction targets and initiatives to achieve those targets, in comparison to HEIs; organisations report on different aspects of emission scopes making it difficult to compare like for like. For example, HEIs operate an academic year calendar from September of one year to August of the following year posing a problem in determining the appropriate emission factors to use, monitoring progress, and this has its impact on the overall CF, considering also changing conversion factors. Furthermore, the public sector climate change reporting requirements is for the period from April of one year to March of the following year making it even more difficult for HEIs and highlights the difficulties of estimating emissions particularly non-mandatory Scope 3 emissions. Table 6.6 shows the development of this key theme and sub-themes.

Table 6.6: Theme 4 - developed key theme and sub-themes

Initial sub-theme	Final sub-theme	Key theme
Carbon inventory	Difficulties in estimating Scope 3 emissions	Carbon reporting
Difficult to achieve staff mileage emissions reduction		
Conflicting carbon reporting requirements		
Data cleansing		

6.3.4.1 Difficulties in estimating Scope 3 emissions

The emission sources from which data used to calculate CFs are the same across the sector. They largely include electricity, gas, and water use in buildings; travel emissions from fleet, staff/student commute and business travel; and waste disposal. These emission sources closely mirror those reported in the case study undertaken in Chapter 4

² [The Climate Change \(Duties of Public Bodies: Reporting Requirements\) \(Scotland\) Order 2015](#) came into force in November 2015 and requires the 180 ‘large Public Bodies’ (i.e., those classified as Major Players) to report annually on compliance with their ‘Climate Change Duties’. (SSN, 2019).

and the corporate emissions reported by Scottish public sector bodies in Chapter 5. However, there are variations in the scopes reported on and the emission sources used to calculate each organisations footprint. For example, one organisation includes street lighting, whilst another excludes business travel for example, housing emissions for LGAs and supply chain emissions are reported by 89% interviewees as being excluded from the scope of reporting; whilst travel emissions is generally perceived as underreported by interviewees. For example, one university interviewee stated that *“the other thing we have discovered is that not all travel is booked through the travel agents, I think in some categories and up to 30% under reporting, so we are just trying to address that at the moment using last year’s data”*; whilst another university interviewee stated *“We report staff and student commuting to Scottish Government, but we do not include it as part of our target setting. We figure it’s kind of out of scope because we can’t totally control it”*. The perception of business travel being underreported may be supported by the lack of complete and comprehensive business travel data (Wynes, *et al.*, 2019; University of Toronto Committee on the Environment, Climate Change, and Sustainability, 2020) supplied through a travel management system in the estimation of business travel emissions in the case study (Chapter 4). Reporting of Scope 3 emissions like transport emissions is not mandatory for organisations and this contributes to the underreporting of emissions in this category and the lack of standard methodologies for capturing the scale of emissions.

Activity data for each of the emission sources undergoes data cleansing or verification, then multiplied by the corresponding emission conversion factors (updated annually) and summed up to get the CF as alluded to by all interviewees. The accuracy of the CFs comes into question; the inability to capture data for some emission sources, procurement being one example, with little or no guidance from the government for calculating and reporting on procurement emissions as suggested by 33% interviewees. This is consistent with the Carbon Trust (2018) method of CF calculation used in the case study in which the quality, completeness and reliability of data posed a challenge. Verification of CFs through qualified third-party organisations is encouraged but not mandatory and only one interviewee reported external verification of CF. There is a general perception by interviewees that carbon calculations require a dedicated person or team to champion and that lack of control over certain aspects of an organisation particularly within transportation hinder the ability to reduce emissions. For example,

70% of university interviewees associated luxurious business travel with university status in line with the study of Wynes, *et al.* (2019) which highlights in the abstract that senior academics were responsible for more travel emissions compared to early career academics.

It is clear from the interviews the difficulty faced by public sector bodies in accurately estimating emissions associated with procurement and travel (Scope 3 emissions); and subsequently in reducing these associated emissions and influencing staff/student behaviours. However, public sector corporate emissions associated with FFs increased between 2015 and 2019 due to the increase in reporting of Scope 3 travel and transport emissions as shown in Section 5.9. Interviewees report electricity and gas as representing most reported emissions, followed by travel and transport associated emissions, whilst waste replaces transport as a major emission source for two organisations. Example statements from interviewees include: *“Electricity and gas account for almost 50% of our emissions, followed by Scope 3 business travel. Key reasons are heating of buildings and the need to travel for research, it’s part of research culture to travel”* and *“The highest carbon emissions come from electricity and gas unsurprisingly, that’s for Scopes 1 and 2. Scope 3 will be international and long-haul flights”*. Electricity and gas particularly from energy use in buildings contribute significantly to public sector corporate emissions with an average 70% of reported corporate emissions as shown in Section 5.2 and represents 52% of emissions estimated in the case study (see Table 4.17). For those 11% who report procurement emissions there is a consensus that the emission factors associated with procurement have been unchanged for a few years and should financial spending constraints be removed, emissions are likely to increase due to increase in spending.

6.3.5 THEME 5: ACTIONS REQUIRED TO REDUCE RELIANCE ON FF

The actions required to reduce reliance on FFs must be targeted and by concerted effort of all appropriate parties. Some of these actions will encompass (i) leadership (ii) financial investments (iii) national policy (iv) infrastructure development (v) technological solutions (vi) carbon offsetting and (vii) behavioural change in reducing consumption regardless of energy source. With the recent emergence of climate emergencies being declared at local government (Gudde, *et al.*, 2021), national government, and global levels (for example Bristol City Council was the first UK

unitary Authority to declare Climate Emergency in November 2018 (Hoolohan, *et al.*, 2021); Scotland in April 2019 and the EU in November 2019 (Climate Emergency Declaration, 2019a; 2019b)), it is possible that this will serve as a catalyst to developing strategic action required to limit what is often dubbed climate catastrophe. Table 6.7 shows the development of this key theme and sub-themes.

Table 6.7: Theme 5 - developed key theme and sub-themes

Initial sub-theme	Final sub-theme	Key theme
Decarbonisation of energy sources	Radical zero-carbon revolution	Actions required to reduce reliance on FFs
Divestment		
Carbon offsetting	Reduced energy consumption and carbon offsets	
Implement energy efficiency measures		
Government investment in grid infrastructure	Financial instruments and governance	
Investment in EV infrastructure		
Governance		

6.3.5.1 Radical zero-carbon revolution

The UK's binding commitment to achieving net-zero emissions by 2050 (or earlier within Devolved Administrations), requires urgent rallying of forces like, and perhaps exceeding those that brought about the Industrial Revolution of the 18th and 19th Centuries, in order to transform into a radical zero-carbon and low carbon green economy. There are a range of renewable and low carbon energy sources which are in use however they need properly tested on a large scale, for example more large scale onshore/offshore wind and hydro technologies, wind turbines directly wired to mains feed and distributed to buildings; CHP fuelled by hydrogen, biomass or geothermal; solar PV arrays and thin plastic solar PV for building roofs; heat pumps (ground source and water source) and solar water heater collectors. 83% of interviewees suggest that to achieve net emissions a radical zero-carbon revolution is required. Interviewees suggest that what is required is a climate ready and resilient decentralised systems which are still connected to national infrastructure, repurposing existing systems for example CHP to run on hydrogen, and large-scale energy storage solutions for example battery for energy storage, renewables with storage for electricity, and wind turbines with battery storage. Example responses from interviewees include: *“I think we need to be doing as much as possible to invest and exploit renewable potential in Scotland. We need to be trying our hardest to develop large-scale energy storage solutions to deal with the*

problem that you have with intermittency with renewables” and “I think it’s that combination of energy efficiency and low carbon heating and that’s the real challenge for older building stock and in terms of where we traditionally get our heat from. That’s a huge infrastructure change potentially, to change the heating system “. A key element to eliminating reliance on FFs is decarbonising the electricity and gas grids and were possible generating electricity and heat at the same time which is more efficient than generating them individually.

Interviewees alluded to the requirement of a combination of infrastructure change in heat and power generation, and the upgrading of national infrastructure to take renewable energy, with 56% of interviewees suggesting the possibility of electrifying heating systems thereby increasing reliance on green electricity. Whilst the electricity grid continues to be decarbonised, action(s) need to be accelerated to ensure the electricity grid is fully decarbonised and the technology required to achieve this is likewise required. 83% interviewees highlight heat and transport as areas requiring attention with regards FF consumption and call for research into decarbonising heat which is largely gas and transportation. For example, one LGA interviewee stated that *“we really need to focus on things under our control so we can do better, so electrification of our vehicle fleet chief amongst that and obviously as I said as much as possible decarbonisation of heat”*, whilst another stated *“I think at this stage as a Council we need to accelerate a lot more investment in our property portfolio and transport fleet, to decarbonise the heat sources and obviously the motor force for our transport as well”*.

Popular options for decarbonising heat highlighted by interviewees include: the potential for using heat pumps to recover heat from sewerage; exploring heat from industry renewable energy sources; deep geothermal exploration; generating hydrogen using renewables off-peak; and potential for hydrogen to replace gas. Just under half of interviewees said they were aware of ongoing trials to blend hydrogen into gas at national level, however, highlight the requirement for the technology to transport hydrogen (Qadrdan *et al.*, 2020; Birkitt *et al.*, 2021). From the views and opinions of interviewees with regards to transportation and travel, electrification appears to be the only option being discussed across the public sector with calls for expeditious action in

improving EV infrastructure, normalising larger EVs like Heavy Goods Vehicles, Refuse Collection Vehicles, and research into electric run aeroplanes.

6.3.5.2 Reduced energy consumption and carbon offsets

Reducing energy consumption remains a key part of reducing emissions regardless of the energy source amongst other things like consumption costs for example. This could be challenging taking account of growing population and subsequently energy demand however, 77% of interviewees acknowledge reducing energy consumption should be the focus from national to local levels and individual efforts. The following quotes are examples of interview responses supporting reducing energy consumption:

- *“there is huge potential for savings or at least cost avoidance in utilities. I think that’s the way to pitch it going forward. So, utilities, reducing consumption for example, can make you far more financially resilient, but then you throw in the opportunity to generate revenue through renewables and sale of excesses”.*
- *“The main focus for emission reduction is reducing energy consumption and reducing fuel use form fleet that’s probably the two main areas of focus”.*
- *“In some respect, you get the behaviour stuff right, you get the energy efficiency stuff right, the last thing that you should be doing is investing hundreds of thousands of pounds in renewable energy source. You use your energy efficiently first of all, and the last thing you do is throw your money at renewables. So those are things that have much quicker paybacks”.*

Energy efficiency is one way of reducing consumption through the upgrade of systems to use less energy, like wise reducing fuel use for travel through electrification of transport and reducing the need for travel (through teleconferencing for example) to encourage less travel.

By consensus all interviewees highlight behavioural change at all levels as important in playing a role in reducing emissions through public awareness campaigns on energy use and active travel but call for the government to step up in EV infrastructure and in making public transportation easier. One university interviewee was keen to highlight the need for the smarter use of buildings for example more occupancy, more flexible working, and cohabitation of different services within buildings. Another LGA interviewee stated that *“So all those other three things, using buildings smarter,*

consuming less will mitigate the demand to breach the gap. So renewable technologies will get more efficient, the buildings will become more efficiently used and that will breach that gap". Behavioural change from individuals and wider society through mitigation actions like reducing energy consumption and travel (air and road), and adaptation measures like emergency and planned response to extreme weather events (Whitmarsh, Poortinga, and Capstick, 2021), is a vital part in addressing climate change. Behavioural change would not succeed in isolation and requires amongst others the availability of adequate infrastructure for example for active and public transportation, and the implementation of policies favourable to domestic uptake of renewable and low carbon technologies for heating, access to EVs and sustainable diets (Carmichael, 2019).

The idea of paying for carbon offsets emanated from the Kyoto Protocol's flexible mechanisms, whilst a parallel voluntary carbon offsets market has developed. Carbon offsets allow nations, organisations, and individuals to reduce carbon by compensating for excess emissions in one location through carbon reductions in another (Bumpus and Livermnan, 2008), and 33% of interviewees see this as having a role to play in achieving net-zero emission targets, examples quotes of which include the following:

- *"This is tricky, zero by 2040 target...that calculation...knowing that we can get there is not just based on operational changes, it was based on offsetting"*
- *"I have never been a fan of offsetting, but I do see in this case that there are benefits for Scotland and benefits for us in the short term, as a short-term measure"*.
- *"I think already the solutions are there. It won't be zero carbon, but it will be a lot lower carbon and I think as we move towards lower and lower carbon, whilst you might not get to zero, some thought for investment in other measures might allow us to get to carbon neutrality i.e., planting trees or whatever it might be, and I think therefore we will begin to move towards that"*.

Carbon offsetting provides a cheaper alternative for mitigating GHG emissions and climate change however, it is not a physical reduction in emissions. It is also not without its controversy, for example issues associated with commodifying carbon which is largely reliant on scientific and political input (Bumpus and Livermnan, 2008), and social justice implications (Kashwan, 2021). Furthermore, post conclusion of the

interviews, the UK Government in late 2019 pledged to plant 30000 hectares of new woodland by 2024 but reports suggest that this tree planting target will not be achieved (Confor, 2022). This casts significant doubt and questions perhaps the over anticipation of contribution that carbon offsetting to achieving net zero emissions by 2050 when tree planting targets are not achievable.

In addition to carbon offsetting, two organisations state that they also intend to achieve emission reduction targets through land acquisition, peatland, and woodland however these do not seem to form part of documented strategies for achieving emission reduction targets by the organisations. One respondent from an LGA suggests that cities, could require ample carbon reservoirs and planting of trees on derelict land to reduce emissions and meet both organisational emission reduction targets and those of the entire city. However, this position by the respondent conflicts with the Scottish Governments ambition of delivering 100,000 affordable homes by 2031/32 (Scottish Government, 2021c).

6.3.5.3 Financial instruments and governance

There appears to exist, a potential lack of government urgency in actions with the perception of consequences appearing to be further down the line. However, that should be the counter argument, protecting, and limiting the environmental impacts for future generations – ‘sustainability’. There is a requirement for the government and organisations to accelerate its commitment towards carbon neutrality, with calls for financial instruments and governance which is essentially politics and leadership alluded to by interviewees; resulting from increasing public demand for low carbon societies envisaged by 78% of interviewees to drive change for example a university interviewee stated that *“Now I think it’s a combination of you need to regulate force but also you need to encourage people. But there needs to be a demand from the public which I think we are only starting to see now. Governments aren’t going to want to enforce anyone to do things unless there was an outcry for it, and now there does seem to be more of an outcry for it”*.

Ronaghi, Reed and Saghaian (2020) examined the impact of economic factors and governance on GHG emission; they find that people participation in decision-making is vital to good governance which itself they conclude is the key factor to reducing GHG

emissions. All interviewees highlighted collaboration between the government, public organisations, and private organisations as being required, with a consensus of calls for government investment in grid infrastructure and transport infrastructure, including EV and active travel infrastructure. The need for nations to reduce GHG emissions can often be politically hindered for example the combination of different political party agendas and the change in power in government. Interviewees overwhelmingly raised the issue of FF divestment by organisations and the government, with 56% of interviewees suggesting their organisations are already divesting or planning to divest in the near future and 72% calling for government to remove FF subsidies and take to drastic measures to subsidise renewable energy technologies, perhaps through government legislation and incentives for businesses, examples quotes of which include the following:

- *“They can stop being hypocrites in pursuing FF friendly policies. Stop subsidising the FF industry, subsidise the renewable energy industry. Promote research into decarbonising transport, promote research to decarbonise heat. Stop outsourcing production to the developing world where the carbon intensity of the energy could be higher. Stop expanding airports, charge air travel, I mean it is endless, invest in public transport, invest in cycle lanes”*
- *“The fact the UK govt is still subsidising FF is ridiculous by the way, so that’s definitely still a barrier. I suppose it’s just the general culture change around it as well”*
- *“we’ve been realistic about what our capacity is, so obviously looking at other alternative options of either investing in greener technology, or divesting, or moving towards a carbon neutral state”*

One suggestion raised by 17% of interviewees is for bigger renewable energy commitments for new building developments in government building planning policies; for example, making electricity heating mandatory as the electricity grid becomes continuously decarbonised. Government leadership is vital in fostering research into, and uptake of renewable and low carbon energy technologies. A few interviewees (17%) suggest that feasibility studies for renewable technologies should take account of future impacts for example, the ability to change fuel sources in decentralised systems. Finally, and importantly, when the question of government funding arose it was clear

from all interviewees that the government needs to provide more grants which do not have to be repaid in comparison to government loans.

6.4 CONCLUSION

Through semi-structured interviews with sector actors within the Scottish Public Sector this chapter set out to assess their views and opinions on the implications of FF reliance in the context of their affiliated organisations and exploring with them how this can be addressed. Sector actor responses are analysed using thematic analysis to report patterns within the data set in detail (Braun and Clarke, 2006; 2012) thereby providing a detailed account of themes within the explicit meanings of the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Kiger and Varpio, 2020). The discussions surrounding these themes as generated from the analysis of interview responses is critically analysed using authoritative evidence from literature to support or counter sector actor views and opinions.

Five key themes as shown in Figure 6.1 below resulted from the thematic analysis of interview responses. With clear evidence of significant reliance on FF energy sources within affiliated organisations, it highlights the challenges that lie ahead in decarbonising the energy sector and achieving net-zero emissions. Whilst efforts are being made to reduce FF use and its reliance, this level of effort requires to be amplified and catalysed through a targeted concerted approach of key stakeholders (not limited to the public and private sectors, industry, investors, local and national governments). It also requires adequate financial instruments and governance to stand a chance of aligning with the aspiration of a zero-carbon energy revolution and overcoming the barriers to moving away from FFs. The difficulties of capturing Scope 3 emissions highlighted through the analysis is in line with studies highlighting difficulties in estimating Scope 3 emissions, for example, (Alvarez, Blanquer and Rubio, 2014).

Although the barriers to moving away from FF highlighted through this thematic analysis may already be well discussed in wider literature the results reaffirm these barriers within the specific context of these public sector bodies. More so in the case of this research it contributes to the framework development presented in the following chapter. The prominence of these barriers which are mainly hinged on the availability of finances highlights the necessity for accelerating efforts to address FF reliance. This will be particularly challenging with the added complications of the possibility of a new

era of austerity resulting from the necessity for the COVID-19 pandemic economic recovery and the conflict between Ukraine and Russia.

The following chapter brings together the research work by consolidating the research findings and presenting a framework for addressing the reduction in reliance of FFs in line with the research question, research aims, and research objectives.

Figure 6.1: Thematic map showing five key themes and corresponding sub-themes

CHAPTER 7:
FRAMEWORK DEVELOPMENT

7.1 INTRODUCTION

FFs (oil, coal, and natural gas) remain the principal source of energy consumption globally and despite Scotland virtually eliminating emissions associated with fossil-fired electricity generation two areas, transport (highest emitting sector) and buildings (heating) require urgent decarbonisation efforts (CCC, 2020). This translates to reducing reliance on FF energy sources such as petrol and diesel mostly for transportation and gas for meeting heating consumption demands in Scotland and Scottish public sector bodies. However, these are well-established FF markets with huge infrastructure, which makes FF a continued reliable energy source and requires significant advancement, capacity, and availability of renewable energy sources and technologies to change the narrative. Such challenges open the channel for exploring means by which FF reliance can be reduced for example by proposing a framework that can be used to reduce FF reliance.

The burning of FF is the largest known contributor to climate change Soeder (2021); whilst emissions associated with FF sources are often reported, individually, the collective reporting and monitoring of emissions from FF sources by organisations is lacking. The measure of emissions associated with the collective use of FF sources is required to monitor progress in reducing emissions associated with FF and invariably the reliance on FF.

This study set out to explore and develop an understanding of Scotland's public sector bodies reliance and attitude to FF energy sources, to aid planning, and decision making on FF issues and policies, within the sector. This chapter consolidates the findings of previous chapters to propose a novel co-created stakeholder framework that can be used by Scottish public sector bodies to address the reduction of FF reliance, as well as assist HE operational units improve their CF.

7.2 RESEARCH FINDINGS

Figure 7.1 highlights the main findings from the CF case study, document review, and interview analysis, in line with the research aims and objectives, to answer the research question.

Figure 7.1: Highlights of some findings from each aspect of the mixed method study research

7.3 DEVELOPING A FRAMEWORK TO REDUCE RELIANCE ON FF ENERGY SOURCES

There is a necessity to reduce FF reliance within public sector bodies as well as address the research gap in publications focused on reducing public sector FF emissions. To address this phenomenon of FF reliance it was critical to first establish the wider narrative of the sectors reliance on FF energy sources within the scope of the research. By engaging with this phenomenon through the consolidation of the research objectives, specifically by establishing a baseline assessment for an operational unit at UWS, analysing sources and quantities of corporate emissions reported to the Scottish Government, and by interviewing sector actors on the subject; a co-created framework emerges, see Figure 7.2.

The overwhelming reliance on FF energy sources is evident from the findings of this mixed method study research undertaken reasons for which in addition to well-established FF markets and infrastructure identified earlier in the chapter, include demand for transportation and travel requirements for staff, clients, goods and services being largely reliant on FFs; high building heating demands particularly from colder spells of winter; and limited renewable energy capacity to meet these demands amongst others.

7.3.1 Case study

The case study established a baseline CF of 682 tCO₂e and highlights the need for processes and structures within the establishment to enable better emissions data collation, recording and reporting of emissions including collectively for FF sources. By establishing a carbon emissions baseline for an operational unit at the UWS and identifying the amount and sources of contributing FF emissions, the unit can understand its emission profile and take appropriate steps to record, monitor, and implement measures to reduce FF associated emissions.

As part of establishing the CF baseline, specific steps to help the unit improve its CF and be more carbon efficient were identified and have been incorporated into the proposed framework. These were largely the result of the difficulties encountered in gathering data required to accurately estimate the baseline footprint, and as such highlights the need for improving data accuracy and quality. The main contributors to the established baseline emission CF present as areas of interest for targeting emission

reductions with electricity (approximately 35%), gas (approximately 32%), staff commute (approximately 16%), and business travel (approximately 16%). Of particular significance is targeting reductions from the FF associated emissions which in combination represent approximately at least over 62% of the baseline emissions that is the combination of an almost even split between travel related emissions by way of staff commute and business travel (dominated by road and air travel) which generally form a core part of an educational establishment's operations, and gas use.

7.3.2 Document review

The review and analysis of emissions reported by public sector bodies to the Scottish Government under The Climate Change (Duties of Public Bodies: Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Order 2015 as amended, allowed for the quantification of the extent of reliance on FF energy sources and highlights the significance of this reliance in proffering a framework to reduce reliance. The extent of reliance on FFs is quantified as the percentage contribution of FF associated emissions to overall reported sector emissions.

Despite evident reductions in reported emissions between 2015/16 and 2018/19 (15% sector-wide and 23% participating organisations), the increase in the percentage of emissions associated with FF energy sources over this period by 24% (sector-wide) and 61% (participating organisations) suggests not just a reliance on FFs but also increased reliance of FFs. A contributing factor to the increasing annual composition of FF emissions and therefore reliance in the context of this thesis, is the lower rate of decrease in reported FF emissions compared to the decrease in overall reported emissions for example, over the period in which reported emissions reduced by 23% sector-wide, the corresponding reduction in FF emissions was only 5%.

Another notable contributing factor is the limited impact of savings reported from emission reduction projects which represent between 3% and 5% of reported emissions and dominated by projects to reduce electricity emissions. The ability to increase the capacity of FF related emission reduction projects to levels enjoyed by the implementation of those associated with electricity presents an opportunity to reduce FF reliance and contributes to the framework. Like the case study emissions from electricity and gas would again appear as the main contributors particularly in combination averaging around 70% of reported emissions, whilst on average FF

emissions sources from heating and transportation demand represent around half of reported sector emissions. By quantifying reliance and identifying contributing FF emission sources, targets can be focused accordingly to aid reporting, monitoring and decision making to reduce FF reliance.

7.3.3 Interviews

Interviewing sector actors offered the opportunity to develop an understanding of the sectors FF reliance and to explore opportunities to reduce reliance through the opinions and views of experts from HEIs and LGAs. Whilst some may argue that Scotland's reliance on FF energy sources is well known, the responses from sector actors confirm this to be the case for Scotland's public sector and this understanding feeds into the framework development. This is in addition to the consolidated findings of the case study and analysis of emissions reported by sector bodies to the Scottish Government providing the platform from which a framework to address FF reliance is proposed.

With sector actors reporting that over half of their affiliated organisations emissions are FF related, the associated FF emissions result from energy use in buildings, with most organisations depending on the supply of energy from the National Grid. Although grid electricity is getting decarbonised FFs still contribute to the fuel mix supplied through the UK grid. However, it should be noted that all reference to FF sources and emissions in this thesis exclude any potential contributions from electricity as overall electricity remains less dependent on FFs. Despite advances in renewable energy accounting for 24% of total Scottish energy consumption in 2019 (Scottish Energy Statistics Hub, 2021b), it is simply not enough, and to address the persistent reliance on FFs to meet energy demands and fuel for components of travel and transportation, renewable and low carbon energy sources must be accessible in sufficient capacities to replace FFs.

Although it is arguably well documented, the lack of funding and government support for renewable technologies, practicalities and cost implications of increased investment in renewable technologies and upgrade of existing energy infrastructure, emerged from the analysis of sector actor responses as prominent barriers to increasing renewable energy capacity. Whilst such efforts as to catalyse advancements in the future availability, affordability and deployment of renewable energy sources is welcomed by public sector bodies, in the meantime, a framework based on the findings from the

mixed method study, for use by public sector bodies is a contribution to addressing FF reliance.

7.3.4 Significance of findings

The significance of the research findings particularly from the three aspects of the research discussed above drawn specifically from focus on HEIs and LGAs, by way of a framework to address reliance on FF energy sources and for use by Scottish public sector bodies (and can be adapted by other organisations), represents an original contribution to subject of FF reliance. The research discusses the implications of FF reliance for public sector bodies, highlighting the need for measuring and reporting FF sources and emissions, and facilitates the deepening of knowledge on the topic of FF reliance.

Developing a framework to reduce reliance on FFs can be as simple as identifying FF energy sources for example diesel, petrol, natural gas, oil etc.; measuring and reporting on FF consumption to set targets to reduce consumption; and harnessing the use alternative low-carbon or renewable energy sources of energy. Realising these, however, can be complex as it depends on the organisational needs or priorities, the availability of and access to low carbon alternative sources of energy, and well established national low-carbon or renewable energy infrastructure which is currently lacking.

Sources of FF energy are well documented in academic and grey literature however, it has been critical within the context of this thesis to establish and highlight the makeup of emission sources attributable to FFs, from those emissions reported by Scottish public sector bodies. Establishing individual sources of FF emissions commonly reported by sector bodies enables such organisation to collate them into an FF emissions category thereby forming the basis for monitoring, reporting and measuring FF emissions within public sector bodies. The FF emissions sources considered in this thesis, include:

- Natural gas and other heating fuels like gas oil and kerosene
- Travel and commute from flights, staff and student commute, and other business travel
- Transport Fuels like diesel, petrol, LPG, hybrid, and fuel oil
- Well to Tank for transport to site for burning oil/biomass wood pellets

- Coal (industrial)

It is without doubt that the role of the Scottish Government in enabling a society less reliant on FF energy sources is critical to the ability of organisations to make significant reductions in their FF reliance. This calls for partnership and collaborative working between the Scottish government and Scottish public sector bodies to aid the capacity of organisations to reduce their energy consumption including increasing the use of low carbon and renewable energy technologies. This can be achieved by improving politics and government leadership to expand the scale of technologies at national level, to decarbonise heat and electricity; expand scale of EV and its infrastructure to reduce reliance on FF driven transportation; and the implementation of other consistent national policies in support of net-zero emission ambitions.

Therefore, the proposed framework for addressing FF reliance in the Scottish public sector as shown in Figure 7.2 encompasses a collaborative and joined-up approach between public sector bodies and the Scottish Government to achieve reductions in FF reliance.

Figure 7.2: Proposed framework for addressing FF reliance in the Scottish public sector

CHAPTER 8:
RESEARCH CONCLUSION

8.1 SUMMARY OF THESIS MAIN POINTS

This chapter concludes the research by summarising the main points of the thesis, and providing concluding statements, limitations, and recommendations for future research. It also highlights the implications of the thesis for Scottish public sector bodies and the significance of the thesis.

The continued release of CO₂ into the atmosphere from the burning of FFs like oil, gas, and coal, predominantly for heating, electricity and transportation has significant implications for climate change. It is well documented and acknowledged in the thesis that Scotland (and indeed the UK) have made notable progress in decarbonising the electricity grid, still, more decarbonisation efforts are required particularly in the other significant quarters of heat and transportation which remain heavily reliant on FFs. However, despite this grounded scientific knowledge, FF energy sources continue to play a key part in the functionality of organisations to meet increasing demands for heating, transportation and even electricity in buildings. Although some organisations evidence emission reductions the overall picture indicates a lack of progress in meeting organisational emission reduction targets. Likewise evident is the lack of specific organisational reporting on FF related emissions. Reporting specifically on FF related emissions is an approach that can assist organisations in better understating their FF emissions profile and in considering actions they can take to address FF reliance. By exploring and developing an understanding of the reliance on FF energy sources through the lens of Scottish public sector bodies, this research work proposes a framework that such organisations can use to reduce their reliance on FF.

This has been achieved by undertaking a mixed method study encompassing employing the PRISMA and PICO framework to identify existing evidence on procedures to reduce FF reliance from literature available on the Scopus electronic database however, this yielded nil results with no further analysis carried out. Nevertheless, this research work contributes to addressing this gap in research, through consolidation of findings from the other methods employed into a framework. The case study method highlights both the challenge of establishing a CF for an HEI operational unit and the opportunities for targeted actions to reduce emissions from gas, petrol, diesel, and jet fuel which when combined as FFs is responsible for most of the CF. Reliance on these FF energy sources generally form a core part of an HEI's operations (and other public sector bodies), the

combined implications of which warrant collaboration with other stakeholders to establish standardised models for specific reporting on FF emissions. Emissions reported to the Scottish Government by public sector bodies indicate annual reductions in the total quantities of reported emissions based on the document review method. However, analysis suggests that the associated percentage share of combined FF emissions increased annually and averaged about half of total reported emissions over the four-year period from 2015 -2019. The increased reporting of Scope 3 travel emissions the most notable contributing factor, supporting the requirement the proposal for accounting, measuring, monitoring and reporting on FF emissions. To explore sector actor opinions on the subject matter, a semi-structured interview method is employed in which thematic analysis is used to transcribe interview responses, generate initial codes, identify and report on themes that emerged from the analysis in contribution to the framework to reduce FF reliance.

8.2 CONCLUDING STATEMENTS

It is evident from this research and in literature that reliance on FF energy sources has been a key aspect of human development over recent centuries and equally responsible for the retreating glacier, global warming and the largest known contributor of GHG emissions to the atmosphere. Its continued use however, has serious consequences with major environmental, social, and economic implications impacting human survival, mental health and well-being, poorer nations, and economic growth. The challenge is huge and in the context of organisations discussions ensue from capturing relevant data, measuring, reporting, and making efforts to reduce FFs. The lack of procedures to aid sector bodies reduce FF emissions and of focus on reporting, despite increasing evidence of its impacts as seen in the media is a notable concern. Furthermore, considering the well-established FF market and infrastructure, travel requirements including fuel demand for transportation, increasing energy demands, and other significant barriers highlighted in the thesis, culminates the significant challenge of achieving net-zero emissions, which requires concerted effort from all stakeholders.

Focus must therefore be shifted immediately to reducing FF reliance in response to climate change and this thesis demonstrates how reporting of FF emissions can enable HEIs, LGAs and the wider public sector target actions to impact FF related GHG reductions. The focus on specific measuring and reporting of FF related emissions at all

levels (micro, meso and macro) is of particular importance due to the increase in FF reliance and absence of a direct provision for measuring or targeting reduction of emissions associated with FF within climate change related legislation in the UK. The framework proposed in this thesis as shown in Figure 7.2 sets the scene for this required focus and for future research in ensuring that focus on reducing reliance on FF remains on the climate change agenda.

8.3 LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The case study to estimate the 2015/16 CF for the then SoSS was met with the inability to engage with the school with regards improving its CF following its restructure in 2018 and limiting this aspect of the research however, the lessons learnt have been incorporated within the developed framework. Furthermore, to establish the baseline it was necessary to make certain assumptions due to the lack of data, a chief factor in determining organisational and operational boundaries. This necessitated the use of physical footprints of rooms in conjunction with UWS EMS returns to estimate emissions from electricity, gas, water supply and water treatment; projection of the results of a mini travel survey; and Scottish national average statistics for calculating travel emissions, as examples. Although the initial plan was to use CMPs as the basis for the document review, they are often not up to date and usually span four to five years on average. The information sought from the CMPs, i.e., emission sources, CF, and emission reduction initiatives are available in the mandatory climate change public bodies reports to the Scottish Government, and for this reason these reports were used in place of CMPs.

Key decisions regarding the scope were made taking account of their implications to the researcher. For example, in relation to the sample size for the interviews which intended to target thirty sector actors, revised to twenty due to challenges in securing the target number, however, only eighteen interviews were completed. It is likely that the results of the interview analysis will not vary much if at all, should all the revised target of twenty sector actors have been interviewed. It may be argued that interviews could have been conducted via Microsoft Teams and Zoom online platforms or over the phone however, at the time of seeking ethical approval these platforms were not commonplace, and with interviews averaging 60 to 90 minutes, phone interviews were not suitable. The thematic analysis process was a cumbersome but highly engaging through the

processes of manual transcription, coding, and theme formulation in analysing interview responses. Whilst the decision was informed from the onset and may be characterised as a delimitation, the use of NVivo software may potentially have generated a larger workable sample size, yielding different outcomes by way of codes and themes.

This study was completed within the narrow scope of LGAs and HEIs in the Central belt geographical area of Scotland. It is therefore recommended that a study of similar purpose is undertaken, extended to represent a sample size encompassing every region of Scotland, and other sector bodies with focus on obtaining more robust empirical evidence to improve measuring and reporting on FF reliance within public sector bodies. Research to establish a reporting methodology and explore the legislative implications of mandatory reporting on FF to reduce its reliance is also recommended.

8.4 RESEARCH OUTPUTS AND PREDICTIONS

Whilst undertaking this research work elements of the research were presented in contribution to a couple of conferences by way of a conference poster at the Energy Technology Partnership annual conference 2018 (Glasgow) and by way of an abstract and conference poster at the Scottish Alliance for Geoscience, Environment & Society 2019 Global Climate Challenges for a Blue Green Economy (Edinburgh). The conference poster for the former conference ‘Carbon Efficiency in the Scottish Public Sector’ (Appendix 15) is published as open access on UWS research portal (Idundun, McLellan and Hursthouse, 2018) whilst the abstract and conference poster for the latter conference ‘Reliance on fossil fuels in the Scottish public sector’ (Appendices 16 and 17 respectively) is published as open access on UWS research portal (Idundun, Hursthouse and McLellan, 2019), and in the SAGES’ 19 conference ‘Book of Abstracts’ (SAGES, 2019). A manuscript resulting directly from aspects of this research was accepted and published in the ‘Sustainability’ journal special issue “The Role of Higher Education Institutions for Sustainability”, on 30 September 2021. The title published manuscript is ‘Carbon Management in UK Higher Education Institutions: An Overview’, a copy of which is securely bound into the thesis (Appendix 18).

The results of the research findings including the proposed framework can be useful to a target audience representing, but not limited to, managers, policy makers, and researchers in implementing policies and procedures which consider the impacts of individual organisations’ activities on climate change. FF emission information

provides a foundation for understanding reliance on FF energy sources within the sector to aid decision-making regarding mitigation actions to reduce FF reliance. In addition to the framework for reducing FF reliance, this research study highlights the need to, and importance of, shifting focus to reducing reliance on FFs to combat climate change through the collective measurement, recording, and reporting, of emissions associated with FF energy sources. Increased reporting specifically on FF emissions will increase corporate awareness on the implications of burning FFs to achieving net-zero emission targets and foster collaboration amongst organisations in finding solutions.

8.5 SOLUTIONS

There are numerous issues facing humanity today some perhaps with pressing humanitarian consequences and a big part of the solution is discussing these issues no matter how difficult the conversations may be. The COVID-19 pandemic for example, the impacts of which are being investigated across a range of subjects in some ways brought about a realisation that drastic climate change policies for example phasing out FFs, and continued development of renewable and low carbon energy technologies, to reduce reliance on FFs and associated climate change impacts can indeed be implemented by Governments to fruition however, not without careful considerations. The drastic measures that ensued at local, national, and international levels in response to the pandemic by way lockdowns forced organisations for example, HEIs to reconsider the model of how education is delivered and move to online delivery of education provisions spontaneously. However, as the tension between face to face and online delivery models persist with an array of implications (highlighted within the thesis) to be considered for example, implications on travel (business, staff and student commute); a developing hybrid of both facets may lend it to be the favoured model.

Scientists recently declared climate change is widespread, intensifying, and vigorous sustained reductions in GHGs required to keep warming to 1.5°C. This strengthens the calls for urgent climate action particularly in the context of Scotland following from COP 26 held in Glasgow (31 October to 12 November 2021). This should bring about the much-needed alacrity and opportunities to environmental and sustainability professionals or actors in proffering carefully considered drastic solutions to reduce FF reliance. One that starts with the measuring and reporting of FF use followed by the combination of reduced consumption and increased renewable capacity; and includes

adequate financial instruments and governance, and policies that favour a net-zero transition; with consideration for capacity to review, audit and update the framework.

REFERENCES

- Abbott, P., DiGiacomo, M., Magin, P., and Hu, W. (2018) 'A Scoping Review of Qualitative Research Methods Used With People in Prison. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*', 17(1). doi: 10.1177/1609406918803824.
- Åberg, M., Fälting, L., Lingfors, D., Nilsson, A.M. and Forssell, A. (2020) 'Do ground source heat pumps challenge the dominant position of district heating in the Swedish heating market?', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 254. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120070.
- Ahrens, T. and Ferry, L. (2020) 'Financial resilience of English local government in the aftermath of COVID-19', *Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting & Financial Management*, 32(5), pp. 813-823. doi: 10.1108/JPBAFM-07-2020-0098.
- Akgün, E.Z., Monios, J., Rye, T. and Fonzone, A. (2019) 'Influences on urban freight transport policy choice by local authorities', *Transport Policy*, 75, pp. 88-98. doi: [10.1016/j.tranpol.2019.01.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2019.01.009).
- Al Khajeh, E.H. (2018) 'Impact of Leadership Styles on Organizational Performance', *Journal of Human Resources Management Research*, 2018(2018), Article ID 687849, doi: 10.5171/2018.687849.
- Alcalde, J., Smith, P., Haszeldine, R.S. and Bond, C.E. (2018) 'The potential for implementation of negative emission technologies in Scotland', *International journal of greenhouse gas control*, 76, pp.85-91. doi: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2018.06.021.
- Alsaiifi, K., Elnahass, M., Salama, A. (2020) 'Carbon disclosure and financial performance: UK environmental policy', *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 29(2), pp. 711–726. doi: 10.1002/bse.2426.
- Altan, H. (2010) 'Energy efficiency interventions in UK higher education institutions', *Energy Policy*, 38(12), pp.7722-7731. doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2010.08.024.

Alvarez, S., Blanquer, M. and Rubio, A. (2014) 'Carbon footprint using the compound method based on financial accounts: The case of the School of Forestry Engineering, Technical University of Madrid', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 66, pp. 224-232. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.11.050.

Ambrose, J. (2019). *Rise of renewables may see off oil firms decades earlier than they think*. The Guardian. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2019/oct/14/rise-renewablesoil-firms-decades-earlier-think>. Published (Accessed: 09 January 2023).

APSE Energy (2020) *APSE Energy Climate Emergency Survey Report*. Available at: <https://www.apse.org.uk/apse/index.cfm/local-authority-energy-collaboration/apse-energy-publications1/apse-energy-climate-emergency-survey-report/> (Accessed: 19 January 2023).

Arena, A.P and de Rosa, C. (2003) 'Life cycle assessment of energy and environmental implications of the implementation of conservation technologies in school buildings in Mendoza—Argentina', *Building and Environment*, 38(2), pp. 359-368.

Ashworth, J. (2022) *Net zero is cheaper and greener than continuing the use of fossil fuels*. Available at: <https://www.nhm.ac.uk/discover/news/2022/september/net-zero-cheaper-and-greener-than-continuing-use-fossil-fuels.html> (Accessed: 08 January 2023).

Audit Scotland (2022) *Scotland's public finances: Challenges and risks*. Briefing. Available at: <https://www.audit-scotland.gov.uk/> (Accessed: 03 January 2023).

Bailey, D. (2022) *The ICE Ban Cometh. Can we have a Plan please?* Centre for Brexit Studies Blog, Centre for Brexit Studies. Available at: <https://www.open-access.bcu.ac.uk/id/eprint/10484> (Accessed: 08 January 2023).

Baker, S. and Edwards, R. (2017) 'How many qualitative interviews is enough? Expert voices and early career reflections on sampling and cases in qualitative research', National Centre for Research Methods Review Paper. Southampton, GB. Available at: https://eprints.ncrm.ac.uk/id/eprint/2273/4/how_many_interviews.pdf (Accessed: 17 December 2022).

- Banister, D. (2019) 'The climate crisis and transport', *Transport Reviews*, 39(5), pp. 565-568. doi: 10.1080/01441647.2019.1637113.
- Beech, N. and Anseel, F. (2020) 'COVID-19 and Its Impact on Management Research and Education: Threats, Opportunities and a Manifesto', *British Journal of Management*, 31(3), pp. 447–449. doi: 10.1111/1467-8551.12421.
- Birchall, S.J. and Bonnett, N. (2021) 'Climate change adaptation policy and practice: The role of agents, institutions and systems', *Cities*, 108, p. 103001. doi: 10.1016/j.cities.2020.103001.
- Birkitt, K., Loo-Morrey, M., Sanchez, C. and O'Sullivan, L. (2021) 'Materials aspects associated with the addition of up to 20 mol% hydrogen into an existing natural gas distribution network', *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 46(23), pp. 12290-12299. doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.09.061.
- Blanco-Portela, N., R-Pertierra, L., Benayas, J. and Lozano, R. (2018) 'Sustainability Leaders' Perceptions on the Drivers for and the Barriers to the Integration of Sustainability in Latin American Higher Education Institutions', *Sustainability*, 10(8), p. 2954. doi: 10.3390/su10082954.
- Bompard, E., Botterud, A., Corgnati, S., Huang, T., Jafari, M., Leone, P., Mauro, S., Montesano, G., Papa, C. and Profumo, F. (2020) 'An electricity triangle for energy transition: Application to Italy', *Applied Energy*, 277, p. 115525. doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.115525.
- Borrownan, P., Singh, R. and Bulleid, R. (2020) *The local climate challenge: A new partnership approach*. The Green Alliance. Available at: <https://green-alliance.org.uk/publication/the-local-climate-challenge-a-new-partnership-approach/> (Accessed: 11 December 2022).
- BP (2019) *BP Statistical Review of World Energy 2019*. 68th Edition. Available at: <https://www.bp.com/content/dam/bp/business-sites/en/global/corporate/pdfs/energy-economics/statistical-review/bp-stats-review-2019-full-report.pdf> (Accessed: 23 August 2023).

BP (2020) *BP Statistical Review Of World Energy 2020*. 69th Edition. Available at: <https://www.bp.com/content/dam/bp/business-sites/en/global/corporate/pdfs/energy-economics/statistical-review/bp-stats-review-2020-full-report.pdf> (Accessed: 21 August 2023).

BP (2023) *BP Statistical Review Of World Energy 2023*. 72nd Edition. Available at: <https://www.bp.com/en/global/corporate/energy-economics/statistical-review-of-world-energy.html> (Accessed: 29 August 2023).

Bramah, M. (2016) 'The prospects for municipal energy in the U.K.' *apse direct news*, (January / February), ISSN 16465-2493 (Moving forward in 2016), pp. 6-7.

Brand, C., Götschi, T., Dons, E., Gerike, R., Anaya-Boig, E., Avila-Palencia, I., de Nazelle, A., Gascon, M., Gaupp-Berghausen, M., Iacorossi, F., Kahlmeier, S., Panis, L. I., Racioppi, F., Rojas-Rueda, D., Standaert, A., Stigell, E., Sulikova, S., Wegener, S. and Nieuwenhuijsen, M. J. (2021) 'The climate change mitigation impacts of active travel: Evidence from a longitudinal panel study in seven European cities', *Global Environmental Change*, 67. doi: 10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102224.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) 'Using thematic analysis in psychology', *Qualitative Research in Psychology*. 3(2), pp. 77-101. doi: 10.1191/1478088706qp063oa.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2012) 'Thematic analysis.', in Cooper, H., Camic, P., Long, D.L., Panter, A.T., Rindskopf, D. and Sher, K.J. (eds.) *APA Handbook of Research Methods in Psychology*: Washington, DC: American Psychological Association, pp. 57–71. doi: 10.1037/13620-004.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2014) 'What can “thematic analysis” offer health and wellbeing researchers?', *International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-being*, 9(1). doi:10.3402/qhw.v9.26152.

BriteGreen (2017) *University Carbon Report*. Available at: <https://www.brite-green.co.uk/index.php/our-work/reports-publications/university-carbon-report> (Accessed: 21 August 2023).

Buda, A., de Place Hansen, E.J., Rieser, A., Giancola, E., Pracchi, V.N., Mauri, S., Marincioni, V., Gori, V., Fouseki, K., Polo López, C.S., Lo Faro, A., Egusquiza, A., Haas, F., Leonardi, E. and Herrera-Avellanosa, D. (2021) ‘Conservation-Compatible Retrofit Solutions in Historic Buildings: An Integrated Approach’, *Sustainability*. MDPI AG,13(5), p. 2927. doi: 10.3390/su13052927.

Budd, L. and Ison, S. (2020) ‘Responsible Transport: A post-COVID agenda for transport policy and practice’, *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 6, 100151. doi: 10.1016/j.trip.2020.100151.

Bui, M., Adjiman, C.S., Bardow, A., Anthony, E.J., Boston, A., Brown, S., Fennell, P. S., Fuss, S., Galindo, A., Hackett, L. A., Hallett, J. P., Herzog, H. J., Jackson, G., Kemper, J., Krevor, S., Maitland, G. C., Matuszewski, M., Metcalfe, I. S., Petit, C., Puxty, G., Reimer, J., Reiner, D. M., Rubin, E. S., Scott, S. A., Shah, N., Smit, B., Trusler, J. P. M., Webley, P., Wilcox, J. and Mac Dowell, N. (2018) ‘Carbon capture and storage (CCS): The way forward’, *Energy & Environmental Science*, 11(5), pp. 1062-1176. doi: 10.1039/c7ee02342a.

Bulkeley, H. and Kern, K. (2006) ‘Local government and the governing of climate change in Germany and the UK’, *Urban Studies*, 43(12), pp. 2237-2259. doi: 10.1080/00420980600936491.

Bumpus, A.G. and Liverman, D.M. (2008) ‘Accumulation by Decarbonization and the Governance of Carbon Offsets’, *Economic Geography*, 84(2), pp. 127-155. doi: 10.1111/j.1944-8287.2008.tb00401.x.

Carbon Trust (2018) *Carbon footprinting guide*. Available at: <https://www.carbontrust.com/resources/guides/carbon-footprinting-and-reporting/carbon-footprinting/#docdownload-6865> (Accessed: 21 August 2023).

Carbon Trust (2019) *SECR explained: Streamlined Energy & Carbon Reporting framework for UK business*. Available at: <https://www.carbontrust.com/news-and-events/insights/secr-explained-streamlined-energy-carbon-reporting-framework-for-uk> (Accessed: 23 August 2023).

- Carbon Trust (2020) *Local authorities* [Insight]. 20 April. Available: https://businessdocbox.com/Green_Solutions/70098353-Sector-overview-local-authorities-saving-energy-in-local-authority-buildings.html (Accessed: 21 August 2023).
- Cardemil, J.M., Schneider, W., Behzad, M. and Starke, A.R. (2021) ‘Thermal analysis of a water source heat pump for space heating using an outdoor pool as a heat source’, *Journal of Building Engineering*, 33. doi: 10.1016/j.job.2020.101581.
- Carmichael, R. (2019) *Behaviour change, public engagement and Net Zero. A report for the Committee on Climate Change*. Available at <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publications/> and <http://www.imperial.ac.uk/icept/publications/> (Accessed: 07 January 2023).
- Chan, M. (2009) *Carbon management: a practical guide for suppliers*: University of Cambridge Programme for Sustainability Leadership and Business in the Community. Available: <https://www.cisl.cam.ac.uk/resources/publication-pdfs/carbon-management-a-practical-guide-for-suppliers-1.pdf> (Accessed: 21 January 2023).
- Child, M., Ilonen, R., Vavilov, M., Kolehmainen, M. and Breyer, C. (2019) ‘Scenarios for sustainable energy in Scotland’, *Wind Energy*, 22(5), pp.666-684. doi: 10.1002/we.2314.
- Chou, M. (2021) ‘Australian local governments and climate emergency declarations: Reviewing local government practice’, *Australian Journal for Public Administration*, 80, pp. 613–623. doi: [10.1111/1467-8500.12451](https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8500.12451).
- Christensen, L.T., Morsing, M. and Thyssen, O. (2020) ‘Timely hypocrisy? Hypocrisy temporalities in CSR communication’, *Journal of Business Research*. 114, pp. 327-335. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.07.020.
- Christis, M., Athanassiadis, A. and Vercalsteren, A. (2019) ‘Implementation at a city level of circular economy strategies and climate change mitigation – the case of Brussels’, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 218, pp. 511-520. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.01.180.

Clabeaux, R., Carbajales-Dale, M., Ladner, D. and Walker, T. (2020) ‘Assessing the carbon footprint of a university campus using a life cycle assessment approach’, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 273, p. 122600. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122600.

Clarity (2022) *Global business travel, by the global business travel agents*. Available at: <https://claritybusinessstravel.com/global-business-travel-services/> (Accessed: 24 December 2022).

Clark, D. (2022) *Population of Scotland 1971-2021*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/367788/population-of-scotland/> (Accessed: 08 January 2023).

Climate Change Act 2008 (2050 Target Amendment) Order 2019, No. 1056. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2019/1056/made> (Accessed: 23 January 2023).

Climate Change (Emissions Reduction Targets) (Scotland) Act 2019, (asp 15). Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2019/15/introduction/enacted> (Accessed: 23 January 2023).

Climate Change (Scotland) Act 2009, (asp 12). Available at: <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2009/12> (Accessed: 23 January 2023).

Climate Emergency Declaration (2019a) *Scotland and Wales: World’s first governments to declare a climate emergency*. Available at: <https://climateemergencydeclaration.org/scotland-worlds-first-government-to-declare-a-climate-emergency/> (Accessed: 23 January 2023).

Climate Emergency Declaration (2019b) *European Union declares a climate emergency*. Available at: <https://climateemergencydeclaration.org/european-union-declares-a-climate-emergency/> (Accessed: 23 January 2023).

Committee on Climate Change (2019a) *Net Zero – The UK’s contribution to stopping global warming*. Available at: <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/net-zero-the-uks-contribution-to-stopping-global-warming/> (Accessed: 23 January 2023).

Committee on Climate Change (2019b). Reducing emissions in Scotland – 2019 Progress Report to Parliament. Available at: <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/reducing-emissions-in-scotland-2019-progress-report-to-parliament/> (Accessed: 23 January 2023).

Committee on Climate Change (2020) *Reducing emissions in Scotland 2020 Progress Report to Parliament*. Available at: <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/reducing-emissions-in-scotland-2020-progress-report-to-parliament/> (Accessed: 23 January 2023).

Committee on Climate Change (2021) *Progress in reducing emissions in Scotland – 2021 Report to Parliament*. Available at: <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/progress-reducing-emissions-in-scotland-2021-report-to-parliament/> (Accessed: 12 December 2022).

Confor (2022) *Confor accuses UK Government of "total policy failure" on tree planting (16 June 2022)*. Available at: <https://www.confor.org.uk/news/latest-news/confor-accuses-uk-government-of-total-policy-failure-on-tree-planting/> (Accessed: 07 January 2023).

Connolly, K. (2015) ‘G7 leaders agree to phase out fossil fuel use by end of century’, *The Guardian Online*, 8 June. Available at: <http://www.theguardian.com/world/2015/jun/08/g7-leaders-agree-phase-out-fossil-fuel-use-end-of-century> (Accessed: 23 January 2023).

Corver, M. (2019) *Higher education is big business*. Available at: <https://wonke.com/blogs/higher-education-is-big-business/> (Accessed: 13 January 2023).

Cranmer, A., Ericson, J.D., Broughel, A.E., Bernard, B., Robicheaux, E. and Podolski, M. (2020) ‘Worth a thousand words: Presenting wind turbines in virtual reality reveals new opportunities for social acceptance and visualization research’, *Energy Research & Social Science*, 67, p. 101507. doi: 10.1016/j.erss.2020.101507.

Crossley, J. (2021) *How To Write The Methodology Chapter The What, Why & How Explained Simply (With Examples)*. Available at: <https://gradcoach.com/how-to-write-the-methodology-chapter/> (Accessed: 24 February 2023).

Davis, A. and Whyte, B. (2022) 'Making the shift to sustainable transport in Scotland', *Cities & Health*, 6(2), pp.267-274. doi: 10.1080/23748834.2020.1812332.

De Wolf, C., Pomponi, F. and Moncaster, A. (2017) 'Measuring embodied carbon dioxide equivalent of buildings: A review and critique of current industry practice', *Energy and Building*, 140, pp. 68-80. doi: org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.01.075.

Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (2016) *Greenhouse gas reporting - Conversion factors 2016*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/greenhouse-gas-reporting-conversion-factors-2016> (Accessed: 23 January 2023).

Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (2018) *Emissions reduction pledge 2020: guidance for emissions reporting in public and higher education sectors in England 2018-2020*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/emissions-reduction-pledge-2020-emissions-reporting-in-public-and-higher-education-sectors> (Accessed: 10 December 2022).

Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (2020) *National Statistics. Sub-national electricity and gas consumption summary report 2019*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/sub-national-electricity-and-gas-consumption-summary-report-2019> (Accessed: 23 January 2023).

Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (2022) *Public Sector Decarbonisation Scheme: The Public Sector Decarbonisation Scheme provides grants for public sector bodies to fund heat decarbonisation and energy efficiency measures*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/public-sector-decarbonisation-scheme> (Accessed: 13 November 2022).

Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy, Trevelyan A-M. and Sharma, A. (2021) *End to coal power brought forward to October 2024* [Press release]. 30 June. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/end-to-coal-power-brought-forward-to-october-2024> (Accessed: 23 March 2023).

Department for Energy Security and Net Zero, Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy, and Kwarteng, K. (2022) *Correspondence: Ensuring security of electricity supplies for winter 2022 to 2023*. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/ensuring-security-of-electricity-supplies-for-winter-2022-to-2023> (Accessed: 23 March 2023).

Department for Energy Security and Net Zero, Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs and Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (2019) *Guidance: Environmental reporting guidelines: including Streamlined Energy and Carbon Reporting requirements*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/environmental-reporting-guidelines-including-mandatory-greenhouse-gas-emissions-reporting-guidance> (Accessed; 14 November 2022).

Department of Energy and Climate Change (2013) *DECC Carbon Management Plan*. Available at: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/253095/carbon_management_plan.pdf (Accessed: 24 January 2023).

Department of Energy and Climate Change (2021) *UK emissions statistics: frequently asked questions*. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/996190/uk-emissions-statistics-frequently-asked-questions.pdf (Accessed: 24 January 2023).

Distance Calculator (no date) *Distance Calculator*. Available at: <http://www.distancesfrom.com/> (Accessed: 24 January 2023).

Drumm, S., Bradley, C. and Moriarty, F. (2022) ‘‘More of an art than a science’? The development, design and mechanics of the Delphi Technique’, *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy*, 18(1), pp.2230-2236.

Durojaye O., Laseinde T. and Oluwafemi I. (2020) ‘A Descriptive Review of Carbon Footprint’, in Ahram T., Karwowski W., Pickl S. and Taiar R. (eds.) *Human Systems Engineering and Design II. IHSED 2019. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing, vol 1026*. Cham: Springer, pp. 960-968. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-27928-8_144.

Ebhota, W.S. and Jen, T.C. (2020) ‘Fossil Fuels Environmental Challenges and the Role of Solar Photovoltaic Technology Advances in Fast Tracking Hybrid Renewable Energy System’, *International Journal of Precision Engineering and Manufacturing-Green Technology*, 7, pp. 97–117. doi: 10.1007/s40684-019-00101-9.

Economic and Social Research Council (2021) *ESRC Research Funding Guide 2021*. Available at: <https://esrc.ukri.org/funding/guidance-for-applicants/research-funding-guide/> (Accessed: 24 January 2023).

EM Magazine (2020) *How UK universities can meet carbon reduction targets*. Available at: <https://www.energymanagemagazine.co.uk/how-uk-universities-can-meet-carbon-reduction-targets/> (Accessed: 24 January 2023).

Energy Saving Trust (2019) *Energy Saving Trust: supporting district heating in Scotland (Blog Post: 27 August 2019)*. Available at: <https://energysavingtrust.org.uk/energy-saving-trust-supporting-district-heating-scotland/> (Accessed: 08 January 2023).

Environmental Association for Universities and Colleges (2015) *University of the West of Scotland – NUS Award Success*. Available at: https://www.eauc.org.uk/university_of_west_scotland_awards_success (Accessed: 13 March 2023).

Environmental Association for Universities and Colleges (2016) *Summary report on Scottish Further and Higher Education Carbon Emissions 2014-15*. Available at: http://www.sustainabilityexchange.ac.uk/scottish_fhe_emissions_15 (Accessed: 24 January 2023).

Environmental Association for Universities and Colleges (2022) *The Climate Commission urge every university and college to sign up to the Race to Zero for Universities and Colleges*. Available at: https://www.eauc.org.uk/climate_commission (Accessed: 10 December 2022).

Environmental Association for Universities and Colleges, Scottish University Directors of Estates, JC Carbon Consulting and Carbon Forecasting (2015) *Scottish Universities Carbon Management Performance Review Project*. Available at: http://www.eauc.org.uk/higher_education_sector_carbon_management_plan (Accessed: 24 January 2023).

Environmental Association for Universities and Colleges, National Union of Student, University and College Union, Association of Colleges and College Development network (2017) *Sustainability in Education 2017*. Available at: https://s3-eu-west-1.amazonaws.com/nusdigital/document/documents/38977/20180122_State_of_the_sector_report_2017_FINAL.pdf (Accessed: 24 January 2023).

Erickson, M., Hanna, P. and Walker, C. (2021) 'The UK higher education senior management survey: a stactivist response to managerialist governance', *Studies in Higher Education*, 46(11), pp. 2134-2151. doi: 10.1080/03075079.2020.1712693.

European Commission (no date) *Progress made in cutting emissions*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/clima/eu-action/climate-strategies-targets/progress-made-cutting-emissions_en (Accessed: 24 January 2023).

European Commission (2019) *New data and analyses for building the Energy Union in a robust way - the 2018 energy prices and costs report in Europe*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/news/new-data-and-analyses-building-energy-union-robust-way-2018-energy-prices-and-costs-report-europe-2019-jan-09_en (Accessed: 24 January 2023).

Evans, S. (2019) *Analysis: UK electricity generation in 2018 falls to lowest level since 1994*. Available at: <https://www.carbonbrief.org/analysis-uk-electricity-generation-2018-falls-to-lowest-since-1994> (Accessed: 24 January 2023).

Fan, J.I., Hou, Y-B., Wang, Q., Wang, C. and Wei, Y-M. (2016) ‘Exploring the characteristics of production-based and consumption-based carbon emissions of major economies: A multiple-dimension comparison’, *Applied Energy*, 184, pp. 790-799. doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.06.076.

Fet, A. M. (1998) *Environmental Management Tools and their Application - A Review with References to Case Studies*. Available at: <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/summary?doi=10.1.1.605.5478> (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Filimonau, V., Archer, D., Bellamy, L., Smith, N. and Wintrip, R. (2021) ‘The carbon footprint of a UK University during the COVID-19 lockdown’, *Science of The Total Environment*, 756. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.143964.

Findler, F., Schönherr, N., Lozano, R., Reider, D. and Martinuzzi, A. (2019) ‘The impacts of higher education institutions on sustainable development: A review and conceptualization’, *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 20(1), pp. 23-38. doi: 10.1108/IJSHE-07-2017-0114.

Fink-Hafner, D., Dagen, T., Doušak, M., Novak, M. and Hafner-Fink, M. (2019) ‘Delphi method: strengths and weaknesses’, *Advances in Methodology and Statistics*, 16(2), pp.1-19.

Fossil Free (no date) *About Fossil Free*. Available at: <http://gofossilfree.org/uk/about-fossil-free/> (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Fouseki, K. and Cassar, M. (2014) ‘Energy efficiency in heritage buildings: Future challenges and research needs’, *The Historic Environment: Policy & Practice*, 5(2), pp. 95–100. doi: [10.1179/1756750514Z.00000000058](https://doi.org/10.1179/1756750514Z.00000000058).

Foxon, T.J., Gross, R., Chase, A., Howes, J., Arnall, A. and Anderson, D. (2005) ‘UK innovation systems for new and renewable energy technologies: drivers, barriers and systems failures’, *Energy Policy*, (16), pp. 2123-2137. doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2004.04.011.

Gibbs, D. and O'Neill, K. (2015) 'Building a green economy? Sustainability transitions in the UK building sector', *Geoforum*, 59, pp. 133-141. doi: 10.1016/j.geoforum.2014.12.004.

Glasgow City Council (2021a) *COP26 volunteers to get 'climate literate' in time for global summit in Glasgow*. Published 15 September 2021. Available at: <https://www.glasgow.gov.uk/index.aspx?articleid=27537> (Accessed: 12 December 2022).

Glasgow City Council (2021b) *COP26 volunteers reflect on experiences as global conference closes in Glasgow*. Published 16 November 2021. Available at: <https://www.glasgow.gov.uk/index.aspx?articleid=27702> (Accessed: 12 December 2022).

Gómez, N., Cadarso, M-Á. and Monsalve, F. (2016) 'Carbon footprint of a University in a multiregional model: The case of the University of Castilla-La Mancha', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 138, pp. 119-130. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.06.009.

Granberg, M., and Elander, I. (2007) 'Local governance and climate change: Reflections on the Swedish experience', *Local Environment*, 12(5), pp.537-548. doi: 10.1080/13549830701656911.

Gudde, P., Oakes, J., Cochrane, P., Caldwell, N. and Bury, N. (2021) 'The role of UK local government in delivering on net zero carbon commitments: You've declared a Climate Emergency, so what's the plan?', *Energy Policy*, 154. doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112245.

Guerrieri, M., La Gennusa, M., Peri, G., Rizzo, G. and Scaccianoce, G. (2019) 'University campuses as small-scale models of cities: Quantitative assessment of a low carbon transition path'. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 113. doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2019.109263.

Guinée, J.B., Heijungs, R., Huppes, G., Zamagni, A., Masoni, P., Buonamici, R., Ekvall, T. and Rydberg, T. (2011) 'Life Cycle Assessment: Past, Present, and Future', *Environmental Science & Technology*, 45 (1), pp. 90-96. doi: 10.1021/es101316v.

Haque, N. (2020) '29 - The Life Cycle Assessment of Various Energy Technologies', in Letcher, T.M. (ed.) *Future Energy (Third Edition)*, pp. 633-647. Elsevier, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-08-102886-5.00029-3.

Harteis, C. (2022) 'Delphi-Technique as a Method for Research on Professional Learning', in Goller, M., Kyndt, E., Paloniemi, S., Damşa, C. (eds) *Methods for Researching Professional Learning and Development. Professional and Practice-based Learning*, 33, pp. 351-371. Springer, Cham, doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-08518-5_16.

Hawes, M. (2020) *SMMT response to Government's 2035 end of sale announcement*. Available at: <https://www.smmt.co.uk/2020/02/smmt-response-to-governments-2035-end-of-sale-announcement/> (Accessed: 08 January 2023).

Heijungs, R., Huppes, G. and Guinée, J.B. (2010) 'Life cycle assessment and sustainability analysis of products, materials and technologies. Toward a scientific framework for sustainability life cycle analysis', *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 95(3), pp. 422-428, doi: 10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2009.11.010.

Hickman, R. and Banister, D. (2007) 'Looking over the horizon: Transport and reduced CO₂ emissions in the UK by 2030', *Transport Policy*, 14(5), pp. 377-387. doi: 10.1016/j.tranpol.2007.04.005.

Hickman, R. and Banister, D. (2019) 'Transport and the environment', in Stanley, J. and Hensher, D.A. (eds.) *A Research Agenda for Transport Policy*, pp. 25-33, Edward Elgar Publishing. doi: 10.4337/9781788970204.

Higher Education Funding Council for England (2010) *Carbon management strategies and plans: A guide to good practice*. Available at: https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20100406211739/http://www.hefce.ac.uk/pubs/hefce/2010/10_02/ (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Higher Education Funding Council for England (2012) *Measuring Scope 3 carbon emissions – transport: A guide to good practice*. Available at: https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20120118164931/http://www.hefce.ac.uk/pubs/hefce/2012/12_02/ (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Higher Education Statistics Agency (2021a) *Higher Education Student Statistics: UK, 2019/20 - Student numbers and characteristics. Statistical Bulletin SB258*. Available at: <https://www.hesa.ac.uk/news/27-01-2021/sb258-higher-education-student-statistics/numbers> (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Higher Education Statistics Agency (2021b) *Higher Education Staff Statistics: UK, 2019/20. Statistical Bulletin SB259*. Available at: <https://www.hesa.ac.uk/news/19-01-2021/sb259-higher-education-staff-statistics#notes> (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Higher Education Statistics Agency (2022) *What is the income of HE providers?* Available at: <https://www.hesa.ac.uk/data-and-analysis/finances/income> (Accessed: 13 January 2023).

HM Government (2021) *Net Zero Strategy: Build Back Greener*. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1033990/net-zero-strategy-beis.pdf (Accessed: 01 February 2023).

Hoolohan, C., McLachlan, C., Jones, C., Larkin, A., Birch, C., Mander, S. and Broderick, J. (2021) 'Responding to the climate emergency: how are UK universities establishing sustainable workplace routines for flying and food?', *Climate Policy*, doi: 10.1080/14693062.2021.1881426.

HP (2022a) *HP Compaq Elite 8300 Series – Specifications*. Available at: <https://support.hp.com/us-en/document/c03345460> (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

HP (2022b) *HP Elite Display E201 20-inch LED Backlit Monitor - Specifications*. Available at: <https://support.hp.com/us-en/document/c03715521> (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Hunziker, S. and Blankenagel, M. (2021) *Research Design in Business and Management: A Practical Guide for Students and Researchers*. Springer Nature.

Idundun, E., McLellan, I. and Hursthouse, A. (2018) 'Carbon efficiency in the Scottish public sector', ETP Annual Conference 2018, Glasgow, United Kingdom, 29/10/18. Available at: <https://research-portal.uws.ac.uk/en/publications/carbon-efficiency-in-the-scottish-public-sector> (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Idundun, E., McLellan, I. and Hursthouse, A. (2019) ‘Reliance on fossil fuels in the Scottish public sector’, SAGES’19 Global Climate Challenges for a Blue Green Economy, Edinburgh, United Kingdom, 27/11/18 - 28/11/19. Available at: <https://research-portal.uws.ac.uk/en/publications/reliance-on-fossil-fuels-in-the-scottish-public-sector> (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (2007) *Climate Change 2007: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Edited by Solomon, S., Qin, D., Manning, M., Chen, Z., Marquis, M., Averyt, K.B., Tignor, M. and Miller H.L. (eds.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA. Available at: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar4/wg1/> (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (2010) *Understanding Climate Change - 22 years of IPCC assessment*. Available at: https://archive.ipcc.ch/pdf/press/ipcc_leaflets_2010/ipcc-brochure_understanding.pdf (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (2013) ‘Summary for Policymakers’, in: Stocker, T.F., Qin, D., Plattner, G.-K., Tignor, M., Allen, S.K., Boschung, J., Nauels, A., Xia, Y., Bex, V. and Midgley, P.M. (eds.) *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA. Available at: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar5/wg1/> (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (2014) ‘Summary for policymakers’ in Field, C.B., V.R. Barros, D.J. Dokken, K.J. Mach, M.D. Mastrandrea, T.E. Bilir, M. Chatterjee, K.L. Ebi, Y.O. Estrada, R.C. Genova, B. Girma, E.S. Kissel, A.N. Levy, S. MacCracken, P.R. Mastrandrea, and L.L. White (eds.) *Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Part A: Global and Sectoral Aspects. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, pp. 1-32. Available: https://www.ipcc.ch/pdf/assessment-report/ar5/wg2/ar5_wgII_spm_en.pdf (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (2021a) ‘Summary for policymakers’, in Masson-Delmotte, V., Zhai, P., Pirani, A., Connors, S. L., Péan, C., Berger, S., Caud, N., Chen, Y., Goldfarb, L., Gomis, M. I., Huang, M., Leitzell, K., Lonnoy, E., Matthews, J. B. R., Maycock, T. K., Waterfield, T., Yelekçi, O., Yu, R. and Zhou, B. (eds.) *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. In Press, 2021a; 89 pp.

Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (2021b) *AR6 Synthesis Report: Climate Change 2022*. Available at: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/sixth-assessment-report-cycle/> (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

International Civil Aviation Organization (2016) *Carbon Emissions Calculator*. Available at: <http://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/CarbonOffset/Pages/default.aspx> (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Jackson, T. and Lynch, W. (2011) ‘Public sector responses to climate change: Evaluating the role of Scottish local government in implementing the Climate Change (Scotland) Act 2009’, *Commonwealth Journal of Local Governance*, (8/9), May-November 2011. Available at: <http://epress.lib.uts.edu.au/ojs/index.php/cjlg> (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Jaganmohan, M. (2022) *Monthly minimum temperature in Scotland from 2015 to 2021 (in degrees Celsius)*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/585082/monthly-minimum-temperature-in-scotland/> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

Jansen, D. (2021) *How To Choose Your Research Methodology: Qualitative vs Quantitative vs Mixed Methods*. Available at: <https://gradcoach.com/choose-research-methodology/> (Accessed: 24 February 2023).

JMP Consultants Ltd (2012) *Measuring Scope 3 carbon emissions – transport: Report to HEFCE by JMP Consultants Ltd*. Available at: https://www.eauc.org.uk/measuring_scope_3_carbon_emissions (Accessed: 26 January 2023).

Jowitt, P. and Johnson, A. (2014) *Topic guide: Carbon management of infrastructure services*. doi: 10.12774/eod_tg10_feb2014.mwh.

Kallio, H., Pietilä, A.-M., Johnson, M. and Kangasniemi, M. (2016) 'Systematic methodological review: developing a framework for a qualitative semi-structured interview guide', *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 72(12), pp. 2954– 2965. doi: 10.1111/jan.13031.

Kameyama, Y., Morita, K. and Kubota, I. (2016) 'Finance for achieving low-carbon development in Asia: The past, present, and prospects for the future', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 128, pp. 201-208. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.12.089.

Kandananond, K. (2017) 'The Greenhouse Gas Accounting of A Public Organization: The Case of A Public University in Thailand', *Energy Procedia*, 141, pp. 672-676. doi: 10.1016/j.egypro.2017.11.091.

Kashwan, P. (2021) 'Climate Justice in the Global North: An Introduction', *Case Studies in the Environment*, 5(1). doi: 10.1525/cse.2021.1125003.

Kealy T. (2020) 'Corporate Social Responsibility Through a Wind Turbine Lens—A Literature Review', *Evaluating Sustainable Development and Corporate Social Responsibility Projects*, pp. 17-58. doi: [10.1007/978-3-030-38673-3_2](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-38673-3_2).

Keane, K. (2020) 'Power sector problems see greenhouse gas target missed', *BBC News Online*, 16 June. Available at: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-scotland-53063990> (Accessed at: 26 January 2023).

Keeling, C.D., Piper, S.C., Bacastow, R.B., Wahlen, M., Whorf, T.P., Heimann, M. and Meijer, H.A. (2005) 'Atmospheric CO₂ and ¹³CO₂ exchange with the terrestrial biosphere and oceans from 1978 to 2000: observations and carbon cycle implications', in Baldwin, I.T., Caldwell, M.M., Heldmaier, G., Jackson, R.B., Lange, O.L., Mooney, H.A., Schulze, E.D., Sommer, U., Ehleringer, J.R., Denise Dearing, M. and Cerling, T.E. (eds.) *A History of Atmospheric CO₂ and its effects on Plants, Animals, and Ecosystems*. New York: Springer Verlag, 177, pp. 83-113. doi: Available: 10.1007/0-387-27048-5_5.

Kiger, M.E. and Varpio, L. (2020) 'Thematic analysis of qualitative data: AMEE Guide No. 131', *Medical Teacher*, 42(8), pp.846-854, doi: 10.1080/0142159X.2020.1755030.

- Klein-Banai, C. and Theis, T.L. (2013) 'Quantitative analysis of factors affecting greenhouse gas emissions at institutions of higher education', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 48, pp.29-38. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2011.06.004.
- Kneifel, J. (2010) 'Life-cycle carbon and cost analysis of energy efficiency measures in new commercial buildings', *Energy and Buildings*, 42(3), pp.333-340. doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2009.09.011.
- Kuzemko, C. and Britton, J. (2020) 'Policy, politics and materiality across scales: A framework for understanding local government sustainable energy capacity applied in England', *Energy Research & Social Science*, 62, doi: 10.1016/j.erss.2019.101367. 101367.
- Larsen, H.N., Pettersen, J., Solli, C. and Hertwich, E.G. (2013) 'Investigating the carbon footprint of a university: The case of NTNU', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 48, pp.39-47. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2011.10.007.
- Leal Filho, W., Eustachio, J.H.P.P., Caldana, A.C.F., Will, M., Lange Salvia, A., Rampasso, I.S., Anholon, R., Platje, J. and Kovaleva, M. (2020) 'Sustainability Leadership in Higher Education Institutions: An Overview of Challenges', *Sustainability*, 12(9), 3761. doi: 10.3390/su12093761.
- Lee, K-H. (2011) 'Integrating carbon footprint into supply chain management: The case of Hyundai motor company (HMC) in the automobile industry', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 19(11), pp.1216-1223. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2011.03.010.
- Li, Z., Chen, Z., Yang, N., Wei, K., Ling, Z., Liu, Q., Chen, G. and Ye, B.H. (2021) 'Trends in research on the carbon footprint of higher education: A bibliometric analysis', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 289. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125642.
- Local Government Association (2020) *Climate Change Survey 2020. Research Report, February 2020*. Available at: <https://www.local.gov.uk/publications/climate-change-survey-february-2020> (Accessed: 27 January 2023).
- Logan, K.G., Nelson, J.D., Osbeck, C., Chapman, J.D. and Hastings, A (2020) 'The application of travel demand management initiatives within a university setting', *Case Studies on Transport Policy*, 8(4), pp. 1426-1439. doi: 10.1016/j.cstp.2020.10.007.

- Lomer, S. (2018) 'UK policy discourses and international student mobility: the deterrence and subjectification of international students', *Globalisation, Societies and Education*, 16(3), pp. 308-324. doi: 10.1080/14767724.2017.1414584.
- Lowe, R. (2007) 'Technical options and strategies for decarbonizing UK housing', *Building Research & Information*, 35(4), pp. 412-425. doi: 10.1080/09613210701238268.
- Lowes, R., Rosenow, J., Qadrdan, M. and Wu, J. (2020) 'Hot stuff: Research and policy principles for heat decarbonisation through smart electrification', *Energy Research & Social Science*, 70. doi: 10.1016/j.erss.2020.101735.
- Mahmoudian, F., Lu, J., Yu, D., Nazari, J.A. and Herremans, I.M. (2021) 'Inter- and intra-organizational stakeholder arrangements in carbon management accounting', *British Accounting Review*, 53(1),100933. doi: 10.1016/j.bar.2020.100933.
- Manz, P., Kermeli, K., Persson, U., Neuwirth, M., Fleiter, T. and Crijns-Graus W. (2021) 'Decarbonizing District Heating in EU-27 + UK: How Much Excess Heat Is Available from Industrial Sites?', *Sustainability*, 13(3):1439. doi: 10.3390/su13031439.
- Marsden, J., Darke, S., Hall, W., Hickman, M., Holmes, J., Humphreys, K., Neale, J., Tucker, J., and West, R. (2020) 'Mitigating and learning from the impact of COVID-19 infection on addictive disorders', *Addiction*, 115(6), p. 1007– 1010. doi: 10.1111/add.15080.
- Matsas, I.C., Mintsis, G., Basbas, S. and Taxiltaris, C. (2022) 'Autonomous Vehicles: Impact on Human Life-A Statistic and Descriptive Overview of Research Results, Using the Delphi Method', *Conference on Sustainable Urban Mobility*, pp. 435-450. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Matthews, H., Scott, Weber, C. and Hendrickson, C. (2008a) 'Estimating carbon footprints with input-output models', *International Input Output Meeting on Managing the Environment: Input – Output & Environment*. Seville, Spain, 9 – 11 July. Available at: <https://www.academia.edu/2721625> (Accessed: 27 January 2023).

- Matthews, H.S., Hendrickson, C.T. and Weber, C.L. (2008b) 'The importance of carbon footprint estimation boundaries' *Environmental Science & Technology*, 42(16), pp. 5839-5842. doi: 10.1021/es703112w.
- Mazhar, A.R., Liu, S. and Shukla, A. (2018) 'A state of art review on the district heating systems' *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. 96, pp. 420-439. doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2018.08.005.
- Mazhar, A.R., Liu, S., and Shukla, A. (2020) 'Comprehensive Study of District Heating (DH) in the UK: techno-economic aspects, policy support and trends', in *Low Carbon Energy Supply Technologies and Systems*. CRC publisher, pp, 153-187.
- Mazhar M.U., Bull R., Lemon M., Ahmad S.B.S. (2019) 'Carbon Management Planning in UK Universities: A Journey to Low Carbon Built Environment', in Leal Filho W. and Leal-Arcas R. (eds) *University Initiatives in Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation*. Cham: Springer, pp. 33-56. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-89590-1_3.
- Measham, T.G., Preston, B.L., Smith, T.F., Brooke, C., Gorddard, R., Withycombe, G. and Morrison, C. (2011) 'Adapting to climate change through local municipal planning: Barriers and challenges', *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 16(8), pp. 889-909. doi: 10.1007/s11027-011-9301-2.
- Medical Research Council (2021) *Guidance for Applicants 2021*. Available at: <https://mrc.ukri.org/funding/guidance-for-applicants/> (Accessed: 27 January 2023).
- Mehta, D. P. and Wiesehan, M. (2013) 'Sustainable Energy in Building Systems', *Procedia Computer Science*. 19, pp. 628-635. doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2013.06.08.
- Milner, J., Davies, M. and Wilkinson, P. (2012) 'Urban energy, carbon management (low carbon cities) and co-benefits for human health', *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 4(4), pp. 398-404. doi: 10.1016/j.cosust.2012.09.011.
- Molina Azorín, J.M. and Cameron, R. (2010) 'The Application of Mixed Methods in Organisational Research: A Literature Review', *The Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods*, 8(2), pp. 95-105.

Molthan-Hill, P., Robinson, Z.P., Hope, A., Dharmasasmita, A. and McManus, E. (2020) 'Reducing carbon emissions in business through Responsible Management Education: Influence at the micro-, meso- and macro-levels', *The International Journal of Management Education*, 18(1), 100328. doi. 10.1016/j.ijme.2019.100328.

Morgan, A., Zappa, W., Harmsen, R., and Lehmann, P. (2020) 'Evaluating instruments stimulating sustainability transitions: promoting biomass boilers in Germany and the UK', *2020 Energy Evaluation Europe Conference: Accelerating the energy transition for all: Evaluation's role in effective policy making*. London, UK, June 29 – 1 July. Available at: <https://energy-evaluation.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/eee2020-paper-morgan-alexander-33-61-morgan-alexander.pdf> (Accessed: 27 January 2023).

Mura, M., Longo, M. and Zanni, S. (2020) 'Circular economy in Italian SMEs: A multi-method study', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 245. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118821.

National Audit Office (2017) *A Short Guide to Local authorities*. Available at: <https://www.nao.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/A-Short-Guide-to-Local-Authorities.pdf> (Accessed: 27 January 2023).

National Audit Office (2018) *Low-carbon heating of homes and businesses and the Renewable Heat Incentive*. Available at: <https://www.nao.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/Low-carbon-heating-of-homes-and-businesses-and-the-Renewable-Heat-Incentive.pdf> (Accessed: 27 January 2023).

National Audit Office (2021) *Local government and net zero in England*. Available at: <https://www.nao.org.uk/reports/local-government-and-net-zero-in-england/#downloads> (Accessed: 13 November 2022).

National Records of Scotland (2022) *Scotland's population projected to fall*. Available: <https://www.nrscotland.gov.uk/news/2022/scotlands-population-projected-to-fall> (Accessed: 08 January 2023).

Natural Environment Research Council (2021) *NERC research grants and fellowships handbook. Grants awarded on full economic cost basis*. Available at: <https://nerc.ukri.org/funding/application/howtoapply/forms/> (Accessed: 27 January 2023).

NETREGS (2017a) *Cutting your carbon emissions*. Available at: <http://www.netregs.org.uk/environmental-topics/carbon-reduction-and-efficiency/cutting-your-carbon-emissions/> (Accessed: 27 January 2023).

NETREGS (2017b) *Reducing vehicles emissions*. Available at: <http://www.netregs.gov.uk/environmental-topics/air-pollution/reducing-vehicle-emissions> (Accessed: 27 January 2023).

Nicholls, D., Barnes, F., Acrea, F., Chen, C., Buluç, L. Y. and Parker, M. M. (2015) 'Top-down and bottom-up approaches to greenhouse gas inventory methods - A comparison between national- and forest-scale reporting methods', *General Technical Report*. Portland. doi: 10.2737/PNW-GTR-906.

Office for National Statistics (2016a) *Electoral statistics, UK: 2015*. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/elections/electoralregistration/bulletins/electoralstatisticsforuk/2015> (Accessed: 27 January 2023).

Office for National Statistics (2016b) *Population estimates*. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationestimates> (Accessed: 27 January 2023).

Office for National Statistics (2016c) *Dataset: Regional Scottish Data: Sept 2016 to Nov 2016*. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/employmentandemployeetypes/adhocs/006553regionalscottishdatasept2016tonov2016> (Accessed: 27 January 2023).

Office for Students (2020) *Reducing higher education carbon emissions*. Available at: <https://www.officeforstudents.org.uk/media/7199663b-5f6c-49f7-b231-ec5cab2adb81/bd-2020-january-71-reducing-higher-education-carbon-emissions.pdf> (Accessed: 10 December 2022).

Okereke, C. (2007) 'An exploration of motivations, drivers and barriers to carbon management', *European Management Journal*, 25(6), pp. 475-486. doi: 10.1016/j.emj.2007.08.002.

- Ostfeld, R. and Reiner, D.M. (2020) 'Public views of Scotland's path to decarbonization: Evidence from citizens' juries and focus groups', *Energy Policy*, 140, p.111332. doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111332.
- Ottelin, J., Heinonen, J. and Junnila, S. (2018) 'Carbon and material footprints of a welfare state: Why and how governments should enhance green investments', *Environmental Science & Policy*, 86, pp. 1-10. doi: 10.1016/j.envsci.2018.04.011.
- Owen, R., Brennan, G. and Lyon, F. (2018) 'Enabling investment for the transition to a low carbon economy: Government policy to finance early stage green innovation', *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 31, pp. 137-145. doi: 10.1016/j.cosust.2018.03.004.
- Ozawa-Meida, L., Brockway, P., Letten, K., Davies, J. and Fleming, P. (2013) 'Measuring carbon performance in a UK university through a consumption-based carbon footprint: De Montfort University case study', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 56, pp. 185-198. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2011.09.028.
- Page, M. J., Moher, D., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., et al. (2021) 'PRISMA 2020 explanation and elaboration: updated guidance and exemplars for reporting systematic reviews', *BMJ*, 372. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n160.
- Painuly, J.P. (2001) 'Barriers to renewable energy penetration; a framework for analysis', *Renewable Energy*, 24(1), pp. 73-89. doi: 10.1016/S0960-1481(00)00186-5.
- Pandey, D., Agrawal, M. and Pandey, J.S. (2011) 'Carbon footprint: current methods of estimation', *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 178(1), pp. 135-160. doi: 10.1007/s10661-010-1678-y.
- Parker, C., Scott, S. and Geddes, A. (2019) 'Snowball sampling', *SAGE research methods foundations*. Available at: <https://eprints.glos.ac.uk/id/eprint/6781> (Accessed: 02 January 2023).
- Peters, G.P. (2010) 'Carbon footprints and embodied carbon at multiple scales', *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 2(4), pp. 245-250. doi: 10.1016/j.cosust.2010.05.004.

Pietzcker R.C., Longden T., Chen W., Fu S., Kriegler E., Kyle P. and Luderer G. (2014) 'Long-term transport energy demand and climate policy: Alternative visions on transport decarbonization in energy-economy models', *Energy*, 64, pp. 95-108. doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2013.08.059.

Prowse, M. and Snilstveit, B. (2010) 'Impact Evaluation and Interventions to Address Climate Change: A Scoping Study'. *Journal of Development Effectiveness*, 2(2), pp. 228-262. doi: 10.1080/19439341003786729.

Purman, J. R. (2008). *Tracking Your Carbon Footprint: A Step-by-Step Guide to Understanding And Inventorying Greenhouse Gas Emissions*. New York: iUniverse Inc.

Qadrdan, M., Abeysekera, M., Wu, J., Jenkins, N., and Winter, B. (2020) 'The Future of Gas Networks', in *The Future of Gas Networks*. Cham: Springer (SpringerBriefs in Energy book series), pp. 49-68. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-66784-3_5.

Quinlivan, L., & Dunphy, N. (2023) 'A Mixed-Methods Approach to Climate Action Planning', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 22. doi: 10.1177/16094069221150107.

Ramaswamy, M., Marciniuk, D.D., Csonka, V., Colò, L. and Saso, L. (2021) 'Reimagining Internationalization in Higher Education Through the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals for the Betterment of Society', *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 25(4), pp.388-406. doi: 10.1177/10283153211031046.

Raybould, B., Cheung, W.M., Connor, C. and Butcher, R. (2020) 'An investigation into UK government policy and legislation to renewable energy and greenhouse gas reduction commitments', *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, 22, pp. 371–387. doi: 10.1007/s10098-019-01786-x.

Reimers, F.M. (2021) 'Education and Climate Change: The Role of Universities', in *International Explorations in Outdoor and Environmental Education*. Cham: Springer Nature. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-57927-2.

- Ren, C., Deng, Y. and Cao, S-J. (2018) 'Evaluation of polyethylene and steel heat exchangers of ground source heat pump systems based on seasonal performance comparison and life cycle assessment', *Energy and Buildings*, 162, pp. 54-64. doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.12.037.
- Revelle, R.R. and Shapero, D.C. (1978) 'Energy and Climate', *Environmental Conservation*, 5(02), pp. 81-91. doi: 10.1017/S0376892900005506.
- Ridhosari, B. and Rahman, A. (2020) 'Carbon footprint assessment at Universitas Pertamina from the scope of electricity, transportation, and waste generation: Toward a green campus and promotion of environmental sustainability', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 246. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119172.
- Robertson, G. P. and Grace, P. R. (2004) 'Greenhouse Gas Fluxes in Tropical and Temperate Agriculture: The need for a Full-Cost accounting of Global Warming Potentials', *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 6(1), pp.51-63. doi: 10.1023/B:ENVI.0000003629.32997.9e.
- Robinson, O., Kemp, S. and Williams, I. (2015) 'Carbon management at Universities: A reality check', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 106, pp. 109-118. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.06.095.
- Robinson, O.J., Tewkesbury, A., Kemp, S. and Williams, I.D. (2018) 'Towards a universal carbon footprint standard: A case study of carbon management at Universities', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 172, pp. 4435-4455. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.02.147.
- Romasheva, N. and Ilinova, A. (2019) 'CCS Projects: How Regulatory Framework Influences Their Deployment', *Resources*, 8(4), p. 181. doi: 10.3390/resources8040181.
- Ronaghi, M., Reed, M. and Saghaian, S. (2020) 'The impact of economic factors and governance on greenhouse gas emission', *Environmental Economics and Policy Studies*, 22, pp. 153–172. doi: 10.1007/s10018-019-00250-w.
- Roulston, K. (2018) 'Recruiting participants for a qualitative research study'. Available at: <https://qualpage.com/2018/03/12/recruiting-participants-for-a-qualitative-research-study/comment-page-1/> (Accessed: 02 January 2023).

Roxburgh, C. (2017) Email to Ebiyon Idundun, 9 January.

Rugg, R. (2004) 'Local Government Carbon Management Programme', *IAPSC Conference*, Birmingham, United Kingdom, 7 September. Available at: http://www.iapsc.org.uk/assets/document/R_Rugg.pdf (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

Ruiz-Campillo, X., Castán Broto, V. and Westman, L. (2021) 'Motivations and intended outcomes in local governments' declarations of climate emergency'. *Politics and Governance*, 9 (2). pp. 17-28. doi: 10.17645/pag.v9i2.3755.

Ryan, A. and Hauser, C. (2020) 'Reflecting on the role of academia–private sector partnerships in moving forward with the SDGs', in Georg von Schnurbein (ed.) *Transitioning to Strong Partnerships for the Sustainable Development Goals*. Basel: MDPI, pp. 83-94. doi: 10.3390/books978-3-03897-883-1.

SAGES (2019) *SAGES'19 Global Climate Challenges for a Blue Green Economy: scientific evidence; its relevance; societal solutions*. Available at: <https://www.research-innovation-scotland.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/SAGES-Full.pdf> (Accessed: 04 January 2023).

Saha, A.K., Al-Shaer, H., Dixon, R. and Demirag, I. (2021) 'Determinants of Carbon Emission Disclosures and UN Sustainable Development Goals: The Case of UK Higher Education Institutions', *Australian Accounting Review*, 31(2), pp. 79-107. doi: 10.1111/auar.12324.

Salix Finance (2022) Scotland. Available at: salixfinance.co.uk/loans/scotland-loans (Accessed: 24 November 2022).

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2012) *Research methods for business students*. 6th edition. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P., and Thornhill, A., (2019) 'Research Methods for Business Students' Chapter 4: Understanding research philosophy and approaches to theory development', Researchgate. Net. In book: *Research Methods for Business Students*. Edition: 8, Chapter: 4. Publisher: Pearson Education.

School Leadership Group, School of Science and Sport, University of the West of Scotland (2015) 'Revised Operational Plan', *School of Science and Sports Data Base*. (Accessed: 20 January 2017).

School of Science and Sport, University of the West of Scotland (2016) 'Operational planning Review: March 2016', *School of Science and Sports Data Base*. (Accessed: 20 January 2017).

Scopus (2022) *What is Scopus Preview?* Available at: https://service.elsevier.com/app/answers/detail/a_id/15534/supporthub/scopus/#tips (Accessed: 12 February 2023).

Scott, T. and Mhunpiew, N. (2021) 'Impact of Government Policies and International Students on UK University Economic Stability', *International Education Studies*, 14(5), pp.1-7. doi: 10.5539/ies.v14n5p1.

Scottish Energy Statistics Hub (2021a) *Proportion of electricity generation by fuel*. Available at: <https://scotland.shinyapps.io/sg-energy/?Section=RenLowCarbon&Subsection=RenElec&Chart=ElecGen> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

Scottish Energy Statistics Hub (2021b) *Share of renewable energy in gross final consumption Scotland, 2009 – 2019*. Available at: <https://scotland.shinyapps.io/sg-energy/?Section=WholeSystem&Chart=RenEnTgt> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

Scottish Energy Statistics Hub (2021c) *District heat networks Scotland, 2018*. Available at: <https://scotland.shinyapps.io/sg-scottish-energy-statistics/?Section=LocalEnergy&Chart=DistrictHeat> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

Scottish Government (2018a) *Public bodies in Scotland: guide*. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/public-bodies-in-scotland-guide/> (Accessed: 16 April 2023).

Scottish Government (2018b) *Publication – FactSheet: Energy Efficient Scotland user guide: energy efficiency measures*. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/energy-efficient-scotland-user-guide-energy-efficiency-measures/> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

- Scottish Government (2020a) *Scottish Budget 2020-21*. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/news/scottish-budget-2020-21/> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).
- Scottish Government (2020b) *Scottish greenhouse gas emissions 2018*. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-greenhouse-gas-emissions-2018/pages/2/> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).
- Scottish Government (2021a) *Scottish Greenhouse Gas statistics: 1990-2019*. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-greenhouse-gas-statistics-1990-2019/documents/> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).
- Scottish Government (2021b) *Annual Energy Statement & Quarterly Statistics Bulletin - December 2021*. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/quarterly-energy-statistics-bulletins/> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).
- Scottish Government (2021c) *Housing to 2040*. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/housing-2040-2/> (Accessed: 03 January 2023).
- Scottish Government (2022) *Scottish Greenhouse Gas Statistics 2020*. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-greenhouse-gas-statistics-2020/> (Accessed: 12 December 2022).
- Seyis, S. (2020) 'Mixed method review for integrating building information modeling and life-cycle assessments', *Building and Environment*, 173, p.106703. doi: 10.1016/j.buildenv.2020.106703.
- Shale-Hester, T. (2022) *UK's 2030 petrol and diesel ban: what is it and which cars are affected? New conventional petrol and diesel cars and vans will be banned from sale in the UK from 2030 - here's everything you need to know*. Available at: <https://www.autoexpress.co.uk/news/108960/uks-2030-petrol-and-diesel-ban-what-it-and-which-cars-are-affected> (Accessed: 08 January 2023).
- Shahriar, S., Al-Ali, A.R., Osman, A.H., Dhou, S. and Nijim, M. (2020) 'Machine learning approaches for EV charging behavior: A review', *IEEE Access*, 8, pp.168980-168993. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3023388.

Shine, K.P., Fuglestedt, J.S., Hailemariam, K. and Stuber, N. (2005) 'Alternatives to the Global Warming Potential for Comparing Climate Impacts of Emissions of Greenhouse Gases', *Climatic Change*, 38(3), pp. 281-302. doi: 10.1007/s10584-005-1146-9.

Singh, A.P., Agarwal, A.K., Agarwal, R.A., Dhar, A. and Shukla, M.K. (2018). 'Introduction of alternative fuels', in Singh A., Agarwal R., Agarwal A., Dhar A. and Shukla M. (eds.) *Prospects of Alternative Transportation Fuels*. Singapore: Springer (Energy, Environment, and Sustainability book series), p. 3-6. doi: 10.1007/978-981-10-7518-6_1.

Soeder, D.J. (2021). 'Fossil Fuels and Climate Change', in *Fracking and the Environment*. Cham: Springer, pp. 158-185. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-59121-2_9.

Sönnichsen, N. (2022) *Average monthly gas prices in Great Britain 2015-2022*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1174560/average-monthly-gas-prices-uk/> (Accessed: 08 January 2023).

Sullivan, R. and Goulson, A. (2013) 'Ten years of corporate action on climate change: What do we have to show for it?', *Energy Policy*, 60, pp. 733-740. doi: [10.1016/j.enpol.2013.05.025](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2013.05.025).

Sustainable Scotland Network (no date) *Reports Public Bodies Climate Change Duties*. Available at: <https://sustainableScotlandNetwork.org/reports> (Accessed: 20 December 2023).

Sustainable Scotland Network (2019) *Public Bodies Climate Change Reporting 2017/18 Analysis Report*. Available at: <https://sustainableScotlandNetwork.org/reports> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

Sustainable Scotland Network (2020) *Public Bodies Climate Change Reporting 2018/19 Analysis Report*. Available at: <https://sustainableScotlandNetwork.org/reports> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

Swain, H. (2016) *The business of running a university*. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/higher-education-network/2016/may/14/the-business-of-running-a-university> (Accessed: 13 January 2023).

Synge, M. (2021) 'Regulation of universities as charities: One step forward, two steps back', *Legal Studies*, 41(2), pp. 214-233. doi: 10.1017/lst.2020.39.

Tasci, G. (2021) 'The impact of COVID-19 on Higher Education: Rethinking internationalization behind the iceberg COVID-19 and Higher Education', *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction (special issue)*, 13(1), pp. 522–536. Available at: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1285811> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

The Climate Change (Duties of Public Bodies: Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Order 2015, SSI 2015/347. Available at: <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ssi/2015/347/contents/made> (Accessed: 29 January 2022).

The Greenhouse Gas Emissions Trading Scheme Auctioning Regulations 2021, No. 484. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2021/484/regulation/36> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

The Guardian News (2020) 'UWS Lanarkshire has ditched traditional lecture halls in favour of an open, technology-rich environment', The Guardian News Online, 10 April. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/education/2019/apr/10/sustainable-buildings-that-inspire-award-winner-and-runners-up> (Accessed: 21 December 2022).

Tingey, M., and Webb, J. (2020) *Net zero localities: ambition & value in UK local authority investment*. Energy Revolution Research Centre. Strathclyde: University of Strathclyde Publishing. ISBN 978-1-909522-59-6.

Tiseo, I. (2022a) *Global CO2 emissions 1970-2020, by sector*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/276480/world-carbon-dioxide-emissions-by-sector/> (Accessed: 02 January 2023).

Tiseo, I. (2022b) *Global greenhouse gas emissions shares 2018, by sub sector*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1167298/share-ghg-emissions-by-sub-sector-sector-globally/> (Accessed: 02 January 2023).

Transport Scotland (2014) *Scottish Transport Statistics No 32 2013 Edition*. Available at: <https://www.transport.gov.scot/publication/scottish-transport-statistics-no-32-2013-edition/> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

Tuesta, Y.N., Soler, C.C. and Feliu, V.R. (2021) 'Carbon management accounting and financial performance: Evidence from the European Union emission trading system', *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(2), pp. 1270–1282. doi: 10.1002/bse.2683.

Uitto, J.I., Puri, J. and van den Berg, R.D. (2017) 'Evaluating Climate Change Action for Sustainable Development: Introduction', in Uitto, J.I., Puri, J. and van den Berg, R.D. (eds.) *Evaluating Climate Change Action for Sustainable Development*. Cham: Springer, pp. 1-12. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-43702-6_1.

Ukcop26.org (2021) COP26; *The Glasgow Climate Pact*. Available at: <https://ukcop26.org/the-glasgow-climate-pact/>. (Accessed 12 December 2022).

United Kingdom Government (2015) *Policy paper: 2010 to 2015 government policy: greenhouse gas emissions*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/2010-to-2015-government-policy-greenhouse-gas-emissions/2010-to-2015-government-policy-greenhouse-gas-emissions> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

United Kingdom Government (2021) *UK enshrines new target in law to slash emissions by 78% by 2035* [Press release]. 20 April. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/uk-enshrines-new-target-in-law-to-slash-emissions-by-78-by-2035> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

United Kingdom Government (2023) *Research and analysis - UK greenhouse gas emissions: other technical reports. Supplementary technical reports relating to greenhouse gas emissions*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-greenhouse-gas-emissions-explanatory-notes> (Accessed: 20 June 2023).

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (no date) *The Doha Amendment*. Available at: <https://unfccc.int/process/the-kyoto-protocol/the-doha-amendment> (Accessed: 17 June 2023).

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (2016) *Non-State Actors Partner with Governments to Boost Climate Action* [Announcement]. 18 November. Available at: <https://newsroom.unfccc.int/news/non-state-actors-partner-with-governments-to-boost-climate-action> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (2017) *COP23 Kicks Off with Strong Calls to Hold to Paris Agreement Path* [Article]. 06 November. Available: <https://unfccc.int/news/cop23-kicks-off-with-strong-calls-to-hold-to-paris-agreement-path> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (2018) *UN Climate Change COP24 Partners Demonstrate Value of Collaborative Climate Action* [Article]. 17 December. Available at: <https://unfccc.int/news/un-climate-change-cop24-partners-demonstrate-value-of-collaborative-climate-action> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (2019) *At COP25, a Call to Turn the Tide on Deforestation* [Article]. 12 December. Available at: <https://unfccc.int/news/at-cop25-a-call-to-turn-the-tide-on-deforestation> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (2021a) *What is the Kyoto Protocol?*. Available at: https://unfccc.int/kyoto_protocol (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (2021b) *History Of The Convention / UNFCCC*. Available at: <https://unfccc.int/process/the-convention/history-of-the-convention#eq-2> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (2021c) *COP26 Reaches Consensus on Key Actions to Address Climate Change* [Press Release]. 13 November. Available at: <https://unfccc.int/news/cop26-reaches-consensus-on-key-actions-to-address-climate-change> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

United States Environmental Protection Agency (2022) *Understanding Global Warming Potential*. Available at: <https://www.epa.gov/ghgemissions/understanding-global-warming-potentials> (Accessed; 14 November 2022).

University of Toronto Committee on the Environment, Climate Change, and Sustainability (2020) *Addressing University of Toronto's Business-Related Scope 3 Air Travel Emissions*. Available at: https://sustainability.utoronto.ca/wp-content/uploads/CECCS_Nov-2020_Business-Air-Travel-Report.pdf (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

University of the West of Scotland (2010) *Climate Change Action Plan 2010 - 2014*. Available at: https://www.eauc.org.uk/climate_change_action_plans_ccaps (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

University of the West of Scotland (2014) *UWS Corporate Strategy 2014/20*. Available at: https://www.uws.ac.uk/media/3337/uws_corporate-strategy2014-2020.pdf (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

University of the West of Scotland (2016) *UWS Sustainability Plan 2016 to 2020*. Available at: <https://www.uws.ac.uk/about-uws/uws-commitments/sustainability/> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

University of the West of Scotland (2018) *UWS Sustainability Annual Report 2016/17*. Available at: <https://www.uws.ac.uk/media/4501/uws-sustainability-annual-report-2016-17.pdf> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

University of the West of Scotland (2019) *UWS Sustainability Annual Report 2017/18*. Available at: <https://www.uws.ac.uk/media/5112/annual-report-v3.pdf> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

University of the West of Scotland (2020) *UWS Delivering Sustainability 2018/19*. Available at: <https://www.uws.ac.uk/media/5966/sustainability-annual-report-18-19-webfinal.pdf> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

University of the West of Scotland (2021) *UWS Delivering Sustainability 2019-20*. Available at: <https://www.uws.ac.uk/about-uws/uws-commitments/sustainability/> (Accessed: 2 December 2023).

Universities UK (no date) *Higher education in numbers*. Available at: <https://www.universitiesuk.ac.uk/facts-and-stats/Pages/higher-education-data.aspx> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

Valls-Val, K. and Bovea, M.D. (2021) 'Carbon footprint in Higher Education Institutions: a literature review and prospects for future research', *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, 23(9), pp.2523-2542. doi: 10.1007/s10098-021-02180-2.

- Valls-Val, K. and Bovea, M.D. (2022) ‘Carbon footprint assessment tool for universities: CO2UNV’, *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 29, pp.791-804. doi: 10.1016/j.spc.2021.11.020.
- Vasileiou, K., Barnett, J., Thorpe, S. and Young, T. (2018) ‘Characterising and justifying sample size sufficiency in interview-based studies: systematic analysis of qualitative health research over a 15-year period’, *BMC Med Res Methodol*, 18(1), pp. 1-18. doi: 10.1186/s12874-018-0594-7.
- Vickerman, R. (2021) ‘Will Covid-19 put the public back in public transport? A UK perspective’, *Transport Policy*, 103, pp.95-102. doi: 10.1016/j.tranpol.2021.01.005.
- Villena, V.H. and Dhanorkar, S. (2020) ‘How institutional pressures and managerial incentives elicit carbon transparency in global supply chains’, *Journal Operational Management*, 66(6), pp. 697–734. doi: 10.1002/joom.1088.
- Waas, T., Hugé, J., Ceulemans, K., Lambrechts, W., Vandenabeele, J., Lozano, R. and Wright, T. (2012) *Sustainable Higher Education – Understanding and Moving Forward*. Brussels: Flemish Government – Environment, Nature and Energy Department.
- Wadanambi, R.T., Wandana, L.S., Chathumini, K.K.G.L., Dassanayake, N.P., Preethika, D.D.P. and Arachchige, U.S. (2020) ‘The effects of industrialization on climate change’, *Journal of Research Technology and Engineering*, 1(4), pp. 86–94.
- Wade, J. (2021) *Energy: Public sector has the power to drive the net-zero transition*. Available at: <https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/energy-public-sector-has-the-power-to-drive-the-net-zero-transition/104014/> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).
- Warren, K. (2020) *Qualitative vs Quantitative Research 101: A Plain-Language Explanation (With Examples)*. Available at: <https://gradcoach.com/qualitative-vs-quantitative-research/> (Accessed: 25 February 2023).
- Welsh Government (2021) *How Wales is tackling the climate emergency with a framework of targets and carbon budgets*. Climate change targets and carbon budgets. Available at: <https://gov.wales/climate-change-targets-and-carbon-budgets> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

Whitmarsh, L., Poortinga, W. and Capstick, S. (2021) 'Behaviour change to address climate change', *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 42, pp.76-81. doi: 10.1016/j.copsyc.2021.04.002.

Wiedmann, T. and Minx, J. (2008) 'A Definition of Carbon Footprint', in Pertsova, C.C. (eds.), *Ecological Economics Research Trends*. New York: Nova Science Publishers, 2, p. 1-11.

Wiedmann, T., Wood, R., Minx, J.C., Lenzen, M., Guan, D. and Harris, R. (2010) 'A Carbon Footprint Time Series of the UK – Results from a Multi-Region Input–Output Model', *Economic Systems Research*, 22(1), pp. 19-42. doi: 10.1080/09535311003612591.

Woiceshyn, J. and Daellenbach, U. (2018) 'Evaluating inductive vs deductive research in management studies: Implications for authors, editors, and reviewers', *Qualitative Research in Organizations and Management*, 13(2), pp. 183-195. doi: 10.1108/QROM-06-2017-1538.

Woo E-J. and Kang E. (2020) 'Environmental Issues As an Indispensable Aspect of Sustainable Leadership', *Sustainability*, 12(17), 7014. doi: 10.3390/su12177014.

World Health Organization (2014) *WHO calls for stronger action on climate-related health risks*. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news/item/27-08-2014-who-calls-for-stronger-action-on-climate-related-health-risks> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

World Resources Institute and World Business Council for Sustainable Development (2011) *Greenhouse Gas Protocol Corporate Value Chain (Scope 3) Accounting and Reporting Standard*. Available at: <http://www.ghgprotocol.org/standards/scope-3-standard> (Accessed: 29 January 2023).

Wright, L.A., Kemp, S. and Williams, I. (2011) 'Carbon footprinting': towards a universally accepted definition', *Carbon management*, 2(1), pp. 61-72. doi: 10.4155/cmt.10.39.

Wynes, S., Donner, S. D., Tannason, S. and Nabors, N. (2019) 'Academic air travel has a limited influence on professional success', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 226, pp. 959-967. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.109.

- Yaqoot, M., Diwan, P. and Kandpal, T.C. (2016) 'Review of barriers to the dissemination of decentralized renewable energy systems', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 58, pp. 477-490. doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2015.12.224.
- Yi, Y.K. and Kang, B. (2020) 'Integrating a wind turbine into a parking pavilion for generating electricity', *Journal of Building Engineering*, 32. doi: 10.1016/j.jobbe.2020.101471.
- Yu, Y. and Moskal, M. (2019) 'Missing intercultural engagements in the university experiences of Chinese international students in the UK', *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 49(4), pp. 654-671. doi: 10.1080/03057925.2018.1448259.
- Zhang, Y., Akkurt, N., Yuan, J., Xiao, Z., Wang, Q. and Gang, W. (2020) 'Study on model uncertainty of water source heat pump and impact on decision making', *Energy and Buildings*, 216. doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2020.109950.
- Zvezdov, D., and Hack, S. (2016) 'Carbon footprinting of large product portfolios. Extending the use of Enterprise Resource Planning systems to carbon information management', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 135, pp. 1267-1275. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.06.070.

LIST OF APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Semi-structured interview Guide.

Appendix 2: Ethics Approval Confirmation.

Appendix 3: Participant information sheet.

Appendix 4: Mini Travel Survey for SoSS Staff Commute.

Appendix 5: Calculation Breakdown for SoSS Staff Commute Activity Data and Emissions.

Appendix 6: SoSS Business Travel – Air.

Appendix 7: SoSS Business Travel – Rail.

Appendix 8: Calculation Breakdown for Business Travel - Hire of UWS Vehicle Fleet Emissions.

Appendix 9: Calculation Breakdown for SoSS Business Travel - Air Emissions.

Appendix 10: UWS Vehicle Usage: SA13JXD.

Appendix 11: UWS Vehicle Usage: TN07LPW.

Appendix 12: UWS Vehicle Usage: SH54XSP.

Appendix 13: UWS Vehicle Usage: ST07VPM.

Appendix 14: Sample consent Form.

Appendix 15: Conference poster presented at the ETP annual conference 2018

Appendix 16: Abstract submitted the SAGES'19 conference 2019

Appendix 17: Conference poster presented at the SAGES'19 conference 2019

Appendix 18: Published manuscript 'Carbon Management in UK Higher Education Institutions: An Overview'

Appendix 1: Semi-structured interview Guide

Interview Guide - Outline Interview Questions

- 1a. Please explain your responsibility for carbon reduction within your organisation
- 1b. Are you familiar with the issues associated with fossil fuel consumption as it affects your organisation?
2. In your opinion what best describes your organisations approach to fossil fuel reduction?
3. Are you aware of the global divestment campaign? **Probe** - is your organisation involved?
- 4a. Can you tell me the emission sources that account for your organisations carbon footprint
- 4b. How the organisational carbon footprint is calculated?
- 5a. Can you tell me to what extent your organisation relies on fossil fuels? **Probe** - what percentage fossil fuels contribute to overall carbon emissions. **Further Probe** - reasons why?
- 6a. Does your organisation have carbon reduction targets/initiatives.
- 6b. What are the areas of focus for emission reduction? **Probe** – is there a specific travel emission reduction target(s)?
- 7a. Do the targets/initiatives include behavioural and technological change.
- 7b. Are these included in organisational strategies?
8. In terms of staff engagement with respect to carbon reduction within your organisation, what does this look like?
- 9a. In your opinion is your organisation doing enough to achieve its carbon reduction targets (including reducing travel emissions).
- 9b. What can be done to reduce or eliminate reliance on fossil fuels?
- 10a. What are the barriers facing your organisation in reducing travel emissions.
- 10b. What are the barriers to switching from fossil fuels to clean and/or renewable technology?
11. What will you say are the key agendas and technical themes for overall carbon reduction and travel emissions reduction within your organisation?

Appendix 2: Ethics Approval confirmation

Ethics application

 1 attachments (17 KB)

Guidelines for reports to the school of science and sport ethics committee.docx;

Dear Mr Idundun,

Further to your application to the school ethics committee for the study entitled; "Carbon Efficiency In The Scottish Public Sector", I have received the reviewer's comments on your resubmission and the committee is now able to **approve** your study. Your approval number is **3-5-16-001**. Please note that it is a condition of approval that the committee receive a report on the work either at its conclusion or twelve months after approval (whichever is sooner). I have attached a copy of the guidelines for these reports to this email.

Good luck with your research,

GWB

Dr Gary Boyd

Please consider the environment and think before you print University of the West of Scotland is a registered Scottish charity. Charity number SC002520. Legal disclaimer The information transmitted is the property of University of the West of Scotland and intended only for the person or entity to which it is addressed and may contain confidential and/or privileged material. Statements and opinions expressed in this e-mail may not represent those of the University. Any review, retransmission, dissemination and other use of, or taking of any action in reliance upon, this information by persons or entities other than the intended recipient is prohibited. If you received this in error, please contact the sender immediately and delete the material from any computer.

Appendix 3: Participant Information Sheet

Participants Information Sheet - Carbon Efficiency in The Scottish Public Sector

Invitation Paragraph

Before you decide to take part in this research it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. The proposed research study has been reviewed and approved by the School of Science & Sports Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland.

What is the purpose of the study?

The research question for the study is "To what extent is Scotland's public sector reliant on fossil fuels and why?" The aims of the planned research are to determine the extent to which public sector organisations are reliant on fossil fuel energy, reasons for reliance on fossil fuel energy, the barriers to total reliance on clean and renewable energy; to develop sensible steps that can be taken to reduce and where possible eliminate the reliance on fossil fuel energy; and to develop steps to help the School of Science and Sports, University of the west of the Scotland, improve its carbon footprint and be more efficient.

The main research objectives addressing the aims and the research question are:

1. To review available literature on the Scottish public sector's reliance on fossil fuels.
2. To undertake a semi-structured interview with sector professionals
3. To undertake a review of the mandatory carbon reporting reports of the chosen LGA's and universities
4. To undertake a case study on the School of Science and Sports, University of the West of Scotland to develop a baseline carbon footprint

Do I have to take part?

Your participation is voluntary, and you will not be paid for participating. I would like you to consent to participate in this study as I believe that you can make an important contribution to the research. If you do not wish to participate you do not have to do anything in response to this request. I am asking you to take part in the research because you are a sustainability/environmental staff within a Local Authority or University in Scotland and I believe you can provide important information to me that will contribute towards evaluating the research I am undertaking. Please do contact me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information (see correspondence information). Take time to decide whether you wish to take part, there is a two-week response window from the date you receive this information.

What will I do if I take part?

Participation will involve being interviewed only and interviews will have a 30 to 90-minute duration. Should the need arise further contact may be made to obtain further information, however this can be done by other means such as email. Notes will be written during the interview and the interview audio taped. If you are happy to participate please read this information sheet and a consent form to be signed by you will be made available prior to commencing the interview.

What questions will I be asked during the interview?

Research questions will be asked based on the following areas; however other questions may arise throughout the course of the interview: carbon management strategies and policies, carbon footprints and emissions calculations, carbon reduction initiatives and

Appendix 4: Mini Travel Survey for SoSS Staff Commute

Name	Base Campus	Car	Train	Bus	Cycle	Foot	
Staff 1	Hamilton	X					
Staff 2	Hamilton	X					
Staff 3	Paisley				X		
Staff 4	Paisley	X					
Staff 5	Paisley	X					
Staff 6	Paisley	X					
Staff 7	Paisley	X					
Staff 8	Paisley	X					
Staff 9	Paisley					X	
Staff 10	Paisley	X					
Staff 11	Paisley		X				
Staff 12	Hamilton	X					
Staff 13	Hamilton	X					
Staff 14	Paisley				X		
Staff 15	Paisley	X					
Staff 16	Paisley	X					
Staff 17	Hamilton		X				
Staff 18	Paisley		X				
Staff 19	Paisley	X					
Staff 20	Paisley					X	
Staff 21	Hamilton	X					
Staff 22	Paisley	X					
Staff 23	Hamilton	X					
Staff 24	Hamilton	X					
Staff 25	Paisley	X					
Staff 26	Paisley	X					
Staff 27	Paisley					X	
Staff 28	Paisley	X					
Staff 29	Hamilton		X				
Staff 30	Paisley	X					
Staff 31	Paisley		X				
Staff 32	Hamilton		X				
Staff 33	Paisley	X					
Staff 34	Hamilton	X					
Staff 35	Hamilton	X					
Staff 36	Paisley	X					
Staff 37	Hamilton	X					
Staff 38	Paisley	X					
Staff 39	Hamilton	X					
Staff 40	Hamilton	X					
Staff 41	Paisley	X					
Staff 42	Hamilton	X					
Staff 43	Hamilton			X			
Staff 44	Paisley	X					
Staff 45	Paisley		X				
Staff 46	Paisley		X				
Staff 47	Paisley	X					
Staff 48	Hamilton	X					
Staff 49	Hamilton	X					
Staff 50	Paisley	X					
Staff 51	Paisley	X					
Staff 52	Paisley	X					
Staff 53	Paisley	X					
Staff 54	Paisley		X				
Staff 55	Paisley	X					
Staff 56	Paisley		X				
Staff 57	Paisley		X				
	Total	40	11	1	2	3	Total
	Percentage	70.18	19.298	1.754	3.5088	5.2632	100

Appendix 5: Calculation Breakdown for SoSS Staff Commute Activity Data and Emissions

Step 1: Calculate the Scottish mileage in this category (multiply mileage per person by the population)

Mileage per person – commute = 2111 miles/year (Statistical Bulletin - National Travel Survey 2011/2012: Scotland Results: Average distance travelled per person per year by purpose and main mode – commuting/business) (Transport Scotland, 2014)

Scottish Population Size = 5,373,000 (mid 2015 data used) (Office for National Statistics (ONS), 2016b)

Total Scottish Commute Mileage/Year = 2111 X 5373000 = 11342403000 miles

Step 2:

Divide total mileage by the number of people in employment (in Scotland)

Number of people in employment = 2,604,000 (Dec to Feb 2016 data used) (ONS, 2016c)

Individual average commute mileage per person in employment in Scotland/year = 11342403000/2604000 = 4356 miles/year

Step 3:

Estimate mileage for SoSS (multiply individual mileage of people in employment by number of staff)

Number of SoSS Staff = 110

SoSS Mileage = 4356 X 110 = 479160 miles = 771133 km

Step 4:

Apply an average carbon emissions factor for a unit of mileage (km) based on split between car, bus and train. Based on the mini travel survey carried out the following splits were made: Car – 70%, Bus – 2%, Train – 19%, Bicycle – 4% and Foot – 5%.

Car

Activity Data – 70% of total SoSS staff commute mileage (771133 km) = 539793 km

Average Car Conversion (emissions) factor = 0.18695

Emissions = 539793 X 0.18695 = **100,914 kgCO₂e**

Bus

Activity Data – 2% of total SoSS staff commute mileage (771133 km) = 15423 km

Average Local Bus Conversion (emissions) factor = 0.10172

Emissions = 15423 X 0.10172 = **1,569 kgCO₂e**

Train

Activity Data – 19% of total SoSS staff commute mileage (771133km) = 146515km

National Rail Conversion (emissions) factor = 0.04885

Emissions = 146515 X 0.04885 = **7,157kgCO₂e**

Appendix 6: SoSS Business Travel – Air

Booking Date	Booking Type	Route	Adults	Haul	Distance (Miles)
18/08/2016 15:08	Flight	Glasgow to Barcelona	1	Short	1048.3
18/08/2016 15:08	Flight	Hotel	1	Short	1048.3
22/08/2016 14:47	Flight	Edinburgh to Prague - Vaclav Havel Prague (PRG)	1	Short	832
22/08/2016 14:47	Flight	Prague - Vaclav Havel Prague (PRG)	1	Short	832
30/08/2016 00:00	Flight	Glasgow to Prague	1	Short	869.3
30/08/2016 00:00	Flight	Prague to Glasgow	1	Short	869.3
30/08/2016 15:31	Flight	Glasgow to Houston	1	Long	5442.7
30/08/2016 15:31	Flight	Houston to Glasgow	1	Long	5442.7
12/09/2016 10:57	Flight	London Gatwick (LGW) - Glasgow	1	Domestic	369.7
31/10/2016 11:54	Flight	London Gatwick (LGW) - Glasgow International (GLA)	1	Domestic	369.7
14/09/2016 16:09	Flight	Edinburgh to Singapore - Changi International (SIN)	1	Long	6642
14/09/2016 16:09	Flight	Singapore to Seoul - Incheon International (ICN)	1	International	2873.9
14/09/2016 16:09	Flight	Seoul - Incheon International (ICN) to Singapore	1	International	2873.9
15/09/2016 12:02	Flight	Singapore - Changi International (SIN) to Edinburgh (EDI)	1	Long	6642
19/09/2016 14:36	Flight	Glasgow International (GLA) - London	1	Domestic	369.7
19/09/2016 14:36	Flight	London Gatwick (LGW) - Glasgow International (GLA)	1	Domestic	369.7
28/09/2016 16:31	Flight	Glasgow International (GLA) Accra - Kotoka (ACC)	2	Long	7022.8
28/09/2016 16:31	Flight	Kotoka (ACC) - Glasgow International (GLA) Accra	2	Long	7022.8
28/09/2016 16:31	Flight	Edinburgh (EDI) - Luton	1	Domestic	307
28/09/2016 16:31	Flight	Luton - Edinburgh (EDI)	1	Domestic	307
30/09/2016 16:02	Flight	Glasgow International (GLA) - London	1	Domestic	369.7
30/09/2016 16:02	Flight	London Gatwick (LGW) - Glasgow International (GLA)	1	Domestic	369.7
28/10/2016 11:27	Flight	Edinburgh to Bristol	1	Domestic	318.9
28/10/2016 11:27	Flight	Bristol to Edinburgh	1	Domestic	318.9
31/10/2016 10:23	Flight	London Gatwick (LGW) - Glasgow	1	Domestic	369.7
31/10/2016 10:23	Flight	Glasgow - London Gatwick (LGW)	1	Domestic	369.7
02/11/2016 09:13	Flight	Glasgow to Bristol	1	Domestic	318.2
02/11/2016 09:13	Flight	Bristol to Glasgow	1	Domestic	318.2
02/11/2016 11:40	Flight	Glasgow to London	1	Domestic	369.7
02/11/2016 11:40	Flight	London to Glasgow	1	Domestic	369.7

Appendix 7: SoSS Business Travel – Rail

Date/Time	Booking Type	Route	Adults	Distance (km)
05/08/2016 11:31	Rail	Paisley to Glasgow	1	11
05/08/2016 11:38	Rail	Paisley to Glasgow	1	11
05/08/2016 11:41	Rail	Paisley to Glasgow	1	11
23/08/2016 14:23	Rail	Glasgow to Liverpool	1	311
06/09/2016 16:11	Rail	Glasgow to Edinburgh	1	76
08/09/2016 10:25	Rail	Chichester - Paisley	1	701
19/09/2016 16:37	Rail	Gatwick Airport - London	1	40
30/09/2016 10:27	Rail	Glasgow to Leeds	1	345
07/10/2016 15:06	Rail	Glasgow Central	1	580
11/10/2016 13:43	Rail	Glasgow to Manchester	1	314
11/10/2016 13:48	Rail	Glasgow to Manchester	1	314
12/10/2016 13:16	Rail	Glasgow to Liverpool	1	311
13/10/2016 16:31	Rail	Glasgow to London	1	580
19/10/2016 10:53	Rail	Glasgow to London	1	580
25/10/2016 14:47	Rail	Glasgow to London	1	580
27/10/2016 09:25	Rail	Paisley to Glasgow	1	11
28/10/2016 11:57	Rail	Bristol Airport to Bristol	1	13
28/10/2016 13:26	Rail	Liverpool to Glasgow	1	324
02/11/2016 11:40	Rail	Gatwick to London	1	40
11/11/2016 13:25	Rail	Glasgow to Liverpool	1	311
14/11/2016 14:12	Rail	Glasgow to London	1	580
				6044

Appendix 8: Calculation Breakdown for Business Travel - Hire of UWS Vehicle Fleet Emissions

Ford Focus 1.6 TDCI

Activity Data – Total 2015/16 mileage = 2571miles

Conversion (emissions) factor using small car by car size = 0.23618

Therefore, carbon emissions = 2571 X 0.223618 = **607.22kgCO_{2e}**

VW Transporter 1.8 TDCI

Activity Data – Total 2015/16 mileage = 710miles

Conversion (emissions) factor using medium car by car size = 0.28551

Therefore, carbon emissions = 710 X 0.28551 = **202.71kgCO_{2e}**

Ford Mondeo 2.0 TDCI

Activity Data – Total 2015/16 mileage = 2208miles

Conversion (emissions) factor using medium car by car size = 0.28551

Therefore, carbon emissions = 2208 X 0.28551 = **630.41kgCO_{2e}**

Ford Transit (Minibus) 2.4TDCI

Activity Data – Total 2015/16 mileage = 3343miles

Conversion (emissions) factor using large car by car size = 0.36166

Therefore, carbon emissions = 3343 X 0.36166 = **1209.03kgCO_{2e}**

Total emissions from hire of the UWS vehicle fleet is **607.222kgCO_{2e} + 202.71kgCO_{2e} + 630.41kgCO_{2e} + 1209.03kgCO_{2e} = 2649.37kgCO_{2e}.**

Appendix 9: Calculation Breakdown for SoSS Business Travel - Air Emissions

Airport distances were obtained from the ICAO Carbon Emissions Calculator (ICAO, 2016).

Domestic flights

Activity Data - Distance travelled (4-month period) = 8982km (5581.2miles)

Conversion (emissions) factor using average passenger class with RF = 0.27867

Therefore, carbon emissions = $8982 \times 0.27867 = 2503\text{kgCO}_2\text{e}$

Short haul flights

Activity Data - Distance travelled (4-month period) = 8850km (5499.1miles)

Conversion (emissions) factor using economy class with RF = 0.16508

Therefore, carbon emissions = $8850 \times 0.16508 = 1461\text{kgCO}_2\text{e}$

Long haul flights

Activity Data - Distance travelled (4-month period) = 61501km (38215miles)

Conversion (emissions) factor using business class with RF = 0.42565

Therefore, carbon emissions = $61501 \times 0.42565 = 26178\text{kgCO}_2\text{e}$

International flights

Activity Data - Distance travelled (4-month period) = 9250km (5747.7miles)

Conversion (emissions) factor using business class with RF = 0.39764

Therefore, carbon emissions = $9250 \times 0.39764 = 3678\text{kgCO}_2\text{e}$

Total emissions from business travel – air = $2503\text{kgCO}_2\text{e} + 1461\text{ kgCO}_2\text{e} + 26178\text{ kgCO}_2\text{e} + 3678\text{ kgCO}_2\text{e} = 33820\text{ kgCO}_2\text{e}$ for the 4-month period.

To get an annual equivalent of emissions associated with business travel - air, **33820 kgCO₂e** for the 4-month period is multiplied by 3 to give **101460kgCO₂e** per annum.

Appendix 10: UWS Vehicle Usage: SA13JXD

DATE	MILEAGE AT START	MILEAGE AT FINISH	TOTAL MILEAGE	COST AT 1-180 MILES	COST AT + 180 MILES	SCHOOL/DEPT
07-Aug-15	32229	32316	87	£39.15	£0.00	Science & Sport
18-Sep-15	34924	35120	196	£81.00	£4.00	Science & Sport
25-Sep-15	35186	35205	19	£8.55	£0.00	Science & Sport
07-Oct-15	35508	35552	44	£19.80	£0.00	Science & Sport
18-Nov-15	36893	36935	42	£18.90	£0.00	Science & Sport
25-Nov-15	37151	37188	37	£16.65	£0.00	Science & Sport
18-Jan-16	22483	22659	176	£79.20	£0.00	Science & Sport
29-Jan-16	23424	23448	24	£10.80	£0.00	Science & Sport
02-Feb-16	23448	23573	125	£56.25	£0.00	Science & Sport
04-Feb-16	23615	23662	47	£21.15	£0.00	Science & Sport
05-Feb-16	23680	23847	167	£75.15	£0.00	Science & Sport
12-Feb-16	24123	24287	164	£73.80	£0.00	Science & Sport
20-Feb-16	24878	25066	188	£81.00	£2.00	Science & Sport
24-Feb-16	25213	25301	88	£39.60	£0.00	Science & Sport
01-Mar-16	25621	25627	6	£2.70	£0.00	Science & Sport
01-Mar-16	25627	25653	26	£11.70	£0.00	Science & Sport
04-Mar-16	25653	25722	69	£31.05	£0.00	Science & Sport
12-May-16	26276	26480	204	£81.00	£6.00	Science & Sport
18-Sep-16	27557	28041	484	£81.00	£76.00	Science & Sport
05-Jul-16	28511	28558	47	£21.15	£0.00	Science & Sport
12-Jul-16	28583	28633	50	£22.50	£0.00	Science & Sport
14-Jul-16	28638	28687	49	£22.05	£0.00	Science & Sport
26-Jul-16	29147	29379	232	£81.00	£13.00	Science & Sport
Total			2571.00	£975.15	£101.00	

Appendix 11: UWS Vehicle Usage: TN07LPW

DATE	MILEAGE AT START	MILEAGE AT FINISH	TOTAL MILEAGE	COST AT 1-180 MILES	COST AT + 180 MILES	SCHOOL /DEPT
17-Aug-15	88405	88531	126	£56.70	£0.00	SSS
26-Aug-15	88541	88636	95	£42.75	£0.00	SSS
20-Oct-15	90712	90770	58	£26.10	£0.00	SSS
29-Oct-15	91174	91184	10	£4.50	£0.00	SSS
11-Dec-15	92701	92749	48	£21.60	£0.00	SSS
19-Jan-16	92848	93030	182	£81.00	£0.50	SSS
31-Mar-16	94219	94269	50	£22.50	£0.00	SSS
11-Apr-16	94384	94385	1	£0.45	£0.00	SSS
03-May-16	94570	94595	25	£11.25	£0.00	SSS
21-Jun-16	95143	95193	50	£22.50	£0.00	SSS
27-Jul-16	96111	96176	65	£29.25	£0.00	SSS
Total			710.00	£318.60	£0.50	SSS

Appendix 12: UWS Vehicle Usage: SH54XSP

DATE	MILEAGE AT START	MILEAGE AT FINISH	TOTAL MILEAGE	COST AT 1-180 MILES	COST AT + 180 MILES	SCHOOL/DEPT
06-Aug-15	125322	125423	101	45.45	0.00	Science & Sport
01-Sep-15	126025	126056	31	13.95	0.00	Science & Sport
01-Sep-15	126056	126082	26	11.7	0.00	Science & Sport
03-Sep-15	126082	126208	126	56.7	0.00	Science & Sport
23-Sep-15	126865	126931	66	29.70	0.00	Science & Sport
29-Sep-15	127134	127238	104	46.80	0.00	Science & Sport
05-Oct-15	127347	127526	179	80.55	0.00	Science & Sport
14-Oct-15	127806	127905	99	44.55	0.00	Science & Sport
20-Oct-15	127987	128092	105	47.25	0.00	Science & Sport
28-Oct-15	128308	128378	70	31.50	0.00	Science & Sport
05-Nov-15	128536	128689	153	68.85	0.00	Science & Sport
18-Nov-15	128798	128901	103	46.35	0.00	Science & Sport
09-Dec-15	129375	129412	37	16.65	0.00	Science & Sport
15-Dec-15	129422	129568	146	65.70	0.00	Science & Sport
13-Jan-16	129683	129709	26	11.70	0.00	Science & Sport
20-Jan-16	129714	129835	121	54.45	0.00	Science & Sport
03-Feb-16	130387	130460	73	32.85	0.00	Science & Sport
04-Feb-16	130460	130574	114	51.30	0.00	Science & Sport
17-Feb-16	130905	130959	54	24.30	0.00	Science & Sport
18-Mar-16	131526	131531	5	2.25	0.00	Science & Sport
22-Mar-16	131531	131580	49	22.05	0.00	Science & Sport
23-Mar-16	131653	131753	100	45.00	0.00	Science & Sport
22-Jun-16	133914	134234	320	81.00	35.00	Science & Sport
Total			2208.00	930.60	35.00	

Appendix 13: UWS Vehicle Usage: ST07VPM

DATE	MILEAGE AT START	MILEAGE AT FINISH	TOTAL MILEAGE	COST AT 1-180 MILES	COST AT + 180 MILES	SCHOOL/DEPT
16-Feb-15	43738	43813	75	33.75	0.00	SSS
20-Feb-15	43812	43966	154	69.30	0.00	SSS
25-Feb-15	43996	44021	25	11.25	0.00	SSS
20-Mar-15	44436	44569	133	59.85	0.00	SSS
27-Mar-15	44692	44816	124	55.80	0.00	SSS
02-Apr-15	45086	45148	62	27.90	0.00	SSS
15-Apr-15	45152	45211	59	26.55	0.00	SSS
21-Apr-15	45211	45372	161	72.45	0.00	SSS
28-Apr-15	45372	45376	4	1.80	0.00	SSS
25-Sep-15	46739	46783	44	19.80	0.00	SSS
02-Oct-15	46783	46829	46	20.70	0.00	SSS
09-Oct-15	46904	47007	103	46.35	0.00	SSS
16-Oct-15	47081	47127	46	20.70	0.00	SSS
20-Oct-15	47127	47180	53	23.85	0.00	SSS
21-Oct-15	47180	47212	32	14.40	0.00	SSS
23-Oct-15	47213	47257	44	19.80	0.00	SSS
30-Oct-15	47442	47488	46	20.70	0.00	SSS
06-Nov-15	47560	48114	554	81.00	93.50	SSS
13-Nov-15	48163	48210	47	21.15	0.00	SSS
20-Nov-15	48214	48494	280	81.00	25.00	SSS
27-Nov-15	48677	48723	46	20.70	0.00	SSS
30-Nov-15	48723	48786	63	28.35	0.00	SSS
04-Dec-15	48829	48875	46	20.70	0.00	SSS
14-Jan-16	48984	49119	135	60.75	0.00	SSS
08-Feb-16	49213	49289	76	34.20	0.00	SSS
10-Feb-16	49289	49381	92	41.40	0.00	SSS
22-Feb-16	49464	49559	95	42.75	0.00	SSS
24-Feb-16	49559	49616	57	25.65	0.00	SSS
26-Feb-16	49616	49798	182	81.00	0.50	SSS
07-Mar-16	49908	49999	91	40.95	0.00	SSS
17-Mar-16	50292	50395	103	46.35	0.00	SSS
23-Mar-16	50447	50494	47	21.15	0.00	SSS
24-Mar-16	50494	50499	5	2.25	0.00	SSS
13-Apr-16	50585	50632	47	21.15	0.00	SSS
18-Apr-16	50632	50769	137	61.65	0.00	SSS
26-Apr-16	50776	50805	29	13.05	0.00	SSS
TOTAL			3343	1290.15	119	

Appendix 14: Sample consent Form

Carbon Efficiency in The Scottish Public Sector

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed for my PhD thesis research project: 'Carbon Efficiency in The Scottish Public Sector'.

I am now seeking your formal 'informed consent' to be interviewed.

Consent for Participation in Interview Research

I volunteer to participate in a research project conducted by Mr. Ebiyon Idundun from University of the West of Scotland. I understand that I will be one of approximately 30 people being interviewed for this research.

1. My participation in this project is voluntary. I understand that I will not be paid for my participation and may withdraw participation by contacting the researcher any time up to within a calendar year of the date of giving my consent. I do not need to give reasons for exercising the right to withdraw or change my consent status level and there will be no repercussions as a result.
2. I understand that if I feel uncomfortable in any way during the interview session, I have the right to decline to answer any question or to end the interview.
3. The interview duration will be between 30 and 90 minutes. Notes will be written during the interview. An audio tape of the interview and subsequent dialogue will be made. If I don't want to be taped, I understand that I will not be able to participate in the study.
4. I understand that the researcher will not identify me by name in any reports using information obtained from this interview, and that my confidentiality as a participant in this study will remain secure. Subsequent uses of records and data will be subject to standard data use policies which protect the anonymity of individuals and institutions.
5. I understand that this research study has been reviewed and approved by the School of Science and Sports Ethic Committee of the University of the West of Scotland.
6. I have read and understand the participant information document. I have had all my questions answered to my satisfaction, and I voluntarily agree to participate in this study.
7. I have been given a copy of this consent form.

Signed:

Job Title:

Dated:

Thank you in advance for your consent and for participating in my PhD research project.

Ebiyon Idundun

Address & telephone number for correspondence

Carbon Efficiency in the Scottish Public Sector

16-17 October 2018

Celebrating
10 Years

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is a global concern cutting across all sectors of our society. The burning of fossil fuels to create energy is the most significant contributor to human induced climate change (IPCC, 2007). Fossil fuel has been in use since the 18th century and fueled the process of industrialisation (Cuff and Gaudie, 2008), however remains the most dominant of energy sources, whilst the use of renewable energy is growing at a slow rate (IEA, 2017). There are growing calls for urgent and concerted action in tackling climate change (Ulto et al., 2017).

The public sector is a key player in achieving carbon reduction targets (DECC, 2018). Part 4 (Duties of public bodies relating to climate change) of The Climate Change (Scotland) Act 2009, places a mandatory climate change duty reporting requirement on Scottish Public Bodies (those identified as 'Major Players', due to their larger influence or impact on climate change) (Scottish Government, 2018). Of the 150 major players, there are 32 local authorities, and 44 further and higher education institutions together representing just over 50% (Sustainable Scotland Network (SSN), n.d.). For the purpose of this research, the scope of the public sector is limited to Universities and Local Authorities in Scotland. Local authorities play a key role in implementing transport measures and in making homes, public buildings and businesses more energy efficient (CCC, 2016). The Further and Higher Education sector on the other hand are experiencing strong growth (Jewett, 2005), rapid expansion (Altan, 2010) and expected to provide intellectual and practical leadership in achieving sustainable societies (Altan, 2010).

With pressure on organisations to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, we present findings from an exploratory study on the ongoing reliance on fossil fuels in the public sector, using a multi-method qualitative approach of literature review, case study, interviews and document review.

AIMS

- To determine the extent to which Scotland's public sector is reliant on the use of fossil fuels
- To develop sensible steps that can be taken to reduce/eliminate reliance on fossil fuel energy
- To develop steps to help the School of Science and Sport (SSS), be more carbon efficient

INTERVIEWS ANALYSIS RESULTS

Example of a code applied to a segment of data

Data extract when I first started with the local authority back in 2002, utility prices were so cheap, there was no real incentive to try and reduce your consumption because we were not paying a lot for gas and the electricity encourages fossil fuel use	Codes for Cheap utility prices encourages fossil fuel use
--	--

Example of codes grouped into of potential themes and sub-themes

Code	Sub-theme	Theme
Cheap utility prices encourages fossil fuel use		
Cost implications of switching from fossil fuels to clean energy	Cheaper to use fossil fuels	Barriers to relying on renewable technology
Uncertainty of the impact of investing in new technology which has not been installed		
Ultra-low gas prices further switch to alternative energy		
Capital cost of installation is expensive		
Clear marketing programs are not enough without clear to raise gas prices		
Although some carbon prices have reduced it is still not cost effective		
Unlucky Scottish government funding, even a loan you can't really pay for it or feed-in tariff		

Example of a developed main theme and sub-themes

Main sub-theme	Final sub-theme	Key theme
Cheaper to use fossil fuels	Price of utilities and cost	
Renewable energy not cost efficient		
Available funding subject to cost benefit analysis of reduction in emissions	Lack of funding	Barriers to relying on renewable technology
Lack of government support and funding		
Decarbonising grid is challenging	No one size fits all technology	
EU tax incentives		
Limited local heating systems which do not meet carbon reduction targets		

CONCLUSION

A baseline carbon footprint of 486513kgCO₂e was established for the School of Science and Sport. 45% of emissions resulted from fossil fuel energy sources. To date, the analysis of interview responses reveals there is evidence of reliance on fossil fuels and efforts to reduce its use however, there are significant barriers to moving away from fossil fuels and a need to improve carbon reporting. It is anticipated that the findings of this research will be beneficial in providing an understanding of the ongoing reliance on fossil fuel energy within the Scottish public sector. Future work to be completed include: working towards publication of review papers, concluding interviews and analysis of responses, and analysis of mandatory carbon reporting submissions of participating organisations.

REFERENCES: Altan, S. (2010) Energy efficiency in public buildings: a review of energy consumption in public buildings. Energy Efficiency and Management, 1(1), 1-10. CCC, (2016) The Carbon Footprint of the Public Sector. London: Carbon Trust. DECC, (2018) Carbon Footprint of the Public Sector. London: Carbon Trust. IEA, (2017) World Energy Outlook 2017. Paris: International Energy Agency. IPCC, (2007) Climate Change: The Physical Science Basis. Working Group I Contribution to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Geneva: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Jewett, J. (2005) The Carbon Footprint of the Public Sector. London: Carbon Trust. Ulto, P., et al. (2017) The Carbon Footprint of the Public Sector. London: Carbon Trust.

Reliance on Fossil Fuels in the Scottish Public Sector

E. Idundun^a, A.S. Hursthouse^a, I. McLellan^a

^a School of Computing, Engineering & Physical Sciences, University of the West of Scotland,

The consumption of fossil fuels from energy creation is the most significant contributor to human induced climate change, [1] however fossil fuels remain the most dominant of energy sources, whilst the use of renewable energy is growing at a slow rate, [2]. International action in tackling climate change has led to increased pressures to measure, record and report carbon footprints. The public sector has a key role to play in reducing emissions and increasing uptake of renewable energy technologies.

The study aims to investigate and present findings from an exploratory study on the reliance on fossil fuels in Scotland's public sector with focus on Universities and Local Government Authorities. A multi-method qualitative study approach is employed, using information gathered from a literature review, case study, and thematic analysis of semi-structured interviews with sector professionals.

The case study developed a carbon footprint baseline for a School at the University of the West of Scotland. Electricity was the greatest contributor of overall emissions followed by travel, and over 45%

of all emissions resulted from fossil fuel sources through road travel, air travel and gas use in buildings. These findings are in line with findings of similar studies [3], [4]. The thematic analysis of semi-structured interview responses resulted in five key themes namely: 'evidence of ongoing reliance on fossil fuels', 'efforts to reduce fossil fuel use', 'actions required to reduce reliance on fossil fuels', 'barriers to moving away from fossil fuels'

and 'carbon reporting'. The use of fossil fuel energy sources in buildings for space heating, cooling, and electricity, and its persistent reliance for transportation, evidence reliance on fossil fuels, [5], [6]. Government and organisational initiatives, and the uptake of renewable and low carbon energy justify efforts to reduce fossil fuel use however, a zero-carbon energy revolution, reduced energy consumption and carbon offsets, and financial instruments and governance are further required. Lack of funding and support, practicalities and cost implications, and lack of an alternative energy source to replace fossil fuels are sub themes highlighting the main barriers to moving away from fossil fuels. Difficulties in estimating accurate carbon emissions associated with procurement, reducing emissions associated with staff mileage and influencing staff travel behaviours are also highlighted, in line with studies highlighting difficulties in estimating Scope 3 emissions, for example, [7].

[1] IPCC. *Climate Change 2007: The Physical Science Basis*, 2007.

[2] BP. *BP Statistical Review of World Energy 2018*, 2018.

[3] Robinson O., Kemp S. and Williams I. *Carbon management at universities: a reality check*, 2015, 106:109-118.

[4] Ozawa-Meida L., Brockway P., Letten K., Davies J. and Fleming P. *Measuring carbon performance in a UK University through a consumption-based carbon footprint: De Montfort University case study*, 2013, 56: 185-198.

[5] Mehta D. P. and Wesehan M. *Sustainable Energy in Building Systems*, 2013,19: 628-635.

[6] Pietzcker R.C., Longden T., Chen W., Fu S., Kriegler E., Kyle P. and Luderer G. *Long-term transport energy demand and climate policy: Alternative visions on transport decarbonization in energy-economy models*, 2014, 64: 95-108.

[7] Alvarez S., Blanquer M. and Rubio A. *Carbon footprint using the Compound Method based on Financial Accounts. The case of the School of Forestry Engineering, Technical University of Madrid*, 2014, 66: 224-232.

Keywords: carbon footprint, fossil fuels, public sector

SAGES
Scottish Association for Geoscientists, Environmental and Society

Reliance on Fossil Fuels in the Scottish Public Sector

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

The Effects of Burning Fossil Fuels

The consumption of fossil fuels from energy creation is the most significant contributor to human induced climate change, [1] however fossil fuels remain the most dominant of energy sources, whilst the use of renewable energy is growing at a slow rate, [2].

THE RESEARCH DESIGN:

The study investigates and presents findings from an exploratory study on the reliance on fossil fuels in Scotland's public sector, using information gathered from a literature review, case study, and thematic analysis of semi-structured interviews with sector professionals.

CASE STUDY RESULTS:

INTERVIEW RESULTS:

Efforts to reduce fossil fuel use

- Government and organisational initiatives
- uptake of renewable and low carbon energy

Carbon reporting

- difficulties in estimating Scope 3 emissions

Actions required to reduce reliance on fossil fuels

- radical zero-carbon revolution
- reduced energy consumption and carbon offsets
- financial instruments and governance

Evidence of ongoing reliance on fossil fuels

- Energy use in buildings
- Fuel for transportation

Barriers to moving away from fossil fuels

- Lack of funding and support
- practicalities and cost implications
- lack of an alternative energy source to replace fossil fuels

CONCLUSION:

The case study revealed electricity and travel as the greatest emission contributors with over 45% of emissions attributed to fossil fuel sources [3], [4]. The interview responses revealed evidence of reliance on fossil fuels [5], [6]; efforts being made to reduce its use however; more action is required to overcome the barriers to moving away from fossil fuels and a need to improve carbon reporting [7]. Future work to be completed is the analysis of mandatory carbon reporting submissions of participating organisations. It is anticipated that the findings of this research will be beneficial in providing an understanding of the reliance on fossil fuel energy in the Scottish public sector.

REFERENCES:

[1] IPCC. Climate Change 2007: The Physical Science Basis., 2007.
 [2] BP. BP Statistical Review of World Energy 2018., 2018.
 [3] Robinson O., Kemp S. and Williams I. Carbon management at universities: a reality check., 2015, 106:109-118.
 [4] Ozawa-Meida L., Brockway P., Letten K., Davies J. and Fleming P. Measuring carbon performance in a UK University through a consumption-based carbon footprint: De Montfort University case study., 2013, 56: 185-198.
 [5] Mehta D. P. and Wiesehan M. Sustainable Energy in Building Systems., 2013,19: 628-635.
 [6] Pietzcker R.C., Longden T., Chen W., Fu S., Kriegler E., Kyle P. and Luderer G. Long-term transport energy demand and climate policy: Alternative visions on transport decarbonization in energy-economy models., 2014, 64: 95-108.
 [7] Alvarez S., Blanquer M. and Rubio A. Carbon footprint using the Compound Method based on Financial Accounts: The case of the School of Forestry Engineering, Technical University of Madrid., 2014, 66: 224-232.

Review

Carbon Management in UK Higher Education Institutions: An Overview

Ebiyon Idundun, Andrew S. Hursthouse

School of Computing, Engineering & Physical Sciences, University of the West of Scotland, Paisley PA1 2BE, UK;

Abstract: The paper presents a review of carbon management in relation to UK Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), forms part of a wider study on the ongoing reliance on fossil fuels in Scotland's public sector with a focus on Universities and Local Government Authorities. It compares the CF (carbon footprint), emission sources, and the fossil fuel contribution to the CFs reported in 3 identified articles relating specifically to the estimation of CF for HEIs. The consumption of fossil fuels results in human induced climate change however, fossil fuels boosted the industrialization process and remains the dominant source of global energy consumption. Action in tackling climate change has led to organizations coming under increasing pressures to monitor and report their CFs. HEIs have a key role to play in reducing its reliance on fossil fuels and reducing GHG (greenhouse gas) emissions through delivery of scientific research and innovative carbon management solutions, increase in its uptake of renewable energy technologies, educating and training future leaders, and raising public awareness, in contribution to a sustainable society. This paper highlights the need for a shift of focus to reducing fossil fuel reliance in response to climate change and demonstrates how HEIs can impact GHG reductions.

Citation: Idundun, E.; Hursthouse, A.S.; McLellan, I. Carbon Management in UK Higher Education Institutions: An Overview. *Sustainability* **2021**, *13*, 10896. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131910896>

Academic Editor: Wen-Hsien Tsai

Received: 10 August 2021
Accepted: 27 September 2021
Published: 30 September 2021

Publisher's Note: MDPI stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright © 2021 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Keywords: public sector; higher education institutions; carbon management; carbon footprint; greenhouse gas emissions

1. Introduction

It is recognized that climate change, and its associated issues, is a global environmental and social concern, impacting our mental health and well-being, poorer nations, and economic growth [1,2]. The Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (IPCC) is confident that the observed warming since the mid-20th Century is a consequence of anthropogenic influence [3], responsible for the retreating glacier and estimated to be responsible for global warming of about 1.09 °C above pre-industrial levels [4]. The issues associated with fossil fuel use continue to be a global growing concern, with the burning of fossil fuels as the largest known contributor of Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to the atmosphere [5], and the apparent continued global reliance on fossil fuel energy sources [6]. Large-scale use of fossil fuels determined the process of industrialization; its continued use has major environmental implications such as acid rain and deposition, loss of plant and animal ecosystems and global warming [7,8]. Fossil fuels remain the principal source of global energy consumption today with oil (33.1%), coal (27.0%), and gas (24.2%) having the largest shares in global primary energy consumption in 2019 [6], and the European Union (EU) relies on fossil fuels, importing oil (68%), gas (28%), and hard coal (4%) estimated at approximately £266 billion in 2017 [9].

Public sector organizations like Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) consume fossil fuels directly or indirectly in their day-to-day activities. They often face however the dichotomy between maintaining organizational standards and ethos and reducing organizational emissions. The use of fossil fuel energy sources within HEI buildings for space heating, cooling, and electricity, and its persistent reliance for transportation evidence

reliance on fossil fuels [10–12]. For example, motorized forms of transportation for road and air travel are overwhelmingly reliant on fossil fuels [13], like petrol, diesel, jet fuel and LPG. This is likely to be the case for some time yet particularly when considering air travel is a fundamental part of how HEIs organizations operate. However, the COVID-19 pandemic forced HEIs to online delivery of education provisions [14], and whilst this presents the potential opportunity for HEIs to reduce emissions associated with business travel, there are the issues of education inequalities [15] and the carbon implications of working and studying from home [14].

There is therefore an increasing need to reduce the reliance on fossil fuels and to reduce drastically GHG emissions, for example, the ‘basket of six’ highlighted within various IPCC reports [4]: carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), perfluorocarbons (PFCs) and sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆). The fossil fuel industry is well established within societies globally; reducing reliance on fossil fuels will clearly be challenging however is non-negotiable [16] and requires a systematic approach through concerted action to address the issue and avoid climate tipping points [17–19].

The recognition of human induced climate change has led to international progress in addressing climate change and its associated issues. Figure 1 shows a timeline of some international actions taken by way of reports and conferences since the establishment of the IPCC in 1988.

Figure 1. Timeline of reports and conferences on Climate Change showing international action (post creation of IPCC in 1988). (AR—Assessment Report, COP—Conference of Parties, MOP—Meeting of Parties to the Kyoto Protocol; [20–27].

This paper therefore highlights the reliance on fossil fuels by HEIs and questions how and why HEIs can impact GHG reductions given the significance of its position within society and the leadership expectations bestowed on it as demonstrated by its spontaneous adaptation to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Legislative Framework for GHG Emission Reductions

The EU requires member states to participate and contribute to its initiatives to reduce GHG emissions whilst acting to achieve reduction targets and increase the efficiency and use of renewable energy. Some of these initiatives include: (i) EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), (ii) Renewable Energy Directive, (iii) Energy Efficiency Directive, (iv) New car and van CO₂ targets, (v) 2030 Climate & Energy Framework [28–33]. However, it is important to note that at the time of writing the UK ceases to be a member state of the EU as of January 2020 however, the UK governments aim is that all current legislation is transposed and will still be applicable post Brexit. For example, the statutory instrument ‘The Greenhouse Gas Emissions Trading Scheme Auctioning Regulations 2021’ which came into force in April 2021 to ensure that emissions from sectors covered by the EU ETS remain covered by a carbon pricing policy post Brexit [34].

The UK Climate Change Act 2008 regulates the reduction of net GHG emissions with targets to reduce emissions to Net-zero GHGs by 2050 based on the 1990 baseline [35]. The Act places the onus on the Secretary of State, Scottish Ministers in the Climate Change (Scotland) Act 2009 [36], to achieve reduction targets. Whilst there are no specific targets set for public sector organizations like HEIs within the Act, and no direct provision for measuring or targeting reduction of fossil fuel emissions within the Act(s), the HEI sector aspires to exceed its sector-level targets [37]. The Act covers all the United Kingdom however Wales, Northern Ireland and Scotland have dedicated reduction targets. The Committee on Climate Change (CCC) recommended new targets following the assessment of the UKs long-term emission targets of net-zero greenhouse gases by 2050 for the whole of the UK [38].

The UK Government, and Devolved Administrations, have taken several actions in its bid to reduce GHG emissions and meet its reduction targets and EU targets. They include but not limited to: (i) setting climate change targets to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050, (ii) incorporation of international aviation and shipping emissions into the Carbon Budget for consistent accounting, (iii) generation of 50% of electricity from low carbon sources, (iv) ambitious strategies to support decarbonization in polluting industries, (v) being the first G7 country to action support for a transition to clean, green energy in the oil and gas industry’s (50% reduction by 2030), and (vi) launch of ‘Together For Our Planet’ campaign, calling on all to take action on climate change [39].

2. Carbon Management

The role of the HEIs is pivotal in carbon management, seen as neutral and trusted, with the capacity to raise public awareness, educate and train future leaders, deliver scientific research and innovative carbon management solutions to combat climate change [40–42]. More so with the contribution of academics across the world in contributing to scientific knowledge through IPCC reports. Although climate change is a global concern, its impacts are very much experienced locally. This re-emphasizes the need for public engagement to foster partnerships, collaborations, and transformation in behavior in response to climate change, and HEIs are well positioned to deliver on this requirement [42–44]. There is growing popularity within organizations for ‘carbon management’ policies, largely due to the perceived contribution they can make in reducing global emissions [45], in reducing and improving their GHG emissions [46], opportunities for financial savings through energy efficiency measures [47], as a result of stakeholder pressure [48].

Carbon management policies, procedures and practices focus on the processes of developing solutions to reduce carbon emissions. Focusing on the ‘basket of six’ GHGs, carbon management relies on careful carbon accounting (e.g., measuring organizational

carbon footprint), reduction in energy use, raw material consumption and waste generation [46,49–51]. Implementing carbon management policies and strategies would ultimately result in the reduction of carbon emissions and yield cost savings for organizations. For example, improving energy efficiency in buildings will decrease the building's energy consumption, operating costs, and its carbon footprint [52]. Other reasons for organizations to implement carbon management protocols are those which cut across the triple bottom line (i.e., social, economic and environmental): (i) to reduce organizational impacts, (ii) to reduce public health risks resulting from air pollutants, (iii) to improve the public image of a business, (iv) to comply with, and prepare for, legislation [49,53–55].

Businesses have brought to the fore of their agendas the need for reducing GHG emissions, ultimately putting pressure on organizations to implement carbon management policies and practices. Carbon Management involves reducing GHG emissions, the efficient use of energy, investing in research and technology to develop and capitalize on alternative renewable and low carbon energy sources, including carbon capture and storage, and accountability through measurement and reporting [44,49,50,56,57]. Lee [58], classifies six categories of carbon management activities in addressing climate change at corporate level as: emission reduction commitment; product improvement; process and supply improvement; new market and business development; organizational involvement and external relationship development. Wade, Dargusch, and Griffiths [59] and Wade, and Griffiths [60] identified best practice carbon management (BPCM) attributes namely: compliance; culture and values; knowledge creation and sharing; monitoring, reporting, and energy efficiency; resource allocation and R&D; networking/stakeholder engagement; strategy; and target setting.

2.1. Measuring GHG Emissions

Purman [61] and Pandey et al. [62] suggest that emissions are measured, either directly or by using emission factors or models to calculate emissions. To reduce GHG emissions, an organization must understand its emissions profile (i.e., identify sources of emissions resulting from its operations, including measuring, and recording the corresponding emissions) and establish a baseline from which subsequent emissions can be measured against. Whilst organizations are under increasing demand to measure their carbon footprint, there is a lack of academic definitions of the term 'carbon footprint' within studies or how it should be calculated [62,63]. Carbon footprints are often used to describe emissions associated with CO₂ or the other GHGs in CO₂ equivalents [62,64,65], based on their Global Warming Potential (GWP). The range of GHGs and GWPs pose potential difficulties an organization can have when calculating their carbon footprint [66].

Adding to the complexity is Wiedmann and Minx [63], who state that carbon footprints should measure CO₂ emissions only and other GHGs should not be included; where other GHGs are included, it should be termed 'climate footprint'. They argue that some GHGs are not carbon based and are difficult to quantify due to lack of data; any conversions to CO₂ which is based on assumptions will likely increase uncertainties and errors in footprint calculations. Whilst there is a valid argument for the collective measure of GHG emissions to be termed Climate Footprint [67], current carbon footprint reporting of CO₂ and other GHGs in CO₂ equivalents is well established. They form the basis of baseline measurements for organizations and as such the term 'carbon footprint' encompassing other GHGs in CO₂ equivalents is used within this paper.

There are various environmental audit systems used for assessing environmental management impacts at different levels (micro, meso and macro), examples include Environmental Accounting (EAc), Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC), Environmental Auditing (EA) and Environmental Management Systems (EMS) [68]. Arena and de Rosa argues that LCA is the only comprehensive and legitimate method accepted by the scientific community for assessing the environmental impacts of products and services through their life cycle [69]. LCA plays an important role in tracking emissions of an entire supply chain, carbon footprint calculations and in the establishment of protocols and guides

for GHG accounting [62,63,70]. Carbon Trust identifies four main types of carbon footprint for organizations as follows: (i) organizational (based on GHG protocol and must include scopes 1 and 2 emissions; with flexibility for reporting scope 3 emissions), (ii) value chain, (iii) product (based on PAS 2050) and (iv) supply chain carbon footprints [71]. Figure 2 shows the different boundaries of organizational, product and supply chain footprints.

Figure 2. Boundaries of organizational, product and supply chain footprints (Adapted from Carbon Trust [71]).

Whilst the methods for calculating carbon footprints are evolving, two main approaches to performing LCA for carbon footprints are: bottom up or process analysis (PA) and top down or input-output analysis (IO) are currently being used [62,63,70]. In some cases, a combination of both approaches also referred to as a hybrid approach is also utilized (for example: [62,63,72]). The IO analysis has variations including economic input-output (EIO) analysis [62,70,73], environmental input-output (EIO) analysis [65], environmental extended input-output (EEIO) analysis [72,74,75] and environmentally extended multi-region-input-output (EEMRIO) analysis [76]. Much research has been conducted on bottom up and top down approaches and there are advantages and disadvantages to both approaches, (Table 1). The variation in methodologies used to calculate carbon footprints, along with their operational scope, population, emission sources reported, contribute to the complexity of comparing carbon footprints of HEI [74–76]. However, in practice, organizations are now using carbon footprint results to identify opportunities to reduce costs associated with their operations [77], for example reducing utility costs through energy efficient operations, consuming less energy and use of more energy efficient machinery and equipment.

Table 1. Comparison of Bottom-up and Top-down approaches for carbon footprint estimation [63,78].

PA—Bottom-Up Approach	IO—Top-Down Approach
Better suited for micro systems like an individual product or service, or relatively small groups of products and particular processes (cradle to grave estimation)	Better suited for meso (sector level) and macro systems (aggregate of meso systems) like industrial sectors, individual businesses, households, larger product groups and governments (comprehensive and robust estimation)
Suffers from a system boundary problem—only on-site (mostly first-order, and some second-order impacts)	Accounts for higher order impacts and sets the whole economic system as boundary (at the expense of site-specific detail)
Not suitable for calculating footprints for macro systems	Limited suitability for calculating footprints for micro systems
Potential for specific and dedicated strategies and incentives to reduce emissions in a micro system	Potential for overall efficiency gains across meso /macro systems
Site specific accuracy of data	Utilizes aggregated data which may not accurately represent site specific conditions
Non-standardized measurements with potential to differ from site to site	Standardized measurements
Requires more staffing resources to for estimation	Requires fewer staffing resources for estimation
Limited data sources and potential to utilize a top-down database as proxy for missing data	Availability of a range of data sources
Difficult to achieve consistency in reporting due to lack of control systems	Consistency of reporting system due to effective control systems

Private and Public Sector Roles

The need for collaboration between various sectors, industries, governments, and stakeholders as never been more important in addressing climate change and its impacts. Walker and Cass suggest that the social organization of renewable energy technologies is evolving as a heterogeneous category of energy supply and highlight the need to consider the social and geographical implications of this evolution [79]. They characterized five modes of renewable energy implementation in the UK, including ‘private supplier mode’ which emerged post, the energy utilities, and infrastructures privatization in 1989. From the 1990s, the private sector continues the transition from the traditional ‘rule-taker’ role to a more engaging role as a ‘rule-maker’ in relation to the governance of global climate and energy, achieved through private regimes and a hybrid governance regime built on public-private partnerships [80]. Pattberg and Stripple consider global climate governance approaches to include international and public sources of authority, public-private interventions and private interventions [81].

The Kyoto Protocol in a bid to assist involved parties achieve emission targets, whilst also encouraging the private sector and developing countries to contribute their quota, included emissions trading, clean development mechanism (CDM) and Joint Implementation (JI) as market-based mechanisms [82]. CDM is heavily reliant on the private sector which itself involves different types of actors such as CDM project advocates, consultants, brokers, investment funds, Departments of Environment, and private initiatives; like mitigation projects, and to create carbon-trading systems, such as the World Bank's Prototype Carbon Fund (PCF) [80,81].

Talukdar and Meisner suggest a link between countries that allow a greater private sector involvement in economic activities, foreign direct investment and well-developed capital markets, and positive impacts on their environment [83]. That private sector appears to be in transition to the role of 'rule-maker', plays an active role in implementing climate change mitigation mechanisms, and plays a significant role in global decision-making with respect to multi-stakeholder participation. However, their lack of legitimacy poses problems in decision-making; Andrade and Puppim de Oliveira [80], argue that the current architecture should guarantee that the private sector does not hijack global climate and energy governance decisions.

There is a lack of enough private sector investment in low carbon technologies for several reasons, including gaps in research and policy making, and financial gaps. Bradford and Fraser suggest that Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) make up a large portion of private sector economic activities and likely a major contributor to GHG emissions in the UK [84]. They highlight the gap in research and policymaking from UK Government and local authorities in relation to SMEs and recommend policy options for local authorities to facilitate significant reductions in energy consumption and GHG emissions.

There is a growing acceptance of the role to be played by public sector in leading by example, promoting energy efficiency improvements, influencing private sector organizations, and acting as a catalyst for action in reducing GHGs across society [85,86]. However, to go beyond aspiring to achieve or exceed legislative targets, taking lead on climate action to set good examples and act as a catalyst for reducing emissions across society, the public sector needs to strengthen its contributions, increase its pace of change, improve the poor energy efficiency of its buildings, and overcome the challenges and barriers of national austerity and investment deficiencies [85–88].

The role of public sector support in addressing financial gaps that occur when finance suppliers are unable to meet business demand for long-term low carbon investments is explored by Owen et al. [89]. They highlight the financial gaps as an institutional barrier; however, suggest that public sector support can limit the gaps through suitable finance ecosystem approach for low carbon investments by government. It was estimated that around \$5.7 trillion of annual investment in green infrastructure by 2020 was required, largely in today's developing world, to ensure investments needs are met beyond 2020 the growth of private and public funding levels require to be sustained [90]. Multilateral development banks, a principal source of public funding, committed \$2.9 billion to energy efficiency programs in 2015 representing 14% of all mitigation investments, with renewable energy receiving double that amount [91]. In the UK over £92 billion has been invested in clean energy since 2010, this figure includes investments totaling £12 billion from the Green Investment Bank since its establishment in 2012 alongside private sector and third-party investment partners [92].

3. Carbon Management in HEIs

The UK HEI sector, like other business sectors of the UK, is committed to reducing GHG emissions resulting from their operations in order to contribute to achieving net zero emissions by 2050 as set by The Climate Change Act 2008 [36]. The sector is also required to comply with other EU-induced frameworks like the EU ETS. The Climate Change (Duties of Public Bodies: Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Order 2015 [93] requires HEIs to annually report on compliance with climate change duties. Furthermore,

there are sector specific requirements, such as CRC, carbon reduction requirements for the Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE), and those set by the Universities and Colleges Climate Commitment for Scotland (UCCCS). Requirements to contribute to achieving UK reduction targets; vast operational scope of the HE sector; circa 2.5 million enrolled students in the UK [94]; 223, 525 academic staff working across 197 UK HE providers [95]; and over £37 billion annual operating expenditure [96], all indicate that the sector has a key part to play in contributing to achieving UK emission targets. This subsequently justifies the need for HEIs to take the lead in reducing emissions within the sector. Through UK legislation on climate change and sector specific requirements UK HEIs (and indeed other public sector organizations) have developed and implemented CMPs (Carbon Management Plans) [97].

However, Robinson et al. demonstrated through a 'reality check' that current CMPs are not a good indicator of future performance and underestimates the challenges faced by HEIs in reducing carbon emissions [98]. Some HEIs, however, have embedded the results of their carbon footprint into their CMPs and agreed carbon emission reduction action plans [75,97]. Despite the focus on carbon management at HEIs, a report reveals that 13% of HEIs do not have a carbon reduction plan [98], with few institutions having a grasp of their GHG emission profile resulting directly and indirectly from their activities [99]. Reports of recent surveys reveal overall sector emissions have increased in recent years in Scotland [100] and decreased by 7% in English Universities in 2015/16 [100], however most UK Universities are not on track to meet their reduction targets [100–102]. It is worth highlighting the potential implication of the HEIs forced move to online delivery on emission, and although Filimonau et al., found the carbon footprint of a mid-sized UK University to have reduced during the COVID-19 lockdown, they suggest the implications of this move be considered carefully [14]. Although the recent surveys suggest evidence of carbon reductions for some UK HEIs, they corroborate the identified needs for a uniform approach to carbon reduction across the sector, and organizational shift in shared responsibilities for carbon management [100,101].

The benefits of carbon management strategies include: carbon emission reduction, public health and quality of life improvements, meeting climate change mitigation targets, potential for financial savings, organizational credibility particularly in enhancing recruitment for example of staff or students, limiting risks associated with in-action on climate change [103,104]. These should motivate HEIs to do much more particularly with the increasing physical size of many HEIs resulting from student population growth [105]. However, this increase in physical size of HEIs is likely to bring about an increase in its energy use and travel requirements, which are reliant on fossil fuel energy sources, further highlighting the need to increase investment in, and uptake of renewable sources of energy in HEIs to reduce reliance on fossil fuels and carbon emissions. Although emissions associated with fossil fuel sources for example fuels like diesel and petrol for transportation, and natural gas are often reported, they are reported individually. There appears to be a lack of reporting and monitoring of emissions associated with the collective use of fossil fuel sources which is required to monitor progress in reducing reliance on fossil fuels and ultimately aid planning and decision making on fossil fuel issues and policies within HEIs. For carbon management in HEIs to be worthwhile it is vital to overcome the barriers of time, cost and data reliability in assessing Scope 3 emissions [99], financial and staff resources [98], and focus on reducing fossil fuel associated emissions through the uptake of renewable energy technologies, and divestment to end financial support to the fossil fuel industry [106].

4. Carbon Footprint of HEIs

4.1. Introduction

HEIs should be motivated to do much more in developing methods for quantifying emissions associated with their vast operations and annual expenditure and take action to reduce fossil fuel emissions to contribute to achieving UK reduction targets, particu-

larly with the increasing physical size of many HEIs resulting from student population growth [105].

Several studies cutting across continents of the world have been carried out to assess, estimate, or calculate GHG emissions, or carbon footprints of HEIs [107], for examples: Letete et al. estimated the carbon footprint of the University of Capetown, South Africa [108]; Gómez et al. calculated the carbon footprint of the University of Castilla-La Mancha, Spain [72]; Butt measured GHG emissions for Massey University, New Zealand [109]; Varón-hoyos et al. quantified the carbon footprint of the Technological University of Pereira, Colombia [110]; Ridhosari and Rahman measured the carbon emission associated with electricity, transportation, and waste generation only, for the generated at the Universitas Pertamina, Indonesia [111]; Larsen et al. investigated the carbon footprint of the Norwegian University of Technology and Science, Norway [74]; and Clabeaux et al. assessed the carbon footprint of Clemson University, United States [112], to mention a few. This section briefly looks at the reported carbon footprints of 3 UK HEIs and compares emission sources, footprint by Scope, and fossil fuel contribution to emissions where this can be identified from the list of emission sources reported within the articles.

4.2. Method

Using the ScienceDirect database and Google Scholar to search for literature, there are limited studies focusing on the calculation, estimation, or assessment of carbon footprints specifically for UK HEIs. The search terms used in ScienceDirect database are 'carbon footprint, University' and 'greenhouse gas', University, including 'carbon footprint' and 'university' as keywords to ensure results focus on the carbon footprint of UK HEIs. These search terms yielded 7 and 6 article results, respectively, of which only 2 articles were specifically related to the carbon footprint of a UK HEI, with the remainder being duplicates. Google Scholar was used in a bid to supplement the focused article results sought from ScienceDirect database. The search term used in Google Scholar was 'carbon footprint, UK Universities', whilst this yielded excessive number of articles, a quick review of the article titles (and abstract in several cases) for the first 20 pages of results, sorted by relevance, resulted in only 1 other focus article, bringing the total number of articles found to 3. Gu et al. quantified the carbon footprint of the University of Keele, Staffordshire [113]; Ozawa-Meida measured the carbon footprint for De Montfort University, Leicester [75]; and Townsend and Barrett derived the carbon footprint of the University of Leeds, Leeds [114].

The 3 articles relating specifically to estimating the carbon footprint of UK universities are reviewed with respect to the estimated carbon footprints and where possible the fossil fuel contribution to this, and emissions sources reported within the articles. The following section presents the findings of the review of these articles and a comparative table of the findings.

4.3. Findings and Discussion

The use of ScienceDirect database and Google Scholar search engine indicates that there are limited number of studies that have been undertaken to estimate the carbon footprint of UK HEIs within the context of academic literature and highlights the need for more academic studies of carbon footprints of UK HEIs.

The carbon footprints reported in the reviewed articles were calculated for different academic sessions and periods. Consumption-based methodology using LCA approach was employed in the calculations of the carbon footprint reported by Gu et al. for 2010/11 (Keele University) [113] and Ozawa-Meida et al. for periods 2005/06 to 2008/09 (De Montfort University) [75]. However, Townsend and Barrett used EEIO analysis based on financial data to derive the 2010/11 carbon footprint (Leeds University) [114]. In terms of corresponding actions to reduce their carbon footprints, some examples specified include onsite electricity generation by solar PV, installing building management systems, upgrading to energy efficient lighting, switch to electric vehicle fleet, and sustainable procurement measures [75,113,114].

The emission sources reported within the articles cover Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 emission sources. Whilst Gu et al. and Ozawa-Meida et al. reported identical Scope 1 and Scope 2 emissions, the breakdown of Scope 1 and Scope 2 emissions is not reported by Townsend and Barrett [75,113,114]. The review highlights the range of Scope 3 emissions reported within the articles particularly with the use of financial expenditure data as the basis for the EEIO analysis [114] and with procurement emissions [75]. The corresponding percentages of the different Scopes (1–3) vary considerably across the reviewed articles possibly due to a combination of the variations in methodology, period, or year for which the carbon footprint was calculated, and the operational boundaries unique to each HEI.

The contribution of fossil fuel associated emissions to the total reported carbon footprints within the reviewed articles was derived from the emission sources reported within the articles and include travel related emissions and use of natural gas for building heating. This was possible for the articles which used the consumption-based methodology which allowed for easy identification of fossil fuel related emission sources however, in the case of the EEIO methodology it this was not possible due to the range and merging of emission source categories based on institution spend. The fossil fuel share of emissions, 47% in the case of Gu et al. [113], and 36% in the case of Ozawa-Meida et al. [75] suggests the extent of reliance on fossil fuels within the affiliated HEIs. Table 2 compares the emission sources and carbon footprint of the reviewed articles, including the fossil fuel contribution where applicable, and the per student carbon footprints.

Table 2. Comparison of UK HEI Carbon Footprint Assessment.

Article	Emission Sources			Footprint				
	Scope 1	Scope 2	Scope 3	Scope 1 (%)	Scope 2 (%)	Scope 3 (%)	Fossil fuel Share (%)	Total (tCO ₂ e)
Gu et al. [113]	Natural gas, Owned transport	Grid electricity, on-site generated electricity	Water supply, Wastewater treatment, waste disposal, Food procurement	47	39	14	47 (Natural gas & Owned transport)	14,393 (1.5/student)
Ozawa-Meida et al. [75]	Gas use & Owned fleet	Grid electricity	Procurement, Travel	6	15	79	36 (Travel-related emission & Gas use)	51,080 (2.4/student)
Townsend and Barrett [114]	None reported	None reported	Raw materials & chemicals, Food & drink, Paper & publishing, Manufactured products, Machinery & computers, Utilities & construction, Transport & communication, Business services, Public services.	18	31	51	None identified	161,819 (5.3/student)

The per student carbon footprint estimated in Table 2 was derived by dividing the carbon footprints by the student population as reported within the articles. Whilst this offers a means of comparing emissions per student it should be done with caution considering that different methods of estimating carbon footprints, the vast scope of operational boundaries and emission sources reported, and the size of the HEI to mention a few. The per student carbon footprint for the reviewed articles show a range of 1.5 tCO₂e/student to 5.3 tCO₂e highlighting the impact of student population on estimating carbon footprints.

5. Conclusions

The large-scale use of fossil fuels boosted industrialization and today it remains the principal source of energy consumption. Since inception of IPCC in 1988 it continues to be key in the growing acceptance of human induced climate change resulting mainly from burning fossil fuels. International action in addressing climate change and its associated issues led to global agreements such as the ‘Paris Agreement’. The UK regulates net

reduction of GHG emissions through ambitious targets set by the Climate Change Act and other initiatives such as investment in low-carbon technologies and setting national policies and strategies. HEIs need to capitalize on their unique position at the center of global societies in raising awareness and in addressing the issues of reliance on fossil fuels causing climate change, to contribute to carbon emission reductions.

The role of carbon management practices in reducing GHG emissions to meet climate change targets is becoming increasingly necessary. Organizations are under increasing pressure to measure, record and report their carbon footprint. In practice, organizations use carbon footprint results to identify opportunities to reduce operational costs. LCA play an important role in carbon footprint calculations and two main approaches to performing LCA for carbon footprints currently being used are: bottom up (PA) and top down (IO). PA is better suited to micro systems such as individual or small groups of products or services but suffers from system boundary issues, i.e., site-specific, and a lack of consistency in reporting due to lack of control systems. IO on the other hand is better suited for meso (sector level) and macro systems, accounts for higher order impacts at the expense of site-specific detail and provides consistency in reporting due to effective control systems. The hybrid of both approaches is also often used for robust and comprehensive analysis and increases the reliability of carbon footprint estimates. However, HEIs can do more to improve carbon footprint estimations particularly those associated with Scope 3 emissions, and establish standardized models for accounting, measuring, monitoring, and reporting on fossil fuel emissions, in collaboration with other stakeholders.

The public sector has a pivotal role in reducing reliance on fossil fuels and GHG emissions through carbon management practices or enabling sustainable private companies through grants to reduce GHGs. Public sector organizations like HEIs have significant influence in research, education, and the social, economic, and environmental wellbeing of society. They equally are expected to be responsible as well as lead by example in reducing energy consumption, reducing reliance on fossil fuels, and tackling climate change to enable sustainable societies. Through legislation on climate change and sector specific requirements these organizations have implemented CMPs and emission reduction action plans. However, there appears to be an imbalance across the HEI sector as only a few of these organizations have a grasp of their GHG emission profile resulting from their operations and most face difficulty in achieving their reduction targets. Whilst HEIs differ in size and function, a uniform approach to carbon reduction across the sector in collaboration with the private sector, Government(s), and wider society, is necessary. The COVID-19 pandemic presents opportunities for HEIs to reconsider the model of how education is delivered taken account of potential issues that may arise, for example inequalities associated with online education delivery, and transfer of emissions from workplaces to homes.

As renewable energy technologies evolve with various modes of implementation, they are an important element in reducing GHG emissions and tackling climate change. Global climate and energy governance approaches include international and public sources of authority, public-private interventions, and private interventions. The private sector's role in global decision making with regards multi-stakeholder participation raises concerns of its potential autonomy in climate governance decisions in some quarters, citing lack of their legitimacy in decision making. Gaps in financing, research and policy making limit private sector investment in low carbon technologies. The public sector needs to strengthen its contributions in times of austerity and investment deficiency, improve its poor energy efficiency buildings, and limit financial gaps through a suitable finance ecosystem approach for low carbon investment by government. The UK Government recently demonstrated its commitment to accelerating green financing through the release of its first Green Finance Strategy which sets out how this ambition will be achieved however, sustained annual investment is required to bridge the financial gaps in green infrastructure investment.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, Investigation and Writing—Original draft preparation: E.L., Writing—Review and editing: A.S.H. and I.M. Supervision: A.S.H. and I.M. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- IPCC. Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. 2014. Available online: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar5/wg2/> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
- Prowse, M.; Snilstveit, B. Impact evaluation and interventions to address climate change: A scoping study. *J. Dev. Eff.* **2010**, *2*, 228–262. [CrossRef]
- IPCC. Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. 2013. Available online: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar5/wg1/> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Summary for policymakers. In *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis*; Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change; Masson-Delmotte, V., Zhai, P., Pirani, A., Connors, S.L., Péan, C., Berger, S., Caud, N., Chen, Y., Goldfarb, L., Gomis, M.L., et al., Eds.; Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, UK, 2021; in press.
- IPCC. Climate Change 2007: The Physical Science Basis. 2007. Available online: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar4/wg1/> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
- BP. *BP Statistical Review of World Energy 2020*, 69th ed. 2020. Available online: <https://www.bp.com/content/dam/bp/business-sites/en/global/corporate/pdfs/energy-economics/statistical-review/bp-stats-review-2020-full-report.pdf> (accessed on 19 June 2021).
- Cuff, D.J.; Goudie, A. *The Oxford Companion to Global Change*; Oxford University Press: Oxford, UK, 2008.
- Wadanambi, R.T.; Wandana, L.S.; Chathumini, K.K.G.L.; Dassanayake, N.P.; Preethika, D.D.P.; Arachchige, U.S. The effects of industrialization on climate change. *J. Res. Technol. Eng.* **2020**, *1*, 86–94.
- European Commission. *Report from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: Energy Prices and Costs in Europe*. Brussels, 9.1.2019 COM (2019) 1 Final. 2019. Available online: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=COM2019:1:FIN&from=EN> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
- Mehta, D.P.; Wiesehan, M. Sustainable energy in building systems. *Procedia Comp. Sci.* **2013**, *19*, 628–635. [CrossRef]
- Pietzcker, R.C.; Longden, T.; Chen, W.; Fu, S.; Kriegler, E.; Kyle, P.; Luderer, G. Long-term transport energy demand and climate policy: Alternative visions on transport decarbonization in energy-economy models. *Energy* **2014**, *64*, 95–108. [CrossRef]
- Bompard, E.; Botterud, A.; Cognati, S.; Huang, T.; Jafari, M.; Leone, P.; Mauro, S.; Montesano, G.; Papa, C.; Profumo, F. An electricity triangle for energy transition: Application to Italy. *Appl. Energy* **2020**, *277*, 115525. [CrossRef]
- Brand, C.; Götschi, T.; Dons, E.; Genike, R.; Anaya-Boig, E.; Avila-Palencia, I.; de Nazelle, A.; Gascon, M.; Gaupp-Berghausen, M.; Iacorossi, F.; et al. The climate change mitigation impacts of active travel: Evidence from a longitudinal panel study in seven European cities. *Glob. Environ. Change* **2021**, *67*, 102224. [CrossRef]
- Filimonau, V.; Archer, D.; Bellamy, L.; Smith, N.; Wintrip, R. The carbon footprint of a UK University during the COVID-19 lockdown. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2021**, *756*, 143964. [CrossRef]
- Tasci, G. The impact of COVID-19 on higher education: Rethinking internationalization behind the iceberg COVID-19 and higher education. *Int. J. Curric. Instr.* **2021**, *13*, 522–536.
- Ebhota, W.S.; Jen, T.C. Fossil fuels environmental challenges and the role of solar photovoltaic technology advances in fast tracking hybrid renewable energy system. *Int. J. Precis. Eng. Manuf. Green Technol.* **2020**, *7*, 97–117. [CrossRef]
- Keeling, C.D.; Piper, S.C.; Bacastow, R.B.; Wahlen, M.; Whorf, T.P.; Heimann, M.; Meijer, H.A. Atmospheric CO₂ and 13CO₂ exchange with the terrestrial biosphere and oceans from 1978 to 2000: Observations and carbon cycle implications. In *A History of Atmospheric CO₂ and Its Effects on Plants, Animals, and Ecosystems*; Baldwin, I., Caldwell, M.M., Hekhmaier, G., Jackson, R.B., Lange, O.L., Mooney, H.A., Schulze, E.-D., Sommer, U., Ehleringer, J.R., Denise Dearing, M., et al., Eds.; Springer: New York, NY, USA, 2005; Volume 177, pp. 83–113. [CrossRef]
- Uitto, J.I.; Puri, J.; van den Berg, R.D. Evaluating climate change action for sustainable development: Introduction. In *Evaluating Climate Change Action for Sustainable Development*; Uitto, J., Puri, J., van den Berg, R., Eds.; Springer: Cham, Switzerland, 2017; pp. 1–12. [CrossRef]
- Barth, M.; Masson, T.; Fritsche, I.; Fielding, K.; Smith, J.R. Collective responses to global challenges: The social psychology of pro-environmental action. *J. Environ. Psychol.* **2021**, *74*, 101562. [CrossRef]
- IPCC. Understanding Climate Change: 22 Years of IPCC Assessment. 2010. Available online: https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/04/ipcc-brochure_understanding.pdf (accessed on 20 June 2021).
- UNFCCC. Non-State Actors Partner with Governments to Boost Climate Action; Announcement. 18 November 2016. Available online: <https://newsroom.unfccc.int/news/non-state-actors-partner-with-governments-to-boost-climate-action> (accessed on 20 June 2021).

22. UNFCCC. COP23 Kicks Off with Strong Calls to Hold to Paris Agreement Path; Article. 6 November 2017. Available online: <https://unfccc.int/news/cop23-kicks-off-with-strong-calls-to-hold-to-paris-agreement-path> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
23. UNFCCC. UN Climate Change COP24 Partners Demonstrate Value of Collaborative Climate Action; Article. 17 December 2018. Available online: <https://unfccc.int/news/un-climate-change-cop24-partners-demonstrate-value-of-collaborative-climate-action> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
24. UNFCCC. History of the Convention. 2019. Available online: <https://unfccc.int/process/the-convention/history-of-the-convention#q-2> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
25. UNFCCC. At COP25, a Call to Turn the Tide on Deforestation; Article. 12 December 2019. Available online: <https://unfccc.int/news/at-cop25-a-call-to-turn-the-tide-on-deforestation> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
26. UNFCCC. Glasgow Climate Change Conference. 2021. Available online: <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/conferences/glasgow-climate-change-conference> (accessed on 2 August 2021).
27. IPCC. AR6 Synthesis Report: Climate Change 2022. 2021. Available online: <https://www.wipcc.ch/report/sixth-assessment-report-cycle/> (accessed on 1 August 2021).
28. European Commission. Climate Change. 2015. Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/clima/sites/clima/files/docs/factsheet_climate_change_2015_en.pdf (accessed on 20 June 2021).
29. Directive 2009/28/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources and amending and subsequently repealing Directives 2001/77/EC and 2003/30/EC (Text with EEA relevance). *Off. J. Eur. Union* **2009**, *140*, 16–62.
30. Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on energy efficiency, amending Directives 2009/125/EC and 2010/30/EU and repealing Directives 2004/8/EC and 2006/32/EC. *Off. J. Eur. Union* **2012**, *315*, 1–56.
31. Regulation (EC) No 443/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 setting emission performance standards for new passenger cars as part of the Community's integrated approach to reduce CO₂ emissions from light-duty vehicles. *Off. J. Eur. Union* **2009**, *140*, 1–15.
32. Regulation (EU) No 510/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 May 2011 setting emission performance standards for new light commercial vehicles as part of the Union's integrated approach to reduce CO₂ emissions from light-duty vehicles. *Off. J. Eur. Union* **2011**, *145*, 1–18.
33. Directive 2009/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the geological storage of carbon dioxide and amending Council Directive 85/337/EEC, European Parliament and Council Directives 2000/60/EC, 2001/80/EC, 2004/35/EC, 2006/12/EC, 2008/1/EC and Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006. *Off. J. Eur. Union* **2009**, *140*, 114–135.
34. UK Government. *The Greenhouse Gas Emissions Trading Scheme Auctioning Regulations 2021*; UK Government: London, UK, 2021.
35. UK Government. *The Climate Change Act 2008 (2050 Target Amendment) Order 2019*; UK Government: London, UK, 2019.
36. Scottish Government. *Climate Change (Emissions Reduction Targets) (Scotland) Act 2019*; Scottish Government: Edinburgh, UK, 2019.
37. Saha, A.K.; Al-Shaer, H.; Dixon, R.; Demirag, I. Determinants of carbon emission disclosures and UN sustainable development goals: The case of UK higher education institutions. *Aust. Account. Rev.* **2021**, *31*, 79–107. [CrossRef]
38. Committee on Climate Change. Net Zero—The UK's Contribution to Stopping Global Warming. 2019. Available online: <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/net-zero-the-uks-contribution-to-stopping-global-warming/> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
39. UK Government. Press Release: UK Enshrines New Target in Law to Slash Emissions by 78% by 2035. 2021. Available online: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/uk-enshrines-new-target-in-law-to-slash-emissions-by-78-by-2035> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
40. Nhamo, G. Higher education and the energy sustainable development goal: Policies and projects from University of South Africa. In *Sustainable Development Goals and Institutions of Higher Education*; Nhamo, G., Mjimba, V., Eds.; Sustainable Development Goals Series; Springer: Cham, Switzerland, 2020. [CrossRef]
41. Ruiz-Mallén, I.; Heras, M. What sustainability? Higher education institutions' pathways to reach the agenda 2030 goals. *Sustainability* **2020**, *12*, 1290. [CrossRef]
42. Zhou, L.; Rudhumbu, N.; Shumba, J.; Olumide, A. Role of higher education institutions in the implementation of sustainable development goals. In *Sustainable Development Goals and Institutions of Higher Education*; Nhamo, G., Mjimba, V., Eds.; Sustainable Development Goals Series; Springer: Cham, Switzerland, 2020. [CrossRef]
43. Hügel, S.; Davies, A.R. Public participation, engagement, and climate change adaptation: A review of the research literature. *WIREs Clim. Change* **2020**, *11*, e645. [CrossRef]
44. Iturriza, M.; Labaka, L.; Omazabal, M.; Borges, M. Awareness–development in the context of climate change resilience. *Urban Clim.* **2020**, *32*, 100613. [CrossRef]
45. Sullivan, R.; Gouldson, A. Ten years of corporate action on climate change: What do we have to show for it? *Energy Policy* **2013**, *60*, 733–740. [CrossRef]
46. Mahmoudian, F.; Lu, J.; Yu, D.; Nazari, J.A.; Herremans, I.M. Inter- and intra-organizational stakeholder arrangements in carbon management accounting. *Brit. Acc. Rev.* **2021**, *53*, 100933. [CrossRef]
47. Akaifi, K.; Elnahass, M.; Salama, A. Carbon disclosure and financial performance: UK environmental policy. *Bus. Strategy Environ.* **2020**, *29*, 711–726. [CrossRef]

48. Villena, V.H.; Dhanorkar, S. How institutional pressures and managerial incentives elicit carbon transparency in global supply chains. *J. Oper. Manag.* **2020**, *66*, 697–734. [CrossRef]
49. Chan, M.-K. *Carbon Management: A Practical Guide For Suppliers*; University of Cambridge: Cambridge, UK, 2009; Available online: https://www.banktrack.org/manage/ems_files/download/carbon_management_a_practical_guide_for_suppliers/lloyds_carbon_management_a_practical_guide_for_suppliers_0.pdf (accessed on 20 June 2021).
50. Jowitt, P.; Johnson, A. Topic Guide: Carbon Management of Infrastructure Services. 2014. Available online: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/57a089b3ed915d622c000365/EoD_Topic_Guide_March14_Carbon_Infrastructure.pdf (accessed on 20 June 2021).
51. Tuesta, Y.N.; Soler, C.C.; Feliu, V.R. Carbon management accounting and financial performance: Evidence from the European Union emission trading system. *Bus. Strategy Environ.* **2021**, *30*, 1270–1282. [CrossRef]
52. Kneifel, J. Life-cycle carbon and cost analysis of energy efficiency measures in new commercial buildings. *Energy Build.* **2010**, *42*, 333–340. [CrossRef]
53. NetRegs. Cutting Your Carbon Emissions. *Environmental Guidance for Your Business in Northern Ireland & Scotland*. 2017. Available online: <http://www.netregs.org.uk/environmental-topics/carbon-reduction-and-efficiency/cutting-your-carbon-emissions/> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
54. NetRegs. Reducing Vehicle Emissions. *Environmental Guidance for Your Business in Northern Ireland & Scotland*. 2017. Available online: <https://www.netregs.org.uk/environmental-topics/air-pollution/reducing-vehicle-emissions> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
55. World Health Organization (WHO). Calls for Urgent Action to Protect Health From Climate Change—Sign The Call. 2019. Available online: <https://www.who.int/globalchange/global-campaign/cop21/en/> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
56. Revelle, R.R.; Shapero, D.C. Energy and climate. *Environ. Conserv.* **1978**, *5*, 81–91. [CrossRef]
57. Bui, M.; Adjiman, C.S.; Bardow, A.; Anthony, E.J.; Boston, A.; Brown, S.; Fennell, P.S.; Fuss, S.; Galindo, A.; Hackett, L.A.; et al. Carbon capture and storage (CCS): The way forward. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2018**, *11*, 1062–1176. [CrossRef]
58. Lee, S.-Y. Corporate carbon strategies in responding to climate change. *Bus. Strategy Environ.* **2012**, *21*, 33–48. [CrossRef]
59. Wade, B.; Dargusch, P.; Griffiths, A. Defining best practice carbon management in an Australian context. *Australas. J. Environ. Manag.* **2014**, *21*, 52–64. [CrossRef]
60. Wade, B.; Griffiths, A. Examining best practice carbon management within Australian organisations: Cases from contrasting sectors. *Australas. J. Environ. Manag.* **2020**, *27*, 156–172. [CrossRef]
61. Purman, J.R. *Tracking Your Carbon Footprint: A Step-By-Step Guide to Understanding and Inventorying Greenhouse Gas Emissions*; iUniverse: New York, NY, USA, 2008.
62. Pandey, D.; Agrawal, M.; Pandey, J.S. Carbon footprint: Current methods of estimation. *Environ. Monit. Assess.* **2011**, *178*, 135–160. [CrossRef]
63. Wiedmann, T.; Minx, J.C. A definition of carbon footprint. In *Ecological Economics Research Trends*; Pertsova, C.C., Ed.; Nova Science Publishers: New York, NY, USA, 2008; pp. 1–11.
64. Robertson, G.P.; Grace, P.R. Greenhouse gas fluxes in tropical and temperate agriculture: The need for a full-cost accounting of global warming potentials. In *Tropical Agriculture in Transition—Opportunities for Mitigating Greenhouse Gas Emissions?* Wassmann, R., Vlek, P.L.G., Eds.; Springer: Dordrecht, The Netherlands, 2004; pp. 51–63. [CrossRef]
65. Shine, K.P.; Fuglestvedt, J.S.; Hailemariam, K.; Stuber, N. Alternatives to the Global Warming Potential for Comparing Climate Impacts of Emissions of Greenhouse Gases. *Clim. Change* **2005**, *68*, 281–302. [CrossRef]
66. UK Government. *Research and Analysis—UK Greenhouse Gas Emissions: Other Technical Reports*; (Supplementary Technical Reports Relating to Greenhouse Gas Emissions); 2021. Available online: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-greenhouse-gas-emissions-explanatory-notes> (accessed on 22 June 2021).
67. Durojaye, O.; Laseinde, T.; Oluwafemi, I. A descriptive review of carbon footprint. In *Human Systems Engineering and Design II, Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Human Systems Engineering and Design (IHSED2019): Future Trends and Applications, Universität der Bundeswehr München, Munich, Germany, 16–18 September 2019*; Ahram, T., Karwowski, W., Pickl, S., Taiar, R., Eds.; Springer: Cham, Switzerland, 2020; Volume 1026, pp. 960–968. [CrossRef]
68. Fet, A. *Environmental Management Tools and Their Application—A Review with References to Case Studies*. 1998. Available online: <http://www.iot.ntnu.no/users/fet/Publi-Forfattenskap/publikasjoner/Lisboa.pdf> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
69. Arena, A.P.; de Rosa, C. Life cycle assessment of energy and environmental implications of the implementation of conservation technologies in school buildings in Mendoza—Argentina. *BUILD. Environ.* **2003**, *38*, 359–368. [CrossRef]
70. Matthews, H.S.; Hendrickson, C.T.; Weber, C.L. Estimating carbon footprints with input output models. In *Proceedings of the International Input-Output Meeting on Managing the Environment*, Seville, Spain, 9–11 July 2008.
71. Carbon Trust. Carbon Footprinting Guide. *Resources & Guides, Carbontrust.Com*. 2018. Available online: <https://www.carbontrust.com/resources/guides/carbon-footprinting-and-reporting/carbon-footprinting/> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
72. Gómez, N.; Cadarso, M.; Monsalve, F. Carbon footprint of a university in a multiregional model: The case of the University of Castilla—La Mancha. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2016**, *138*, 119–130. [CrossRef]
73. Matthews, H.S.; Hendrickson, C.T.; Weber, C.L. The importance of carbon footprint estimation boundaries. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2008**, *42*, 5839–5842. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
74. Larsen, H.N.; Pettersen, J.; Solli, C.; Hertwich, E.G. Investigating the carbon footprint of a university—The case of NTNU. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2013**, *48*, 39–47. [CrossRef]

75. Ozawa-Meida, L.; Brockway, P.; Letten, K.; Davies, J.; Fleming, P. Measuring carbon performance in a UK University through a consumption-based carbon footprint: De Montfort University case study. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2013**, *56*, 185–198. [CrossRef]
76. Alvarez, S.; Blanquer, M.; Rubio, A. Carbon footprint using the compound method based on financial accounts. The case of the School of Forestry Engineering, Technical University of Madrid. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2014**, *66*, 224–232. [CrossRef]
77. Zvezdov, D.; Hack, S. Carbon footprinting of large product portfolios. Extending the use of enterprise resource planning systems to carbon information management. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2016**, *135*, 1267–1275. [CrossRef]
78. Nicholls, D.; Barnes, E.; Acrea, F.; Chen, C.; Buluç, L.Y.; Parker, M.M. Top-down and bottom-up approaches to greenhouse gas inventory methods—A comparison between national- and forest-scale reporting methods. In *General Technical Report PNW-GTR-906*; Pacific Northwest Research Station, U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service: Portland, OR, USA, 2015. [CrossRef]
79. Walker, G.; Cass, N. Carbon reduction, ‘the public’ and renewable energy: Engaging with socio-technical configurations. *Area* **2007**, *39*, 458–469. [CrossRef]
80. Andrade, J.C.S.; de Oliveira, J.A.P. The role of the private sector in global climate and energy governance. *J. Bus. Ethics* **2015**, *130*, 375–387. [CrossRef]
81. Pattberg, P.; Stripple, J. Beyond the public and private divide: Remapping transnational climate governance in the 21st century. *Int. Environ. Agreem.* **2008**, *8*, 367–388. [CrossRef]
82. UNFCCC. The Kyoto Protocol Mechanisms: International Emissions Trading Clean Development Mechanism Joint Implementation. 2007. Available online: <https://unfccc.int/resource/docs/publications/mechanisms.pdf> (accessed on 23 June 2021).
83. Talukdar, D.; Meisner, C.M. Does the private sector help or hurt the environment? Evidence from carbon dioxide pollution in developing countries. *World Dev.* **2001**, *29*, 827–840. [CrossRef]
84. Bradford, J.; Fraser, E.D.G. Local authorities, climate change and small and medium enterprises: Identifying effective policy instruments to reduce energy use and carbon emissions. *Corp. Soc. Responsib. Environ. Manag.* **2008**, *15*, 156–172. [CrossRef]
85. Audit Scotland. Improving Energy Efficiency: A Follow-Up Report. 2010. Available online: https://www.audit-scotland.gov.uk/uploads/docs/report/2010/nr_101209_energy_efficiency_followup.pdf (accessed on 19 June 2021).
86. Environmental Association for Universities and Colleges; National Union of Students; University and College Union; Association of Colleges; College Development Network. Sustainability in Education. 2017. Available online: https://www.sustainabilityexchange.ac.uk/files/20180109_state_of_the_sector_report_2017_final.pdf (accessed on 20 June 2021).
87. Jackson, T.; Lynch, W. Public sector responses to climate change: Evaluating the role of Scottish local government in implementing the climate change (Scotland) Act 2009. *Commonw. J. Local Gov.* **2011**, *89*, 112–135. [CrossRef]
88. Jensen, T.; Dowlatabadi, H. Challenges in financing public sector low-carbon initiatives: Lessons from private finance for a school district in British Columbia, Canada. *Clim. Policy* **2017**, *18*, 878–888. [CrossRef]
89. Owen, R.; Brennan, G.; Lyon, F. Enabling investment for the transition to a low carbon economy: Government policy to finance early stage green innovation. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* **2018**, *31*, 137–145. [CrossRef]
90. World Economic Forum. The Green Investment Report: The Ways And Means To Unlock Private Finance For Green Growth. 2013. Available online: http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_GreenInvestment_Report_2013.pdf (accessed on 23 June 2021).
91. Retailack, S.; Johnson, A.; Brunert, J.; Rasoulinezhad, E.; Taghizadeh-Hesary, F. Energy efficiency finance program. In *Handbook of Green Finance*; Sachs, J., Woo, W., Yoshino, N., Taghizadeh-Hesary, F., Eds.; Springer: Singapore, 2019; pp. 291–314. [CrossRef]
92. HM Government. Green Finance Strategy, Transforming Finance for a Greener Future. 2019. Available online: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/green-finance-strategy> (accessed on 23 June 2021).
93. Scottish Government. *The Climate Change (Duties Of Public Bodies: Reporting Requirements) (Scotland) Amendment Order 2020*; Scottish Government: Edinburgh, UK, 2020.
94. Higher Education Statistics Agency. Higher Education Student Statistics: UK, 2019/20—Student Numbers and Characteristics (Statistical Bulletin SB258). 2021. Available online: <https://www.hesa.ac.uk/news/27-01-2021/sb258-higher-education-student-statistics/numbers> (accessed on 22 June 2021).
95. Higher Education Statistics Agency. Higher Education Staff Statistics: UK, 2019/20 (Statistical Bulletin SB259). 2021. Available online: <https://www.hesa.ac.uk/news/19-01-2021/sb259-higher-education-staff-statistics#notes> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
96. Universities UK. Higher Education in Numbers. Available online: <https://www.universitiesuk.ac.uk/facts-and-stats/Pages/higher-education-data.aspx> (accessed on 6 June 2021).
97. Mazhar, M.U.; Bull, R.; Lemon, M.; Ahmad, S.B.S. Carbon management planning in UK universities: A journey to low carbon built environment. In *University Initiatives in Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation*; Leal Filho, W., Leal-Arcas, R., Eds.; Springer: Cham, Switzerland, 2019; pp. 33–56.
98. Robinson, O.; Kemp, S.; Williams, I. Carbon management at universities: A reality check. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2015**, *106*, 109–118. [CrossRef]
99. Robinson, O.; Tewkesbury, A.; Kemp, S.; Williams, I. Towards a universal carbon footprint standard: A case study of carbon management at universities. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2018**, *172*, 4435–4455. [CrossRef]
100. Environmental Association for Universities and Colleges. Summary Report on Scottish Further and Higher Education Carbon Emissions 2014–15. 2016. Available online: https://www.sustainabilityexchange.ac.uk/files/eauc_fhe_report_v2_-_key_findings_summary.pdf (accessed on 20 June 2021).

101. Brite Green. *University Carbon Report—Brite Green 2015/16 University Carbon Progress Report*. Fourth Annual University Carbon Report On The Carbon Performance Of HEFCE-Funded Universities. 2017. Available online: <https://brite-green.co.uk/index.php/our-work/reports-publications/university-carbon-report> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
102. Environmental Association for Universities and Colleges; Scottish Association of University Directors of Estates; JC Carbon Consulting; Carbon Forecasting. *Scottish Universities Carbon Management Performance Review Project*. 2015. Available online: http://www.sfac.ac.uk/web/FILES/ReportsandPublications/Scottish_Universities_CMP_review_project.pdf (accessed on 20 June 2021).
103. Milner, J.; Davies, M.; Wilkinson, P. Urban energy, carbon management (low carbon cities) and co-benefits for human health. *Curr Opin. Environ. Sustain.* **2012**, *4*, 398–404. [[CrossRef](#)]
104. Okereke, C. An exploration of motivations, drivers and barriers to carbon management. *Eur. Manag. J.* **2007**, *25*, 475–486. [[CrossRef](#)]
105. Klein-Banai, C.; Theis, T.L. Quantitative analysis of factors affecting greenhouse gas emissions at institutions of higher education. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2013**, *48*, 29–38. [[CrossRef](#)]
106. Fossil Free. About Fossil Free. Available online: <http://gofossilfree.org/uk/about-fossil-free/> (accessed on 20 June 2021).
107. Valks-Val, K.; Bovea, M.D. Carbon footprint in higher education institutions: A literature review and prospects for future research. *Clean Technol. Environ. Policy* **2021**. [[CrossRef](#)]
108. Letete, T.C.M.; Mungwe, N.W.; Guma, M.; Marquard, A. Carbon footprint of the University of Cape Town. *J. Energy S. Afr.* **2011**, *22*, 2–12. [[CrossRef](#)]
109. Butt, Z.H. Greenhouse gas inventory at an institution level: A case study of Massey University, New Zealand. *Greenh. Gas Manag. Manag.* **2012**, *2*, 178–185. [[CrossRef](#)]
110. Varón-Hoyos, M.; Osorio-Tejada, J.; Morales-Pinzón, T. Carbon footprint of a university campus from Colombia. *Carbon Manag.* **2021**, *12*, 93–107. [[CrossRef](#)]
111. Ridhosari, B.; Rahman, A. Carbon footprint assessment at Universitas Pertamina from the scope of electricity, transportation, and waste generation: Toward a green campus and promotion of environmental sustainability. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2020**, *246*, 119172. [[CrossRef](#)]
112. Clabeaux, R.; Carbajales-Dale, M.; Ladner, D.; Walker, T. Assessing the carbon footprint of a university campus using a life cycle assessment approach. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2020**, *273*, 122600. [[CrossRef](#)]
113. Gu, Y.; Wang, H.; Xu, J.; Wang, Y.; Wang, X.; Robinson, Z.P.; Li, F.; Wu, J.; Tan, J.; Zhi, X. Quantification of interlinked environmental footprints on a sustainable university campus: A nexus analysis perspective. *Appl. Energy* **2019**, *246*, 65–76. [[CrossRef](#)]
114. Townsend, J.; Barrett, J. Exploring the applications of carbon footprinting towards sustainability at a UK university: Reporting and decision making. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2015**, *107*, 164–176. [[CrossRef](#)]